

A DEGREE IS NOT NECESSARILY THE ANSWER: A
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INITIAL POLICE
LEARNING IN SCOTLAND, SWEDEN, AND FINLAND

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the
University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of
Philosophy

November 2022

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Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, this thesis is the result of my own individual work and has not been submitted for DBA, DProf, EngD or PhD or comparable academic award at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Preface and acknowledgement

As a young boy I had devoured books on policing, particularly detective stories and those which provided accounts, often humorous, of police work. I avidly watched TV police dramas such as *The Sweeney*, *Shoestring*, *Hill Street Blues*, *Starsky and Hutch* and the like, and at one point sped around the streets of Cardiff on my Chopper pedal cycle dressed in Starsky's three-quarter length cardigan (knitted by my grandma) and blue suede, adidas trainers. My pre-socialisation was a lengthy affair and despite being largely based on fiction, I was convinced that policing was the career for me, providing many of the things I craved: a varied, interesting, and worthwhile career; a sense of belonging; the chance to become a detective (a role I coveted above all others), as well as job and financial, security. I can vividly recall sitting on the living room floor at home listening to the tall tales of a family friend and police officer who had spent years working in Cardiff Bay, then a tough and run-down area of the city. His embellished stories full of humour, camaraderie, excitement, and even the odd bit of danger, sealed it. I wanted to be a police officer. Having been refused permission by my parents to apply for the Police Cadets, it would be another four years following completion of secondary school and spells as a factory worker, waiter, shop worker and soldier before I finally realised my childhood ambition, joining Thames Valley Police in January 1984.

I loved 'the job' and was fascinated by it. Even during the early years, I would avidly read Home Office research papers on policing and frequently borrowed books and reports from the nearby Bramshill Police College library. I wanted to know how policing worked and how to improve what we did. I wasn't ambitious (beyond wanting to be a detective and live on a houseboat like the 1980s television fictional character Shoestring) and had no ambitions to be promoted, quite the opposite. However, as I matured, I regretted not having taken up the offer to study for an undergraduate degree when I finished secondary school. Completion of an HNC in Police Studies, a BSc, and an MSc in Strategic Leadership, were followed by other qualitative studies on and with Police Scotland, and the Scottish Crime Campus, under the supervision of Professor Fyfe, all of which led naturally to this PhD. My hope, should this thesis be conferred with the authority of a doctoral degree, is that its contribution will not only

help advance academic knowledge in this field, but also help to inform a broader strategic policy debate with regards police professionalisation through higher academic education. Above all, I would like to see initial police learning in Scotland develop a closer relationship with Higher Education (HE) and put the ‘science’ together with the ‘art’ and ‘craft’ of policing.

Before turning to the thesis itself, there are several people who have supported me in completion of this study and whose contribution I wish to acknowledge.

Firstly, I would like to thank my supervision team which has grown and evolved over the past few years. Professor Denise Martin, now of Abertay University, and Dr Andrew Wooff of Edinburgh Napier University, both of whom devised the idea for this study, secured funding for the studentship, encouraged my application, and steered me through the first 18-months before being joined by the other members of the team. Dr Colin Atkinson of the University of the West of Scotland who stepped in as my Director of Studies when Professor Martin moved on to Abertay. Dr Atkinson took on his role with an infectious level of enthusiasm, commitment, and creativity which, together with his intellect and passion for all things policing, have been inspirational and sustaining. Professor Rowena Murray, also then of the University of the West of Scotland and now retired, who also joined the team later, bringing her considerable experience to my supervision and academic writing. Any remaining similarities to parsimonious police management speak are entirely down to me. I have been, and always will be, indebted to them all for their wise advice and guidance together with the invaluable ‘pastoral’ care which was often required as I constantly fought against the adverse impacts of imposter syndrome, and the odd curve ball which life threw at me, including the impact of thesis writing during a global pandemic. I have felt supported, pushed, pulled, guided, praised, constructively criticised and safe in the hands of my professional, competent, dedicated, and caring team. Above all, I hope I have made some lifelong friendships.

My thanks also go to the University of the West of Scotland for funding my studentship, and to the Scottish Institute for Policing Research (SIPR) without whose additional funding I would not have had the privilege of undertaking research in Sweden and Finland, nor undertaken a week-long summer school at George Mason

University in the United States of America (USA). Beyond financial support, the SIPR family provided me with fellowship and practical support, especially through their memoranda of understanding with both Police Scotland and the Finnish Police University College. I would also like to thank my fellow ‘police learning’ PhD researcher Larissa Engelmann from Edinburgh Napier University. I found our frequent discussions exploring police learning motivating, inspiring, and informative and our writing days invaluable.

I will be eternally grateful to a man I admire greatly and who set me on the path towards a PhD, Professor Nick Fyfe, former Director of SIPR. It was through his encouragement to undertake a SIPR Practitioner Fellowship whilst a serving police officer that I took my first steps towards a PhD. When he later encouraged me to consider undertaking a PhD, I expressed concern that I didn’t have the intellectual capacity. He ‘reassured’ me with the immortal words “well Andy, it’s more about perseverance than intelligence”! I’m still not entirely sure what to make of that, but he was right about the need for perseverance.

I would also like to thank all those police officers, police staff, students, academics, and others who generously allowed me access to their organisations and people. It was a privilege not only to be granted access to interview them during their busy working lives, but also to be trusted with their personal perceptions, beliefs, and opinions. They of course need to remain anonymous, but you know who you are. Without your support this project would not have been achievable. Thank you.

Undertaking this PhD has been such a privilege, one my seventeen-year-old self, leaving school with mediocre qualifications, would never have thought possible. Education and learning have enriched and improved my personal and professional lives immensely. As a (very) ‘mature’ student, it just goes to show that lifelong learning can be exactly that, if the opportunities are available and if they are grasped.

Andrew Tatnell
Callander
July 2022.

Dedication

To my wife Kay, my son Gordon, and my daughter Anna, who have encouraged me throughout and whose own achievements, both academically and in their professional lives, have been such a source of inspiration.

Finally, I would like to acknowledge my mother who sadly died shortly before I began my PhD. Despite her own lack of formal education, she believed in its potential to enrich and improve. Above all, she instilled in me a strong work ethic and a determination to persevere, both of which I have drawn on over the past few years.

Abstract

There has been a trend in policing within some north-western European countries, including Sweden and Finland, towards the academisation of initial police learning. This typically involves university delivery, the inclusion of academic theoretical knowledge, and/or undergraduate degree accreditation. Interestingly, this trend has not been apparent within Scottish policing. There have been no empirical studies which explore why this is the case. This thesis addresses this gap by comparatively analysing policy formulation in relation to initial police learning and its operationalisation in Scotland, alongside two other north-western European countries with similar socio-democratic profiles and policing models, both of which have followed the academisation trend, namely Sweden and Finland.

Data was gathered in 2019 from forty-nine semi-structured, one-to-one interviews and six focus groups involving academics, police officers, and police staff active in policy making and the design and delivery of initial police learning, together with police recruits and policing students. Using Atlas ti analytical software to support coding, the data from each transcribed interview and focus group were inductively and thematically analysed. An iterative, continually cyclical approach was adopted as soon as data began to be gathered, which allowed for patterns, themes and understanding to be developed, and for it to be oriented conceptionally within the theoretical framework of the literature.

The central contribution of this thesis is that police professionalisation has different meanings in different social, cultural, and political contexts which helps to understand why there is no consensus about how policing should be professionalised; that professionalising policing through the academisation of initial police learning is not necessarily the answer and that different approaches are appropriate; and that the approaches deployed must be attuned to the different social, cultural, and political contexts in which they are situated. This thesis addresses a knowledge gap where empirically based, cross-national comparative studies of this type are limited, and makes recommendations for future policy and practice. For example, that initial police learning programmes should move away from traditional learning environments

which focus on acculturation of recruits and policing students into unquestioning hierarchical cultural norms, and towards those which focus on the acquisition of knowledge. Learning environments should provide time and space for self-directed learning, critical thinking, and reflection. The Police University College in Finland provides an exemplar from which other countries may wish to draw lessons.

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Glossary

COP	College of Policing (for England and Wales)
EBP	Evidence Based Policing
EHEA	European Higher Education Area
EQF	European Qualifications Framework
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HMICS	Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Constabulary in Scotland
HNC	Higher National Certificate
IPLDP	Initial Police Learning and Development Programme
ITC	Initial Training Course
LM	Lean Management
MA	Modern Apprenticeship
OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
POLAMK	The Police University College Finland
PCDA	Police Degree Apprenticeship
PEQF	Police Education Qualifications Framework (England & Wales)
PIRC	Police Investigations and Review Commissioner (Scotland)
RECPOL	Recruitment, Education and Careers in the Police
SCQF	Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework
SPCF	Scottish Police Consultative Forum
SIPR	Scottish Institute for Policing Research
SNP	Scottish National Party
SNPA	Swedish National Police Academy
SPA	Scottish Police Authority
SQA	Scottish Qualifications Authority
UCAS	The Universities and Colleges Admissions Service
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
UWS	University of the West of Scotland

Definition of terms

Academisation of initial police learning:

In the context of this thesis, ‘academisation’ means the closer alignment of initial police learning with HE through the inclusion of epistemic knowledge, and/or delivery within a university and/or degree accreditation.

Education:

The word ‘education’ within the context of initial police learning, has been used within this study to differentiate a learning context which either has academic content and/or takes place within an academic setting and is intended to distinguish it from training.

Homogenous policy formulation process:

This is a non-negotiated, myopic, approach to policy formulation (Kingdon, 1995).

Heterogenous policy formulation process:

This is policy formulation which adopts a negotiated approach (Kingdon, 1995) between two or more of the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing.

Initial Police Learning Programme:

The generic term ‘Initial Police Learning Programme’ has been adopted to denote that period of learning which is undertaken by recruits as they are referred to in Scotland; policing students and ‘aspirants’ as they are referred to in Sweden; and policing students as they are referred to in Finland. It is that period of learning at the very beginning of a police officer’s career before they are fully confirmed in the role of a full-time, permanently employed police constable.

Mainstream university:

In the context of this thesis, this is a university which is not a university controlled by policing and which is not confined to the delivery of policing related training and education.

Police:	It is necessary to define what is meant by ‘police’ in this thesis. Policing “connotes a specific aspect of social control: the activities aimed at preserving the security of a particular social order, and social order in general” (Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki, 2019, p. 4). Police in this thesis refers to “state organized specialist ‘police’” (Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki, 2019, p. 4) or “state-sponsored police organizations” (Pearson-Goff and Herrington, 2014, p.15).
Police staff:	Those members of a police service’s workforce who are not police officers. Sometimes referred to as ‘civilian’ staff a term which has largely been dropped within United Kingdom (UK) policing.
Senior Rank:	Any police officer who has obtained a supervisory, management, or leadership role.
Training:	In this study, training has been taken to mean learning which focuses on developing technical skills which require to be applied repetitively.
Working Class:	Taken from (Moberg, 2020, p.69) – “Upper secondary education is often associated with being a skilled worker, and compulsory education can be approximated to unskilled workers in most cases. Therefore, a crude distinction of working class and middle class can be based on the parent’s educational background.”

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter, which is presented in seven sections, explains the rationale for this study. It foregrounds the principal area of inquiry, namely why initial police learning in Scotland does not mirror the trend towards the academisation taking place within other north-western European countries.

It begins (section 1.1) by providing an overview of how policing is organised in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland. It describes how policing in each country operates within broadly similar socio-democratic political contexts, with each single, national force being organised along broadly similar lines within national governance structures, to which operationally independent chief officers are scrutinised and held to account. The governance and oversight of initial police learning in each of the case study countries are also described.

It then moves on (section 1.2) to outline attempts within Western-style police agencies to continue to professionalise by involving Higher Education (HE) institutions and actors in the education of their police recruits and policing students. Despite the view of some scholars that research as to the effectiveness of HE in this regard is scant and inconclusive, there has nevertheless been an increasing trend towards the academisation of initial police learning programmes. This trend has been observed in other north-western European countries, such as Sweden, Finland, Norway, the Republic of Ireland, Northern Ireland, England, and Wales, but not Scotland which has instead retained the more traditional 'craft' based approach founded primarily on experiential learning.

Section 1.3 outlines the educational entry requirements for those people wishing to join policing in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland. It explains that in Scotland, no academic qualifications are required to enter the two-year initial police learning programme, whilst in Sweden and Finland, applicants must have the requisite secondary school qualifications for entry to undergraduate-level, university-based, degree programmes. It also provides a brief overview of the initial police learning programmes in the case study countries, from the selection process, through the

different learning phases, to completion and qualification, before situating these different models within the broader UK and European context.

Section 1.4 provides justification for undertaking this study. It argues that despite the rapidly expanding academisation of initial police learning programmes, and policing becoming graduate-entry only, evidence of its benefits is scant and inconclusive (Brown, 2020; Terpstra and Schaap, 2021). Early scoping and informant interviews undertaken for this study indicated that policy formulation had probably been based more on professional judgement and experience than research. Hough and Stanko (2019, p.5) had suspected this had been the case in relation to the introduction of the Police Education Qualifications Framework (PEQF) in England and Wales. This thesis, therefore, seeks to address the rationale underpinning the different approaches to initial police learning within the case study countries. In doing so, it provides an analysis of the extent to which the situated socially, culturally, and politically constructed notions of profession, professionalism, and professionalisation have influenced policy formulation and implementation. Adopting a cross-national, comparative approach also answers calls by scholars within the broader sociology of profession literature, such as Noordegraaf and Steijn (2013, p.236), for comparative studies within different national contexts so that more refined understandings of the reconfiguration of public services can be developed.

Section 1.5 describes the research aim, objectives, and research questions. The chapter concludes in section 1.6 with an overview of this thesis.

1.1 Expanding academisation of initial police learning

“Most Western-style police agencies are attempting to professionalise their police and, as a major part of this process, are involving the HE system in some format for educating their police officers” (Rogers and Frevel, 2018, p.2). This is reflected in other north-western European countries, where the role of HE as regards initial police learning programmes is an expanding one. This trend has emerged despite being the subject of conflicting debate, not only within the literature, but also within policing. For example, some scholars such as Wimshurst and Ransley (2007, p.106) have

argued that the effectiveness of HE in police reform agendas, “remains ambivalent”. Others, such as Brown (2020), have challenged claims of a causal relationship between academic attainment and the professionalism of individual police officers. Green and Tong (2020, p.296) argued that “there is still not a decisive body of work that can clearly articulate the full range of benefits HE can bring to policing”. However, others are of the view that “there are real potential benefits to be grasped by requiring a degree at the point of entry into the police service” (Hough and Stanko, 2019, p.6).

Police Scotland, however, has not followed this trend. HE has no role in Police Scotland’s post-entry initial learning programme. The traditional, two-year, post entry, ‘craft’ based model has remained fundamentally unchanged since the 1960s, despite Scotland having “explicitly looked to northern and western Europe for evidence of the operation and effectiveness of national police organisations” (Fyfe, 2014, p.10). Surprisingly, with the notable exception of Martin and Wooff (2020), there has been no empirical research undertaken which explores why. Therefore, a focus of this study has been to understand why Scotland has bucked the academisation trend. In doing so, Scotland will be compared with two other north-western European countries which are further along the degree-accreditation pathway, namely Sweden and Finland. In Sweden, the initial police learning programme has evolved into a compulsory, pre-entry, two-and-a-half-year, mainstream university-based model which is not degree-accredited. In Finland, the initial learning programme has evolved into a compulsory, pre-entry, three-year, police university college based, Bachelor’s degree accredited programme. In doing so, this study has explored the extent to which these initial police learning models, and the extent to which they are aligned with HE, have been influenced by the social, cultural, and political contexts within each of the case study countries. It has done so through the perceptual lenses of those involved in policy formulation, and its operationalisation.

1.2 The governance and organisation of policing in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland

State policing within each of the case study countries operates within broadly similar socio-democratic environments and similar policing systems. They are more closely

aligned with the Anglo-Saxon tradition than the continental tradition found elsewhere in Europe, such as France and Spain for example (Inzunza and Wikström, 2020, p. 1258). Whilst each force is organised along broadly similar lines within national Governmental structures, namely the Justice Directorate in Scotland, and Ministries of the Interior in Sweden and Finland, the Chief Constable and Police Commissioners are operationally autonomous, although subject to scrutiny and accountability through various oversight and governance arrangements.

State policing in each of the case study countries has recently “been reconfigured, shifting from largely decentralized and often fragmented systems to become more centralized, national arrangements” (Terpstra and Fyfe, 2015, p.1). This has resulted in each country moving from regional to single, national force structures.

1.2.1 Organisational structures

In 2013, following the amalgamation of eight pre-existing regional police forces and two national policing agencies, Police Scotland became Scotland’s first national, single police force. Comprising approximately 17,500 police officers and 5,500 police staff, Police Scotland serves a population of about 5.5 million people over a geographical area of 28, 168 square miles, a third of the UK’s landmass, and comprising urban, rural, island and remote communities (Police Scotland, 2022). It is headed by a Chief Constable, comprises a number of national and regional specialist departments (Specialist Crime, Operational Support), three regional policing regions, thirteen Divisional Commands, and thirty-two Area Commands “aligned with the boundaries of local authorities each with a local commander” (Fyfe *et al.*, 2021, p.265). Atkinson (2013, p.7) argued that police reform in Scotland was being driven largely by “increasing public and political scrutiny due to its perceived inefficiencies and duplication of efforts”. Terpstra and Fyfe (2015, p.2) argued that “in Scotland, the main focus was on financial savings”. Whatever the drivers were, outcomes of the reform have included greater vertical and horizontal fragmentation (Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019).

Established in 2015, the Swedish Police Authority comprises the Office and the National Police Commissioner (a Government appointee), the National Operations Department (which directs and supervises police activities nationally and internationally), five national departments (Human Resources, Information Technology, Financial Affairs, Communication, Legal Affairs), the National Forensic Centre, seven Police Regions (South, West, East, Stockholm, Centre, Bergslagen, North), twenty-seven Police Districts, and ninety-five Local Police Districts. At the time of data gathering in 2019, the Swedish Police Authority establishment was about 21,000 police officers and 13,000 police staff (Ministry of Justice Sweden, 2021). There is also a Special Investigations Department which is independent of the Swedish Police Authority, and which, under the direction of the Special Prosecution Office, investigates offences committed by police officials, police students, prosecutors, judges, and members of parliament. The head of the department is a government appointee. Strategic direction is provided by a combination of statute, annual directions issued by the Swedish Government, and the National Police Commissioners 'directional document'.

Finland's single national force polices a population of about 5.5 million people. The Police Commissioner who chairs the Police Board, oversees eleven regional police areas, (with the self-governing region of Åland having its own department), and four national police units: the National Bureau of Investigation; the Finnish Security Intelligence Service; the National Traffic Police; and the Police University College, which is situated in Tampere, about one hundred miles north of Helsinki. The force establishment comprises about 7,200 officers and 3,000 police staff, which represents 137 police officers per 100,000 people (Police of Finland, 2022), has a low reported crime rate of 23.32 (Numbeo crime index, 2022), and high levels of public trust, ranging from 91% in 1999 to a high of 98% (Vuorensyrjä and Rauta, 2020). By comparison, Scotland has 322 police officers per 100,000 people (Eurostat, 2022), a moderate crime rate (Numbeo crime index, 2022)¹, and an 87% level of public trust (Scottish Household Survey, 2020), whilst Sweden has 203 officers per 100,000

¹ The Numbeo crime index (2020) does not separate out Scotland from the wider UK which is shown as 43.71

people (Eurostat, 2022), a moderate crime rate of 47.07 (Numbeo, 2022), and a high level (76%) of public trust (Medieakademin, 2022).

1.2.2 Governance and oversight of policing

Following the reinstatement of the Scottish Parliament in 1999, responsibility for policing was devolved from the UK Government at Westminster to the Scottish Government in Edinburgh. The Scottish Government's Justice Minister, the Scottish Police Authority (SPA), and the Chief Constable of Police Scotland, are collectively responsible for strategic governance. Independent oversight is also provided by Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Constabulary in Scotland (HMICS) and the Police Investigations and Review Commissioner (PIRC). Local Scrutiny Panels comprising elected councillors representing their local communities and with whom local police commanders have a duty to consult when developing local policing priorities, provide a degree of local scrutiny and accountability. The Chief Constable and their chief officer team are appointed by the SPA, to whom they are accountable. The Chief Constable together with Police Scotland's Senior Leadership Board determine strategy, policy, and direction, and has legal independence concerning day-to-day operational decision-making.

In Sweden, oversight at a national level is provided through the Public Council. Chaired by the Police Commissioner and comprising representatives from each of the political parties represented in the Swedish Parliament, the Riksdag, the Council provides public transparency. Similar Public Councils operate within regions chaired by regional police commanders.

Finland has a heavily centralised system of governance. The Finnish Government's Ministry of the Interior, through its Police Department, supervises and sets the general directions, priorities, and targets for the National Police Board under the auspices of the Police Act 1995. The Police Board, which is chaired by the Police Commissioner, develops the Government's priorities and general directions into objectives for each police department and national unit, including the Police University College, which is also known as POLAMK (Poliisi, 2022). Democratic control is also exercised through

the Advisory Board of Police Affairs in conjunction with the Ministry of the Interior. The Council of State appoints the chairman, vice-chairman, and members as well as their personal deputy members. The Board is appointed for a maximum of three years. Each local police department also has an advisory board to deal with police affairs and police operations. Municipal councils elect the members of the local advisory boards for the duration of their term of office.

1.2.3 Governance and oversight of initial police learning

Broadly, the governance and oversight of initial police learning within each of the case study countries encapsulates the ‘three worlds’ of national Governments (be that the SPA in Scotland, or the Ministries of the Interiors in Sweden and Finland); academia; and policing (Police Scotland, the Swedish Police Authority, and the Police Board in Finland). However, as this study shows, the extent to which these three worlds interact with one another and influence policy and its operationalisation, varies.

Briefly, in Scotland, Police Scotland has a virtual monopoly as regards both. Whilst academia’s involvement has ebbed and flowed on the ‘tides and currents’ (Greene, 2012) of Scottish policing’s internal politics, the Scottish Government, through the SPA, appears from the data gathered for this study in 2019, to have played a largely passive role. In Sweden on the other hand, national Governments have had considerable involvement in agenda setting and policy formulation. Whilst the Police Authority have retained ‘ownership’ of the national curriculum, delivery of the initial two-year ‘classroom-based’ phase of the two-and-a-half-year programme, has been contracted out to five mainstream universities. In Finland, national Governments, as in Scotland, have played a largely passive role, with agenda setting, policy formulation, and its operationalisation sitting primarily with policing, supported by academia and POLAMK. That said, in 2013, the Finnish Parliament enacted the 2013 Police University College Act (Jansson *et al.*, 2018, p.432), which had been driven largely by the police and academia. The Act stipulated that POLAMK be awarded University of Applied Science status, that it provides university-level education, and that it has autonomy with respect to teaching and research. It led to the previous two-year, pre-entry Diploma for policing students, evolving into the current three-year,

pre-entry, BSc accredited, initial learning programme. The Act provides that POLAMK is overseen by the National Police Board, which is chaired by the Police Commissioner in Finland, which in turn is under the direction of the administrative sector of the Ministry of the Interior (Jansson *et al.*, 2018). The Act also suggests that POLAMK has its own Board, chaired by POLAMK's Director. The Board is appointed by the National Police Board, serves for three-year terms, with membership comprising POLAMK Personnel, Bachelor's Degree and Master's Degree students, representatives from the Emergency Services College, students completing their Bachelor's Degree, and representatives from other internal security authorities and organisations in the field. Amongst other duties, the Board ratifies the curricula for the undergraduate and postgraduate degree programs.

1.3 Initial police learning in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland

1.3.1 Scotland

Acceptance onto Police Scotland's two-year, post-entry, initial police learning programme does not require any academic qualifications. Having passed the selection process, which includes basic numerical and English comprehension tests amongst others, new entrants must successfully complete the two-year Probationer Training Programme to be appointed permanently. Unlike in Sweden and Finland, new entrants are attested as constables in the first week of the programme, which endows them with all the powers which accompany that office and are fully salaried.

Police 'recruits' as they are known in Scotland, then attend an eleven-week Initial Training Course (ITC) at the Scottish Police College, which is delivered by Police Scotland staff, who are largely experienced police officers. It focuses on providing the minimum knowledge and skills required to begin the twenty-one-month 'on-the-job' practice phase. Subject to successful completion of the ITC, recruits are then deployed to a 'shift' or team of uniformed, first response officers with responsibility for policing a defined geographical area, where they undertake a twenty-one month 'on-the-job' practice phase. Initially recruits are mentored by a 'tutor', a more experienced police constable on the shift. There are no further classroom-based theoretical learning

phases during the probationary period, but recruits must pass a series of knowledge, skills, and fitness tests. On successful completion of the programme, recruits are confirmed in the rank of constable, with employment in a full-time, permanent post being assured, unlike in Sweden and Finland. At the time of writing (mid-2022), the two-year initial learning programme had recently become part of the Modern Apprenticeship Scheme, which not only enables Police Scotland to draw down funding from the UK Government's apprenticeship levy, but also for a new Scottish Qualifications Authority (SQA) Certificate in Policing to be awarded to recruits who have successfully completed the programme. Whilst SQA approval creates a tighter external quality assurance regime, decisions concerning programme curriculum, delivery methods, and so on, remain under the complete control of Police Scotland. The Scottish approach has been categorised as an example of the "Anglo-Saxon" model of initial police learning by Moberg (2020, p.57), "where police students undergo a short vocational training period that does not require previous education."

1.3.2 Sweden

In Sweden, prospective recruits must have the requisite secondary school qualifications for entry to undergraduate-level, university-based, degree programmes. Having successfully completed the selection process, which includes rigorous psychological assessment, they attend one of five Swedish Police Authority approved universities for two years, where they are taught by university academics and experienced police officers. During this initial two-year, university-based learning phase, they do not come under the control of the Police Authority, are not salaried, do not have the legal powers of a police officer, and are not operationally deployable. In comparison with the eleven-week Initial Training Course in Scotland, this initial 'classroom-based' phase, aims to develop a more comprehensive theoretical knowledge and practical skills base. They must then successfully complete six months of 'on-the-job' practice learning, supervised by experienced 'tutor' constables. During this phase, they are temporarily employed as 'aspirants' (probationary officers) by the Swedish Police Authority, during which they receive a salary, and are endowed with the powers of a police officer.

On completion of the practice phase, ‘aspirants’ return to university to reflect on their practice experience, before ‘graduating’ from the programme in ceremonies which echo those of university graduation ceremonies. Unlike in Finland, ‘graduation’ does not result in the award of an academic qualification, although some universities offer credit points as recognition of prior learning, which can be put, in conjunction with further HE learning, towards degree accreditation. On successful completion of the programme, students can apply to be permanently appointed as a police constable. Whilst successful completion of the programme does not guarantee employment as a police officer, at the time of data gathering, on-going challenges concerning the attraction of policing students and the retention of early career officers, coupled with the uplift in officer numbers, meant that in practice, there was a surfeit of vacancies. Although not degree accredited, the initial police learning programme in Sweden reflects the approach in Nordic countries, which have “a tradition for having long and academically oriented police education programmes” (Moberg, 2020, p.57). There has been a long-running political debate, primarily between the Social Democrats and the Conservative parties, around developing the programme into a 3-year Bachelor’s Degree, although this debate remains unresolved.

1.3.3 Finland

In Finland, policing students require the minimum level of secondary school qualifications for entry to a University of Applied Science. Having successfully completed the selection process, which, as in Sweden, includes rigorous psychological assessment, they undertake a three-year, pre-entry policing programme. This comprises an initial eighteen-month period of theoretical and vocational learning based at POLAMK, where, as in Sweden, they are taught by university academics and experienced police officers. During this initial eighteen-month learning phase, they are not salaried, do not have the legal powers of a police officer, and are not operationally deployable. As in Sweden, this initial ‘classroom-based’ phase, aims to develop a more comprehensive theoretical knowledge and practical skills base. They must then successfully complete an eleven-month ‘on-the-job’ practice learning phase, supervised by experienced ‘tutor’ constables. During this phase, they are temporarily employed as police officers, during which they receive a salary, and are

endowed with the powers of a police officer. They then return to POLAMK for twenty weeks, during which they complete a work-related dissertation. On successful completion of the programme, students are awarded a Bachelor's degree and can apply for a permanent position. As in Sweden, the initial police learning programme is provided to students free of charge, with state-provided grants and loans available for living expenses.

1.3.4 Wider UK and north-western European context

Within the wider UK context, policing in England and Wales has recently seen the introduction of the Policing Education Qualifications Framework (PEQF, 2020) by the College of Policing (COP), which means that all recruits will require a degree to be confirmed in the role of police constable. This might either be a degree in professional policing that applicants have undertaken prior to joining the police, a non-policing degree (which requires the additional completion of a two-year graduate diploma in professional policing practice), or a three-year Police Constable Degree Apprenticeship (PCDA). The PCDA is delivered by a police force in collaboration with a HE provider and is subject to policies and guidelines issued by national apprenticeship agencies. PCDA student officers must have at least two Advanced Level, secondary school qualifications to gain entry, are employed by the police, salaried, have the powers of a police officer, and undertake a part-time undergraduate policing degree whilst also operating as front-line, first-response constables. In Northern Ireland, police recruits undertake twenty-three weeks of learning at the Northern Ireland Police College which is university accredited, and results in the award of an Advanced Diploma in Policing.

Europe has different models of police education, with those in the Nordic region (which includes Sweden and Finland) being, in comparison with Scotland, “relatively academic and long”, and requiring secondary school qualifications for admission (Fekjær and Petersson, 2019, p.938). These programmes have moved away from traditional police training schools to become closely aligned with HE either through the development of specialist Police University Colleges (as in Finland), or specialist police learning faculties within mainstream universities (as in Sweden). Increasingly,

these programmes involve a vocationally focused undergraduate degree which comprises theoretical learning (episteme), combined with the development of technical or ‘craft’ skills (techne), and experiential learning during a tutor-supervised, ‘on-the-job’ learning phase which takes place within the “swampy..., messy, confusing” (Schön, 1987, p.3) environment of operational policing.

1.4 Justification for the research

Despite the rapidly expanding academisation and degree accreditation of initial police learning, the empirical evidence base is “scant and inconclusive” (Terpstra and Schaap, 2021, p.1). Much of the discourse within the literature is, as Brown (2020) has argued, founded largely on questionable Anglo-American studies and theorising. Hough and Stanko (2019, p.5) argued that the PEQF “is based on the presumption that degree entry will confer considerable benefits on policing” which, whilst “supported by some research evidence... probably rests more on professional judgement and experience than formal research”. Early scoping undertaken to identify case study countries indicated that this may also have been the case as regards initial police learning in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland.

Cross-national comparative studies systematically analyse “national realities to identify similarities and differences” (de Maillard and Roché, 2018, p.385). Within the broader sociology of profession literature, scholars such as Noordegraaf and Steijn, (2013, p.236), have called for comparative studies within different national contexts as they “might be valuable to develop more refined understandings” of the “reconfiguration of professional public services”. Whilst comparative approaches are “always relevant” they argued, “there seems to be all the more reason to compare public service sectors and (national) contexts” (Noordegraaf and Steijn, 2013, p. 236). The report *Perspectives on Police Sciences in Europe* (2007) by the European Agency for Law Enforcement Training’s (CEPOL) Project Group on a European Approach to Police Science, highlighted the need for “truly comparative studies of police as an institution and of policing as an activity” (Bjorgo and Damen, 2020, p. xvi). Up until that point, it was claimed, there had been “no attempts to compare between countries

with very different systems of policing and police education” (Bjorgo and Damen, 2020, p. xvi).

Despite this leading to a recently published longitudinal study (Bjorgo and Damen, 2020) which encapsulated six European countries, including Scotland and Sweden, but not Finland, the data for these initial findings was gathered several years ago, since when as the authors themselves acknowledged, “seismic changes have taken place within policing”, including initial police learning. Whilst that study focused on the perceptions of policing students and recruits regarding the impact of initial police learning on their professional development, it only included data gathered around a decade ago from Scottish recruits undertaking the initial phase of the learning. Scotland withdrew from the study shortly thereafter. Whilst the study revealed interesting findings which advance the discourse within this field, it did not explore how and why the different approaches to initial police learning had developed.

This thesis therefore seeks to address the rationale underpinning the different approaches to initial police learning within Scotland, Sweden, and Finland. In doing so, it will analyse the extent to which the socially, culturally, and politically constructed notions of profession, professionalism and professionalisation have influenced HE’s role within the respective initial police learning programmes. In doing so, it not only aims to provide empirical insights into the relatively scant research with regards academic education within initial police learning in the case study countries, but also to make a meaningful contribution to policy and practice. This comparative approach, therefore, provides an opportunity to draw out the key characteristics of particular social, political, and organisational contexts in influencing policy formulation and its operationalisation within the case study countries.

1.5 Aim, objectives, and research questions

Rather than repeat previous attempts to analyse the impact of HE on the attitudes and beliefs of individual police officers, this study focuses on the perceptions of those within academia and policing who influence policy and practice in this area, those who implement it, and those who are its intended beneficiaries, namely the police recruits

and policing students. The study also aims to explore and understand the extent to which these perceptions have been influenced by factors such as organisational culture, myths, realities, and the reconfiguration of professional work (Martin and Wooff, 2020).

1.5.1 Research questions

The principal research question therefore is:

“To what extent do the different social, cultural, and political contexts in Scotland, Sweden and Finland influence the perception of the role of higher education in police recruit learning?”

The study was further guided by the following supplementary research questions:

1. How has initial police learning evolved in the case study countries?
2. What knowledge, skills and behaviours do ‘policy network actors’ (Savage, Charman and Cope, 2000) within the case study countries perceive as desirable in a professional police officer?
3. To what extent are the current approaches to initial police learning perceived by ‘policy network actors’ within the case study countries as helping in the development of desirable professional attributes?
4. What factors explain the divergence between ‘policy network actors’ perceptions within the case study countries on the impact, or potential impact, of academic education on the professionalisation of police recruits and policing students?

These supplementary questions are designed to guide the study on a journey which will culminate in a series of findings which address the primary research question.

1.6 Thesis summary

Chapter 1 begins by providing a brief, broad overview of how policing is organised in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland, including the governance and oversight of initial police learning. It then outlines attempts within Western-style police agencies to continue to professionalise policing by involving HE in the education of their police recruits and police students. It explains that whilst this has led to a trend of academisation within other north-western European countries, Scotland has retained the traditional, ‘craft’ approach. The justification for this study is also provided together with the study's research questions.

Chapter 2 provides a “comprehensive assessment and critical interpretation” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p. 84) of literature and research that are relevant to the research questions (King and Wincup, 2008, p.18). It critically analyses the discourse concerning the academisation of initial police learning and explores and analyses relevant debates within the sociology of profession literature. It concludes by arguing that no comparative, empirical studies appear to have been undertaken which analyse the role of academic education in initial police learning within Scotland, Sweden, and Finland, and the extent to which they were perceived as helping or hindering professionalisation.

Chapter 3 presents and justifies the multiple, cross-national, case study research framework and *emic* approach to gathering data research which was selected for this study. It highlights how, through a purposive and snowballing sampling strategy, forty-nine, one-to-one, semi-structured interviews and six focus groups involving 86 participants provided a rich, in depth, multi-faceted analysis and understanding of the research problem. Ethical considerations are also explored, during which my positionality as an ‘outsider insider’ researcher (Brown, 1996), together with gathering data from people for whom English is a second language, are highlighted. Finally, the chapter presents considerations regarding data recording, data security, data analysis, and data evaluation.

Chapter 4 explores and uncovers what and who influenced policymaking, together with the ‘how’ of the policy-making processes, within the case study countries. It highlights how the extent of interplay and relational power between the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of national Governments, academia, and policing, are key to understanding the similarities and differences in the evolution of initial police learning within the case study countries.

Chapter 5 focuses upon contrasting notions of organisational and occupational professionalism in the case study countries and analyses their interplay with the extent to which epistemic, ‘craft’, and experiential knowledge were foregrounded as privileged forms of knowledge, and sources of cultural capital, within initial police learning. In revealing that ethical decision making was often foregrounded by participants when exploring their understanding of professionalism, this chapter argues for a greater appreciation of ‘practical wisdom’ (*phronesis*) as part of ethical decision making by professionals working within challenging and complex environments.

Chapter 6 uncovers the extent to which participants in the case study countries perceived the overall learning architecture of their respective initial learning programmes, were helping to develop prevailing notions of police professionalism. It highlights that whilst the programmes in Scotland and Finland were generally perceived as being helpful, this was not the case in Sweden, where the two-year, university-based initial ‘classroom’ phase, followed by a six-month practice phase, was perceived by police officers as foregrounding the needs of academia over those of policing.

Chapter 7 foregrounds how academics, police officers, and policing students in Sweden (despite their perception that the needs of academia were being foregrounded over those of policing) and Finland perceived degree-level education as enhancing professionalism. However, whilst HE and qualifications were acknowledged as forms of self-legitimacy by police officers in Scotland and those in oversight and governance roles, they had no organisational legitimacy. Concerns in Scotland that the introduction of a graduate-entry only policy might deter applicants from socially or

economically deprived backgrounds, thereby adversely affecting policing's representativeness, are also highlighted.

Chapter 8 discusses the key themes developed within the findings chapters through the lenses of meaning, context, and process. It argues that the tendency amongst academics, and some senior police officers, to draw on the trait-based paradigm of defining profession, conflicts with contemporary notions of profession which are being reconfigured by the social, cultural, and political realities of public service work, including policing. It then moves on to discuss the multi-directional influence of context on agenda setting, policy formulation, and the extent to which intended policy outcomes were being realised. Finally, it reflects on the broader implications and challenges of police professionalisation through HE and explores how the findings from this study might be drawn upon to develop an alternative approach to the ongoing professionalisation of policing where HE is precluded (as in Scotland), through the targeted use of micro-credentials.

Chapter 9 reflects on the application of the research design, focusing on the benefits and challenges of undertaking a multiple, cross-national comparative analysis, of gathering data from people for whom English is a second language, and of being an 'outsider insider' researcher.

Chapter 10 directs attention to how the research questions have been successfully addressed. In doing so it discusses the central contribution to this thesis: that police professionalisation has different meanings in different social, cultural, and political contexts which helps to understand why there is no consensus about how policing should be professionalised; that professionalising policing through the academisation of initial police learning is not necessarily the answer and that different approaches are appropriate; and that the approaches deployed must be attuned to the different social, cultural, and political contexts in which they are situated. This thesis addresses a knowledge gap where empirically based, cross-national comparative studies of this type are limited. It also makes several recommendations for policy and practice, including future policymaking processes, the duration of learning phases, and moving away from traditional learning environments which focus on acculturation into cultural norms, and towards those which focus on learning. The chapter concludes

with a discussion of the study's limitations, makes suggestions for future research, and provides some brief concluding thoughts before bringing the thesis to a close.

Chapter 2: Literature review

Introduction

Chapter 2, comprising five sections, provides an overview and critical analysis of relevant scholarly literature, in terms of informing this study's design, which existed prior to the commencement of data gathering in 2019². However, there are subsequent studies which inform the analysis, discussion and concluding chapters.

It begins (section 2.1) by presenting the approach taken, namely a “reasonably comprehensive assessment and critical interpretation” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.84) of the literatures from the broad and vibrant topic of police professionalisation through HE and “which bear directly on the emerging research question” (King and Wincup, 2008, p.18). However, given that much of the research has been undertaken in a limited range of countries, principally the UK, the USA, and Australia, with little having been found in relation to Sweden and Finland which was in English, the literature base is rather narrow.

Section 2.2 begins by providing an overview and critical analysis of the evolution of various theoretical vantage points within the sociology of profession literature. It then moves on to highlight how, within public services, the trait-based, ‘classic’ notion of profession is being countered by a more philosophical, holistic, and ‘hybrid’ notion (Noordegraaf, 2015). This alternative discourse moves beyond the veil created by a list of ‘traits’, to encapsulate the ‘motivational force, the ‘belief system’ (Wynia *et al.*, 2014), which more closely reflects the ‘reconfigured’ realities and complexities of professional work within the ambiguous occupational domains of public services, which are subjected to ‘hybrid notions of occupational control, reconfiguration, restratification, and relocation (Noordegraaf, 2016). It then critically analyses the debate concerning the symbolism of profession as a disciplinary logic and means by

² Some journal articles were ‘on-line first’ articles which were subsequently published and allocated post-2019 publication dates.

which employers promote professionalisation strategies, before concluding with an analysis of the complex and contested debates about policing as a profession and policing's attempts to professionalise. In doing so, it highlights several recurring themes within the literature concerning the closer alignment of initial police learning with HE as part of wider, on-going professionalisation agendas which reflect a greater acknowledgement by the academy that the complex, situated, and rapidly shifting social, cultural, political, and economic contexts of police work on the one hand, and police culture, police knowledge and knowing on the other, have become inextricably intertwined.

The chapter then moves on in section 2.3, to critically analyse the rich and significant volume of research and theory concerning 'police culture' which, despite being complicated, contested, and contradictory, has dominated academic debate for the past half century. It begins with the 'classic' accounts which frequently portrayed police culture as 'homogenous, static, and unchanging (Loftus, 2009), negative (Silvestri, 2017), rigid and linear (Aston, Murray and O'Neill, 2021). It then moves on to explore contemporary accounts which have modified and refined the 'classic' accounts and led to more nuanced, complex, and multifaceted understandings of police culture which suggest a 'cultural plurality (Hendriks and van Hulst, 2016) shaped by internal organisational and external operating environments (Atkinson, 2017). In doing so, it highlights Charman's (2017) longitudinal study of police recruits in England which showed that the 'old characteristics' of police culture, such as the blue code of silence and crime fighting, were being buried and replaced by new characteristics such as self-protection, compassion, and communication. The culture of this 'new breed of police officer was over layering the heroic, crime-fighting, machismo culture of previous generations of officers.

Section 2.4 explores and analyses relevant debates within the literature concerning police professionalisation through the academisation of initial police learning. It begins by exploring literature regarding the traditional approach to preparing new entrants for independent patrol, before moving on to analyse the debate concerning the organisational and individual benefits which might be derived from the

academisation of initial police learning. In doing so, it highlights the claims of some scholars that much of the empirical literature on which these arguments are founded, is neither consistent nor compelling (Brown, 2020). It then moves on to analyse relevant literature concerning the associated challenges of police professionalisation through HE, highlighting the often binary, reductionist discourse which consistently portrays a fundamental perceptual dichotomy between not only the ‘two-worlds’ of academia and policing (Hallenberg, 2012), but also between reforming ‘management cops’ (and politicians) and ‘street cops’ (Ruess-Ianni and Ianni, 1983, cited in Punch, 2007, p.108). Finally, it builds on Hallenberg’s (2012) theoretical concept of “two-worlds-thinking” regarding the interplay between academia and policing, to encapsulate the relationship with the ‘third-world’ of politics highlighted by Furuhagen (2015) and Green (2018). The resultant concept of ‘three-worlds thinking’ has been utilised in this study to create new knowledge concerning the interplay and relational power, between politics, academia, and policing, during policy formulation and its implementation in the case study countries.

The chapter concludes (section 2.5) by arguing that there are gaps within the literature: that no comparative, empirically-based studies appear to have been undertaken which investigate why policy makers in Scotland, Sweden and Finland adopted different strategies with regards the role of academic education in initial police learning; that there appears to have been little research exploring contemporary notions of profession and professionalisation with the case study countries; that there has been little research attention given of the extent to which, within Scotland, Sweden and Finland, their respective policy approaches were perceived as helping professionalisation; and that there has been little research which explores perceptions in Scotland, Sweden and Finland concerning HE’s role within their respective initial police learning programmes.

2.1 Approach

Whilst not exhaustive, this review seeks “to arrive at an overview of [the] field of study through a reasonably comprehensive assessment and critical interpretation of

the literature” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p. 84). The emphasis is on “*relevance* of the material, rather than striving for comprehensiveness” (Robson, 2011, p. 51). “Relevant’ works are those that have important implications for the design, conduct, or interpretation of the study, not simply those that deal with the topic” (Maxwell, 2006, p.28). As King and Wincup (2008, p.18) suggested:

The reality is that reviewing the literature, or more precisely literatures, has to be done with a clear sense of purpose. In each and every case the key question to pose must be what relevance does this have for my research? An appropriate review of the literature *excludes* those pieces of work which do not bear directly on the emerging research question.

Therefore, in exploring the main themes and concepts of current and past works as they relate to the research questions, this chapter seeks to synthesise and critically analyse the strengths and weaknesses of relevant empirical and theoretical literature drawn from the sociologies of professionalism, organisational theory, and policing. It also seeks to highlight any relevant knowledge gaps.

2.2 Sociology of profession literature

How the *differentia specifica* (Brante, 2011, p.5) of professions should be defined, has “haunted studies of professions for a long time” (Brante, 2011, p.4). However, whilst it has been suggested in the sociology of professions, “from various theoretical vantage points, that debating the definition of profession is “a sterile exercise...it is actually at the root of understanding what professions are about and how they operate” (Saks, 2012, p.1). This chapter, therefore, begins with an analysis of the key theoretical concepts within the sociology of profession literature.

Professions are often regarded in the sociology of profession literature as “a particular kind of occupation or an institution with special characteristics” (Evetts, 2014, p.31). These special characteristics are used to separate some occupations, such as the “classic professions... medicine and the law” (Lumsden, 2017, p.3) from other occupations, and professionals from other workers (Collins, Dewing and Russell, 2009). In attempting to clarify these ‘special characteristics’, the study of professions

has tended to characterise them “as occupations (with a focus on professional work, labour markets and inequalities), and professions as part of social order and regulations” (Lumsden, 2017, p.3). One such account of profession is the functionalist account which appears to have emerged from, and been influenced by, sociological concepts which argue for a “functional relationship between professions and society” (Saks, 2012, p.2). For example: the Durkheimian perspective of collective social solidarity in modern, advanced societies through occupation and division of labour; and the “Foucauldian notion of professionalisation as a mode of disciplinary control” (Lumsden, 2017, p.5) whereby the governed, through the microphysics of power, “are constituted as autonomous subjects, regulating their own conduct” (Fournier, 1999, p. 284). The Durkheimian perspective suggests that within modern advanced societies the division of labour into complex, organised segments through the market and the State, makes people more reliant on one another, and thereby wider society, through the different functions they perform. Social bonds become more like contracts in modern societies. Drawing on the Foucauldian notion of liberal government, the State attempts “to reconcile freedom (of individuals, of the market) and control” (Fournier, 1999, p.283). Professions are central to liberal government and the requisite “microphysics of power (Foucault, 1973) through which the governed are constituted as autonomous subjects, regulating their own conduct” (Fournier, 1999, p.284). Scholars subscribing to this notion of professions, such as Carr-Saunders and Wilson (1933, cited in Saks, 2012), argued that they were therefore, a stabilising force in society.

In developing the argument that professions are part of social order, Parsons (1951) recognised that professions, together with the “capitalist economy, [and] the rational-legal social order...were all interrelated and mutually balancing in the maintenance and stability of a fragile normative social order” (Evetts, 2003, p.400). In maintaining this stability and normative social order, professions, and occupations “presume to tell the rest of their society what is good and right for them” which requires ‘lay-people’ to “place their trust in professional workers”, and in doing so, to accept professional’s authority (Evetts, 2003, p.400). Professionals require “to be worthy of that trust, and to maintain it” by developing “the authority of the expert and cultivating “a proper

balance between self and collective interest” (Evetts, 2003, pp.400-406). This traditionally formed the basis of a social contract in return for which occupations were afforded professional status which, in turn, usually afforded them elite social status (Colins *et al.*, 2009 – in Lumsden 2017, p.3), power, financial rewards, and a high degree of autonomy and self-regulation. Within this sociological account of professions, professions “are viewed as elements of a larger system that is shaped by inter-professional rivalry as well as by producer and client dynamics” (Lumsden, 2017, p.4). These dynamics establish professional ‘jurisdiction’ and status once “members are able to successfully defend claims to esoteric knowledge” when challenged by others (Lumsden, 2017, p.4). Professional status, therefore, within this functionalist tradition is “contested, negotiated and socially constructed, involving boundary-work and identity-work” (Lumsden, 2017, p.4).

However, as scholars have frequently argued, being a professional “is also about conducting and constituting oneself in an appropriate manner” (Fournier, 1999, p.287). In other words, conducting oneself in a professional manner, or with professionalism:

Re-imagining labour as offering ‘professional service’ serves to construct an image of quality and reliability appealing to the allegedly increasingly discerning and demanding customer; it also opens up some imaginary space within which self-actualising employees can strive for continuous fulfilment and improvement. (Fournier, 1999, p.299)

To become so central Fournier (1999, p.285) argued, professions need to become legitimate and worthy of the label profession:

The inscription of the professions within the network of liberal government is conditional upon the professions conducting themselves in appropriate ways; that is, in ways that are recognised as legitimate and worthy of the ‘professional label’ both by the relevant profession itself, and by other constituents in that network (e.g. the clients, the state, the market)... Thus the professions have to establish their legitimacy in the eyes of those in the name of whom they govern (e.g. state, clients).

Professions establish their legitimacy within the chain of connections “through the proliferation of expert practical knowledge [which]... can govern events and

individual conduct ‘at a distance’... rather than through the exercise of domination over oppressed subjects” (Fournier, 1999, p.283). As Fournier (1999, pp.285-286) argued, this reputation:

may depend on conformity with local customs and beliefs than on professional criteria...it is never established once and for all but is continuously contested and re-negotiated. Thus, the professions need to establish and continuously work at maintaining their legitimacy in terms that map over with the norms and values of other actors in the network of liberal government (e.g., other professions, clients, state, media).

The task of moving beyond these earlier observations on professions as distinctive groups, different from other occupations in the division of labour, has been attributed by many scholars to have begun with “Parson’s... early distinction between professionals and bureaucrats” (Lumsden, 2017, p.3). This simple distinction evolved into the taxonomic approach of the 1950s and 1960s, in which professions “were seen as possessing a diverse range of characteristics [which] centrally encompassed knowledge and expertise” (Saks, 2012, p.2). This was developed, it was argued, through “theoretical knowledge, long education, examinations, licensing, specific association, organization, various types of control, collegiality, ethics, work for the common good, autonomy, discretion, sometimes class position” (Brante, 2011, p.5). It is generally recognized by those scholars who subscribe to this trait-based definitional approach, that “recognized professions typically had a stronger formal knowledge and higher educational base than other occupations” (Saks, 2012, p.2). This, it has been argued, was important “especially in versions of the approach that presented such characteristics in the form of an ‘ideal type’, against which professions could be judged” (Saks, 2012, p.2). Whilst there is a plethora of different traits suggested within the broader literature, there are some traits which are more frequently identified. Green and Gates’ (2014) literature review for example, identified ‘characteristic clusters’ which reflect those traits and which are more frequently identified: social movement, socialisation into the profession, ‘exclusive’ self-organising membership, registration, and system of rewards which supports a degree of monopoly rights in respect of practicing the profession; autonomy (particularly from political interference); self-regulation, code of ethics and accountability; higher

education, lifelong commitment to learning; and a body of knowledge (often referred to as a ‘unique corpus of knowledge’).

Within the trait-based notion of profession, the concept a ‘continuum of professions’ is important to some scholars. This approach categorises professions into “league tables glorifying one or other professions depending on the range and weighting” of traits (Saks, 2012, p. 2). This ranges from the more powerful, high-status ‘classic professions’ such as medicine and law (Eraut, 1994), through the less powerful ‘emerging’ or ‘semi-professions’ (Etzioni, 1969), which are neither a ‘true’ profession, nor an ‘artisan’ occupation, to artisan occupations. The Aristotelian concept of “‘techne’ – ‘knowing how to’ – was the equivalent of craft knowledge, it was an art (hence the term ‘Artisan’ and was... variable and context dependent...)” (Grint, 2007, p. 234). Policing has often been categorised within the literature as either an artisan occupation, or a semi-profession.

However, some scholars have criticized both the functionalist and trait-based writers and argued that they were “reflexively presenting professional ideology rather than reality (Saks, 2012, p.2). Others scholars, such as Eraut (1994), have argued that the concept of profession should be considered as an ideology, without attempting to distinguish ‘true’ professions from others, that professions are a group of occupations the boundary of which is ill-defined. This perspective suggests that merely developing a list of attributes which can simply be ticked off for an occupation to be considered a profession, or for an individual to be considered a professional, was not sufficiently nuanced. It does not, some scholars have argued, provide an adequate understanding of the complexity of professional work within “ambiguous occupational domains”, such as public services, which are subjected to “hybrid” notions of “occupational control” (Noordegraaf, 2007, p.761), and to reconfiguration through reorganisation, restratification, and relocation (Noordegraaf, 2013, 2015, 2016). Scholars espousing this view challenge the notion that occupations can be defined as “pure” (Noordegraaf, 2007, p. 761), and have argued that whether an occupation is or is not to be regarded as a profession within complex, modern societies cannot be determined absolutely, and that there should be no “attempting to distinguish ‘true’ profession

from other contenders...” (Eraut, 1994, p.1). Rather, a more holistic view should be taken, considering the issue from various perspectives. For example, taking account of the views of connective occupations or professions (Dingwall and Allen, 2001), the public (Freidson, 1999, p.117), or members of the occupation itself (Furuhagen, 2015, pp.30-31). This phenomenological, philosophical, holistic approach goes beyond the “veil created by lists of professional expectations and suggests [the] *why...*”, the “motivational force – the belief system” (Wynia *et al.*, 2014, p.712), or essence of what it means to be a professional, which the trait-based paradigm fails to fully capture. For example, studies of police officers, such as Lumsden’s (2017) four-year longitudinal study of fifteen police recruits from an English force, found that they had a strongly held belief that policing was more than just a job, as did Loftus’s (2009) oft-cited ethnographic study within a northern English police force. This reflects the views of scholars such as Scott (1999, p.52) that:

Professionalism is ... as an ideology, a set of beliefs and values which underpin its activities. In particular, professionalism embodies the values of service, integrity, and reliable standards.

Despite criticism of the trait approach, some scholars such as (Thursfield, 2012), have argued that the trait-based model is still necessarily drawn upon in contemporary conceptualisations of profession. Much of the police professionalisation literature, for example, often argues that to be considered a pure profession policing should, establish codes of ethical practice, professional bodies (such as the COP in England and Wales), and align learning more closely with HE in order that it could start developing a unique corpus of knowledge (Rogers and Frevel, 2018, p.75; Neyroud, 2011, p.44).

However, despite the arguments of scholars such as Thursfield (2012), and police practitioners (as he was then) such as Neyroud (2011), a general agreement appears to be emerging within contemporary literature that the concept of ‘profession’ is changing. The increasingly “complex and challenging world” (Schön, 1987, xiii) in which professionals operate, especially those within public services, is being reflected in a more nuanced discourse of professionalism amongst some scholars of the early twenty-first century. Scholars such as Evetts (2018), Noordegraaf (2015, 2016), and

Noordegraaf and Steijn (2013) for example, recognise the rapidly increasing complexity of capitalist economies within which contemporary western organisations and workers operate. This includes policing, which some scholars have argued, is being “substantially impacted by the process of late modernity” (Cockcroft and Hallenberg, 2021, p.3), including “profound and rapid social complexity” (McLaughlin, 2007, p.87).

However, there are divergent views as to the drivers and outcomes of that change with regards notions of profession. Julia Evetts (2018, p.45) for example, argued that managerial concepts such as New Public Management are the main drivers behind a “top-down” re-branding of the ideology of profession by managers of bureaucratic organisations. The focus of this top-down re-branding is to drive change, drive performance, control work and control workers, which has shifted professional values towards rationality and efficiency. Echoing the trait-based approach to defining profession and professionalism, scholars such as Evetts (2018), have argued that this has led to an increasing tension between individual professionalism as an occupational value on the one hand, and professionalism as an organisational managerialist value on the other. In rejecting this notion, Noordegraaf (2007) on the other hand, argued that in reality, most professions are at best a ‘hybrid’ of both.

Noordegraaf (2016, p.789) argued that these neoliberal managerial redesigns of professional work “often remain too organizational” and should instead be “related to wider social and societal trends and developments” in which professional work is reconfigured (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.790). These broader societal, economic, and cultural shifts require a re-thinking of the “constructed and therefore relative nature of traditional professionalism” (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.803). For example, service sector professionals are increasingly working in large-scale, horizontally fragmented organisations which are operating within challenging budgetary constraints, all of which requires increasingly well-organised, effective, and efficient management of demand and resources: what Noordegraaf (2016) refers to as ‘reorganization’ and ‘restratification’. Professional work he argued, is also being ‘relocated’ and ‘fluid’ across organisational and professional boundaries, locally, nationally, and

internationally (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.791). Importantly, for the purposes of this study, he suggests that these reconfigurations may or may not occur at all, and that if they do, they may not all occur at the same time. Differences in the interplay between broader social, cultural, political, and economic contexts on the one hand, and organisational and occupational cultures on the other (Bourdieu's concepts of 'field' and 'habitus'³) within Scotland, Sweden, and Finland, may therefore help to understand and explain notions of profession, professionalism, and the role of HE within initial police learning programmes as part of wider, on-going professionalisation agendas.

2.2.1 The symbolism of profession

Despite the divergent discourse concerning professions and professionalism within the literature, many scholars, such as Evetts (2003, p. 30) recognise:

...the power of the discourse of professionalism and how professionalism is increasingly used both as an ideology to promote occupational change and control as well as a disciplinary mechanism for professional and aspiring professional workers in new as well as existing occupational contexts.

Drawing on the "Foucauldian notion of profession as a mode of disciplinary control" (Lumsden, 2017, p.5), it has been argued by some scholars that the powerful symbolism of profession is increasingly being used by wide range of occupations as a "disciplinary logic" (Lumsden, 2017, p.6), which "services to profess 'appropriate' work identities and conducts" (Fournier, 1999, p.280), and thereby to control workers (Evetts, 2009). It has also been argued that the symbolism of profession is being used by employers to promote "occupational change and...based on Foucauldian concepts

³ "In simple terms, a field is a social space of conflict and competition, where certain resources (capital) and constraints are at stake, while habitus is a system of dispositions that integrate past experience and enable individuals to cope with a diversity of unforeseen situations. In policing, these dispositions include the skills, cognitions, attitudes, values, and physical attributes officers acquire as part of being in the job" (Chan, 2007b, p.131).

of legitimacy” (Evetts, 2009, p.140) by which, through negotiation, “make a claim for authority, expertise, and status” (Lumsden, 2017, p.3).

However, despite the powerful symbolism of profession and professionalism, it has been “interpreted in different ways (both positive and negative) at different times by sociologists” (Evetts, 2003, p.27). For example, some scholars have portrayed professions in general as “powerful, privileged, self-interested monopolies (Evetts, 2003, p. 26), although since the 1990s, a reappraisal of the significance of professions has led some scholars to suggest that this is too simplistic and overly focused on the archetypical ‘classic’ professions of medicine and the law (Evetts, 2003, p.29). Others, such as Friedson (1999, 2001) have argued that professions are “a unique form of occupational control of work which has distinct advantages for both clients and practitioners, over market, organizational and bureaucratic forms of control which impoverish and standardize the quality of service to customers” (Evetts, 2003, pp.26-27).

2.2.2 Policing as a profession

As with other occupations within post-industrial knowledge societies (Noordegraaf, 2007, p.761) which are associated with “complexity, uncertainty, instability” (Schön, 1983, p.14), policing has faced pressure to continually professionalise. This reflects a broader discourse within the sociology of professions literature, including that concerning policing, which recognises the interplay between the increasingly complex external operating environments and internal policies and practices. Bayley (2016, p. 164) for example, suggested that “[p]olicing has become dramatically more complex in six ways: its tasks, public demands, strategies, technology, accountability, and resources”.

Much of the policing literature reflects policing’s attempts, as with other occupations, to professionalise “first and foremost by imitating classic, strong professions such as medicine and law” (Noordegraaf, 2007, p.761). However, debates within the academy about whether policing is a profession, a ‘semi-profession’ (Etzioni, 1969), or an

artisan trade (Jones, 2016, p.233) have often defined policing as a blue-collar occupation rather than a profession, which historically has recruited predominantly from blue-collar, working-class backgrounds (Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki, 2019, p.89; Kruse, 2020, p.11). Scotland, unlike other north-western European police services which have academised their initial police learning programmes, still does (Moberg, 2020, pp. 69-70). Scholars have argued that having police officers from diverse backgrounds who understand the social context of the communities from which they are drawn (Christopher, 2015), inspires public “trust and confidence” within those community groups, thereby enhancing opportunities to handle problems in a better way” (Moberg, 2020, p.58).

Whilst there have been “periodic, authoritative, public claims that the police are a profession” (Holdaway, 2017, p.2), as with much of the literature in this area, the debate about policing and police professionalism is complex. Despite this, Bryant, et al., (2014, p.388) argued that there has been general agreement that policing is not just a ‘job’ but has vocational aspects, the claim for which “normally gravitates around the themes of consensual legitimacy, personal authority, the exercise of discretion; themes that support the notion of the office of constable”. There is some evidence from empirical studies which suggest that police officers consider themselves to be professionals. For example, Lumsden’s (2017, p.10) study of police officers in England, suggested that police officers viewed policing “as a profession, a career” and a “lifetime commitment”. However, other scholars such as Charman (2017) take a contrary view, arguing that people entering policing, as in other public service occupations, no longer view it as a job for life. Indeed, the COP in England and Wales has recognised that the contemporary workforce needs to be flexible, with officers having the possibility of leaving and re-joining. This “optimistic view” of professionalism (Evetts, 2014, p.36) reflects the principle that professional work is that which is considered important to wider society. It also reflects the “motivational force – the belief system” (Wynia *et al.*, 2014, p.712) or essence of what it means to be a professional, which transcends lists of desirable professional attributes, including the requirement for new entrants to be graduates.

However, for some policing academics, policing remains “a public service bureaucracy with the ethos of “blue-collar factory workers” pre-occupied “with discipline, their quasi-military management practices” in their “rule-bound world which discourages initiative” (Bayley, 2008, p.14). This rather simplistic argument generates rather black and white dichotomies, such as between “professionals and managers” or between “professional” and “organizational logics”, whereas professional service realities as less black and white” (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.787). In challenging this polarised perspective, Noordegraaf (2016) argued that professional work, especially public service work, is being ‘reorganised’ (for example, through strategies such as New Public Management); ‘restratified’ (for example, through increased specialisation: what Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet (2019, p.344) termed “horizontal fragmentation” in relation to Scotland); and relocated (for example, community policing and multi-agency working), in response to increasingly complex and challenging social, cultural, political, and financial environments. This ‘reconfiguration” of professional work Noordegraaf (2015, p.187) argued, requires a hybrid professionalism which combines “professional and managerial principles such as autonomy and control, or quality and efficiency...to establish contemporary professional actions”.

It may be that this dichotomy will always remain within any notion of police professionalism, given the unquantifiable aspects of professional practice, and the “conflict between the detached stance of the professional and the continuing need for policing to adjust to the social flux within the community” (Rohl and Barnsley, 1995, p.238). These changing societal contexts, together with ‘encroachments’ of managerial controls and organisational reform has, some scholars argued, undermined the foundation of autonomous professional work (Noordegraaf, 2015, p.187). Whilst this might be viewed as a challenge to professional values and autonomy, which might result in “dualistic and oppositional understandings of professionalism versus managerialism”, the debate has “moved on” to show how both “might be intertwined in daily practices” into a “professional/managerial hybridity” (Noordegraaf, 2015, p. 188). Furthermore, his concept of the ‘re-location’ of professional work whereby the boundaries between the work of one occupation, profession, or organisation and the

‘outside worlds’ of others become more fluid’ (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.791), echo’s the inter-professional and cross-disciplinary realities of collaborative working amongst public services. This would tend to support the argument by reformists (for example, Hallenberg, 2017), that police professionalisation through HE can support the relocation of professional work (Noordegraaf, 2016), by providing entry-level police officers with a wider understanding of their role and positionality within a relocated public service landscape.

However, whilst it could be argued that policing does contain some of the “ideal typical” fundamental elements of a profession (Evetts, 2014, p.36), much of the reformist discourse espouses the view “it is lacking “a foundation in abstract concepts and formal learning” (Freidson, 2001, pp.34-35). Therefore, a prevailing view has emerged amongst policing scholars, especially those who research and theorise on police professionalisation, that the traditional ‘craft’ approach to initial police learning is no longer suitable to meet the 21st century needs of policing (Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2017, p.276).

Several recurring themes have been found within the literature which support a closer alignment of initial police learning with HE as part of a wider, on-going professionalisation agenda. Bayley (2016) for example, represented a popular view amongst proponents of police professionalisation through HE, when suggesting that at a macro-level, the rapidly changing and increasingly complex social, cultural, and technological post-modern policing milieu, requires a ‘new professionalism’. This ‘new professionalism’, it is argued, requires police officers who are more intellectual (Furuhagen, 2015), who rely not only on experiential knowledge, but also knowledge which has an academic underpinning and perspective. Christopher (2015, p.388) unequivocally suggests that HE is “required” to manage the demands of “everyday” policing. Within the Swedish context, Green's (2018, p.36) review of Swedish Government enquiries into initial police learning, which were led by academics, underlined “how the police must develop and prepare for a more complex and demanding future” in part, through academisation.

As well as a strategy by which to improve police performance in the rapidly changing and increasingly complex operating environments of twenty-first century policing, academisation of initial police learning will, it is frequently argued within the literature, help to counter a range of shortcomings, including “the more corrosive elements of police occupational culture” (Hough and Stanko, 2018, p.7).

2.3 Police culture

2.3.1 The classic account

The rich and significant volume of research and theory concerning ‘police culture’ reflects what has been a fertile and “lasting topic of interest and debate in the field of police studies” (Bacon, 2014, p.103). Despite being a “complicated, contested and, at times, contradictory” discourse (Bacon, 2014, p.103), about the various dimensions, validity, and usefulness of the concept (Chan, 1996; Silvestri, 2017), it has “dominated academic and practitioner debate for the past half century” (Cockcroft, 2017, p.229), and become pivotal in academic, practitioner, and policy discussions of policing (Paoline, 2003, 2004; Bacon, 2014; Reiner, 2017) in helping to understand how “police work ‘gets done’” (Cockcroft, 2017, p.229).

Broadly, the literature reflects a series of post-Second World War narratives which (Reiner, 2010, pp.11-12) suggests have comprised four historical stages: consensus, controversy, conflict, and contradiction. The consensus stage began with Banton's (1964, p.237) rather sympathetic ethnography exploring policing in Scotland and the USA, which was driven by his belief that British police officers were “treated as intrinsically good” because they “symbolize social order”. The ‘controversy’ and ‘conflict’ stages saw the publication of less sympathetic, reformist studies during an era when policing was subjected to greater media, public, and political scrutiny, and when there was less deference towards established authority. These studies developed a notion of police culture which became “a convenient label for a range of negative values, attitudes, and practice norms among police officers” (Chan, 1996, p.110), and led to unquestioned orthodoxy in which “officers possess a range of predominantly

negative behavioural tendencies” (Loftus, 2009, p.15, Bacon, 2014) which became ‘cognitively burned-in’ (Sklansky, 2007, p.20). Skolnick's (1966) “*locus classicus*” depiction of a beat officer’s ‘ideal-typical working personality’ encapsulates the frequently portrayed core characteristics of police culture; a sense of ‘mission’; cynicism; pessimism; suspicion; isolation/solidarity; police conservatism; machismo; racial prejudice; action-centred; pragmatic (anti-theoretical, common-sense); ‘secrecy’; and a ‘blue code of silence’. The “classic first-generation studies” (Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki, 2019, p.165) frequently portrayed police culture as “homogenous, static, and unchanging” (Loftus, 2009, p.15), negative (Silvestri, 2017), “rigid and linear” (Aston, Murray and O’Neill, 2021, p.42).

However, some scholars such as Cockcroft (2017, p.231), have been critical of what they view as a reductionist approach, reflecting instead that some ‘deviant’ aspects of police culture might also offer some rational advantages. For example, whilst the dark side of police solidarity is frequently portrayed within the literature as protecting colleagues who conduct themselves inappropriately (Westmarland and Rowe, 2018), others such as Waddington (1999) have argued that camaraderie provides physical and emotional support, especially when officers are facing danger and stress. Others have argued that camaraderie is a reason for people seeking to join the police (Charman, 2017, p.255). Atkinson (2013, p.65) argued that there was a “symbiosis” between this uncovering of aspects of policing which had been “previously hidden to the wider society” during the so-called ‘Golden Age’ of policing, and crises of policing during a “cockpit of controversy” (Reiner, 1995, p.74).

These previously dominant understandings of police culture which derived from “a much earlier and different social, economic and political milieu” (Loftus, 2009, p. ix), with their narrow focus on junior operational officers, has increasingly been questioned within the literature.

2.3.2 Police culture in transition

Over the past twenty to thirty years, the prevailing schema has begun to be modified (Paoline, 2004), and refined. During this ‘contradiction stage’ (Reiner, 2010, p.11), police culture has increasingly been viewed as neither monolithic, universal, nor unchanging (Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki, 2019, pp.180-183). Work by scholars such as Chan (1996, 1997, 2003, 2007a), Westmarland (2016, 2017), Loftus (2008, 2009, 2010), Waddington (1999), Atkinson (2013, 2017), and Charman (2017) amongst others, has led to more nuanced, complex, and multifaceted understandings of police culture which suggest “complexity” and “variation” (Paoline 2004, p.207).

There is a theme developing within the literature that this ‘cultural plurality’ (Hendriks and van Hulst, 2016), “... is shaped by, and reacts to, the internal organisational environment, as well as the external occupational milieu” (Atkinson, 2017, p.244; Punch, 2007; Loftus, 2009; Bacon, 2014; Silvestri, 2017; Charman, 2017). In supporting this argument, Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki (2019, p. 169) suggest that:

... cultures are shaped, but not determined by the structural pressures of actors’ environments as police officers interpret and act and interact in relations of networks ... their shifts, neighbourhoods, the police organizations with their internal division of labour. Each actors’ responses shape the situations that others act within.

For example, Cain (1973, cited in Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki 2019, p.166), highlighted differences between rural and urban officers, and between countries, whilst Terrill, Paoline III and Manning (2003) found that cultural strength (the extent to which cultural attitudes are shared) varied between workgroups. Cultural variations between countries, are reflected in Bayerl *et al.*'s (2014) qualitative study of one hundred and sixty-six police officers from eight European countries. Within the different social, cultural, and political external conditions (‘field’), the lived dispositions of police officers were found to have some core similarities, and some dissimilar characteristics between countries.

However, despite these scholarly efforts to provide a richer, more nuanced understanding of police culture, Silvestri (2017, p.297) argued that “there remains a sustained, over simplified, and unflinching attachment to the idea of police culture as monolithic, static, and negative”. This is epitomised by what Holdaway (2013, p.218) considers to be the “unyielding core” of ‘cop culture’ which have been reinforced by an extensive body of literature. This consistent and unchanging core of police culture (Atkinson, 2017) might in part be attributable to the view that there are some common characteristics, particularly within industrialised modern liberal democracies, because essentially, they face similar problems in their role. Whilst some writers such as Sklansky (2011, p.7) suggest that the essentially unchanging core role of policing is persistently ‘pulling back’ police culture to the old professionalism of crime fighting and top-down management, others such as Charman (2017) take a different view.

Charman’s (2017) longitudinal study in Evermond Constabulary (a fictional name), a medium-sized police force in the south of England, explored, as she explained (Charman, 2017, pp.177-178) why:

police recruits in the early months and years of their policing careers appeared to be quite different in terms of their attitudes towards their role and position as police officers than they were in the first days and weeks of their police training. What influenced those changes appeared to be unclear.

In Cockcroft’s (2018, p.292) opinion, Charman’s (2017) study was:

a welcome and timely departure from what sometimes can come across as ‘smash and grab’ police ethnographies which, whilst helpful, can tend to replicate previous findings and be somewhat linear in their explanatory power.

Based on a series of qualitative-based open questions with a more quantitative element, Charman’s participants were asked to “rank order questions in order to assess their beliefs as to the most important priorities of a police officer and the most important characteristics” (Charman, 2017, p.179). They were given a choice of five priorities and five characteristics, which was repeated at each of the four interview stages “in order to be able to assess with more certainty the nature of the potential

changes in views towards a variety of policing issues” (Charman, 2017, p.179). Two cohorts of recruits ($n=24$) who joined several months apart were interviewed individually on four occasions over a four-year period: five weeks into their thirteen-week ITC; after six-months service when they were on shift and had completed their ten-week attachment to a tutor constable; after one year of service after they had been granted Independent Patrol Status; and finally after four-year’s service, after they had all had passed their probationary period. Tutor constables were also interviewed ($n=7$). In total, ninety-eight interviews were undertaken totalling forty-four hours. Of the twenty-four recruits, most had previous policing experience either as Police Community Support Officers, Special Constables, or as police staff. Most were aged in their twenties, with 25% holding an undergraduate degree.

One area of significance revealed by this study was “the advent of what Charman calls “#newbreed” officers (Cockcroft, 2018, p.272). For this “relatively new cultural grouping of police officers... communication skills and a focus on community engagement replace physical toughness and crime fighting as the primary domains” (Cockcroft, 2018, p. 292). Charman argued that the “old characteristics” of police culture, such as “the blue code of silence and crime fighting” are being “buried” and being replaced by “new characteristics” such as a “blue code of self-protection, compassion and communication” (Charman 2017, p.339). The culture of this ‘new breed’ was over layering the heroic, crime-fighting, machismo culture of previous generations of officers. This contradicts, to an extent, the arguments of scholars that “occupational culture endures because the fundamentals of the police role remain intact” (Loftus, 2010, pp. 16-17). That said, as Charman (2017) highlighted, the fundamentals of the role are changing, as responding to vulnerability becomes foregrounded over responding to reports of crime. Changes within police culture, therefore, are likely through small shifts in the way that officers think and act – to become “knowledge workers” – and “by taking on this identity” to “contribute to cultural change, and to police reform generally in their own tiny, but significant corner of the organisation” (Marks *et al.*, 2010, p.292). This thesis begins to colour in some of the cultural similarities and differences in police culture within and between Scotland, Sweden, and Finland.

2.4 Police professionalisation: the academisation of initial learning

2.4.1 Initial police learning: the traditional approach

The focus of initial police learning has traditionally been to prepare entry-level police officers for independent patrol. It is still very much posited on practical knowledge learned from limited classroom-based theoretical training, more extended ‘on-the-job’ practice learning, and acculturation into occupational culture passed on by more experienced peers (Charman, 2017).

The initial, post-employment/post-entry ‘classroom-based’ phase, which usually took place within police training ‘centres’ or ‘schools’, predominated within British policing until relatively recently, and was comparatively short (weeks or a few months). Almost entirely within the control of, and run by police officers, the initial learning phase delivered within traditional police training colleges has been much criticised within the literature. Toch (2008, p.63) for example, argued that it is “...hard to see how an organization can inculcate its officers with a readiness to exercise wise and informed discretion when the officers are being barked at, marched about and treated like recalcitrant children” (see also Cao, Huang and Sun, 2016). Fielding (2018, pp.106-107) supports this view suggesting that it “infantilizes recruits”, and that the “military style ‘Passing Out Parade’ coming at the end of the residential phase rather than the end of probation underlined the separation of classroom and on-the-job training”. However, others disagree. For example, Heslop (2011, p.305) argued that the traditional approach is “a great ‘leveller’ as a recruit’s previous background provided little advantage”, whilst Macvean and Cox (2012, p.18) argued that it enables bonding, which provides a foundation of trust relationships between colleagues who provide support, both physical and emotional, when coping with violence or the threat of violence which is “a recurring feature of police culture” (Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki, 2019, p.172). As will be revealed later in this thesis, the bonding of police recruits and policing students in the case study countries during the initial ‘classroom based’ phase of their initial learning programmes was also found by this study to be of importance.

The initial, 'classroom' based learning phase, is usually followed by a lengthy period of on-the-job experiential learning on the 'street', under the mentorship of a more experienced officer. There is an acknowledgement within the literature that an element of work-based learning within a blended approach, is a "crucial component of the learning process for police officers" (Tong and Wood, 2011, p.71). Studies have consistently found that police officers foreground on-the-job, experiential learning as a form of learning and source of cultural capital, perceiving it as "relevant (learning by doing) and real (dealing with actual crimes rather than role play)" (Tong and Wood, 2011, p. 71). However, whilst acknowledged as "crucial" by some (Tong and Wood, 2011, p. 71) and "no bad thing" by others (Fenwick, 2015, p.235), on-the-job, experiential learning requires key supporting structures, of which mentoring by more experienced officers has consistently been found to be of particular importance in closing the theory-practice gap, and developing interpersonal skills (Bergman, 2017; Charman, 2017). However, it remains the "least well-evaluated aspect of police training" (Charman, 2017, p. 73).

This 'craft' model of learning is often associated within the sociology of profession literature, with an artisan or 'blue-collar' occupation (Bayley, 2008; Rogers and Frevel, 2018), rather than a profession. Scholars who subscribe to policing becoming graduate-entry only, frequently cite moving policing from an artisan occupation, based on a body of 'craft' knowledge, developed through practice experience which is "disengaged from science", to one which is based on "a body of authoritative knowledge that is usually associated with the more traditional professions such as medicine or indeed the law" (Neyroud, 2011, p.44).

2.4.2 Academisation of initial police learning: the benefits

Within the broader police professionalisation through HE discourse a consistent theme has emerged which suggests that raising the academic attainment levels of police officers provides both organisational and individual benefits which support wider professionalisation agendas. In the USA, the 1967 Presidents Commission on Law Enforcement and Administration of Justice and the subsequent professionalising

reforms of the 1968 Law Enforcement Education Programme (LEEP) reflected this theme. Citing ten scholarly 1970s evaluations of the USA reforms as part of her submission to the UK Home Affairs Select Committee on Police Training, Foster (1999) went further than the broad recommendation that academic attainment levels should be raised: she argued that graduate entry should be the norm. Despite the datedness and questionable transferability of the American studies, Foster argued that these studies demonstrated college educated police officers to be more open minded, more likely to be tolerant of race and ethnicity, less likely to resort to force, more likely to exercise their discretion, to communicate more effectively, and be subject to fewer complaints than their non-college educated colleagues. Despite the Home Affairs Select Committee Report (1999) acknowledging the benefits that a more academic approach could bring to the delivery of police learning and training, they also highlighted what they perceived as the danger in forcing professional training too far down an academic route.

Reflecting the Committee's acknowledgement of the benefits that a more academic approach could bring, the 2002 Training Matters Report on police training in England and Wales, concluded that the then existing initial police learning programme was "not wholly fit for purpose now, nor to support the police service of the twenty-first century" (HMIC, 2002, p.101). The report "recommended the introduction of accreditation and qualification frameworks, links with further and higher education, alternative training delivery options and continuous professional development" (Tong and Hallenberg, 2018, p.22). It led to a radical change to initial police learning in England and Wales with the introduction of the Initial Police Learning and Development Programme (IPLDP), with the aim of "promoting critical and lateral thinking, improving understanding of community and removing the cultural blocks to modernization" (Brown, 2020, p. 17). Collaborative provision between forces and HEIs was encouraged, which resulted in IPLDP being "delivered by a variety of providers including the police service, and private and public sector organisations... with some police services engaging with universities, colleges and others providing 'in-house' training" (Tong and Wood, 2011, p.70). Some forces partnered with local universities to produce either a certificate in Policing Studies or a two-year Foundation

Degree in policing, whilst other forces opted for National Vocational Qualifications. The continuing argument that there are “real potential benefits to be grasped by requiring a degree at the point of entry into the police service” (Hough and Stanko, 2019, p.6) was eventually reflected in the recent introduction by the COP in England and Wales of the PEQF. This represents a radical shift towards mandatory universal degree entry only (Hallenberg and Tong, 2018). It should be noted, however, that with policing having been devolved from the UK Parliament to the Scottish Parliament when the latter was reconvened in 1999, the Home Affairs Select Committee Report and the HMIC Training Matters Report (2002) had no locus within Scottish policing. Nothing was found in the literature to indicate that either report had influenced the initial police learning model north of the border.

In her study of police learning in England and Wales, Hallenberg (2017) found perceptions that attaching academic qualifications to police learning could enhance policing in several ways. For example, by improving public credibility; by developing the capacity and capability to develop a unique corpus of professional knowledge; by raising economic capital; and by improving policing’s status with other professions or occupations which are graduate-entry only, thereby enhancing inter-agency working. As Rogers and Frevel (2018) highlight, police officers are increasingly required to interact with those who are degree-educated professionals, such as lawyers, doctors, nurses, social workers, and paramedics for example. Through externally recognised academic qualifications Hallenberg (2017, p.17) argued, police “know how, their experience, is turned into expertise, the kind of expertise that is recognised outside the police” within the “competing knowledge claims” of inter-professional working.

At an individual level, it is frequently theorised that the experience of HE provides officers with intellectual curiosity, knowledge, and skills to become positive agents for change, (Wood, Fleming and Marks, 2008), thereby contributing to policing’s unique corpus of knowledge (Hallenberg, 2012). The prevailing discourse is that it also provides entry-level police officers with a deeper knowledge and understanding of the wider social context within which they are operating (Charman, 2017; Hallenberg, 2017); cultivates lifelong learning and development thereby enhancing

the maintenance of a knowledgeable and skilled workforce (Eason and Blandford, 2021, p.6); cultivates reflective practice (Williams, Norman and Rowe, 2019) and critical thinking (McDowall and Brown, 2020, p.4); enhances receptivity to evidence-informed practice (Lum *et al.*, 2012); enhances ability to manage uncertainty (Bruns and Bruns, 2015); enhances ability to apply discretion (Dominey and Hill, 2010; Macvean and Cox, 2012); enhances career flexibility (Hallenberg, 2017); and enhances resistance to negative aspects of police culture (Blakemore and Simpson, 2010; Loftus, 2010; Macvean and Cox, 2012, p.18). Others, however, others have called this discourse into question.

Wimshurst and Ransley (2007, p.106) have argued that the effectiveness of further education or HE in police reform agendas, “remains ambivalent”. Macvean and Cox (2012), Paterson (2011), and (Brown, 2020), have gone further, arguing that much of the empirical literature on which these arguments are founded is neither consistent nor compelling. Brown’s (2020) integrative review of empirical research from five decades (1970 to the present) emanating largely from the USA, with others from Australia and the UK, resulted in her arguing that “the current body of research evidence is methodologically weak and there remains a gap in the literature for the provision of a convincing, unambiguous empirical case demonstrating the value added by graduates to policing” (p. 10). She argued that there were a “number of methodological shortcomings in the research” (p.9) which included: poor operationalising of performance and directionality; different attitude scales making comparison difficult; subjective measures such as self-report or supervisor ratings; and not partialing out socialisation effects of police occupational culture once employed in a police force. It is unclear therefore, whether, or to what extent, the academisation of initial police learning in Sweden and Finland (and the resistance to it in Scotland), has been founded on consistent and compelling empirical research.

Brown (2020) also highlighted studies which contradict the benefits of HE discourse. For example, that by Lancee and Sarrasin (2015, p.499), which suggested that attitudinal differences amongst university students in Switzerland towards immigrants were already present before secondary education, and not attributable to the “alleged

liberalizing effect of education”. This echoes the Aristotelian notion that character is largely formed during childhood, suggesting that the benefits of academisation might be largely at “an external or symbolic level, rather than the ‘up-skilling’ of individual officers” (Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2017, p.276).

This somewhat binary, reductionist discourse is countered within the literature by a more nuanced, complex perspective which, it is argued, more closely reflects the realities of contemporary policing. Scholars such as Innes (2010), Tong and Wood (2011), Aas (2016), Hallenberg, O’Neill and Tong (2016) have argued that contemporary policing entails a combination of ‘art’, ‘craft’ and ‘science’ developed through experience, practical application, and HE respectively. All “are important and should be recognised as a collective contribution to police decision-making” (Williams, Norman, and Rowe, 2019, p.261). There is also an interesting recognition on the part of some scholars such as Syrja (2019, p.20), that the concepts of ‘art’, ‘craft’ and ‘science’ in policing reflect the Aristotelean intellectual virtues of *episteme* (academic or scientific knowledge), *techne* (craft or tacit knowledge), and *phronesis* (the “synthesis of tacit and explicit knowledge [which] incorporates value judgements into the knowledge-creation process to create meaning out of context”). In value-driven occupations or professions such as policing, the notion of *phronesis* has gained recognition amongst some scholars as an important form of knowledge, encapsulating ethics, values, and experience into practice (Eraut, 1994; Flyvbjerg, 2004; Grint, 2007).

2.4.3 Academisation of initial police learning: the challenges

As well as challenges to the validity of empirical research underpinning much of the police professionalisation through HE discourse, “... cultural resistances within the police organization which create hurdles to successful implementation” (Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2017, p.277; Atkinson, 2017, p. 244) are also well rehearsed within the literature. Whilst “... many commentators have identified an ‘inherent anti-intellectualism’ that permeates police thinking” (Punch, 2007, p.111; Lee and Punch, 2004), others have argued that “[s]uch an antipathy reflects a fundamental police

worldview based on a notion of ‘police common sense’ (Holdaway, 1983, p.65) which renders academic education irrelevant. Linked to this is the perception of the police officer as a ‘craftsman’ (Skolnick, 1966), with skills learned through practice on ‘the street’. Studies have demonstrated that these cultural resistances to reform through HE and “antipathy to academic learning” (Lee and Punch, 2004, p.244) persist over time. For example, qualitative studies involving the perceptions of officers who undertook in-service degrees in England during the 1960s (Lee and Punch, 2004), and more recently (Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2017; Williams, Norman and Rowe, 2019), consistently found that they encountered a police culture which “has not been especially positive towards higher education” (Hough and Stanko, 2019, p.5). These findings showed that a “well-established resistance to learning outside the workplace still remains” (Tong and Wood, 2011, p.71). Hallenberg and Cockcroft’s (2017, p. 286) findings suggested that “...whilst the police institution may aspire to be viewed as a profession, underpinned by engagement with HE, at the structural and cultural levels, the integration of HE into the police may expect to encounter resistance”. The current discourse demonstrates that longstanding “...tensions exist between education and training in police thinking in its quest for professionalism...” (Lee and Punch, 2004, p.246).

However, critical analysis of literature which explores this longstanding perception of an epistemological and cultural divide between the “two-worlds” of academia and policing (Hallenberg, 2012, p.5), reveals a more nuanced discourse. Studies have consistently shown that there is a “fundamental” (Canter, 2004, pp.3-4) perceptual dichotomy between academia and the police concerning knowledge and knowing associated with notions of police professionalism, what Hallenberg (2012, p.167) called “two worlds thinking”. Aas (2016, p.12) neatly summarises this dichotomy:

... it is largely the knowledge based on experience that is valued in police culture, and the theoretical/scientific knowledge is correspondingly devalued ... Conversely, there is a scepticism towards the experiential knowledge among academics.

This theory-practice dichotomy, where ‘craft’ knowledge or “practical knowledge” (Aas, 2016, p.6) is generally perceived by police officers as a privileged form of

knowledge and source of cultural capital over academic theoretical knowledge, has long been recognised within the policing literature (Willis, 2013; Willis and Mastrofski, 2014, 2016, 2018). The notion of professionalism amongst police officers, particularly ‘street cops’, is founded on policing as a craft comprising craftsmen and women who most effectively develop their craft in the 'real world' of the street rather than through classroom-based learning and reading books (Manning, 1979, p.49). White and Heslop (2012, p.344) emphasised this tension within nursing and policing, whereby on completion of their initial ‘classroom-based, theoretical phase of learning new entrants were often advised by their practice mentors to “forget everything you’ve been told, this is where you learn the job for real” (see also Van Maanen, 1973, p.414 cited in Green and Tong, 2020, p.296).

These contrasting perspectives between the ‘two-worlds’ of academia and policing (Hallenberg, 2012), reflect the broader debate as to what constitutes professionalism within policing as encapsulated by Chan (2003, p.311):

The struggle over the meaning of “professionalism” - between traditional “street cops” and those wanting to produce a “new breed” of professional police who make independent judgements, value integrity above peer solidarity, and take a more compassionate approach to policing.

Amongst those wanting to produce this ‘new breed’ of degree-educated, entry-level police officers are those academics, senior police officers and politicians who view this as an important part of the wider police professionalisation agenda. However, a consistent theme within the literature is that which portrays a “cultural schism... between academia and policing (Hallenberg, 2012) and between street officers and managers in the police (Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2017, p.274). Within the police professionalisation through academisation discourse, there appears to be little which illuminates understandings within and between junior and senior officers. This study aims to glean new insights by understanding how senior officers and the rank and file, including police recruits in Scotland and policing students in Sweden and Finland, perceive notions of profession, professionalism and professionalisation through the academisation of initial police learning.

With regards the role of politicians in the professionalisation of policing through HE agenda, Furuhausen (2015) and Green (2018, p.35) provided useful historical insights into the “long-lasting, and bit muddy, developments of Swedish police basic training” along the academisation policy pathway. Of particular interest for the purposes of addressing this study’s research question concerning how initial police learning has evolved within Sweden was Green’s (2018, p.36) observation that:

A special feature of this development [the move from delivery of initial police learning from largely being at the Swedish National Police Academy to entirely within universities] is that a political dimension has emerged between the Social Democrats, who clearly are in favour of a reform, and the Conservatives, who have been protracting the question of a merger with higher education.

Green (2018) revealed the situated and complex interplay between politics, academia, and policing and the relational power within and between them in the academisation of initial police learning in Sweden. In doing so, he highlighted the extent to which the “political dividing line” (Green 2018, p.43) between the Conservative and Social Democratic political parties, the views of Swedish educational and judicial committees, and the views of the Swedish Police Union, impacted on agenda setting and charted the development of the education of trainees away from the national police academy to mainstream universities following the election of the Social Democrat party in 2014. Whilst Hallenberg’s (2012) theoretical concept of “two-worlds-thinking” is helpful in understanding the interplay between academia and policing with regards police professionalisation through HE, it does not encapsulate the relationship with the ‘third-world’ of politics highlighted by Furuhausen (2015) and Green (2018). This study will therefore add new knowledge by utilising the concept of ‘three-worlds-thinking’ in its analysis of the situated interplay, and relational power, between politics, academia, and policing. By expanding Hallenberg’s (2017) concept of “two worlds thinking” to include the world of politics, and drawing on concepts from the theory of organisation literature, such as Kingdon’s (1995) three separate ‘streams’ concept, and Murray and Harkin's (2017) concept of ‘cool’ or ‘heated’ political climates, this study will add new knowledge concerning policy formulation and realisation within the field.

Kingdon's (1995) concept, which compares the benefits and drawbacks of a homogenous, non-negotiated, myopic approach to policy formulation, contrasts with a heterogenous, negotiated approach which encapsulates the cultural and myth influenced perspectives of all actors. Whilst this makes the policy formulation process more conflict-ridden, this broader, participatory approach, it is argued, may result in a higher degree of policy legitimacy. This concept is echoed in Bayley's (2008) review of major police reforms in the USA. Bayley (2008, p.7) noted that "the big reform ideas in policing" were invariably "top down and outside-inside...instigated by people, or events, outside the police themselves", rather than by rank-and-file officers. Bayley (2008, p.14) argued that failure to consult with rank-and-file officers, and to draw on their "wealth of unorganized" and underutilised "rich fund" of "craft knowledge" in shaping strategies, is regrettable.

2.5 Conclusion

Chapter 2 has provided an overview and critical analysis of selected, relevant scholarly literature underpinning the academisation of initial police learning discourse which existed prior to the commencement of data gathering in 2019, and which informed this study's design. It has analysed the arguments that there are organisational and individual benefits to be derived from academisation, including graduate-entry only, together with those who argue that much of research underpinning these claims is neither consistent nor compelling. Some of the purported challenges associated with police professionalisation through HE have also been critiqued, with a focus on the importance of culture on reform. In analysing the relevant debates concerning profession, professionalism, and professionalisation, this chapter has drawn on the work of (Noordegraaf, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2016) highlighting his concept of hybrid, reconfigured notion of public service professionalism which, in moving away from the 'trait based' paradigm, more closely reflects the realities and complexities of contemporary policing in the case study countries. It also highlighted the argument that the contemporary realities of policing require a professional knowledge which blends the 'art', 'craft', and 'science' of policing (Wood *et al.*, 2018, p.176). Finally,

this chapter identified gaps within the literature which helped to refine the focus of this study and shape its design, which will be explored in the following chapter.

Chapter 3: Research method and design

Introduction

Having critically analysed relevant literature, this chapter presents and justifies the research method and design. Comprising five sections, the chapter begins (section 3.1) by explaining how the methodological approach underpinning this study's design has been influenced by social constructionist ontological and interpretivist epistemological positions. It goes on to explain why a qualitative, *emic* approach to gathering data was deemed suitable for discerning and interpreting the meanings of people's lived experiences of how policies had evolved and been implemented, within their social, historical, and cultural contexts (Creswell, 2014).

It moves on in section 3.2, to present the multiple, cross-national, case study research design framework (Yin, 2018) which was selected for this study. It highlights how this design enabled "multiple facets of the phenomenon to be revealed and understood" (Baxter and Jack, 2008, p.544), from the rich and detailed data gathered over a period of time (Creswell, 2014, p.14) from forty-nine one-to-one, semi-structured interviews and six focus groups, thereby providing "substantial" analytic benefits (Yin, 2018, p.61). It then moves on to discuss the rationale underpinning the sampling strategies adopted and explains how, through a combination of purposive and snowball sampling, participants were selected from key policy network actors (Savage, Charman and Cope, 2000). They included those who had shaped or influenced policy such as Chief Police Officers; those with governance or oversight responsibilities; police unions; academics with an interest in police education; and those who put these policies into practice. The latter included, for example, those with responsibility for directing pre- and post-entry initial police learning programmes, those delivering initial learning such as educators, trainers, tutor constables, and operational commanders. It also included those who undertook the initial learning programmes, namely police recruits in Scotland, and policing students in Sweden and Finland.

Section 3.3 discusses the deontological ethical stance adopted for this study and goes on to highlight the arrangements which were put in place to guard against harm to participants, including ensuring that their consent was fully informed and freely given, that their anonymity was assured, and their data protected. It then moves on to highlight and discuss the ethical considerations arising from my positionality as an ‘outside inside researcher’ (Brown, 1996), and conducting interviews with participants for whom English was a second language.

In section 3.4, considerations regarding data recording, data security, data analysis, and data evaluation are presented. This section discusses the use of an iterative approach to data coding (Saldana, 2016), the development of key themes from the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006), and the criteria against which the findings were evaluated (Yardley, 2000). Section 3.5 briefly summarises the chapter.

3.1 Research strategy: epistemological and ontological considerations

Initial informant interviews suggested that it was policy makers’ socially, culturally, and politically constructed notions of profession, professionalism, and professionalisation which influenced policy formulation and implementation, rather than empirical research evidence. Therefore, values and beliefs which shaped these professional judgements needed to be explored to understand how and why initial police learning has taken different trajectories in the case study countries, especially in relation to the role of HE. Quantitative research methods have often been used to analyse the extent to which HE improves the professionalism of police officers, such as their attitudes and behaviours. However, this would not, it is argued, provide an understanding of why policy actors support, resist, or are indifferent to HE and academic theoretical knowledge having a role within initial police learning programmes as part of wider professionalisation strategies. Understanding these perceptions is important within the context of broader police reform, including police professionalisation.

The methodological approach of this study has, therefore, been influenced by a constructionist ontological position. Constructivism “asserts that social phenomena and their meanings are continually being created by social actors. It implies that social phenomena are not only produced through social interaction but are in a constant state of revision” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.28). This means that there is no single reality or truth, that multiple realities exist through the contextualised and negotiated interpretations of social actors which evolve through experience. Interpretivism is concerned with understanding how people make sense of their lives and seeks to get inside their heads to understand the multi-layered reasons and motivations which shape the individual lenses through which they perceive “the world in which they live and work” (Creswell, 2014, p.8). Bryman (2016) suggests this involves a triple layer of interpretation in which the researcher’s interpretation of other people’s perceptions is then further interpreted considering the relevant concepts, theories, and literature. Given this ontological and epistemological framework, a qualitative research approach was identified as a fitting method by which to address the research questions.

An interpretative research approach aims to develop understanding by discerning and interpreting the meanings of people’s lived experiences within their social, historical, and cultural contexts (Creswell, 2014). It typically involves an *emic* approach to gathering data (collecting the perceptions primarily of individuals and groups within their own environments), as opposed to an *etic*, or outsider’s perspective (Hancock and Algozzine, 2017, p.8). The researcher’s role is to interpret the meaning inductively (theory generating) through the identification of patterns or categories and by using appropriate literature to understand and explain often complex and contradictory situations. Adopting such an approach enabled this study to explore actor’s subjective, lived experiences of policy formulation and its operationalisation, whilst doing so within the natural context of their respective geographical and organisational spaces. As Miles and Huberman (1994, p.147) argued in their influential book *Qualitative Data Analysis*:

Qualitative analysis, with its close-up look, can identify mechanisms, going beyond sheer association. It is unrelentingly local and deals well with the complex network of events and processes in a situation. It can

sort out the temporal dimension, showing clearly what preceded what, either through direct observation or retrospection.

Additionally, Maxwell (2020, p.183) argued:

Qualitative research, with its unique ability to identify the actual processes operating in a specific event or case, and the contextual influences on these, is thus particularly relevant to understanding how policies and programs lead to particular (sometimes unexpected) outcomes.

The focus of this study, therefore, was to gather data regarding the perspectives of participants who had lived experiences of the actual processes operating within the case study countries regarding how policies had evolved, the extent to which the intended outcomes were being realised, and the extent to which both had been influenced by the meaning attached to notions of profession, professionalism, and professionalisation. One-to-one in-depth interviews and focus groups provide an effective approach by which to “interpret the general topics in which the researcher is interested” (Bryman, 2016, p.501). This study engaged with a wide spectrum of policy network actors (Savage, Charman and Cope, 2000) covering a range of experiences, backgrounds, situations, and perspectives from academia, policing and quasi-governmental institutions, such as the SPA and HMICS. Participants included strategic policy makers and influencers; those responsible for interpreting and enacting the policies; and those recruits or policing students who were undertaking, or had recently undertaken, initial police learning programmes.

3.2 Research design

3.2.1 Multiple, cross-national, case study

Of the various research design frameworks which would have been appropriate for this study, the most suitable for answering the research questions was felt to be the case study design, an approach utilised by Banton (1964) in his pioneering study of policing in Scotland and the USA. Despite case study research being “one of the most challenging of all social science endeavours” (Yin, 2018, p.3), it is “commonly found

in many social science disciplines” (Yin, 2018, p.5). It allows the researcher to investigate “a contemporary phenomenon (the case) in depth and within its real-world context” (Yin, 2018, p.15). Case studies are useful for supporting the deconstruction and subsequent reconstruction of various phenomena using a “variety of data sources” so that the phenomenon “is not explored through one lens, but rather through a variety of lenses which allows for multiple facets of the phenomenon to be revealed and understood” (Baxter and Jack, 2008, p.544). Adopting a *multiple* case study approach involving a comparative exploration and analysis of initial police learning in more than one country, provided not only additional, multi-faceted lenses through which to view the phenomena, but also “substantial” analytic benefits (Yin, 2018, p.61). This comparative approach provided a multi-faceted lens through which develop an in-depth knowledge of each programme, gather rich and detailed data from a variety of sources over a period of time (Creswell, 2014, p.14), and a means by which to analyse the phenomena. Each case study was bounded by space (the national, geographical boundaries of each case study), by time (the duration of the initial police learning programmes), and by the duration of the data gathering phase of this study (Creswell, 2014, p.14). It was further bounded by the selection of participants which is discussed in more detail in a later section of this chapter.

3.2.2 Sampling strategy: selection of case study countries

Finland, Scotland, and Sweden were selected as the case study countries based on a combination of similarities and differences which, it was felt, would provide the basis for an effective comparative analysis. To approach comparative analyses of policing scientifically, studies need to be grounded in an understanding of the interplay between contextual constructs such as political ideology, culture, crime, economy, and demography. If they are to have any depth it is “essential for critical analyses and the basis for comparative studies” (Roelofse, 2015, p.245). In summary, all three countries are stable, liberal democracies with similar cultural, demographic, and economic profiles with small populations spread across large geographical areas on the periphery of Europe. All have similar education systems and a similar societal respect for the value of HE. Whilst all have single, national police forces which have recently been

formed from the merger of smaller, legacy forces, with similar policing histories and philosophies, the extent to which initial police learning programmes are aligned with HE and the extent to which they have moved towards policing becoming graduate-entry only, differs.

3.2.3 Sampling strategy: participant sampling

Key policy network actors (Savage, Charman and Cope, 2000) who have a degree of interaction with initial police learning programmes within Scotland, Sweden, and Finland, be that with regards policy formulation or its operationalisation, formed the sample population for this study. The sampling strategy was refined further by purposively sampling (Robson, 2011, pp.148-149) participants from several diverse categories. This included those who shaped or influenced policy such as Chief Police Officers, those with governance or oversight responsibilities, police unions, and academics with an interest in police education; those who put these policies into practice, for example, those with responsibility for directing pre- and post-entry initial police learning programmes and those delivering initial learning to the recruits or students. The latter included educators and trainers during the initial ‘classroom-based’ phase, as well as tutors and operational commanders during the on-the-job practice phase; and those who undertook the initial learning programmes, namely police recruits in Scotland and policing students in Sweden and Finland. However, to provide a necessary degree of flexibility during the data gathering phase, a snowball sampling strategy was also adopted (Clark *et al.*, 2021, pp.383-385). This enabled those participants who had been purposively or pre-identified to “recommend other participants who have experiences or characteristics that are relevant to the research” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, pp.383-384). This technique was especially relevant to this study when networks of policy actors, be they those in policy formulation, or those involved in its operationalisation were the focus of interest, as it “is able simultaneously to capitalize on and to reveal the connectedness of individuals in networks” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.384).

3.2.4 Interviews and focus groups

As this study aimed to understand the perceptions of policy network actors regarding the role of HE in initial police learning, qualitative interviewing techniques were utilised. Unlike quantitative interviews, in qualitative interviewing “there is a greater interest in the interviewee’s point of view” which provides “rich, detailed answers” and “insight into what the interviewee sees as relevant and important” (Clark *et al.*, 2021 p.425).

The use of one-to one, semi-structured interviews based around the themes of policing as a profession, police professionalism, police professionalisation, police culture, and the role of higher academic education in initial police learning, allowed the interviewees “some freedom in how they reply” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.426). They also allowed the flexibility to pick up on interviewees replies and to explore new “insights or concepts which seem promising” (Yin, 2018, p.167).

Both the one-to-one interview guide and the focus group guide were piloted in Scotland in early 2019. Adjustments were made in terms of the one-to-one interview guide (see appendix D) with regards the number of questions asked, especially the number of probing questions, which had resulted in the pilot interview lasting three hours. It was felt that no adjustments were required to the focus group guide (see Appendix E).

Having negotiated and secured access approvals, Table 1 shows how many one-to-one interviews and focus groups were conducted within each country. It also provides antecedent information regarding role, rank, organisation, gender, and whether they were graduates. Snowballing resulted in a greater number of interviews taking place than was envisaged at the very start of this study.

Table 1. One-to-one interview participants: country & role

Country	Total No. of interviews	Police Officers	Academia & Police Staff Educators & HR Specialists	Quasi Govt Oversight & Governance
Finland	17	12	5	0
Sweden	14	10	4	0
Scotland	18	13	3	2
Total:	49	35	12	2

I was “keen to generate representative samples” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.41) of participants as far as reasonably practicable. To that end, the sampling strategy included policy actors at strategic, tactical, and operational levels within the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing. Whilst this proved partially successful with regards the world of politics in Scotland, with access being gained to strategic actors within the SPA and HMICS, access was not secured at any level in Sweden and Finland. Within the world of academia, access was gained to the Heads and Deputy Heads of Schools, subject matter leads, and teachers of relevant degree programmes within universities in Scotland and Sweden, and the Police University College in Finland. Within the world of policing, access was gained to chief officers (strategic), departmental heads and trainers at the Scottish Police College, operational commanders (tactical), and to tutor constables, police recruits, and policing students (operational). Efforts were also made, in conjunction with gatekeepers, to ensure that within each ‘world’, and at each level, participants were representative with regards gender and ethnicity.

The aim of utilising focus groups was for participants to collectively explore and discuss their perceptions and experiences of initial police learning, and to engage critically with the themes which emerged during the discussions (Kitzinger, 1994). The group dynamics “tend to quickly reveal similarities and differences in perspectives, attitudes, preferences, and behaviours among group participants” (Stewart and Shamdasani, 2017, p.48). Whilst a mature methodology, there are challenges, particularly assembling “a group in a single place”, especially if they are

busy (Stewart and Shamdasani, 2017, p.49). In this case, the participants were already gathered, for a learning and development activity as part of their initial learning programme, be that at the Scottish Police College, the Finnish Police University College, or, in the case of Sweden, a university or a police station.

In each country, one focus group comprised students who were in the early stages of their learning but had yet to begin the ‘on-the-job’ practice phase of their respective programme. The other, comprised recruits or students who were either nearing the end of, or had recently completed, their practice phase. The rationale for this approach was to explore the extent to which socialisation into the organisational culture had influenced participant perspectives regarding the cultural capital attached to epistemic knowledge, ‘craft’ knowledge, and experiential knowledge (Heslop, 2011; Pepper, Brown and Stubbs, 2022; Watkinson-Miley, Cox and Deshpande, 2022).

The intention had been that each focus group would contain between six and eight participants on the basis that smaller focus groups of that size are thought to be more suitable for complex and sometimes controversial topics (Moser and Korstjens, 2018, p.14). In most instances this number was achieved, with the smallest group comprising five people and the largest eight. Each focus group comprised only peers from their cohort and, therefore, individuals could not remain anonymous within each focus group. However, participants were requested to maintain confidentiality outwith each focus group by not sharing with others what was discussed or who individual participants were. Quotations used from the data gathered from each focus group were anonymised using individual group identifiers to further protect their anonymity. Wherever possible each cohort was representative of their wider cohort with regards age, gender, and ethnicity. In hindsight, it would have been helpful to also ensure a representative sample with regards academic attainment level and social background.

Focus groups are essentially group interviews facilitated by a moderator or facilitator, which “typically emphasize a specific theme or topic that is explored in depth” through “how people respond to each other’s views and the interaction that takes place within the group” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.453). They allow for group dynamics and shared

experiences, and it is this “inherently social nature” which is the method’s “unique value added” (Cyr, 2015, p.20). They “generate data at three units of analysis, namely, the individual, the group, and the interaction”, with the individual units of analysis being “appropriate for triangulation” (Cyr, 2015, p.1) and being “integrated with other evidence” (Cyr, 2015, p.20).

In this study, the intention had been to utilise the “multiple opinions or viewpoints” (Cyr, 2015, p.20) for the purposes of triangulation, of police recruits in Scotland, and policing students in Sweden and Finland, who were at different stages of acculturation. Those who were in the early stages of their initial police learning programme, and those who had completed, or nearly completed, their programme. It was felt that as such, their experience made them significant sites of collective remembering (Coupland, 2015). This study, therefore, worked with pre-existing clusters of police recruits and policing students who had been living, working, and studying together. An additional advantage derived from involving groups of people who knew each other well, particularly those who had been together for two or three years, was that they were more willing to challenge contradictory statements regarding professed beliefs and opinions (Kitzinger, 1994, p.105).

3.3 Ethical considerations

Having considered several ethical stances, such as universalism and principled relativism, a deontological stance was felt to be most appropriate for this study. A deontological stance “considers certain acts as wrong (or good) in and of themselves” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.112). Identifying which acts were ‘good’ or ‘wrong’, was guided by four broad principles: “whether there is *harm to participants*; whether there is a *lack of informed consent*; whether there is an *invasion of privacy*; whether *deception* is involved” (Diener and Crandall, 1978 cited in Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.113). These ethical principles guided all stages of this study and were constantly reflected on. In addition, treating all those with whom the researcher interacted with dignity and respect, was a guiding value.

Ethical approval for this study was given by the School Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) in April 2018, subject to access approval being secured from appropriate gatekeepers in each of the case study countries (see Appendix A). As part of gaining access approvals in Sweden and Finland, consideration was given as to whether Governmental approval would first be required. In the case of Sweden, the conditions encapsulated within the Ethical Review on Human Research Act (2003) were considered, and in the case of Finland the guidance issued by the Finnish National Board of Research Integrity. In both instances, it was assessed that this study fell outwith the requirements to seek Governmental approval. The plan to secure the requisite gatekeeper approvals was immediately put into action which, whilst broadly similar for each case study country, had to be adapted in relation to each (see chapter 8 of this thesis for reflection on this aspect of the study).

3.3.1 Guarding against harm to participants

The British Sociological Association's Statement of Ethical Practice (BSA, 2017), states that it is important to "anticipate and guard against, consequences for research participants which can be predicted to be harmful". This includes ensuring confidentiality of records and participant's identity, including the publication of data which might inadvertently lead to identification. This is particularly relevant with qualitative research, where "researchers have to take particular care with regard to the possible identification of people and places" (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.115). Ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants has therefore, been an important consideration during this study. However, being a qualitative, cross-national, comparative study and therefore not readily generalisable, the potential impact of the study (particularly within regards to the potential impact on policy and practice) lies in the degree to which it resonates with the reader, especially those who might influence the extent to which academic education has a role within initial police learning programmes. Developing a naming protocol which ensured confidentiality and anonymity whilst also articulating their positionality, was therefore, a challenge. After careful consideration and much experimentation, a nomenclature began to emerge, the outcome of which was the development of a clearly defined naming

protocol which provided a justified and consistent approach, and which addressed these tensions. The nomenclature and participant unique identifiers which have been adopted are detailed in Appendices F and G respectively.

Whilst it was recognised from the outset that “the need for confidentiality can present dilemmas for researchers” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.116), particularly with regards the revelation of unethical or indeed unlawful behaviour by participants, fortunately no such dilemmas materialised during this study. It was recognised at the planning stage, that ‘blowing the whistle’ may result in the researcher “losing credibility among officers, the investigation ending early, or the researcher (and potentially other researchers) being unable to gain access in the future” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.116). If such dilemmas had arisen, the intention had been to seek guidance from the researcher’s supervisors, together with the relevant UWS ethics committees, before deciding on an appropriate course of action. Managing and storing data is another aspect of confidentiality. All research data has been managed in accordance with UWS’s Data Protection Code of Practice.

3.3.2 Informed consent

Whilst covert observations were not part of this study’s research design, the power dynamics were an important consideration with regards informed consent. There was an inherent tension between the benefits of securing gatekeeper approval from senior police officers and academics, and more junior members of staff, police recruits, or policing students feeling compelled to participate. The principal of not only fully informed but freely given consent was, therefore, an important ethical consideration, particularly when senior leaders publicly encouraged their staff to take part or had personally introduced the potential participant to the researcher. Mitigation included providing all potential participants with written information about the study (see appendix B) so that they were fully informed about its aims and objectives, scope, and approach. It was also explained that they should only take part if their consent was genuinely given freely, that they were free to withdraw at any time, and that should they decline to take part or withdraw later, this would not be made known to anyone

else. This was re-emphasised at the start of each interview or focus group. Participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity and that the data they provided would be kept securely in accordance with the current Data Protection legislation applicable in their country. Prior to the interviews or focus groups commencing, written consent was obtained, and the researcher ensured as far as reasonably possible that they were participating with fully informed and free consent. Nobody declined to take part, or subsequently withdrew, and all participants completed a consent form prior to being interviewed or taking part in a focus group. A copy of the template used is shown in Appendix C. As far as is reasonably practicable, the researcher believed that all participants had given their fully informed and freely given consent to take part in this study.

3.3.3 'Outsider-insider' status

Failing to fully consider the effects of researcher positionality may raise ethical concerns. For example, whilst Brown's (1996) typology of policing researchers categorises me as an 'outsider' (a 'civilian' working for a 'civilian' organisation), I had had a thirty-year affiliation with policing, largely within the Scottish context, including as Head of the Probationer (police recruit) Training Division at the Scottish Police College. As such, it was anticipated that there would be a "mutually perceived homogeneity" (Merriam *et al.*, 2001, p.407) and that "meanings [would be] shared" (Merriam *et al.*, 2001, p.406) with police officers. This, it was reasoned, would categorise me as more of an 'outsider insider' researcher (Brown, 1996). It was also anticipated that whilst my network of connections within Police Scotland's senior leadership would be helpful with regards securing access, drawing on them might raise ethical challenges. For example, a desire to support an ex-colleague and/or friend, might place the potential gatekeepers in an invidious and potentially harmful position. In addition, their support in gaining access to those under their command, might leave potential applicants feeling compelled to take part.

I was also conscious of my positionality with regards my age (mid-fifties), gender, social class, ethnicity, nationality, level of education, and that English was my only

language. Throughout this study, I was conscious of these different aspects of my positionality and the impact which they may have on my interactions with participants, and indeed my subsequent analysis and interpretation of the data. However, it was also recognised that my positionality would generally be helpful within a social constructivist and interpretivist approach, and provide a balanced, considered, and credible analysis of the data.

3.3.4 Participants for whom English was a second language

A significant ethical and potentially limiting issue for this study, was “the need to navigate potentially significant language... differences” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p. 297) whilst undertaking interviews and focus groups in English with participants for whom English was a second language. There was a possibility for some misunderstanding, not only of the interview questions, but also of the answers, with regards participants in Sweden and Finland. Failure to address the “attribution of different meanings... can threaten the validity and reliability of the data” (Marshall and While, 1994, p.568). I was particularly concerned that speaking in a second language might leave participants feeling less confident and therefore unable to fully express themselves, thereby leading to “impoverished accounts” (Murray and Wynne, 2001, pp.158-159). The use of suitably qualified translators was considered but deemed beyond the financial constraints of this study.

However, participants in Sweden and Finland generally spoke English well. In the few instances where communication and understanding required more time and effort to ensure mutual understanding, proprietary language translation software (Google Translate) was used. However, this was infrequent and only for the occasional word. Every effort was made to ensure that both participant and researcher achieved a mutual understanding regarding what words and phrases were used, through sense-checking and re-phrasing. Sense-checking of interview and focus group transcripts by the participants had been considered in advance but was not required.

3.4 Data recording, security, analysis, and evaluation

3.4.1 Recording, transcription, and security

All individual interviews and focus groups were audio recorded using a digital recorder, with the permission of the participants, despite the risk that its use might cause respondents alarm or to become self-conscious (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.443). In fact, participants appeared to quickly forget that the interview was being recorded, allowing discussions to flow more naturally. It enabled the researcher to actively listen to what was being said, to concentrate on probing and varying the sequences of questions (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.435) without being distracted by note taking. Recording interviews and focus groups this way also captured the way in which participants said something, as well as what they said, enabling it to be woven into the analysis (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.441). Audio recordings were immediately downloaded onto an encrypted laptop computer, converted from ARF/.WRF files, and stored securely as .mp3 digital files. Interview schedules were developed and are attached (see Appendix D and Appendix E). Interviews and focus groups usually lasted about an hour and a half

Transcriptions of interview recordings were typed up using Microsoft Office word processing software (.docx) to agreed formats and standards, by the researcher and a transcription provider. Transcriptions “allow a more thorough examination of what people say”, “repeated examinations of interviewees’ answers”, and “helps to correct the natural limitations of our memories, and of the intuitive glosses that we might place on what people say” (Heritage, 1984, p. 238, cited in Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.441). They also make the data available for scrutiny and secondary analysis by other researchers. Transcripts were then checked for accuracy against the original audio recording.

3.4.2 Data analysis

Following transcription of the interview and focus group recordings, the data from each were then analysed. Atlas.ti analytical software was used to support coding (Saldana, 2016) of the transcribed interviews using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six phases of thematic analysis: data familiarisation, generation of initial data codes, searching for themes or patterns, reviewing the themes to generate a thematic 'map' of the analysis, defining and naming the themes, and in producing the selection and final analysis of compelling extract examples. Inductive thematic analysis was utilised based on its strength in organising rich data sets, which enabled for the clear summation of participant views and experiences, and the development of key themes which are presented in the findings chapters. An iterative, continually cyclical approach allowed for patterns, themes and understanding to be developed inductively, and for it to be oriented conceptually within the theoretical framework of the literature (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.538). The literature "become[s] an aid once patterns or categories [had] been identified" thereby becoming "a basis for comparing and contrasting findings" (Creswell, 2014, p.28), and "a framework for relating new findings to previous findings (Randolph, 2009, p.2).

Codes generated from the initial coding phase resulted in a large number of codes which were subsequently raised to higher level themes which were of interest (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p. 541). For example, those which related to the influence of occupational culture ('Occ Culture' prefix), organisational culture ('Org Culture' prefix), and politics ('Politics' prefix). These themes were further developed into higher order themes (code groups) aligned with the research questions, namely: policy formulation; desirable knowledge, skills, and behaviours; the influence of initial police learning models on professional development; and factors influencing perceptions concerning the impact, or potential impact, of HE on the professional development of police recruits and policing students. A selection of examples is replicated in Appendix J.

3.4.3 Data evaluation

Given the constructionist ontological position of this study, and the contested nature of the discourse concerning the applicability of quantitative evaluation criteria to qualitative research, this study has adopted Yardley's (2000) four criteria for appraising qualitative research.

Sensitivity to context

Given the comparative, cross-national, case study approach adopted for this study, the complexities of the nuanced social, political, and cultural contexts within Scotland, Sweden, and Finland have been a constant consideration. As too have been the ethical considerations, such as English being a second language not only for all participants in Sweden and Finland, but also for a few participants in Scotland, as well as relational power and the issue of consent.

Commitment and rigour

There has been as substantial an engagement with initial police learning programmes in the case study countries, as time and money would allow.

Both the one-to-one interview and the focus topic guides were piloted, with participants being invited to critique the questions and/or prompts and to make suggestions as to how the questions, and demeanour of the interviewer/facilitator, might be improved. This revealed that the topic guides contained too many questions and prompts, resulting in the pilot interview lasting three hours, and the focus group failing to benefit from the exploratory nature of the group interactions. Following amendment, data was gathered from forty-nine one-to-one, semi-structured interviews and six focus groups (see table 1). One-to-one, semi-structured interviews and the focus groups usually lasted about an hour and a half.

A considerable volume of historical and contemporary policy documents, programme curricula, and internal reports, were also scrutinised to engage as fully as possible with the subject. In Sweden and Finland, three field trips were undertaken in each country. In the case of Finland, this included two extended residential periods of about a month each, during which I lived within the Finnish Police University College, shared accommodation with staff and students, occupied an office within the research department, took meals with staff and students, and socialised with them outwith working hours. Whilst this study did not adopt an ethnographic approach, being embedded in this way provided a level of engagement and understanding which was not realised in the case of Sweden.

Gathering data from more than one data source, namely one-to-one semi-structured interviews, and focus groups, coupled with “respondent validation” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.365) of the emerging findings, provided a degree of triangulation (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.364) and thereby rigour. However, the constraints of time and funding resulted in participants being drawn exclusively from urban spaces. The rigour of this study may have been further enhanced had the perspectives of participants from rural and remote rural spaces been gathered and analysed, particularly in Scotland and Sweden where, it is suspected, junior front-line response officers may have had a greater sense of adhocism than their urban peers.

Transparency and coherence

This thesis has attempted to provide transparency and coherence by clearly articulating the research design, reflecting on the reality of implementing it (see chapter 8), and providing a coherent explanation and interpretation of the findings.

Impact and importance

Whilst this study has yet to have any quantifiable impact on policy and procedure within the case study countries, or indeed elsewhere, I do have a sense that the numerous informal conversations, conference presentations, and discussions with

participants during interviews and focus groups has, to a small degree, informed and influenced the perceptions of some. For example, one of my supervisors had been of the view that every police officer in Scotland should be a graduate, a view which now seems to have been moderated. Discussions with a senior office bearer within the Scottish Police Federation, who in 2019 was opposed to the approaches to initial police learning in Sweden and Finland, recently stated publicly that he was now of the view that the eleven-week ITC in Scotland should be lengthened and broadened so that on completion, police recruits were what they described as ‘the complete package’.

HMICS’ recently published 2022-2025 Scrutiny Plan, includes an intention to undertake an audit and assurance review towards the end of the inspection cycle. HMICS have been made aware of this study and have indicated their interest in the findings being used to inform their work. Police Scotland have also recently initiated a strategic review of training delivery, which includes initial police learning. The findings from this study have also been used to inform their work. A senior policing academic in Scotland said of this study “it won’t just throw a pebble into the pond of initial police learning; it will throw a rock”.

In providing a rare cross-national comparative analysis of initial police learning within Scotland, Sweden, and Finland, this study provides important new insights into the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of politics, academia, and policing and the extent to which socially, culturally, and politically constructed notions of profession, professionalism, and professionalisation underpinned policy formulation and implementation, as opposed to empirical research evidence. It also provides important insights into policy formulation processes and the extent to which relational power between the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing influenced HE’s role within the respective initial police learning programmes. In doing so, it adds to, and hopefully advances in some respects, the police professionalisation through HE discourse, enhances existing empirical and theoretical literature in the field, and provides new knowledge about policy formulation.

3.5 Conclusion

This chapter has presented and justified the research method and design. It explained how the methodological approach underpinning this study's design had been influenced by a constructionist and interpretivist ontological position, and why a qualitative, *emic* approach to gathering data was appropriate. It also described and justified the adoption of a multiple, cross-national, case study research design framework (Yin, 2018) and the rationale underpinning the sampling strategies. It then moved on to discuss ethical considerations, highlighting the benefits and challenges arising from my positionality as an 'outside inside researcher' (Brown, 1996), and the challenges of conducting interviews with participants for whom English was a second language. Considerations regarding data recording, data security, data analysis, and data evaluation were presented, including the use of an iterative approach to data coding (Saldana, 2016), the development of key themes from the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006), and finally, the criteria against which the findings were evaluated (Yardley, 2000). Chapter 9 provides a reflection and discussion on the experience of implementing this study's methodological design.

Chapter 4: Evolution of initial police learning in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland.

Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to describe, analyse, and explain the findings from this study concerning the research question: *how has initial police learning evolved in the case study countries?* In doing so, it describes and analyses key policy influences on the recent evolution of initial police learning within the different contexts of Scotland, Sweden, and Finland. Drawing on organisational and policy science literature, particularly the notion that the variables of context matter in policy formulation (Christensen, Lægreid and Rykkja, 2018), this chapter reveals who and what influenced policy-making, together with the ‘how’ of the policy-making processes, within the case study countries.

Participant perceptions of the macro-level contextual dynamics of policing’s operating environments, and the strategic drivers influencing policymaking in the case study countries, are explored in section 4.1. It highlights the widely held perception that contemporary operating environments are rapidly becoming more complex and demanding. It also compares the meso-level responses to these challenges as regards organisational structure and organisational culture. It explores Police Scotland’s response through increased specialisation which, coupled with a hierarchical culture, has resulted in the marginalisation and de-professionalisation of front-line, junior response officers. It contrasts the organisational responses in Scotland with those in Sweden and Finland. Whilst in Sweden they were like those in Scotland, but less marginalising, in Finland, there was a focus on empowering and enabling front-line, junior response officers to deal with a wider range of more complex tasks in support of a lean management and distributed leadership approach.

Section 4.2 untangles the processes of policymaking within Scotland, Finland, and Sweden, to better understand the evolution of initial police learning policy within each country. In doing so, it explores the interplay between the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of

national Governments, academia, and policing, highlighting the influence of relational power, and the degree of homogeneity or heterogeneity on the policy formulation processes. For example, the homogenous, non-negotiated approach in Scotland, whereby Police Scotland dominated policy formulation; the heterogenous, negotiated approach in Sweden dominated by the Swedish Government; and the heterogenous, negotiated approach in Finland dominated by the Finnish police. It concludes by arguing that these differences in the power relationships, coupled with the degree of congruence between the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of national Governments, academia, and policing, within Sweden and Finland, influenced not only the policy pathways within each country, but also perceptions of legitimacy, both of the policy-making process, and of the initial police learning programmes.

Section 4.3 draws on Newman and Clarke's (2018) concept of the ‘knowledge/power nexus’, and Kingdon’s (1995) Multiple Streams Approach, to explain the findings described in earlier sections (see also Béland, 2016). This section begins by arguing that the situated and constantly changing contexts of policymaking, and in particular the divergent power relationships within the different policy-making approaches, are key to understanding the similarities and differences in the evolution of initial police learning within the case study countries. It then moves on to argue that in Scotland, the homogenous, ‘one world thinking’, non-negotiated approach which involved neither the Government (at least not overtly), nor academia, helps to explain, in part, why Scottish policing had not followed the academisation pathway taken in Sweden and Finland. This section also argues that the dominant positionality of Government within the heterogenous, negotiated approach involving the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of Government, academia, and policing in Sweden, had resulted in the evolution of initial police learning ‘ebbing’ and ‘flowing’ on the ‘tides, currents, eddies, whirlpools, and riptides’ (Greene, 2012) of opposing political ideologies. This, coupled with greater influence being ceded by the Government from policing to academia, had resulted in a widely held perception amongst police officers that the academisation of initial police learning had foregrounded the needs of academia over those of policing. Finally, it argues that whilst the approach to policy formulation in Finland was similar to that in Sweden, it differed in one important respect: it was dominated by the police.

This helped to foreground the needs of policing over those of both Government and academia. That said, progression along the policy pathway had, as in Sweden, been dependent on national Government support to secure the necessary legislative changes as well academia's support for Bachelor's degree accreditation.

The chapter concludes with section 4.4 which briefly summarises the chapter's findings, analysis, and thesis arguments made.

4.1 The policy-making context.

4.1.1 Operational and organisational contexts

A central issue in policymaking is what and who shapes policing policy (Savage, Charman and Cope, 2000, p.30.) The data from this study showed a commonly held perception amongst participants that a major influence on policy formulation concerning initial police learning was the increasingly pressurised, complex, and rapidly changing context within which contemporary policing was operating. In exploring what they meant by complexity, participants consistently referred to the increasing demand to support vulnerable people in society, especially those in mental health crisis; newly emerging crime types such as cyber-crime and international terrorism; changing social demographics arising from rapidly increasing levels of immigration; technological advances; and increased scrutiny and accountability. These comments from senior police officers in Scotland and Sweden reflect these perceptions:

“The complexity's increased... managing and dealing with people with vulnerabilities... managing and dealing with people in crisis, mental health... child protection issues, dealing with modern slavery, dealing with human trafficking... they're complex areas of business...”
[Participant SCP13 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

“It's a complex job. Maybe twenty years ago... the work was simpler if you see what I mean but today it's evolved. We have terrorism, we have gang problems, we have integration problems, we have cyber-crime. There is so much more to the professional police today than it was

twenty, twenty-five years ago.” [Participant SWP06 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

This finding is indicative of the broader discourse within the sociology of professions literature, including that concerning policing, which recognises the interplay between the increasingly complex external operating environments and internal policies and practices. For example, Bayley (2016, p.164) suggested that “Policing has become dramatically more complex in six ways: its tasks, public demands, strategies, technology, accountability, and resources”. Of relevance to this thesis is the notion of “modern societal orders that are known as information or knowledge societies” (Noordegraaf, 2007, p.769). Some scholars have suggested that knowledge societies or knowledgeable societies are associated with “uncertainty, complexity, instability” (Schön, 1983, p.17). Indeed, as this study found, equipping police recruits and policing students to operate within continually evolving, increasingly complex knowledge societies, was found to be a key driver for the academisation of initial police learning in Sweden and Finland.

Whilst the findings developed from the data were broadly consistent in this regard, there were notable differences as respects policing’s response to these challenges. Police Scotland, for example, had focused on developing an ‘instrumental’ policing style of effective and efficient crime control supported by a specialised structural model and a hierarchical, managerialist approach. This “vertically and horizontally fragmented” structural model with its “tasks and responsibilities divided among several actors and units within the organisation” (Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019, p. 349) had also, some participants suggested, resulted in a narrowing of the role and responsibilities of junior, front-line, uniformed, operational response officers, as this senior, operational police commander explained:

“What you’ve got are frontline officers who are just... capturing best evidence and then moving it off to a specialist unit.” [Participant SCP 13 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

As a result, front line, uniformed response officers generally dealt with what this senior officer called “routine” tasks, with anything more complex being dealt with by a specialist unit.

By way of contrast to this approach, this study found that policing in Finland had adopted a less horizontally and less vertically fragmented approach. For example, there were comparatively fewer leaders and fewer specialist departments than in Scotland. This required front line, operational response officers, especially those in the remote rural areas (Wooff, 2015, p.289), to be able to respond, as this senior officer stated, to “any kind of situation they confront”:

“Finland is a vast country in terms of area, but in most areas a very thinly populated country with a very, very small police service... we have 7,200 officers meaning that in many areas of the country, the police density is, very, very thin indeed... in... northern and eastern parts of the country the distance between two police patrols is easily a 100 kilometres or more, meaning that the two officers in the car have to be able to manage any kind of situation they confront. Support is not available... I mean, immediate support is not available, and we cannot afford many specialised units.” [Participant FP02 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

Whilst Sweden had adopted a similar specialist, ‘fragmented’ approach to that adopted in Scotland, it was found that unlike Scotland, policing aspired to adopt the concept of ‘lean management’, as this senior academic working within Swedish police education explained:

“Within the Police Authority they work with the idea of employee driven improvement and development. It has connections to the idea of Lean... you should get more say on how things are being done on the level you are working at... how can one think about taking responsibilities. So, competence being part of development, it takes an understanding of one’s own role, and an understanding of one’s role within a bigger picture, so that you can be able to take part in a bigger picture.” [Participant SWP02 - Senior Academic, Sweden]

Lean Management (LM) is often defined within the broader managerialism literature as a continuous improvement programme which encourages the reduction of waste through uninterrupted workflows (Smith, 2016). It is often associated with managerialist cultures and notions of continuous performance improvement coupled with cost reductions. However, some scholars argue in favour of a LM philosophy founded on respect for people and their core professional values (Cano, Murray and Kourouklis, 2022, p.916), which the Swedish “idea of Lean”, intended to foster

“employee driven improvement and development”, is suggestive of. A similar approach was found in Finland, as this senior police officer explained:

“Finnish policing is based on effective first line policing meaning that the single police patrol must be able to respond independently to most of the tasks ahead.” [Participant FP18 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

This less fragmented approach was widely perceived amongst senior police officer participants in Sweden and Finland as being effective, as this next quotation from a senior police officer and union official in Sweden illustrated. Interestingly, it highlights the contrast between a more horizontally fragmented, specialist approach to a murder scene (as would be found in Scotland) and that of the less horizontally fragmented, LM approach:

“So, all the first-hand actions that need to be taking place, we believe that our first responders are not only first responders they are also investigators. The moment you come to a crime scene you are an investigator. And twenty, twenty-five years ago you can send out investigator. ‘Oh, it’s a murder scene, just freeze, put a tape up and then we’ll send out the professionals’... and it’s not efficient to do it that way.” [Participant SWP06 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

In Finland, these “first-hand actions” included recovering forensic samples (fingerprints, blood samples, shoe impressions) in all but the most serious incidents, with policing students in Finland developing the requisite legal knowledge, forensic knowledge, and technical skills during their initial police learning programme. It might be argued that this approach to LM is value centred in that it prioritises the needs of victims and enables first responders to re-connect with a sense of professionalism, by enabling and empowering them to deal with the whole investigation from initial attendance, through the entire investigatory process, to submitting a case file to prosecutors. Charman (2017, p.256) found amongst new recruits in an English police force that this was “an aspect of the job that they were looking forward to”, but that limitations of their role within a more vertically and horizontally fragmented policing model “was a later source of frustration and indeed stress for some officers”. However, without a more detailed comparative analysis of these contrasting approaches to policing within the case study countries, (which was beyond the scope of this study),

the veracity of the claims made by senior police officers in Sweden and Finland cannot be tested in this thesis.

It was also found that these approaches in Sweden and Finland were complemented by the institutionalised practice of ‘shared leadership’ whereby junior officers were afforded greater individual agency and organisational power than their counterparts in Scotland, as this senior academic in Sweden explained:

“... basically, the idea is that the responsibilities should be pushed down.” [Participant SWP02 - Senior Academic, Sweden]

These findings might be understood, in part, through the lens of organisational culture and in particular, the concepts of hierarchical (control), clan (collaborative), and adhocracy (create) cultures (Cameron and Quinn, 2011). Pushing responsibility down, as the participant in Sweden described in the above data, is suggestive of an adhocracy culture. “A major goal of an adhocracy is to foster adaptability, flexibility, and creativity if uncertainty [and] ambiguity” are typical (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p. 49). Employees are more empowered than those in hierarchical cultures to use their professional judgement. By way of contrast, the data from this study showed there to be a perception amongst police officers in Scotland, from recruits in their first week of their Initial Training Course, to senior operational police officers, that Police Scotland’s organisational culture was hierarchical:

“So, what we’ve got are a lot of officers in policing that are incredibly risk averse... the easy thing is to make no decision or pass it up the chain of command and let somebody else carry responsibility. But what that does is it completely disables your workforce.” [Participant SCP13 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

This senior operational officer attributed this aversion to risk, in part, to what they described as a “blame culture”, and indeed there was evidence within the data, of early socialisation into this risk averse culture, as this observation from a recruit in their first week of Initial Training at the Scottish Police College shows:

“...this week’s all been about standards, uniform, ethics, how to lose your job basically. (Interviewer: And what have they told you was likely

to lose your job?). Lots of things. How long do you have?" [Focus Group SCFG02 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

In unpicking what was meant by “completely disabling your workforce”, the senior officer quoted above went on to explain that the unwillingness of more junior officers and staff to take ‘risky’ decisions, had resulted in a slowing of the decision-making process. Decisions which should, in their view, have been taken by more junior officers and staff, were pushed towards the top of the organisation. The inference taken from this, was that Police Scotland is not maximising the capacity of its workforce. This might be understood by drawing on the work of Murray and Harkin (2017). They argued that following the amalgamation of the pre-existing eight Scottish police forces and two policing agencies into a single Scottish Police Service called Police Scotland in 2013, policing moved from a ‘cool’ political climate with “low scrutiny and minimal political engagement” to a “heated” political environment. This gave rise to “unprecedented scrutiny” (Murray and Harkin, 2017, p.885), which, has created a culture which is “highly risk averse to critical assessment” (Lum, 2014, p.2). This perception amongst some police officers in Scotland of a risk averse culture and organisational inertia, might help to partly explain why Scotland has not followed the academisation of initial police learning pathway, particularly the degree entry only model.

It might also be understood by once again drawing on the concept of organisational culture. Whilst hierarchical cultures have been shown to be successful in stable operational environments, adhocracy cultures have been shown to be more successful in “rapidly changing, turbulent environments” (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p.42). Interestingly a greater tendency towards adhocracy cultures was found within several of the smaller Scottish Police forces which existed prior to the establishment of Police Scotland (Tatnell and Elliott, 2013). One of the possibly unintended consequences arising from the creation of Police Scotland and its strong emphasis, under the first Chief Constable, on hierarchical control through structures, processes, and procedures, coupled with an increasing specialisation of the workforce, led to work processes, especially for junior-ranking, front-line response officers, becoming de-professionalised (Noordegraaf, 2007; Schinkel and Noordegraaf, 2011; Hibbert,

2012), “less dependent on human skills, abilities and knowledge... contributing to de-humanising [and] deskilling” (Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019, pp.353-354) which, Hibbert, 2012) argued can be demoralising.

Given the increasing pressures being placed on Police Scotland, and indeed other public services in Scotland, by the public’s need for their services, and the continuing challenges as regards public sector funding, this thesis argues that there should be a public debate as to whether this dominant notion and understanding of professionalism will be appropriate over the coming decades. It might for example, be argued that Police Scotland’s ability to adapt to the rapidly changing and increasingly complex policing environments within which it is operating, could be enhanced by moving more towards a generalist policing model, which broadens the role of marginalised, de-skilled, junior-ranking front-line response officers, enables greater individual adhocism, and thereby increases organisational capacity. Indeed, given the call made in Scotland’s Christie Commission Report (Christie, 2011) for a more connective notion of professionalism (Meurs and Noordegraaf, 2022) amongst public services, which focuses on providing a person-centred approach to addressing endemic multi-problem social issues, perhaps the debate should be widened to include other public services. However, whilst the policing climate is cooling from the ‘heat’ of the immediate post-reform period, it is probably still too politically ‘hot’ (Murray and Harkin, 2017) for such far-reaching reform. The role of a front-line, junior response officer is therefore, unlikely to change in the immediate future with regards the breadth and complexity of the tasks they will be expected to deal with. This in turn, it is argued, makes it less likely that Police Scotland will recognise the need to move away from the existing traditional approach to initial police learning, and towards an academised model.

As will be argued later in this thesis, these similarities and differences in organisational structures, management approaches, and role expectations of front-line, operational response officers influenced, in part, the similarities and differences of approaches to initial police learning.

4.2 Policy formulation: the influence of national Governments, academia, and policing.

Having described and analysed the key macro-level and meso-level contexts of policy formulation which emerged from this study's findings, this section narrows the contextual focus further by critically analysing the policy formulation process itself. In doing so, it explores unexpected findings which emerged from the data concerning the extent to which the interplay between national Governments, academia, and policing, within each country influenced policy formulation. It highlights the influence of relational power, and the extent to which the homogeneity and heterogeneity of approach, influenced agenda setting and policy formulation pathways. The interplay of these factors, it is argued, helps explain similarities and differences in the evolution of initial police learning within the case study countries.

4.2.1 Scotland

The Police and Fire Reform (Scotland) Act (2012) established the Scottish Police Authority (SPA) as the legal employer of Police Scotland, replacing the pre-existing Local Authority Police Boards which comprised elected councillors from local communities. The SPA is statutorily responsible for maintaining Police Scotland, and is the only body with formal powers to hold the chief constable to account (Malik, 2018, pp.440-441). Scottish Government Ministers set national public policy strategic priorities which the SPA must take account of when establishing their strategic priorities for Scottish policing. Whilst it might be argued that the creation of the SPA established something of a firewall between the Scottish Government and Police Scotland, one strategic actor suggested that the ruling Scottish Nationalist Party's (SNP) independence ideology had influenced the policy agenda across a broad range of issues:

“I think one of the massive adverse unintended consequences of devolution has been a complete preoccupation with comparison to England, the desire to be different.” [Participant SCP 15 - SPA Member]

This desire to be different, was reflected in a decision taken in 2017 by the SPA, in consultation with the Scottish Police Consultative Forum (SPCF), not to adopt a pre-entry, undergraduate degree pathway. Evidence emerged from this study which inferred that the SNP led Scottish Government had influenced the decision as this former member of the SPCF explained:

“(the) more elitist degree route didn’t sit comfortably with the SNP”
[Participant SCP20 - Former Scottish Police Consultative Forum Member]

Whilst it was unclear whether Scottish Ministers had directly or indirectly influenced the policy formulation process in this instance, this member of the SPCF was clearly aware of the SNP led Government’s ideological position. If this were the case, it might be viewed as a further attempt, in addition to the creation of a single, national police service, to define Scottish policing’s exceptionalism within the UK, in support of the Scottish nationalism movement.

As with other Scottish exceptionalisms, the promulgation of policing’s exceptionalism supports the broader political and cultural narrative which increasingly depicts Scotland as not only distinct from but “better than ... England and Wales” (Brangan, 2019, p.782). Since the re-emergence of Scottish nationalism in the 1980s, Scottish Governmental administrations have “found ways to embed an image of national distinction in departments and policies” (Brangan, 2019, p.790), a process which McAra (1999) labelled ‘tartanization’. However, unlike other aspects of the wider Scottish exceptionalism which portray Scottish policy and practice as progressive, similar claims cannot be made concerning the approach to initial police learning. Scotland’s initial police learning model has remained, and appears likely for the foreseeable future to remain, rooted in ‘on-the-job’ master/pupil training, where experiential learning and ‘craft’ skills are foregrounded (Hove and Valles, 2020). Whilst this might in part, be attributable to Scotland’s desire to be perceived as “being different” (see participant SCP 15’s comment above) to England and Wales, as part of wider Scottish exceptionalism, it leaves policing at odds not only with policing in other north-western European countries, to which Scotland frequently looks for policy

inspiration, but also with other public service occupations or professions in Scotland, such as nursing, teaching, and social work.

The issue of ‘control’ and ‘ownership’ during the policy process, as respects initial police learning within each of the case study countries, was a key theme developed through the analysis. In Scotland, strategic and tactical policy actors from Police Scotland, expressed the view that ceding control and ownership to the HE sector would not be acceptable, as this quotation from a senior member of police staff within the learning and development sub-culture exemplifies:

“... academic recognition... it should never be the tail wagging the dog, so if that’s what we need as a service, then that’s fine, we can look at how that fits in with the academic world... rather than saying, well in order to get to that point you’re going to have to do a four-year degree programme.” [Participant SCP06 - Senior Police Staff, Scotland:]

The inference taken from this is that this could impact negatively on policing. Indeed, in Sweden, the broadly held view amongst police officer participants was, that allowing the political and academic “tail” to wag the policing “dog”, had resulted in an initial policing programme which had been designed primarily to meet the academic requirements of an undergraduate degree, rather than the vocational needs of policing. This contrasted with the findings from Finland, where the focus of the Bachelor’s programme had been on meeting the operational needs of policing, with degree accreditation being a welcome by-product.

4.2.2 Sweden

In Sweden on the other hand, strategic actors from both academia and policing, highlighted the influence of opposing political ideologies on the ebb and flow of agenda setting and policy formulation. For example, as part of a wider political ambition to raise academic attainment levels within Swedish society, the left-leaning Swedish Democratic Party’s goal, had been to move Swedish policing towards becoming a graduate ‘profession’ in line with other similar public service ‘professions’, as this chief police officer explained:

“I think this is about ideology. It goes very deep in how they see the society. And it’s not only the police branch, it’s a lot of other branches that they are striving to get on an academic level. It’s important for the Social Democratic Party. Has been for many, many years.” [Participant SWP 11 - Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

In 2015, having regained power, the Social Democrats resumed their long-term ideological aim of academising initial police learning. They established an inquiry to explore the feasibility of developing the two-and-a-half-year programme into a three-year, Bachelor’s degree accredited programme. The working group’s report supported the proposal, which resulted, as an initial step along the academisation pathway, in the Swedish Police Authority being required to contract out the delivery of the initial learning programme from the Swedish Police Academy to universities, with policing students graduating for the last time from the Swedish National Police Academy (SNPA) in 2016 (Green, 2018, p. 36).

The Government subsequently tasked another working group with developing detailed proposals for further progression to realise a three-year, Bachelor’s degree accredited programme. However, as indicated in the data below, the Social Democratic Party decided against laying their proposals before Parliament, as this participant who had been involved in the inquiries explained:

“And they were in charge for eight years, the right-wing, and then they changed 2015 to the Social Democratic Party. And then they said they had some kind of Government declaration. Now, when we are the Government, we will do all of this. And one point was to make the police education academic. So, they raised it on a pretty high political level. I think it’s the first time they did it like that, but they were very clear. In 2015, they decided that we will have this report... we handed over to the Minister of Interior... and they decided pretty quick that they will not try to have a referendum in the parliament because they understood that they will lose. So, they didn’t do anything with the report, we just delivered it, and nothing happened.” [Participant SWP11 - Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

As the same participant explained, the more right-leaning Conservative parties were opposed to further academisation:

“They said no, police training is more a professional training, so we will not have it.” [Participant SWP11 - Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

When pressed what was meant by “professional training”, the participant likened it to learning a craft through experiential learning (as in Scotland):

“A professional on the job training.” [Participant SWP11- Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

Following a general election in 2018, Conservative parties regained the balance of power, and as happens when they “replace liberals, the agenda-setting process is shifted to the right” in Sweden (Jones and Baumgartner, 2012, p.6). This included shifting the agenda away from further academisation of initial police learning, and towards substantial increases in the police officer establishment. This study found that in 2019, progress along the policy pathway towards a three-year Bachelor’s degree-accredited programme had been halted, as this senior police staff member from the Police Authority explained:

“It’s in the wastepaper bin, because it’s moved from below in the pile of papers, moving slowly, slowly, and then waste paper bin. There’s not a majority behind this proposal... [i]n the Government. And that’s why the police don’t do anything. We don’t do anything proactive, which I think we could have, but we don’t. So, it’s nothing, it’s silent. I think in some areas, of course, we can influence the politicians, so I am not sure why we don’t do it here.” [Participant SWP 08 - Senior Police Staff, Sweden]

One senior police officer suggested that the answer might in part, be attributable to the political leanings of police Commissioners who are the equivalent of Chief Constables in the UK:

“So, we supported the suggestion from the Swedish Police Authority, but then I must be honest and say that our former National Police Commissioner [names the Commissioner] he was maybe closer to the Social Democrats, I think, so he was more on that level. The Commissioner we have today is a police officer from the start, he is more in the profession, so I think maybe it would be a different decision today. I don’t know.” [Participant SWP11 - Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

The inference being taken here is that the degree of alignment between the political leanings of the Police Commissioners with the ideological positions of whichever party held the balance of power within the Swedish Government, had also influenced the policy agenda.

As these findings show, the academisation policy pathway had been pushed and pulled in opposite directions largely by the ‘eddies, whirlpools, and riptides’ (Greene, 2012) of Swedish politics. It was “oftentimes disjoint[ed], episodic, and not always predictable” (Jones and Baumgartner, 2012, p.1). This finding echoes the observations of Green (2018, p.36), who commented that:

[a] special feature of this development [the move from delivery of initial police learning from largely being at the Swedish National Police Academy to entirely within universities] is that a political dimension has emerged between the Social Democrats, who clearly are in favour of a reform, and the Conservatives, who have been protracting the question of a merger with higher education.

Academia’s influence on policy formulation in Sweden was also found from this study to have been influential during the policy formulation process. For example, as data from this study shows, the Government working groups had been dominated by academics, both in terms of chairing the inquiries and in terms of membership numbers. As the senior police officer quoted above who had been involved in the policy formulation process explained, the academic members strove to increase the university-based, theoretical phase of the proposed three-year Bachelor’s degree programme, whilst reducing even further the six-month ‘on-the-job’ learning phase, contrary to the desire of Swedish policing that it be increased:

“And I tried that when I was a part of this, to write the report, to have more on the job training, but I didn’t succeed. In the group that was in charge for the report, it was one from the academic world, all of them were from the academic world, but one was from the police education academic, and all of them, including the chairman of this work, was supporting that if we want to make half a year longer, it should be more theoretical. And I had to fight, because they wanted to decrease the on-the-job training part from, I think, six months to four months. So, I think it was thanks to me, I was fighting for if you do it like this, you will have a problem. And I think if they had listened more to me and maybe had

more on the job training.” [Participant SWP11 - Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

Whilst the intended policy outcome, namely a three-year, Bachelor’s degree accredited programme had been broadly supported by the police, the findings from this study show that during the policy formulation process, there had been a relational power imbalance which had resulted in academia controlling the agenda. Whilst the recommendations of the last Government inquiry concerning the implementation of a three-year Bachelor’s degree had been “put in the bottom drawer” (see earlier quotation from participant SWP08), this relational power imbalance had, despite taking place within an heterogenous, negotiated process, nevertheless undermined the programme’s legitimacy in the view of those police participants in Sweden who had been directly involved. In appointing academic chairs to the inquiries, the Government had, it is argued, effectively disempowered the police who, as the findings showed, found it difficult to ensure that the needs of policing were prioritised over those of academia. It is argued that had the process prioritised the needs of policing over those of academia, the resultant policy proposals may have been more palatable to the Conservative parties.

It is possible to argue that the top-down policy-making approach adopted by the Social Democratic Party, might have been a deliberate attempt to challenge policing’s power within the ‘power/knowledge nexus’ (Newman and Clarke, 2018), so as to further develop their long-standing ideology of creating an “intellectual police force” (Furuhagen, 2015, p.30). However, whilst senior leaders within Swedish policing, including the Swedish Police Union, were supportive of a compulsory, pre-entry, three-year, Bachelor’s degree programme, their lack of relational power within the policy formulation process, compared with politics and academia, had resulted in an initial police learning programme which foregrounded the ‘intellectual’ needs of academia, rather than the vocational needs of policing.

4.2.3 Finland

The findings from Finland demonstrated that unlike in Sweden, policy reform had been initiated and driven primarily by the police, with the support of academia, rather than the Finnish Government. That said, fundamental changes to initial police learning had nevertheless required support from the Minister of Education to progress the necessary legislative changes through the Parliament in Finland. As the chief police officer who had initiated the policy pathway towards a Bachelor's degree programme explained, the negotiated approach to policy formulation had necessitated an ideological alignment between policing and national Governments to progress along the policy pathway and achieve its operationalisation:

“I remember first ... when I present my idea of increase the level of police training up to high level education. First reaction in Minister of Education was never, never ever ... it was one Friday morning in June 1999... I turned to my good friend in Finnish Parliament ... my friend learned me one thing, teach me one thing that if this is 1999 but believe me, the next election will be 2001. And the whole idea of education policies should change or will change in 2001. So, I do my homeworks again and I was very aware to situation which was the right moment when I went again to Minister of Education. So always there has to be a bit luck. So, I was just right time in the right place and that there was a new minister which took this very serious and said, ‘absolutely, this is wonderful idea... let’s do, let’s do this and that’... right time, right moment [laughs].” [Participant FP18 – Chief Police Officer, Finland]

Having secured the support of the like-minded Minister of Education, the police moved quickly to draft the proposed legislative changes which were quickly approved by the Government and Parliament in Finland, as this chief police officer who was party to the process explained:

“... it went through the machinery (as he said this is made a movement with his hand to indicate something moving very quickly and made a whooshing noise) like this.” [Participant FP02 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

This rapid implementation of the enabling legislation should, however, be viewed within the wider historical context of the academisation of police learning in Finland, which had begun in the late 1990s with the establishment of a Master's degree

programme for aspiring senior officers, evolving further with the introduction of a two-and-a-half-year pre-entry Foundation degree and, in 2014, with the introduction of the current three-year Bachelor's degree programme.

Academia's relational power within the policy-formulation process was founded on POLAMK's positionality as a statutorily independent University of Applied Science, and its voluntarily, partial subordination to the National Education Board. This voluntary subordination had been required to demonstrate that POLAMK met the academic and quality assurance standards required of a degree awarding institution. However, as this key member of the negotiated policy formulation process explained, one of the main drivers for developing this closer relationship between policing and the HE sector, had been gaining entry to the Bologna Process:

“It was not actually about whether or not POLAMK could be admitted into the academic community, but rather about entering the Bologna model degree structure. I would say the discussions were very focused and I could not sense any major opposition anywhere in the academic arena.” [Participant FP02 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

The Bologna Process was established in 1998 by Ministers of Education from France, Italy, Germany, and the UK and has since been expanded to include almost every country in Europe. In 1999 at a conference in Bologna, twenty-nine European countries adopted a common agenda to remove barriers to academic mobility and harmonisation of HE which led in 2009, to establishment of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA). In 2022, there are forty-nine members of the EHEA including the UK (EHEA, 2022).

Whilst as in Sweden, the policy formulation process in Finland had adopted a heterogenous, negotiated, approach, this study found that the power-relationship had been different. For example, whilst in Sweden the Government and academia had been the dominant voices in their pursuit of political ideology and academic expedience, in Finland the voice and needs of policing had predominated. As this senior police officer explained:

“The main reason definitely, was an analysis of the operative environment of the police. It’s becoming more complicated on several levels. The degree is a completely secondary issue ... it comes as a result from these thoughts, that the police education er, became so, so er, broad, so extensive that it justifies a Bachelor’s level degree.” [Participant FP02 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

Whilst the agreement of the Government in Finland had been necessary to secure the requisite legislative changes in the Parliament, and indeed an initial incongruence of thinking between the police and a certain Government minister had adversely affected the policy pathway, political ideology had not driven the policy agenda. The operational requirements of policing in Finland had been the primary driver. Lengthening the duration of the initial police learning programme and increasing the amount and complexity of theoretical knowledge, including epistemic knowledge, had been intended primarily to meet the operational needs of policing in Finland, and not political ideologies, nor academic expediency.

This thesis argues therefore, that these nuanced differences in the power relationships, coupled with the degree of congruence between the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of national Governments, academia, and policing within Sweden and Finland influenced not only the divergent policy pathways within each country, but also perceptions regarding the legitimacy of their respective initial police learning models.

4.3 Analysis.

In addressing the research question ‘how has initial police learning evolved in the case study countries?’, this chapter has focused on understanding the similarities and differences in the variable contexts within which the policy-making processes were situated, and the extent to which they influenced policymaking (Christensen, Lægveid and Rykkja, 2018). It has sought to understand the underlying dynamics of the interplay between the key organisations involved in those processes, namely national Governments, academia, and policing. There is little within the literature reviewed, which has explored or theorised about this aspect of initial police education, beyond Hough and Stanko's (2019, p.5) suspicion that policy concerning the PEQF in England

and Wales had been based largely on professional judgment and experience rather than academic research, and Terpstra and Schaap's (2021) cross-national comparative study involving the politics of higher police education in Norway, North Rhine Westphalia, and Finland. They found that the introduction and evolution of higher education policy was founded on "dominant actors' views, expectations, and arguments", but do not provide a detailed analysis of the policy formulation processes involved. Therefore, the broader organisational and policy science literature has been drawn upon to move the analysis in this thesis beyond description to explanation, and to make sense of the extent to which the evolution of initial police learning in the case study countries, had been influenced by their respective underpinning policy processes, and the contexts within which they were situated.

Of particular relevance to understanding the findings described in this chapter, is the theoretical concept espoused by scholars such as Kingdon (1995), and Christensen, Laegreid and Rykkja, (2018). They argue that the variables of context - for example, historical, social, cultural, political - matter in policy formulation, with Terpstra and Fyfe (2014) arguing that the political context is of particular significance. These concepts help to explain the findings discussed in this chapter. For example, whilst in each of the case study countries the single, national State police services were essentially autonomous, and all were directly or indirectly accountable to national Governments within their respective governance structures, relational power varied with regards policy formulation. This in turn provided different, nuanced contexts which mattered in terms of agenda setting, policy formulation and policymaking. For example, whilst Police Scotland was directly accountable to the SPA, the latter's apparent lack of involvement in the 2019 review of the eleven-week Initial Training Course, and Police Scotland's dominance within the power, ideas and policy process or 'stream', might, in part, be understood from the work of Malik (2018, p.461) who argued that the SPA was unable to adequately hold Police Scotland to account. Murray and Malik (2019, pp. 188-189) argued that the SNP-led Scottish Government was "both explicitly and more quietly... stymy[ing] strategic leadership, both within Police Scotland and at the SPA" which was preventing Scottish policing from "decisively

moving forward or transforming”. This might help to explain, in part, why there has been a comparative inertia with regards initial police learning.

At the time of data gathering for this study, the political climate in the UK with regards the professionalisation of policing through HE was ‘hot’ (Murray and Harkin, 2017). The introduction of the PEQF in England and Wales was the subject of much, often heated public debate, with the Scottish Government’s Justice Minister (MacAskill, 2016) openly rejecting the notion of a similar approach being adopted in Scotland. The Scottish Independence debate had also been re-ignited following the Brexit referendum, with the SNP led Scottish Government emphasising Scottish exceptionalism within the UK context. It is unsurprising therefore, that with both the SPA and Police Scotland operating in such a “contested and politicised space” (Murray and Malik, 2019, p.188) which, it is argued, still exists at the time of writing (2022), a policy vacuum exists concerning initial police learning. However, in April 2022, HMICS published their three-year Scrutiny Plan, which included an audit and assurance review of the initial police learning programme. Such a review, which allows for a “detailed scrutiny of critical systems in high-risk areas” (HMICS 2022), may provide a stimulus for reform.

The context of the interplay between the national Government and policing in Sweden on the other hand, varied markedly compared with that in Scotland. Unlike the political policy vacuum found within Scotland, the political influence of national Governments, and in particular the tensions between opposing political ideologies, were found to have significantly influenced agenda setting, policy formulation and progression along the policy pathway. In Finland on the other hand, the national Government was not acting as the policy entrepreneur, the police were. Whilst the national Government’s support was required to lay the necessary legislative changes before the Parliament in Finland on completion of the policy formulation process, they took little part in setting the policy agenda.

Kingdon’s (1995) Multiple Streams Approach provides a useful analytical tool in understanding the variables of context within the policy-making processes. It is built

on the ‘garbage can model’ and a ‘streams’ metaphor which is “flexible and simple to apply” to case studies such as this (Cairney and Jones, 2016, p.38). The ‘garbage can model’ identifies universal elements of the policy process which were apparent in this study. For example, the element regarding decision-making not being entirely rational or linear was evident in Sweden; driven by political ideology rather than research evidence and pushed and pulled in opposing directions by the constantly changing power-relationship between the Social Democratic Party and the Conservative parties. Kingdon (1995) also argued that three separate ‘streams’ (the problem stream, the policy stream, and the politics stream) need to coalesce during a brief window of opportunity for policy change to take place, and again this was seen in Sweden and Finland. Firstly the ‘problem’ needs to gain the attention of policymakers and be acted upon before their attention shifts elsewhere. In Scotland, attention had briefly been on the possibility of a degree entry pathway into Scottish policing, but rejected (see Martin and Wooff, 2020).

At the time of data gathering for this study in 2019, attention had also been on revising the eleven-week ITC which has since resulted in minor curriculum changes. In Sweden, attention had shifted from the initial police learning programme, to increasing the police officer establishment, resulting in any further policy changes being “put in the bottom drawer” as one participant explained. In Finland, after a few years of waiting for a change of Government, the police were able to gain the attention and support of the newly appointed Government, with progress along the policy pathway to a three-year, Bachelor’s degree programme being completed very quickly before the opportunity could be lost with another change of Government. Finland was also a good example of Kingdon’s (1995) second stream, the ‘policy’ stream. In that instance, the police had been moving gradually towards an increasingly educated workforce. Following the introduction of a Master’s programme in the late 1990s, the aim was to introduce a three-year, Bachelor’s degree initial learning programme. A senior officer had developed this policy idea to a point where, when the above ‘window of opportunity’ opened, he had a well-developed policy idea to present which, once accepted, he was able to quickly drive through to completion.

This leads neatly on to the third ‘stream’, the ‘politics’ stream. Policy makers need to be paying attention to the ‘problem’ stream and be receptive to the proposed ‘policy’ stream. They then must take cognisance of other factors which might not be rational, for example, their political ideology, beliefs, other political parties, and the broader political climate. For example, is it ‘cool’ or ‘heated’ (Murray and Harkin, 2017). As Cairney and Jones (2016, p.40) put it, do they have the “motive and opportunity” to enable policy change. In Scotland, this study found there to be little broader political appetite for a fundamental change to the initial police learning programme. In Sweden, the political stream coalesced with the ‘problem’ and ‘policy’ streams whenever the Social Democratic Party held the balance of power but flowed in the opposite direction whenever the Conservative parties did. In Finland, the ‘policy’ stream coalesced with the other streams when there was a change of Government, thereby presenting a ‘window of opportunity’ for the well-developed policy to be quickly pushed along the policy pathway to realisation in the form of legislative change.

This study found that politics’ relational power within the policy formulation processes mattered as far as perceptions of ownership and control were concerned. For example, the ‘silent’ role of the Scottish Government through the auspices of the SPA, and the absence of academia, had resulted in the power, policies and ideas elements of Kingdon’s Policy Streams and Windows (1995) framework being situated entirely within policing. Whilst it was found that police officer participants from all levels of Police Scotland broadly believed that the two-year initial police learning programme met the needs of policing, and therefore had internal, organisational legitimacy, the policing ‘power-knowledge nexus’ (Newman and Clarke, 2018) had not been challenged. In so far as initial police learning was concerned, the political and academia ‘streams’ did not interact with, let alone converge with, the ‘policing stream’. This, along with other external influences such as a challenging public sector funding backdrop, had contributed to the initial police learning model remaining fundamentally unchanged since the middle of the twentieth century. Drawing on Murray and Harkin’s (2017) analogy, policy concerning initial police learning had been operating in a ‘cool’ political environment with little attention or critical scrutiny. In the absence of Scottish policing’s ‘power-knowledge nexus’ (Newman and Clarke,

2018) being challenged by a change of political ideology within the Scottish Government, or the introduction of different perspectives, experience, and ideas, through for example, SIPR, the forthcoming inspection by HMICS, and/or the involvement of HE in the policy formulation process, the Scottish initial police learning model is likely to remain fundamentally unchanged.

This contrasted with Sweden, where the ‘power’ sat principally with the national Government who owned and controlled agenda setting and the policy pathway. Interestingly, whenever the Social Democratic Party were in power and had sufficient authority within the Swedish Parliament, they reset the academisation agenda, re-established the policy formulation process or ‘stream’, and made further progress along the academisation policy pathway. This progress was repeatedly halted by the Conservative parties whenever they regained sufficient power, and punctuated the power equilibrium (Jones and Baumgartner, 2012). However, unlike in Finland where the ‘power’ of the policy-formulation process or ‘stream’ sat primarily with the Police Board and the Police University College, in Sweden the Social Democratic Party had devolved much of it to academia. Despite policing being supportive of a three-year, Bachelor’s degree-accredited initial police learning model, senior police participants involved in the policy formulation process believed that with academia having primacy during the policy formulation process, the resultant policy had foregrounded the needs of academia over those of policing. This thereby undermined legitimacy of both the policy process and the resultant university-based initial police learning model amongst police participants in Sweden.

In Finland, by way of contrast, the police had acted as ‘policy entrepreneurs’, initiating and retaining control of the agenda and of the policy formulation process, despite voluntarily becoming subservient to academia to secure access to the Bologna Process and Bachelor’s degree accreditation. A change of national Government in Finland had resulted in the policy ‘streams’ within policing, academia, and national Government converging, thereby providing a ‘window’ of opportunity for the policy process to progress rapidly through the requisite legislative changes to implementation of the three-year degree accredited initial police learning programme.

The Governmental-organisational (academia and policing) relationships and the policy formulation processes in each country were also found to have been influenced by the presence or absence of underpinning legislation. For example, Scottish policymaking required neither Government nor Parliamentary approval, nor legislative changes (unless altering the 2-year duration of the probationary period), leaving Police Scotland legally entitled to make any other changes to curriculum content and method of delivery they wished. However, policymaking in Sweden and Finland necessitated a negotiated approach with national Governments to secure parliamentary approval for the requisite legislative changes, although as was demonstrated, the extent to which national Governments in both countries influenced both the agenda setting and subsequent policy formulation processes differed. The legislative underpinning of policy has some important advantages and disadvantages. For example, from Christensen, Laegreid, and Rykkja's (2018) 'structural' or 'instrumental' perspective, the 'hierarchical' assumption suggests that strategic policy makers are a homogenous group vis-a-vis their thinking. This homogeneity of thinking, they argued, will result in policy makers initiating and pushing through policy which looks very much as they intended, as was found in Scotland.

This homogenous, non-negotiated, myopic, approach to the policy process contrasts with the heterogenous, negotiated approach in Sweden and Finland, which encapsulated the views and interests of national Governments, academia, and policing. Whilst this made the policy formulation process more conflict-ridden, especially in Sweden, some scholars argue that this broader, participatory approach may result in a higher degree of legitimacy (for example, Mosher, 1967, cited in Christensen, Laegreid and Rykkja 2018, p.243). Whilst some scholars (for example, Mosher, 1967) might argue that the Scottish approach reduces legitimacy, the broadly held view amongst Scottish strategic policy actors was that a broader, participatory approach was unnecessary and potentially detrimental to legitimacy. However, this thesis argues that the absence of perspectives from experts, either from the SPA or from Scottish academia, resulted in there being no "other regarding", no collective decision-making, which might constructively challenge policing's 'knowledge-power nexus' (Newman and Clarke, 2018), and thereby positively influence external legitimacy.

Another key element with regards the ‘power-knowledge nexus’ (Newman and Clarke, 2018) within policy processes, are the ‘academia-organizational relationships’. Within the context of police education, Hallenberg’s (2012) concept of “two-worlds-thinking” is a helpful theoretical concept in understanding this relationship within the variable contexts of the case study countries. Whilst her concept emphasises the relationship between academia and policing’s respective notions of learning, it can also be applied to the relationship found by this study between policing, academia, and national Governments. Hallenberg (2012) suggests that whilst academia privileges “formal learning [which] values freedom of thought, independence, and originality”, the police she argued, as indeed have other scholars, “rate experience and practice over theoretical knowledge”, being more concerned with technical training than theoretical knowledge, which, she argued results in a “structural hostility between ‘theorists’ and ‘practitioners’” (Hallenberg, 2012, p. 169). Similar dichotomies of thinking were also found, to different extents, between the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing in the case study countries.

Given the findings discussed in this chapter with regards the importance of politics to the context of policy processes, Hallenberg’s notion of ‘two worlds thinking’ has been developed to encapsulate a third ‘world’: national Governments, or more accurately the political parties comprising them and their ideological predilections with regards initial police learning. This ‘three-worlds-thinking’ model is particularly helpful in understanding the varied choices made by key actors during the policy process, the importance of networks and coalitions, and the role of ideas in shaping policy, all of which are key elements of Kingdon’s (1995) Policy Streams and Windows concept. For example, in Scotland the ‘structural hostility’ between policing and Government on the one hand, and academia on the other, influenced, it is argued, Police Scotland’s reluctance to allow academia any involvement in either policy formulation or its operationalisation. As one police participant pithily explained, Police Scotland would not allow the ‘tail’ of academia to ‘wag the dog’ of policing, which may help to explain why there were no *networks* and *coalitions*, or sharing of academia’s *ideas* and experience, in shaping policy (Terpstra and Fyfe, 2014, p.368). This seems strange, especially given the interplay between Police Scotland and SIPR as regards other

aspects of policing, including an Education and Leadership Network. Indeed section 32 of the Police and Fire (Reform) Scotland Act (2012), states that Police Scotland's "main purpose" is to "improve the safety and wellbeing of persons, localities, and communities in Scotland and that...working in collaboration with others where appropriate, should seek to achieve that main purpose by policing in a way which... promotes measures to prevent crime, harm, and disorder". It is argued therefore, that it is 'appropriate' for Police Scotland to work in collaboration with academia (and others) to enhance, as in Sweden and Finland, the epistemic knowledge of police recruits which, as argued in chapter 5, will enhance their 'practical wisdom', and thereby reduce the 'harm' to vulnerable 'persons', such as those in mental health crisis. This could support and enhance collaborative understanding, "professional behaviours and real-world outcomes" (Murray *et al.*, 2021, p.13) across Criminal Justice and Public Health in Scotland.

In Sweden and Finland, *networks* and *coalitions* were found by this study to exist which encapsulate the 'three-worlds-thinking' of academia, policing, and national Governments. However, whilst Sweden and Finland had both adopted heterogenous, negotiated approaches to policy-formulation and policy-making encapsulating these 'three-worlds', the interplay between them varied, resulting in different approaches to policy formulation, and different perceptions of legitimacy concerning academic education's role within initial police learning. For example, in Sweden, whilst the 'three-worlds thinking' of the Swedish Government (when the Social Democratic Party held the balance of power), academia, and policing, were supportive of a three-year, pre-entry Bachelor's degree model, the asymmetry and inequality of relational power within the heterogenous, negotiated process had resulted in academia having the balance of power within the policy formulation process, as directed by the Swedish Government. This was found by this study to have resulted in a widely held perception amongst police participants in Sweden, that the needs of academia had been foregrounded over those of policing. By way of contrast, whilst the heterogenous, negotiated approach in Finland had also involved the 'three-worlds thinking' of national Government, academia and policing, the police in Finland had retained ownership and control of the policy-formulation process within what was more of a

coalition than in Sweden, with the Government retaining control of the legislative, policy-making process. Whilst it might be argued that this ‘three-worlds thinking’ had not challenged the ‘power-knowledge nexus’ (Newman and Clarke, 2018) of the police to the same extent as in Sweden, it is argued in this thesis that the approach in Finland primarily met the needs of policing there, whilst also managing to meet the needs of academia concerning degree accreditation, and the needs of the Government. This interplay was crucial in influencing perceptions of legitimacy both with regards the policy process, and the revised initial police learning programme within politics, academia, and policing.

These findings concerning the context and process of policymaking within the case study countries, echo those scholars within the broader policing literature who argue that the national context makes a difference, such as Newman and Clarke (2018, p.51), and Bowling, Reiner, and Sheptycki (2019, p.248). The findings from this study have shown that there were “numerous ‘players’ in the field of policing policy” who had each “in some respect attempted to pull and push policing policy in different directions and with different degrees of effectiveness”, with some being “dominant and others subordinate” (Savage, Charman and Cope, 2000, p.46). Whilst this chapter has explored, analysed, and attempted to understand *who* made and shaped policy in relation to initial police learning in the case study countries and *how* they made it, there is also merit in addressing Savage, Charman and Cope’s (2000, p.30) question as to who *should* make or shape policing policy. Whilst the ‘one-world thinking’, homogenous, non-negotiated approach had enabled Police Scotland to retain power over policy formulation, the absence of a coalition encapsulating academia and the Scottish Government, through the auspices of the SPA, had resulted in the absence of any challenges to its ‘power-knowledge nexus’ (Newman and Clarke, 2018). This in turn may raise questions concerning the initial learning programme’s long-term ability to attract, develop, and retain police officers operating within an increasingly complex and demanding operating environment.

Conversely, the politically led heterogenous, negotiated approach in Sweden could be viewed as politicians seeking to challenge the professional power of policing by

reconfiguring the “power-knowledge nexus” (Newman and Clarke, 2018, p.41) more towards themselves and academia as part of a wider strategy to professionalise policing. However, the outcome at the time of data gathering for this study in 2019, revealed concerns amongst both academic participants and policing participants with regards the policy formulation process, and the revised initial police learning programme: concern from academics that the two-and-a-half-year programme was not a three-year programme; concern from police participants that the revised programme had prioritised the needs of academia over those of policing; concern from both that the programme was not degree-accredited and that the policy agenda and pathway continued to be pushed and pulled in opposing directions by the conflicting ideologies of the Social Democratic Party and the Conservative parties; and what Hallenberg (2012, p.169) describes as “structural hostility between ‘theorists’ and ‘practitioners’”. In Finland on the other hand, whilst policing had set the agenda (primarily to develop an initial learning programme which supported their organisational structure, organisational culture, and policing style), the policy pathway had required a heterogenous, negotiated approach which also involved the national Government and academia. The Government (and Parliament) in Finland ‘owned’ the underpinning legislation and were thereby empowered to enable or hinder progression along the policy pathway. Academia’s support was also required in order that the revised initial police learning programme might be accredited as a Bachelor’s degree within the auspices of the wider European Union Bologna Process.

Used in combination these theoretical concepts, drawn from the wider organisational and policy science literature, have helped to disentangle and understand the contextualised interplays between the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of politics, academia, and policing, and the extent to which they influenced agenda setting, policy formulation and policymaking. They have helped to analyse the ‘thinking’ within each ‘world’ and the formations of power between them, and crucially for this thesis, the extent to which these influenced the policy processes. In doing so, they have helped to explain the similarities and differences in the evolution of initial police learning within the case study countries, thereby addressing the research question ‘how has initial police learning evolved in the case study countries?’.

4.4 Conclusion.

In addressing the research question, '*how has initial police learning evolved within the case study countries?*', this chapter began by highlighting the widely held perception that contemporary operating environments were rapidly becoming more complex and demanding. It explored policing's responses, arguing that the increasingly specialist Scottish approach, coupled with a hierarchical organisational culture, had resulted in an expectation that front-line, junior response officers would deal with non-complex, routine tasks. It then highlighted the organisational responses in Sweden (which were similar to, but less marginalising, than Scotland) and in Finland, where the latter focused on empowering and enabling front-line, junior response officers to deal with a wider range of more complex tasks from 'end-to-end', in support of a 'lean management' policing model, facilitated by a distributed leadership approach. It then untangled the processes of policymaking within Scotland, Finland, and Sweden, to better understand the evolution of initial police learning policy within each country, revealing that the degree of homogeneity or heterogeneity and relational power between the 'three-worlds thinking' of national Governments, academia, and policing during the policy formulation processes influenced not only the policy pathways within each country, but also perceptions of legitimacy, both of the policy-making process and of the initial police learning programmes. It also argued that the situated and constantly changing contexts of policymaking, and in particular the divergent power relationships within the different policy-making approaches, are key to understanding the similarities and differences in the evolution of initial police learning within the case study countries.

Chapter 5 moves on to present and analyse participant perceptions of the different approaches to initial police learning within the case study countries, and the extent to which they were perceived as helping professional development.

Chapter 5: Desirable knowledge, skills, and behaviours

Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to describe, analyse, and explain the findings from this study with respect to the research question: *what knowledge, skills and behaviours do 'policy network actors' (Savage, Charman and Cope, 2000) within the case study countries view as desirable in a professional police officer?* It begins in section 5.1, by exploring the principal source of explanatory theoretical inspiration for this chapter, namely the Aristotelean concepts of 'episteme', 'techne' and 'phronesis'.

Section 5.2 reveals that in defining policing as a profession, police officers drew on a sense of vocation and of mission to protect society's vulnerable people, groups, and communities. The section then moves on to reveal the contrasting notions of organisational and occupational professionalism (Evetts, 2009) in Scotland and Sweden on the one hand, with those in Finland on the other. It is argued that the former, guided by a specialist "rational, efficient" (Sklansky, 2011, p.2) notion of organisational professionalism, which was guided by rules imposed and enforced by a hierarchical system of control and direction (Fyfe, 2014; Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019), was de-professionalising (Noordegraaf, 2007, Schinkel and Noordegraaf, 2011, Hibbert, 2012) junior first-responders, by marginalising their role, and confining it to 'routine', less complex tasks. In Finland, by way of contrast, junior front-line first response officers had a more generalist role, and were operating within a lean, distributed system of organisational control and direction, which afforded them greater adhocracy (Cameron and Quinn, 2011). The organisational expectation was that they provide an end-to-end service and undertake a wider range of more complex tasks than their peers in Scotland and Sweden, with minimal recourse to specialists and managers.

Section 5.3 analyses participant perceptions of epistemic knowledge as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital within initial police learning. It reveals that police officers in Scotland generally perceived it as having little or nothing

to do with policing, given the limited, marginalised role of junior, front-line response officers. By way of contrast, policing students, senior officers, and academics in Sweden and Finland, were generally of the view that the inclusion of epistemic knowledge enables officers to understand and respond appropriately to a wide and complex range of tasks and was an important element within a broader police professionalisation agenda. This, despite the apparent dichotomy in Sweden between the “rational, efficient” (Sklansky, 2011, p.2) notion of organisational professionalism, and the individual professionalising benefits of academisation. Finally, this section highlights that whilst policing students in Sweden differentiated between vocationally relevant and non-vocationally relevant epistemic knowledge, this changed over time and with on-the-job practice experience.

Section 5.4 explores the extent to which ‘techne’, ‘knowing how to’, or ‘craft’ knowledge (Grint, 2007), was foregrounded as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital within initial police learning. It reveals that police officer participants, regardless of their experience, rank, or country, generally foregrounded ‘craft’ knowledge (Willis, 2013; Willis and Mastrofski, 2016) over theoretical knowledge (‘epistemic’ and non-epistemic). However, this study also found that police officers in Sweden and Finland were generally of the view that blending vocationally relevant epistemic knowledge with ‘craft’ knowledge (Willis, 2013, Willis and Mastrofski, 2014, 2016, 2018) was an important foundation for developing expertise through experience.

Section 5.5 explores police officer participant perceptions of desirable professional behaviours. It reveals that in each of the case study countries, treating people with dignity, empathy, fairness, and respect whilst conducting themselves with integrity (Westmarland and Rowe, 2018), were regarded as particularly desirable attributes of professional behaviour. It highlights that when discussing integrity, participants frequently used phrases and words such as ‘ethical standards’, and ‘honesty’, and often did so within the context of decision-making, using words and phrases such as ‘professional judgement’, ‘discretion’ and ‘ethical’. This section then moves on to argue in support of those scholars (for example, Grint, 2007; Fenwick, 2015) who have

called for a greater appreciation of ‘phronesis’ as part of the decision making processes of those within public services operating within challenging and complex environments.

In discussing and analysing the findings revealed in this chapter, section 5.6 develops the argument that an important dimension of contemporary police professionalism could be ‘phronesis’: the autonomous application of intellectually, practically, and ethically motivated deliberations in the application of expert decision-making and actions, which is informed by a blending of ‘epistemic’ knowledge, ‘craft’ knowledge, and practical experiential knowledge. This, it is argued, is key to supporting the necessary reconfiguration (Noordegraaf, 2016) of police professionalism within the broader societal, economic, and cultural shifts taking place within the operating environments, ensuring that “effective services are delivered, that norms and values are upheld, and that professional work is trusted and legitimated” (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.784; Martin, 2021).

The chapter concludes with section 5.7 which briefly summarises the chapter’s key argument.

5.1 The theoretical framework

In Book VI of his *Nicomachean Ethics* (350 BC), Aristotle distinguishes between the two intellectual virtues, namely “those of the mind [intellectual], and those of character [moral]. The intellectual virtues comprise phronesis (‘practical wisdom’) and ‘theoretical wisdom’” (Grayling, 2019, p.92), with theoretical wisdom comprising ‘episteme’ (evidence gained through observation and experimentation), and ‘techne’ (technical or craft knowledge).

There are several benefits and challenges associated with drawing on Aristotle’s notions of ‘episteme’, ‘techne’, and ‘phronesis’, as a theoretical framework. The benefits include a way of conceptualising and understanding that contemporary policing requires a combination of theoretical, science-based knowledge (episteme),

replicable skills (*techne*), and practical wisdom (*phronesis*) to achieve resolutions beyond the narrow confines of a “duty or rules approach” (Hurteau and Gagnon, 2022, p.182) which may “not offer an acceptable solution to a complex problem” (Hurteau and Gagnon, 2022, p. 182). DeMartino (2019, p.9) nuances this further by suggesting that practical wisdom is “about helping virtuous practitioners do good in a complex world where what is right or good to do is often uncertain”. As for the challenges, *Nicomachean Ethics* is based on incomplete lecture notes written two millennia ago, lecture notes upon which Aristotle would undoubtedly have expanded when delivering his lectures. The texts drawn on for the purpose of this thesis are translations from the Ancient Greek, the English interpretations of which vary from scholar to scholar. This chapter draws largely on translations and interpretations by Crisp (2014) and Broadie and Rowe (2022). Despite these difficulties, the Aristotelean domains of *episteme*, *techne*, and *phronesis* are reflected in contemporary notions of knowledge, namely explicit knowledge which encapsulates science-based, documented knowledge associated with higher academic learning (*episteme*); implicit knowledge which is associated with practical, ‘craft’ or artistic work undertaken by hand (*techne*); and tacit knowledge, experience-driven and encapsulating societal values, personal values, and organisational values, developed, as Aristotle suggests, largely during childhood as opposed to workplace socialisation.

Before exploring the themes developed from this study’s data concerning what knowledge, skills, and behaviours participants within each of the case study countries perceived as desirable of a professional police officer, this chapter begins by exploring participant perceptions of police professionalism.

5.2 Notions of professionalism

Within each of the case study countries participants generally drew on a notion of police professionalism in their discourse which was guided by their “occupational identities and work practices” (Evetts, 2003, p.399). For example, police officers generally referred to policing as a vocation and believed that policing made a positive

difference to society, as exemplified by these comments from a senior police officer in Sweden:

“I still hold about the importance of doing something that is meaningful and can make a difference to people’s lives... it’s sort of an honour to be a police officer... we always have that thing that we want to take care of things and help people, even if we are on our way home or on a day off ... it’s us against the threats outside. And it’s a pride of being professional and to be that person who stands for the good things.”
[Participant SWP07 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

This “sense of mission” (Loftus, 2010, p.4) features within much of the literature on police occupational culture (Chan, 1996; Chan, 1997; House, 2013; Terpstra and Schaap, 2013; Honey, 2014; Silvestri, 2017; Fekjær and Petersson, 2019; Syrja, 2019; Martin, 2021; Skinns, Wooff and Sprawson, 2021). The findings from this study appear to echo those of Loftus’ (2010, p.4) study of police officers from the north of England who “expressed great pride in the duty of police work... and [its] potential to make a difference”. In illustrating how policing was providing a socially useful service (Bacon, 2016), participants at every level, and in each of the case study countries, frequently highlighted policing’s role in helping to protect society’s vulnerable, as this quotation from a policing student in Sweden about to graduate from the two and a half year initial police learning programme demonstrates:

“I really genuinely think that I can do a difference. I’ve been in my six months practical work, and I can see how the society looks, and how it is out there. And it’s a lot of depression, and a lot of people are using narcotics and are in a downward spiral. And I think that if you pay attention to them, and let them see that you see them, and talk to them, you can make a difference. And that’s why I am wanting to be a police officer.” [Participant SWP12 - Policing Student, Sweden]

When discussing the role of the police service in helping to protect the vulnerable, participants at all levels, and within each of the case study countries, highlighted the extent to which this had become a focus of their activities, rather than the dealing with criminality, albeit that a ‘footprint’ of criminality remained when dealing with vulnerability. This quotation from a senior police officer in Scotland who was undertaking the role of an operational commander, exemplifies this point:

“...locking up the bad guys all the time is becoming less and less daily business. The daily business is encountering vulnerability. Whether that’s children, whether it’s adults, whether it’s the elderly, whether it’s dealing with domestic abuse victims. There is undoubtedly a footprint of criminality, and we’ll continue dealing with that, but the job is becoming more. It demands more of these new recruits.” [Participant SCP13 – Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

This finding echoes the work of other scholars (for example, Charman, 2017, 2018; Fleming and Rhodes, 2018). Charman’s (2017; 2018, p.6) study of police recruits during their first four-years of service showed that policing within a southern English force was more focused on the “congenial activities such as citizen protection, public reassurance and safeguarding rather than on the more combative activities such as fighting crime and catching criminals”. She argued that these notions of professionalism represented a ‘new breed’ of police officer who were more focused on dealing with vulnerability rather than crime. This focus on vulnerability, however, may have more to do with a change in the strategic focus of national Governments and police services rather than being derived from a ‘new breed’ of officer.

Whilst these findings support the broader notion that contemporary police professionalism is guided by “an ideology, a set of beliefs and values which underpin its activities [and] embodies the values of service” (Scott 1999, p.52), they also reveal a tension between the ideology of police recruits and junior officers in Scotland, and that of their force. For example, police recruits with about eighteen-months service, and junior-ranking police officers, expressed the view that their freedom to make decisions, or adhocacy (Cameron and Quin, 2011), within complex situations, had been curtailed by Police Scotland’s notion of professionalism which was guided by rules imposed and enforced by a hierarchical system of control and direction (Fyfe, 2014; Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019). This widely held perception amongst police recruits and junior, front-line response constables, is exemplified in this discussion with a police recruit who had sixteen-months service, and whose reference point was his previous experience as a Special Constable prior to the establishment of Police Scotland:

I: “How much do you feel where you are now, a year and four months in, that you’re being able to apply professional judgements to decisions that you take?”

Male 3: “Not a lot.”

I: “Why’s that?”

Male 3: “Because you don’t get the freedom anymore of using your discretion as much as you used to have.”

[Focus Group SCPFG1 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

This finding might be understood by considering Evetts' (2014) more nuanced concept of professionalism which encapsulates both *occupational professionalism* (having collegial authority, based on practitioner autonomy and discretionary judgment), and *organisational professionalism* (hierarchical structures of responsibility and decision making; standardised work procedures and practice consistent with managerial controls; reliance on external regulation and accountabilities such as target setting and performance review).

The notion of organisational professionalism in Scotland and Sweden was guided by a specialist “rational, efficient” (Sklansky, 2011, p.2) notion of police professionalism guided, as mentioned above, by rules imposed and enforced by a hierarchical system of control and direction (Fyfe, 2014; Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019). It might also be understood by considering Noordegraaf’s (2007, 2015) concept of ‘hybrid’ professionalism. The notion of occupational professionalism found by this study amongst police officers from each of the case study countries was guided by a sense of service, a desire to make a positive difference, particularly to society’s vulnerable. However, recruits in Scotland were of the view that this required a greater freedom to apply individual professional judgement in the nuanced, complex often unique situations they found themselves dealing with. This disconnect between the organisational notion of police professionalism and the occupational notion of professionalism has resulted in a perception amongst some junior officers that they were being de-professionalised.

In Finland on the other hand, the data revealed a closer alignment between notions of occupational and organisational professionalism, with junior front-line operational response constables given greater adhocacy (Cameron and Quinn, 2011) and responsibility to think for themselves when dealing with almost any situation they found themselves in, and to provide as much of an end-to-end service as possible without recourse to specialists. The following quotations demonstrate this point, firstly from a policing student in Finland nearing the completion of their initial learning programme, and secondly from a chief police officer in Finland:

“... here we are taught how to think... we are not just told...if you see a theft you do this, this and this...because no situation is the same, so then you have many options what you could do.” [Focus Group FFG1 - Policing Student, Finland]

“...officers in the car... have to be able to, to manage any kind of situation they confront. Support is not available... I mean, immediate support is not available and er, and we cannot afford many specialised units.” [Participant FP02 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

This might be understood within the context of the organisational notions of professionalism in Finland, which can be described as geographically dispersed, and comprising autonomous, generalist police officers who are guided by a lean, distributed system of control and direction which tended more towards greater adhocacy (Cameron and Quinn, 2011). The comment by the policing student that police officers need to be able to think for themselves, and to select from many possible options an appropriate course of action in any given situation, none of which are the same, is an important point to which this discussion will return in section 5.6.

Interpreting the Swedish data is more complex. Whilst policing students in Sweden had, like their counterparts in Scotland and Finland, a notion of occupational professionalism which was guided by a sense of service, and a desire to make a positive difference, they generally did not express the view that this required a greater freedom to apply individual professional judgement. This finding is significant with regards the pathway towards academisation which Swedish policing has been embarked upon for the past decade and will be discussed further in chapter 6.

5.3 Desirable knowledge: theoretical knowledge

The first of the Aristotelean intellectual virtues which this chapter explores is ‘theoretical wisdom’ (Grayling, 2019, p. 92), which he argued comprises episteme (evidence gained through observation and experimentation), and techne (technical or craft knowledge). The Aristotelean domain of episteme is reflected in the contemporary notions of explicit knowledge which encapsulates science-based, documented knowledge associated with higher academic learning. The findings from this study show that perceptions of episteme’s positionality as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital within policing, was situated and complex, with similarities and differences being found within, and across, the case study countries. For example, there was a widely held perception amongst police officers of all ranks in Scotland that epistemic knowledge, particularly that which they associated with higher academic learning, was not a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital, as this quotation from a sixteen-month service recruit, who had entered as a graduate, demonstrates:

“I think you can have a psychology aspect at the College which could make a massive difference because it does... I mean my tutor slags me for it all the time because I’m always... not making excuses for people, but my understanding of human behaviour, what I’ve learned at Uni[versity] for example, all the environmental factors which come into it and things like that, you do have a much better understanding of human behaviour and the impacts that affect that, and it probably did help me a lot actually.” [Focus Group SCPFG1 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

This perception of epistemic knowledge was reflected in its absence within the initial police learning programme. This perception amongst participants in Scotland (apart from academics), might be explained not only by the ‘rational efficient’ notion of organisational professionalism discussed earlier, but also by the horizontally fragmented (Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019) organisational structures within Police Scotland which had resulted in the role of a front-line response officer becoming narrower and less complex than that of their generalist counterparts in Finland. As this senior operational commander explained, junior, front-line, operational response constables are only expected to deal with routine tasks:

“You’ve got to look at the role that we’re expecting cops to do ... they’re dealing with what we would class as routine business... the skill set of a response cop is to respond to incidents, secure and preserve evidence, do victim protection, and deal with victims in a caring and thoughtful manner, and bring offenders to justice if they can, and if not, package it up and hand it on. That’s the skill set now of a patrol cop. It’s very different from what it was when you and I were operational cops.”
[Participant SCP13 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

Given the more ‘routine’, less complex nature of the role, there was a widely held perception amongst police officers at all levels in Scotland, that junior, first responders required limited theoretical knowledge of any kind, including the law. These findings in relation to the positionality of theoretical knowledge, including epistemic knowledge, as a privileged form of knowledge and a source of cultural capital, might be considered as ‘de-professionalising’ (Noordegraaf, 2007; Schinkel and Noordegraaf, 2011; Hibbert, 2012). By way of contrast, there was a widely held perception amongst policing students, senior officers, and academics in Sweden and Finland, that the inclusion of epistemic theoretical knowledge facilitates professional decision-making by broadening their understanding of the policing environment, as this quotation from a chief officer in Finland demonstrates:

“Now we have seen the first course was, if I remember right, 2015 or 2014, so they are already on the beat [sic]. I can say the skills are even better because they understand more [sic] the problems... the knowledge about the society and to take care [of] the problems so that we really solve the problem. Not just put the case behind us and come back again in that place” [Participant FP18 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

Police officers would, as a result, be competent to undertake a wide and complex range of tasks, with a high degree of adhocacy (Cameron and Quinn, 2011). As this chief police officer in Finland claimed, officers who had graduated from the Bachelor of Science accredited initial police learning programme were more ready to accept responsibility than their predecessors:

“...many of them say that the new young officers are more... they are readier to take responsibility than before.” [Participant FP02 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

It was also found that police officers in Sweden and Finland wanted to understand the rationale underpinning decision-making, as this police inspector in Sweden explained:

“I sense it changed a little bit amongst the new guys I have on my squad now. You can’t just tell them we’re going to do this, and they are why? They don’t just go there and do that, they need to know that this is useful and there is some point to do that, they like to use the research. But when you are out and giving orders, of course, then they have to obey. But in the planning, we don’t have that commando thing really, we talk in a group, and what should we do, and how can we solve this best, and what tactics should we use, then I decide, but it’s a group thing.” [Participant SWP07 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

Organisations which tend towards greater adhocracy, require a style of leadership which tends towards the subordinate centred end of the Leadership Continuum (Tannenbaum and Schmidt, 2006), whereby greater freedom is delegated to junior officers to make decisions independently. Indeed, data from this study showed this leadership approach to be evident within policing in Finland, as this operational police sergeant in Finland explained:

“I think it’s useful, people who can make independent work and good work, they have skills and want to do that... it’s part of modern times. Because on the field we don’t lead people [sic] way. People want to use their own head and skills” [Participant FP13 - Police Sergeant]

These findings suggest an organisational culture in Finland which tends more towards adhocracy, and values flexibility and discretion, as opposed to the Scottish and Swedish organisational cultures, which tend towards hierarchical cultures, and which value stability and control (Cameron and Quinn, 2011; Elliott and Tatnell, 2013).

Despite the differences in organisational notions of professionalism between Sweden and Finland, academics and senior police officers in both countries expressed the view that epistemic knowledge was an important element within a broader police professionalisation agenda which ultimately would enhance quality of service, as this quotation from a chief police officer in Finland shows:

“I am perhaps still a bit of an idealist, but I think that it will result in better service to the people... better police service.” [Participant FP02 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

However, the data also revealed that within the broader concept of theoretical knowledge, policing students in Sweden and Finland differentiated between that which underpinned the development of vocational skills such as mental health (both their own and members of the public), and that which they considered of little operational or practical relevance such as criminology, sociology, and academic research techniques. However, the findings also showed that perceptions concerning epistemic knowledge were more complex and nuanced than this. For example, the extent to which epistemic knowledge was perceived as vocationally relevant, or irrelevant, changed over time. Those in the early phases of their initial police learning programmes generally perceived epistemic theoretical knowledge to be less vocationally relevant than those who were in the final, post experiential learning phases. The following quotation from a policing student in Sweden with regards the psychology of mental health exemplifies this changing perception over time:

“We had some studies in school in the auditorium about the psychology about mental health, what a narcissistic person is, what is PTSD, what isn’t, this is schizophrenia, and this is narcissism, and this means to be a psychopath’, what happens chemically in your brain when you’re narcissistic, and I thought it went too far. But in the practical situations it was very good learning.” [Participant SWP12 - Policing Student, Sweden]

This student’s initial perception that the depth of learning concerning the science of mental health went “too far”, was subsequently amended after their six-month field training which took place after the first two-years of university-based learning. They found that having the relevant epistemic knowledge was helpful when dealing in practice with people in mental health crisis. This changing perception with regards epistemic knowledge over time, bridged the gap between conceptual, theoretical, or epistemic knowledge and professional practice, and might be partly understood by once again considering the different notions of organisational professionalism within the case study countries. For example, within the more horizontally fragmented, specialist policing model, the argument is that those in a higher rank and/or a specialist role, not only benefit from, but also have more opportunity to utilise epistemic knowledge. These comments, firstly from a chief police officer in Scotland who had undertaken postgraduate education relating to their specialist area of work, namely

child protection, and secondly from a senior officer in Scotland who had undertaken a postgraduate degree, but who did not find the epistemic knowledge developed during their education of practical use until they had achieved a senior rank, demonstrate this thinking:

“There were things about child development and psychology that made sense to me after the fact. So, I’m sitting in a course, listening to descriptions of behaviours that I have absolutely experienced and dealt with, but not understood. So, I can see, and I recognised then, that that would have been enormously beneficial to have had that knowledge, if not before, ideally before, but certainly during, actually having the operational responsibility for delivering.” [Participant SCP07 - Chief Police Officer, Scotland]

“I would say that as a young cop, that had about as much relevance as a house brick to me. None whatsoever. Not really as a Sergeant, and very little as an Inspector, but from Chief Inspector upwards and certainly now, I use the skills that I got from that a lot more than I would have done in the more junior ranks.” [Participant SCP13 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

Aristotle used ‘episteme’ to encapsulate scientific knowledge and in doing so differentiated epistemic knowledge from belief or ‘doxa’ and from skill or ‘techne’ (Crisp 2014, p. 203). It is to ‘techne’ that this chapter now turns.

5.4 Desirable knowledge: ‘craft’ knowledge

This section explores the extent to which ‘techne’, ‘knowing how to’, or ‘craft’ knowledge (Grint, 2007), was foregrounded as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital within initial police learning. In Aristotle’s *Nicomachean Ethics* Book VI, the concept of ‘techne’, or “knowing how to, was the equivalent of craft knowledge, it was an art (hence the term ‘Artisan’). Techne refers to other things that do not have an inner purpose – their purpose is to produce other things” (Grint, 2007, p. 234). ‘Techne’ therefore, is usually associated with practical, pragmatic, context-dependent, variable, implicit or ‘craft’ knowledge. The original concept appears today in terms such as technique, technical, and technology (Kinsella and Pitman, 2012, p.1).

Analysis of the data gathered for this study revealed nuanced and situated perceptions of ‘*techne*’s position in relation to the broader meaning of theoretical knowledge discussed earlier. For example, it was found that police officer participants, regardless of their experience, rank, or country, foregrounded ‘craft’ knowledge (Willis, 2013; Willis and Mastrofski, 2016) over theoretical knowledge as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital, as these quotations from experienced senior police officers demonstrate:

“The knowledge which we need to have is actually human interaction and experience on the street, as opposed to something that can be taught.” [Participant SCP05 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

“I think that is because experience in craft knowledge has relevance, sector relevance. It’s relevant to a police officer’s daily routine is that knowledge and credibility. Policing is one of these cultures, regardless of your rank, credibility is everything.” [Participant SCP13 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

These comments reflect the widely held perception amongst police officers within each of the case study countries, that learning the ‘art’ (Crisp, 2014, p. 203) and ‘craft’ of policing, required years of practice and experience to develop, as exemplified by this quotation from an experienced police officer in Sweden:

“It’s a very practical profession... it’s just wrong to say it’s going to be theoretical everything because there is a lot of hands-on work that we need to learn... it’s an art... you cannot only go to an academy and then be [a] fully feathered police officer, it takes years and years from the experience, the silent knowledge, the practical knowledge.” [Participant SWP06 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

Foregrounding personal experience over theoretical knowledge was widely perceived, particularly in Scotland, as the foundation of ‘good’ policing (Holdaway, 1983). Through practice at the “sharp end” on the streets, the ‘art’ or ‘craft’ of policing is honed, and new entrants become a “good practical copper” (Manning, 1979, p. 49). This focus on learning ‘craft’ knowledge in the field has been found in other studies of police learning, for example Hunter and May (2020). However, learning solely or primarily from experience is problematic. In his *Metaphysics*, Aristotle contrasts the person with experience (*empeiria*) with someone who has epistemic knowledge. For

example, the police officer with experience knows that when previously faced with a particular set of circumstances, a particular course of action produced the desired outcome. However, in applying Aristotelian concepts, it might be argued that the police officer with epistemic knowledge goes beyond experience and draws on a wider pool of knowledge than that which has been shown to work beyond their immediate personal experience: a universal truth which has been shown, usually, to produce the desired outcome. The master craftsperson (technites), Aristotle argued, is wiser than the person of experience because they know the cause *and* the reason *why* a particular response should be taken. The desire to understand why a particular course of action should or should not be taken, was frequently highlighted by police officers in Sweden and Finland as important in their notion of both organisational and occupational professionalism. These quotations, firstly from an educator involved in delivering the initial police learning programme in Sweden, and secondly, from a senior operational police commander in Finland, exemplify this:

“And from the beginning of the programme we have this more theoretical course that is called the police role and mission in society. Why are we here? Why?” [Participant SWP 14 - Policing Educator, Sweden]

“In order to make Finnish men to do what you want, you have to motivate them, to say why we are doing this. And it’s very true in our police forces. For our young leaders it’s a very big mistake to say to experienced or inexperienced police officers how to do it. You have to say only what to do and why.” [Participant FP 11 - Senior Police Officer, Finland]

The desire of adult learners to know *why* they are learning, is a well-established concept within the adult education literature (for example, see Knowles, 1970).

Some translations of Aristotelean ‘*techne*’ (for example, Crisp 2014, p. 203) suggest that it encapsulates the production of an external good or virtue (such as feeling safe from crime or good health). Aristotle argued that the value of a virtuous action depends on the person undertaking the action, in that they must act with knowledge and deliberately choose the action not for itself but for the end. Thus, the value of the activity is in the outcome as, for example, in taking a schizophrenic person in crisis to

a place of safety in order that they may be protected from harm. The value is not in taking them to a place of safety, but in protecting them from harm. Aristotle sometimes mentions ‘episteme’ and ‘techne’ in the same breath, and sometimes (as in Nicomachean Ethics VI) he appears to suggest that they are distinct from one another. However, it is argued in this thesis that there is not a binary distinction between ‘episteme’ and ‘techne’, rather there is an interplay between them. For example, when dealing with a schizophrenic in crisis, an officer’s epistemic knowledge and understanding of schizophrenia would blend with their ‘craft’ knowledge or technical skills when interacting with them.

In dealing with complex or even wicked problems⁴ (Grint, 2010; Duke, 2012; Christensen, Lægreid and Rykkja, 2016) which have not been previously experienced, and/or for which there are no policies or accepted practices on which to base a decision, the craftsman or craftswoman might achieve their goal by looking at the mean, the average, and using that as a standard in what it produces. In interpreting what Aristotle meant by the ‘mean’, Grayling (2019, p. 93) suggests that a craftsperson can “acquire something analogous to a technical skill in knowing how to navigate between the vicious extremes between which the mean is the associated virtue”.

This leads the discussion onto the next section which will draw upon the Aristotelean concept of ‘phronesis’ to not only explain and understand participant perceptions regarding the desirable behaviours of police officers, but also to deepen understanding of the findings concerning knowledge and skills, and to argue how it should guide re-configured notions of ‘new’ professionalism.

⁴ Wicked problems are those which are characterised by being unique, intractable, transboundary, unique, and for which there is no agreement as to what an acceptable solution might look like (Rittel and Webber 1973; Christensen, Laegreid and Rykkja, 2016).

5.5 Desirable behaviours

Treating people with dignity, empathy, fairness, and respect, whilst conducting themselves with integrity (Westmarland and Rowe, 2018), were regarded as particularly desirable behaviours within each of the case study countries. This theme echoes the empirical work of scholars such as Charman (2017), who argued that these notions of professionalism represented the emergence of a ‘new breed’ of 21st century police officers who differed from their predecessors, whose occupational notions of professionalism were founded on crime-fighting. When discussing integrity, participants frequently used phrases and words such as ‘judgement’ and ‘ethical standards’, and often did so within the context of decision-making, as firstly this senior actor from the Scottish Police Authority, and secondly a senior operational police commander from Scotland explain:

“You can teach someone how the law operates but you can’t teach them how to apply the law. There’s very much elements of judgement that sit behind that.” [Participant SCP15 - SPA Member, Scotland]

“... the core role of policing is about having good ethical standards in your decision making and leadership. And when I talk about leadership, I don’t mean by rank...” [Participant SCP12 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

Ethical decision-making, it is argued, is increasingly necessary for professional police officers to operate within increasingly complex operational environments (Grint, 2007; Fenwick, 2015). However, it was also found that taking what some officers considered to be ethically valid decisions, what they called ‘doing the right thing’, might conflict with doing it ‘the right way’ as determined by either the law or organisational policy. These quotations, firstly from a senior operational police commander in Scotland (which speaks to discretion, yet is at odds with the perception of the police recruit replicated earlier in this chapter), and secondly from a police Inspector in Sweden, demonstrate this:

“... there is a skillset in policing that’s about expect the unexpected. So, you can’t train for every expectation in policing, or people start to do things right, rather than doing the right thing. So, there is a bit about, I call it intuitive policing. You get a gut feeling for whether something is

right or wrong, and generally when you get the feeling, you get it right.”
[Participant SCP12 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

“Do the right thing by the laws and maybe the right thing is not to do exactly what the law say because I want to do it because of something. Maybe, maybe sometimes to see what the important thing when I come to a situation, what is the best thing to do in this situation.” [Participant SWP07 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

This notion of doing the ‘right thing’ rather than doing it the ‘right way’ was frequently underpinned by participants’ personal notions of value (Lumsden, 2017), as this quotation from a policing student in Finland demonstrates:

“I think you need some sort of a moral compass or some sort of values that you can’t just apply to any other job.” [Focus Group FFG 1 - Policing Student, Finland]

This notion of the “moral compass” or “moral integrity” (Manning, 1977, p.4) of policing, within the broader concept of professional values, is important. It influences work behaviour (Sundström and Wolming, 2014, p.36). Indeed, some scholars (for example, Grint, 2007; Fenwick, 2015) have called for a greater appreciation of ‘phronesis’, so that professionals can operate professionally within challenging and complex environments to “recognise what virtues are appropriate to a specific situation so that action conduces to [a] good life” (Kristjánsson *et al.*, 2021, p.242). It is argued, therefore, that if theoretical knowledge, including epistemic knowledge, and ‘craft’ knowledge (*techne*), helps to identify what are the ‘good’ or right goals or outcomes which might be achieved in any given situation, then “practical wisdom teaches how to reach it” (Grayling, 2019, p.93). Deliberating as to the best course of action in any given situation whilst drawing on appropriate theoretical and ‘craft’ knowledge, together with the officer’s own moral compass or character, underpin the Aristotelian concept of practical wisdom or ‘phronesis’, as this quotation from a police student in Finland, who had completed their eleven-month field training, demonstrates:

“...you need a good combination of them [episteme and techne] so that you can be a good police [officer], because if you don’t know a lot of theory and you just do practical then it’s exactly what I said... that there are certain situations and you act in certain things, but you don’t know

why you do that. But when you know theory then in practice you can do very well, that's my opinion." [Focus Group FFG1 - Policing Student, Finland]

Sometimes also referred to in the literature as 'prudence' (for example, Beckett, 2012, p. 115; Grint, 2007, p.238), it is encapsulated within the Scottish Police College Coat of Arms; the Gaelic 'Bi Glic, Bi Glic' translates in English to 'Be Wise, Be Circumspect (prudent)'.

The interplay between using the knowledge of what are the good or right goals and outcomes and the practical wisdom which comes from maturity or experience in the role of a police officer, is exemplified by this quotation from an experienced operational police commander in Finland:

"Well, of course the education, their training is very, very good. They get [a] very good view on the legislation, on the tactical procedures, on the technical procedures, everything like that. But of course, you need to have experience, the training is not enough, it can't be enough, only in experience, experienced police officers, five-years, or something like that, then you are excellent." [Participant FP11 - Senior Police Officer, Finland]

One experienced police sergeant in Finland described this as being:

"...street-wise..." [Participant FP05 - Police Sergeant, Finland]

An experienced police trainer in Scotland described it as:

"Common sense" (Participant SCP02 - Police Trainer, Scotland)

Whilst interpretations of 'phronesis' differ slightly (for example, see Flyvbjerg, 2004; Kristjánsson *et al.*, 2021), they tend to include the values-based, deliberate consideration of alternatives which "goes beyond analytical, scientific knowledge (*episteme*)" (Flyvbjerg, 2004, p.284), and involves the 'art' of judgement. For example, Kristjánsson (2021, p.239) argued that "*phronesis* explains how mature decision-making is motivated and shaped by substantive moral aspirations and... bridges the gap between moral knowledge and action". Bynner and Terje (2021, p.76) argued that 'phronesis' "employs a value-based rationality, and is used to make value

judgements, and weigh up alternatives”. Whilst still a virtue of the mind, along with theoretical wisdom, Aristotle’s concept ‘phronesis’ is associated with character through the development of ‘good habits’. “By ‘good habits’ Aristotle means a settled disposition to feel and act appropriately” which help to identify the right goal (Grayling, 2019, p.93). Whilst Aristotle was not the first to discuss the concept of ethical or virtuous behaviour (see Plato and Socrates), one aspect of his interpretation which is relevant to the main thesis of this chapter, sets him apart. An emphasis on virtuous action or behaviour which includes courage, temperance, and justice, and the development, as we attain maturity, of ‘practical wisdom’ or ‘phronesis’ (Grayling, 2019, p.92). In attempting to explain what he meant, Aristotle suggested that it is the voluntary choice between alternatives of some particular action, informed by deliberation, selecting a means to an end which is good (Crisp 2014, p.204). In relation to contemporary policing, this might be understood as ethical decision making or doing the right thing in a way which critically engages with the complexities and nuances of local contexts and issues. Aristotle suggested that a person with ‘good’ attitudes and beliefs is likely to apply the right values, whilst the bad person is not. These values are “important because they influence work behaviour” (Sundström and Wolming, 2014, p.36).

Aristotle argued that the formation of a ‘good’, virtuous character takes place largely during childhood. Indeed, within a policing context, the recent RECPOL (2020) study of police recruits from six European countries (including Sweden and Scotland) appears to reflect the notion that practical wisdom is associated with ‘good habits’ formed during character development. For example, the study suggested that “...the personal qualities required to handle personal interactions competently can only be developed to a limited degree through experience and training, so innate qualities are crucial elements” (Inzunza and Wikström, 2020, p.1245). Whilst outwith the scope of this project, it is perhaps worth briefly mentioning that in Sweden and Finland extensive psychological testing forms part of the initial selection processes, during which the attitudinal and behavioural traits, which police services in those countries believe are desirable of a police officer, are assessed. Scotland on the other hand does not.

5.6 Discussion

5.6.1 Notions of police professionalism

The findings discussed and analysed in this chapter, reflect the broader sociology of profession and police professionalism literature in which there are competing definitions of what police professionalism means. Whilst within each of the case study countries participants generally drew on a notion of police professionalism which encapsulated their occupational identities and work practices (Evetts, 2003, p.399), nuanced ideological differences emerged from the data as to what kinds of knowledge, skills, and behaviours were valued and emphasised (Aas, 2016).

Whilst in each of the case study countries notions of police professionalism were guided by theoretical knowledge, ‘craft’ knowledge, and practice or experiential knowledge (Eraut, 1994, p.38), the extent to which each were foregrounded as privileged forms of knowledge and sources of cultural capital were situated and nuanced. This may, in part, be understood as having been influenced by the “top-down” (Evetts, 2018, p.45; Gundhus, 2013), reconfiguration Noordegraaf (2016) of police professionalism by policy makers to drive change. In Finland, this had resulted in what Noordegraaf (2016, p.786) calls “dispersed and distributed” organisational professionalism, guided by a lean, distributed system of control and direction which tends more towards greater adhocracy for generalist, first-responder police officers. Police officers are “granted autonomy to treat cases independently” and “practically, they have discretionary spaces to make case-specific trade-offs” when making substantive decisions: their work is “regulated by occupational (rather than organizational) standards” (Noordegraaf, 2020, p.206).

This contrasted with the specialist “rational, efficient” (Sklansky, 2011, p.2) notion of police professionalism, guided by rules imposed and enforced by a hierarchical system of control and direction (Fyfe, 2014) found in Scotland (Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019). There, it is argued, “frontline staff are expected to comply with procedures rather than think” (Knutsson and Tompson, 2017, p.2), which could be regarded as

organisationally defensive (Argyris, 2004, p. 509) or averse to critical assessment (Lum, 2014, p.2). Whilst it may, in part, be intended to prevent embarrassment or threat, it is argued that it is contributing to the de-professionalisation of front-line, operational response officers.

The “shift towards a system-level bureaucracy” with increasing formalisation of work processes and horizontally fragmented work boundaries (Terpstra, Fyfe, and Salet, 2019, p.350), may have resulted in some unintended consequences. Such as limiting the role of junior, front-line operational response officers to ‘routine’, less complex tasks, limiting their professional autonomy, and limiting their “creative use of discretion in the handling of all kinds of practical situations and problems at street level” (Terpstra, Fife and Salet, 2019, p.353). Whilst this helps to understand why epistemic knowledge was generally regarded within Scottish policing as being unnecessary for police recruits, it raises questions concerning the extent to which the potential benefits which could arise from academisation in Sweden, are being realised at a micro level of analysis.

This contrasts with the less vertically and horizontally fragmented, generalist approach in Finland, where a front-line response officers’ role consists of a broader and more complex range of tasks than their counterparts in Scotland. This helps to understand why (as discussed in chapter 4), policy makers in Finland were of the belief that technical knowledge and experience alone are insufficient to guide the professionalism of front-line, response officers. They were generally of the view that the professional knowledge required of contemporary police officers entails a blend of theoretical knowledge, including epistemic knowledge, ‘craft’ knowledge, and experience (Tong and Bowling, 2006; Wood *et al.*, 2018, p.176). The perception in Scotland, however, was that this was more applicable to complex roles such as those undertaken by senior managers and specialist officers, such as detectives, whose scientific knowledge is “not confined to forensic science but also... psychology, social sciences, crime analysis and studies in policing” (Hallenberg, O’Neill and Tong, 2016, p.102).

Martin (2021) related Noordegraaf's (2015, 2016) concepts of professional hybridity directly to policing, arguing that policing's tendency to situate its attempts to re-professionalise between 'ideal types' of professionalism which favour individual autonomy on the one hand, and organisational professionalism on the other, which standardises and limits individual autonomy, fail to account fully for the broader reconfigurations which are shaping professional identities. This study's synthesis of these different elements of Noordegraaf's (2015, 2016) analytical framework provides new empirically based, cross-national understandings of profession and professionalisation within the context of policing, and how they relate to concepts of learning by new entrants.

5.6.2 Nature of policing knowledge

Whilst it is argued in this chapter that knowledge is a key component of police professionalism within a knowledge-based society (Evetts, 2003, p.396), the findings from this study have shown that there are multiple, situated, and nuanced forms of knowledge associated with notions of police professionalism.

With regards theoretical knowledge, analysis of the data highlighted a dichotomy concerning that knowledge which is regarded as vocationally relevant to what the police do, and that which is not. What is often referred to in the literature as the theory-practice gap, the "disconnects between knowledge generated through scientific research and the needs, expectations, and practices of knowledge users" (Cooke *et al.*, 2021, p.243). Knowing the 'what', the theory (Aristotelian episteme), and the technical or craft knowledge (Aristotelian techne), coupled with the knowing how or practical knowledge (Aristotelean phronesis). This dichotomy was particularly apparent with regards epistemic knowledge's relevance to different notions of police professionalism.

The widely held perception amongst participants in Scotland as to what is regarded as vocationally relevant knowledge, might be understood given the horizontally fragmented (Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019), "rational, efficient" (Sklansky, 2011, p.

2) notion of organisational professionalism guided by rules imposed and enforced by a hierarchical system of control and direction (Fyfe, 2014). The resultant re-positioning of junior, front-line, first response officers to the “marginalised... periphery of police work” (as Atkinson, 2017 argued as respects civilian intelligence analysts) has, in turn, influenced perceptions concerning the kinds of knowledge which are valued. Namely, that which emphasises the functional requirements of the job rather than that which is intellectually broadening.

In Sweden, the focus of knowledge development during the two and a half year initial police learning programme, foregrounds the aims of a liberal HE over vocational aims and outcomes, whilst in Finland the opposite was found to be the case. Whilst the approach in Sweden might be understood in the wider context of a professionalisation strategy, in which the aims of a liberal higher education are perceived as being ideologically helpful (for example, the liberalisation of occupational culture), it is argued, based on this study’s findings, that it inadequately relates to the functions, concerns and thinking of police officers with regards their work activities. In Finland, the vocational aims and liberal aims have been combined more effectively, with the former being foregrounded over those of the latter, to prepare policing students more effectively for the workplace.

Whilst chapters 6 and 7 will explore this study’s findings with regards the nature of initial police learning within the case study countries, and HE’s role within it, this chapter has focused on the nature of knowledge in relation to the different notions of professionalism found within the case study countries, and in particular concerning a key professional attribute, namely decision-making.

In this thesis however, it is argued that the various external and internal forces which are impacting on contemporary policing within the case study countries, resulting in increasingly complex and rapidly changing operating environments, require more than a combination of theoretical knowledge, including epistemic/academic theoretical knowledge, ‘craft’ knowledge, and experiential knowledge. Contemporary police professionalism should, it is argued, also be guided by ‘practical wisdom’ (phronesis):

taking deliberative, ethical decisions which draw on both epistemic knowledge and ‘craft’ knowledge, combined with experiential ‘on-the-job’ knowledge. This, it is argued, would provide a greater understanding of, and ability to respond effectively and ethically to, the evolving complexity of contemporary police work, and could be particularly relevant for generalist, senior, and/or specialist police officers operating with high levels of adhocacy when dealing with multi-problem issues. How this might be realised is explored more fully in chapter 8, the discussion chapter.

For police professionalism to continue to evolve in the 21st century and beyond, the binary discourse which pits tacit knowledge against explicit knowledge, theory against practice, academic against experiential, needs to be overcome. In Finland it largely had been. In Sweden the discourse had become less binary, more blurred. In Scotland the binary discourse was more prevalent regarding epistemic knowledge, which was seen as a threat to the ‘craft’-based notion of professionalism upon which initial police learning was focused. That said, whilst the discourse was less binary in Finland than in Sweden and Scotland this may, in part, be a reflection of the focus on “practically oriented” (Terpstra and Schaap, 2021, p.11) initial police learning programme there. The perception amongst police officers in Sweden that the curriculum was overly academic and theoretical reflects it is argued, academia’s requirements rather than those of Swedish policing. It is also argued that this cultural incongruence (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p.85) may adversely affect the realisation of intended policy outcomes within the wider police professionalisation strategy. It is suggested therefore, that the Swedish Police Authority, Swedish Government and Swedish academia consider re-focusing the initial learning programme to one which is more vocational, as is the case in Sweden with nursing and teaching. Whilst this change would, it is understood, require a legislative change, the findings from this study show that this would help reduce cultural resistance amongst policing students to professionalisation through HE.

This dichotomy between experience-based and epistemic/academic knowledge or ‘thin knowledge’, echoes the findings of other studies (for example, Gundhus, 2013). Whilst its extent varied within the case study countries, the tension between notions

of autonomy based occupational professionalism, which foregrounded experiential knowledge and discretion in decision-making, and organisational and political notions of professionalism, were still evident. It may be that this dichotomy will always remain given the unquantifiable aspects of professional practice, particularly the “conflict between the detached stance of the professional, and the continuing need for policing to adjust to the social flux within the community” (Rohl and Barnsley, 1995, p.238). As discussed in chapter 4 with regards policy formulation, it seems that much of the discourse in Scotland and Sweden is founded more on political ideology and professional opinion, rather than empirical research. This reflects the views of scholars such as (Scott, 1999, p.52) that “professionalism is... as an ideology, a set of beliefs and values which underpin it’s activities.”

5.6.3 Notions of police professionalism: skills and behaviours

As the findings from this study showed, police officers from each of the case study countries identified ‘sound’ decision making as a desirable skill. The ability to do the right thing in any given circumstance, to do what was best for the people involved and/or for the community, to make a positive difference, to have a ‘good’ outcome. Whilst decision-making will usually draw on theoretical and technical knowledge, it will also draw on practical or tacit knowledge. As well as involving actions which are linked to intuition founded on experience (Eraut, 1994, p.253), practical knowledge “also involves the personal motives, interests and values of the practitioner” (Scott, 1999, p.85). Practical knowledge was widely foregrounded as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital (Gundhus, 2013) by officers in Scotland, who referred to it as ‘common-sense’. Whilst it “fits well with the cognitive conservatism of the police culture”, it is “essentially conformity with the existing norms of the group” (Scott, 1999, pp.86-87), rather than intertwining theory and practice. Some officers in Scotland highlighted that using their common-sense to do the ‘right thing’ was sometimes more important than complying with policy or practice and even, in some instances, the law. However, given policing’s increasingly high public and political profile, especially in terms of accountability, ethical decision-making has become increasingly important. Doing the right thing within contemporary policing

requires ethically sound decision-making, particularly when officers are facing situations for which there is little or no previous experience. Professional decision-making, therefore, should also be guided by ‘practical wisdom’ (phronesis), particularly within the increasingly complex and rapidly changing operational environments, and within “dispersed and distributed” policing models which encapsulate a generalist approach (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.786).

5.6.4 Phronesis and the reconstruction police professionalism

The key argument being made in this chapter, advances that made by other scholars (for example, Tong and Bowling, 2006; Innes, 2010; Tong and Wood, 2011; Westera *et al.*, 2016; Hallenberg, O’Neill and Tong, 2016), namely that contemporary police professionalism entails a combination of science, craft, and experience. The argument being made here is that the reconfiguration of contemporary police professionalism (Noordegraaf, 2016), particularly within policing models which encapsulate a generalist approach, should also be guided by ‘practical wisdom’ (phronesis). Synthesising ‘episteme’, ‘techne’, experience, and ethically sound value judgements into the decision-making process, would help to overcome the binary discourse in which tacit knowledge is pitted against explicit knowledge, theory against practice, academic against experiential. Of the Aristotelean virtues of ‘episteme’, ‘techne’ and ‘phronesis’, ‘phronesis’ it is argued, is especially important in “dealing with risk, risk assessment and... uncertainty” (Evetts, 2003, p.397) within the increasingly dynamic, complex, multi-dimensional, and diverse milieu within which contemporary policing operates (Flyvbjerg, 2004, p.284-287; Christopher, 2015).

5.7 Conclusion

In conclusion, the main argument made in this chapter is that within the context of contemporary policing, where decisions often require to be made and action taken in complex, multi-problem scenarios for which rule-bound decision making is unlikely to produce a good outcome, practical wisdom (phronesis) could be helpful. Combined with theoretical (epistemic) knowledge, and ‘craft’ knowledge (techne), the

application of “ethically motivated deliberations, judgments, actions (Breier and Ralphs, 2009, p.485) could aid decision-making which does the right thing by clients and society (see also Evetts, 2006, p.134; Noordegraaf, 2020, p.207). This is particularly appropriate for “a reconfigured image of professionalism in which risks, dilemmas, and ambiguities [are] part of professional working lives” (Noordegraaf, 2020, p.219), especially within organisations which tend towards greater adhocracy for generalist police officers, those in senior promoted posts, and specialist officers. ‘Phronesis’, it is argued, could support the necessary reconfiguration of police professionalism within the broader societal, economic, and cultural shifts taking place within the operating environments, ensuring that effective connective, person-centred services are delivered, that norms and values are upheld, and that professional work is “trusted and legitimated” (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.784).

The extent to which the current approaches to initial police learning within the case study countries were perceived as helping the development of policing students and new recruits within the respective of notions of police professionalism, will be explored and analysed in chapter 6. This will be done by focusing on *what* was being developed, *how* it was being developed, and the spaces *where* it was being developed.

Chapter 6: Initial police learning and developing professionalism

Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to describe, analyse and explain the findings from this study with respect to the research question: *to what extent are the current approaches to initial police learning perceived by 'policy network actors' within the case study countries as helping in the development of desirable professional attributes?*

Section 6.1 reveals that initial classroom-based learning spaces were generally perceived as being helpful in reinforcing the prevailing organisational notions of police professionalism within each country. It shows that in Scotland the 'traditional', regimented, police training school approach emphasised worker compliance with hierarchical cultural norms, and developing only that explicit knowledge required for the comparatively narrow, 'routine' role of a front-line response constable. It goes on to show that Sweden and Finland had moved to university-based environments which were more conducive to developing critical thinking and reflective adult learners. However, as this section goes on to show, these HE learning environments were not always helpful in reforming the negative aspects of police culture. For example, policing students in Sweden isolating themselves from other university students, and some male policing students in Finland, and their police officer instructors, expressing sexist attitudes about female police officers.

Section 6.2 reveals that the eleven-week initial classroom-based phase (ITC) in Scotland, was generally considered sufficient to develop, through training, the theoretical knowledge and technical skills required for the 'routine' role of a front-line response constable. The foregrounding of tacit knowledge developed through 'real world' practice experience was reflected by the inclusion of a twenty-one-month 'on-the-job' practice phase, the longest of the case study countries. This contrasted with the approaches in Sweden and Finland which focused, through longer programmes (two-and-a-half years in Sweden, three-years in Finland), on both training *and* education. They comprised significantly longer, university-based, initial 'classroom-

based' learning phases (two-years in Sweden, eighteen-months in Finland), and shorter 'real world' practice phases (six months in Sweden, eleven months in Finland). This section also reveals that the initial 'classroom-based' phase in Finland was perceived by both academics and police officers as providing sufficient time and space not only to develop the requisite level of theoretical knowledge and technical skills for their generalist role, but also through learning and reflection, to develop and reinforce desirable cultural norms and critical thinking. However, it also reveals that in Sweden, the combination of a two-year classroom-based phase, and a six-month practice phase was perceived by police officers as being unhelpful in bridging the theory-practice divide.

Section 6.3 moves on from the processes of learning to an analysis of participant perceptions regarding the extent to which the product, or outcome, of initial police learning aligned with, and supported, situated notions of police professionalisation. This analysis reveals that in Scotland, at both a meso and micro-level of analysis, the approach to initial police learning was broadly perceived as being helpful. However, it is argued that it is at odds with the macro-level driver of achieving a knowledge-based economy which includes other public services becoming graduate-entry only. In Sweden, by way of contrast, there were misalignments within and between each conceptual level of analysis, which reflected the 'messy' policy formulation and operationalisation processes explored in chapter 4. This section concludes by arguing that in Finland, there was alignment at a macro, meso, and micro level of analysis, between the perceived outcomes of the initial police learning programme and the situated notion of professionalism, which was guided by concepts of a generalist workforce operating within a lean, distributed culture of control.

This chapter concludes with section 6.4 by drawing together the key themes explored in this chapter and once again, as has been the case throughout previous findings chapters, that variables of context (Kingdon, 1995; Christensen, Laegreid and Rykkja, 2018), particularly situated notions of professionalism and cultural norms, have been important in explaining and understanding the findings explored in this chapter.

6.1 Context: settings for initial learning

This section explores the different settings within which initial ‘classroom-based’ phases of the initial police learning programmes took place: the Scottish Police College, Swedish mainstream universities, and the Finnish Police University College.

6.1.1 The initial ‘classroom-based’ phase

This study found that the initial learning environments were perceived by participants as being helpful in some respects, and unhelpful in others, in the development of police recruits and policing students. For example, in Sweden academics involved in the development and delivery of the initial two-year ‘classroom-based’ phase, were of the view that the learning environments of mainstream universities were more conducive to developing situated notions of professionalism than the more traditional Swedish Police Academy, where initial police learning had previously been delivered. As this senior learning and development manager from the Swedish Police Authority explained:

“I think the idea behind, because it was a political initiative once again, and there were some other things as well, but first of all, there was some prejudice about the police academy, that it had partial bad culture, and it was a resting place for people who couldn’t get along with other people or doing the job. Lots of prejudice.” [Participant SWP08 - Senior Police Staff, Sweden]

As this quotation suggests, the decision by the then ruling Social Democratic Party to devolve initial police learning from the Swedish Police Academy to mainstream universities was based, in part, on a perception that the Academy fostered more “corrosive elements of the police occupational culture” (Hough *et al.*, 2018, p.7). Moving the initial ‘classroom-based’ phase of initial police learning to mainstream universities appears therefore, to have been intended in part, to shield policing students from the corrosive elements of police culture (Evetts, 2014, p.41) and thereby help to effect positive cultural change.

Building on this theme of cultural change, the data also showed a perception amongst academics, police educators, and senior police officers in Sweden, that in mixing with academic staff and students from other disciplines and faculties within mainstream universities, policing students would be exposed to different world views. As these quotations firstly from a senior academic involved in developing and delivering the initial police learning programmes, and secondly from the senior member of police staff quoted above from the Swedish Police Authority illustrate, the view was that this would broaden policing student's minds, and thereby lead to greater tolerance:

“It's given us a great opportunity to use all those specialist competences that are here on the campus, that's one perspective. But another perspective is for the students to work in an open environment, together with other students, because if we put them in the forest with no contact with other students or people in society, they will become too closed-minded and I think that won't be good when they are going out to integrate and to solve crimes in society, to prevent crimes. [Participant SWP14 - Senior Academic, Sweden]

“They didn't want the students to be isolated, because if you think about culture, if you never interact with other people, you are just in the isolated area at police academy. Bad culture could grow. You don't get other perspectives. It's very homogenic, it's not good.” [Participant SWP08 - Senior Police Staff, Sweden]

However, it was also found that this intended policy outcome was not being fully realised. The data showed that policing students were largely isolating themselves from students within other faculties, as the same senior police staff member from the Swedish Police Authority explained:

“It was a good idea in theory, in my opinion, because what's happened is that they built five new police academies at universities. The students are in the mini police academies, they don't integrate with other students. Perhaps they go to parties, I don't know, but it's still very isolated and they keep in their buildings.” [Participant SWP08 - Senior Police Staff, Sweden]

Whilst this finding might in part be explained by the physical segregation of policing students from other campus faculties (the two universities from which the data was gathered had physically separate, secure-entry buildings on the periphery of the campuses), it might also be understood considering the studies concerning police

culture in which social isolation has been found to be a lasting cultural norm. For example, Cox and Kirby's (2018) study of 383 students undertaking criminal justice related undergraduate degrees in UK universities, found that those studying for the then Policing Foundation degree, identified themselves as being different and behaving differently to other university students. They "quickly assimilated a police identity, which affected their attitudes and behaviour. The process led to a strengthening of ties within their own student group, at the expense of wider student socialization" (Cox and Kirby, 2018, p.550).

Such apparent insularity and solidarity, this 'us and them' outlook, might also be understood from the work of scholars such as Waddington (1999), who suggested that the very nature of a police officer's role, results in a degree of social isolation, generated in part, by danger and authority (Skolnick, 1966). However, solidarity can, others have suggested, give officers reassurance that their colleagues will back them up and assist them when faced with external threats (Chan, 1996, p.111), especially when facing danger. However, as other scholars have argued, such solidarity may have a dark side, protecting colleagues who conduct themselves inappropriately, and getting 'jammed up' in misconduct (Kane and White, 2009, 2013). It might be argued therefore, that adopting a worldview in which police culture is one of "predominantly negative behavioural tendencies..." (Loftus, 2009, p.15) from which students need to be protected, may result in approaches to initial police learning which hinder rather than help initial professional development. For example, as will be explored in more depth in the following section, this study found that not engaging with 'real-world' policing during the first two-years of the Swedish programme, was perceived by policing students, tutor constables, and senior police officers as being unhelpful in narrowing the practice-theory gap.

The assumption that mainstream universities comprise entirely monolithic and positive learning environments for future police officers is also open to question. This study found a darker side of cultural norms within one of the Swedish universities and within the Finnish Police University College. For example, a member of the teaching staff from one of the Swedish universities delivering the initial learning programme,

claimed that students from other faculties had initiated a sweepstake (a bet) which could be claimed by whoever enticed or provoked a policing student into committing an unethical or illegal act which would result in them being expelled. The findings developed from the Finnish data revealed sexist attitudes and behaviours amongst some policing students and police officer instructors within the Finnish Police University College. For example, this quotation from a policing student at the Finnish Police University College, illustrates the concerns of some male students and instructing staff about the physical strength of women officers, even though all officers carry firearms and other officer safety equipment:

“Well, it will be hard, it’s maybe impossible for that small woman to handle a huge guy. But lucky we are patrolling two of us always, but if something happens to the other one, the small woman has to do.”
[Participant FP05 - Policing Student, Finland]

Similar attitudes were also found amongst police officers in Sweden, as this senior police officer who was an instructor on the initial police learning programme within one of the universities in Sweden demonstrated:

“I definitely want us to have women on the force but... they’ve taken away some of the physical demands that we had before... and in general women are smaller than men. I think it can be a problem. If you don’t even weigh fifty kilos and statistics say that we have mainly male perpetrators. And a normal man weighs more than fifty kilos. Just that or just helping, dragging your own colleague. Do you have the physical ability to do that? For me it is basically about what are you? Are you going to be a problem or of some help to me when shit hits the fan?”
[Participant SWP03 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

These findings regarding conceptions of gender and competency should be considered against findings from the larger, longitudinal, RECPOL study which found that most police recruits in Denmark, Norway and Sweden disagreed that “men are more competent” at handling violence than women, with recruits in Sweden “more often dismiss[ing] the idea that men and women are suited for different police tasks” than their peers in Denmark and Norway (Bloksgaard, Fekjær and Moberg, 2020, p.43). Finland was not part of the RECPOL study, and to date no other research has come to light which explores conceptions of gender and competency within Finnish policing. These findings therefore add to the literature in this regard.

Sexism is a “problematic” (Christopher, 2015, p.395) characteristic of police culture which is frequently highlighted within the literature (see also Heslop, 2011, Brown *et al.*, 2019). Whether these sexist ‘war stories’ were a product of police culture or individual agency is impossible to determine from the data. That said, as Chan (1997, p.66) suggested, the “acculturation process” is not one-way. As Loftus (2009, p.16) argued, police recruits or students have “agency” and “whether, if at all, new recruits accept the cultural norms will depend on many factors including their own individual biography and personality”. Whilst policing has attempted to argue, with some justification, that, intolerance in all of its forms is a “pressing issue for the whole of society, not any one organisation” (HMICS, 2020, p.4), it is argued that policing must do all it reasonably can to minimise intolerance within policing. Whilst “many problems would dissolve, proponents argue, if every constable had a degree” (Punch, 2007, p. 106), the available research evidence for this is, according to some scholars, questionable (see Brown, 2020). Policing should therefore, it is argued, also focus efforts on selecting police recruits and students who are accepting of difference. Police instructors should be selected with the same care, as recruits are very receptive to informal learning derived from trainers, which is “often in direct contrast to the style of policing being taught in the curriculum” (Belur *et al.*, 2020, p.81).

Moving on to the analysis of the data from Scotland, the eleven-week ITC was found to be focused primarily on training as opposed to education, and on acculturating recruits into the prevailing organisational notions of professionalism which, as mentioned previously, were guided by a tendency towards hierarchy within which front-line response constables were expected to be compliant, and to deal with routine tasks. For example, police officers in Scotland frequently highlighted the importance of instilling and reinforcing the sense of hierarchy required in a disciplined organisation. Recruits undertaking the eleven-week Initial Training Course at the Scottish Police College described having to show deference to senior ranks, obeying instructions without question. Recruits were instructed to stand up whenever anyone other than a fellow student entered the classroom, to call anyone other than fellow recruits ‘sir’ or ‘madam’, to undertake military-style drill or marching, maintain short haircuts (for the men) or have all hair tied up above the shirt collar (for women). Whilst

this socialisation process was clearly intended to reinforce organisational cultural norms of hierarchy and unquestioning obedience, some of the recruits were critical of this ‘quasi-militaristic’ (Lagestad, 2014, p.207) approach, questioning its relevance to the realities of policing, as this quotation from an eighteen-month service recruit demonstrates:

“... they teach you at the College to call everyone ‘sir’ and ‘madam’, but in the real world it doesn’t work. People would probably not want to speak to you if you were needing information or needing a statement, you have to speak their language... So, I think there’s a College answer but, in the street [it is different]” [Focus SCPFG01 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

This requirement to comply with the cultural norm within the Scottish Police College with regards deference to hierarchy, was felt by some participants on the other hand to be helpful in developing desirable professional attributes, as this recruit explained:

“I think that the discipline at the College is extremely important because as [other focus group member] said, you get the kids these days who have no clue what they’re doing in life because it’s changed so much, and you bring them into an organisation which needs to be disciplined. If your sergeant tells you to do something you don’t have to wait and say, ‘oh why am I doing this?’” When you are in a life and death situation you have to go and do it. And many people are used today to questioning everything in day-to-day life which is good... normally. However, in this line of job you need to do the work you are told.” [Focus Group SCPFG02 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

Whilst the paternalistic, infantilising language used in this quote (“the kids these days”) might be understood in light of this participant’s “own individual biography and personality” (Loftus, 2009, p.16), the quasi-militaristic, hierarchical culture at the Scottish Police College might be explained by briefly considering the history of the national probationer training programme. It was first established in the late 1950s with most of the heads of the College being retired senior military men who were referred to as Commandants. It was not until the 1980s that senior police officers began to undertake this role. This coupled with being a ‘closed’ learning environment in which the instructing staff have remained primarily experienced police officers, may, in part, help to understand why this approach to the socialisation of police recruits has remained the cultural norm within the Scottish Police College since its inception.

However, aside from the relevance of this regimented, ‘semi-militaristic’ approach to the acculturation of police recruits in Scotland, some participants expressed the view that it detracted from the learning experience, as this senior police staff member at the Scottish Police College explained:

“... the traditional militaristic highly disciplined style... there’s still an element of that, you know, and you see it on a day-to-day basis... I get sometimes it can serve a purpose in terms of the organisation, it’s a can-do organisation that can be called upon to do anything at any given time and you need to have that kind of discipline, so I get that, but sometimes I see barking [shouting] at people in the corridor, and sometimes for what appears to be no apparent reason other than to give instructors... a bit of an ego boost... is that creating a learning experience, a learning environment? I would probably say not” [Participant SCP06 - Senior Police Staff, Scotland]

This police recruit in Scotland with sixteen-months service appeared to echo the views of the educator in this regard:

“I think the whole discipline at the College... there’s too much emphasis on that... it takes your concentration away from what you’re actually there to do.” [Focus Group SCPFG01 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

Analysis of the data gathered from participants at POLAMK showed that whilst a similar ‘semi-militaristic’ approach had previously existed, there had recently been a deliberate move away from that towards a culture more akin to a mainstream university, as this senior police officer explained:

“...my personal policy in this process was that I wanted to, to strip police education of all relics of military education. So, all forms of... all remaining forms of external discipline were thrown away as an example, and instead we emphasised the personal responsibility of the student...” [Participant FP02 - Senior Police Officer, Finland]

Generally, policing students and staff perceived this atmosphere to be more conducive to learning, as this ‘civilian’ educator explained:

“So, the relaxed atmosphere is always good for your brain, so you don’t have to be scared of anything, you learn more, you are more eager to use your abilities.” [Participant FP 16 - Policing Educator, Finland]

However, as this same participant explained, there were some who disagreed with this approach, particularly those who had undertaken lengthy military service prior to becoming a policing student:

“... some students, for instance, who have been working in the army as military police officers, they are a bit disappointed that this is so relaxed, they were maybe wanting more [of] that.” [Participant FP 16 - Policing Educator, Finland]

This ex-military student explained why he was uncomfortable with the lack of stricter discipline:

“I kind of wish they would have strict and disciplined place like I think this used to have. I find it annoying that some people are sleeping at the flat when others are sitting in a classroom and then we get some group project and you kind of just drag them along because they haven’t been studying.” [Participant FP17 - Policing Student, Finland]

Despite the move away from a ‘semi-militaristic’ approach, there was also a widely held recognition amongst the students and staff, that whilst the notion of professionalism in Finland was guided by a generalist approach which tended towards greater adhocacy for junior front-line response officers, policing in Finland remained a hierarchical, disciplined organisation:

“... when you are very young and very eager you are not used to take commands, so it could be a problem for you if you don’t realise that you have to respect the authorities and the hierarchy, it’s very important.” [Participant FP 16 - Policing Educator, Finland]

The Finnish Police University College might therefore be understood as a hybrid of a traditional police training institution and a mainstream university, having “retained more traditional elements” (Terpstra and Schaap, 2021, p.7). For example, whilst it had retained many of the ‘artefacts’ (Schein, 2017) of a traditional police training college such as badges, symbols, and uniforms, it had abandoned marching drills, standing up when instructors entered the classroom, and overly focusing on high standards of uniform preparation (see Rogers and Gravelle, 2020, p.358 for contrast with delivery of the Police Foundation degree in England and Wales). These revised cultural norms within the Finnish Police University College were widely seen amongst

participants in Finland, both from policing and academia, as being more conducive not only to learning, but also to developing police officers capable of thinking and acting in the field with minimal supervision and direction, as this police sergeant with responsibility for overseeing the tutoring of policing students in the field explained:

“It’s good thing because it’s part of modern times. Because on the field we don’t lead people [sic] way. People want to use their own head and skills...” [Participant FP13 - Police Sergeant, Finland]

It also enabled the development of a learning environment which was more reflective of a university of applied science than a traditional training college, providing space and time for self-directed study, and reflection which facilitated deeper learning, which extended beyond the classroom and into the workplace (see Hough and Stanko, 2019). That said, some of the male, ex-military students were less comfortable with the learning environment.

“A bit more like military. Not military, but you had to be in the class, and everything was strict. It should be like that today, I think.” [Participant FP17 - Policing Student, Finland]

This move towards a pedagogical approach that encouraged students to undertake self-directed learning, to critically analyse information, and to be reflective learners, was more indicative of a mainstream university, and coincided with what had previously been the Finnish Police College becoming a University of Applied Science in 2014. Interestingly, when discussing the Swedish university-based approach to initial learning, policing students in Finland commented that they would not feel as comfortable in such an ‘open’ environment, preferring instead the ‘semi-closed’ environment of POLAMK. In justifying their views, they said:

“About mixing with normal... I can’t say normal students... but like from other fields, we learn about things that are sort of... the secrecy levels and some of the material that we get is also secret... and I’m not sure if it would work.” [Focus Group FFG1- Policing Student, Finland]

It is argued, based on these findings, that POLAMK and the Swedish mainstream universities were generally more conducive to theoretical learning and skills developments than the Scottish Police College. Being longer in duration, and less

militaristic, policing students in Sweden and Finland had more time and mental space for theoretical learning and skills development than the eleven-week Initial Training Course at the Scottish Police College. The latter was perceived by students and some ‘civilian’ staff there to be less conducive to learning in that it was too short, with insufficient space within the curriculum for deeper learning and understanding, and overly militaristic, requiring recruits to comply unquestioningly and deferentially to hierarchical control. However, at the other end of the spectrum, having only six months ‘real-world’ practice experience, which did not take place until after the initial two-year university-based phase of the Swedish programme, was perceived by police officers at all levels to be unhelpful. Policing students began the six-month practice phase lacking the confidence to apply their theoretical knowledge and skills in the ‘real world’ of operational policing.

Some senior police officers and staff at POLAMK, suggested that the initial eighteen-month long initial learning phase was helpful in that it provided more time to inculcate desirable professional attitudes and behaviours before students encountered less desirable attitudes and behaviours on ‘the street’. However, sexist attitudes amongst some staff and students at the Police University College were revealed during individual interviews. Interestingly, no sexist attitudes were found amongst police officers in Scotland. It is therefore argued that whilst the lengthy ‘classroom-based’ initial learning phases in Sweden and Finland were in part, intended to re-enforce desirable attitudes and behaviours amongst policing students which were more likely “to survive the more corrosive elements of the police occupational culture” (Hough *et al.*, 2018, p.7), there was evidence that this was not being fully realised. For example, in Sweden students still tended to isolate themselves from non-policing students, and in Finland, sexist attitudes were found amongst some police officers on the staff and amongst students. Whilst scholars argue that police occupational culture is largely “forged on the street, encountering members of the public and dealing with the public and dealing with incidents” (Waddington, 1999, p. 302), these findings show that it was also being formed or reinforced in part, during the initial ‘classroom’ based phases of these initial learning programmes.

On the other hand, it is argued based on this study's findings, that the 'open' Swedish model whilst helping to realise many of the longer-term benefits to be derived from the academisation of initial police learning (which will be fully explored in chapter 7), it is less helpful in realising the shorter-term needs of policing, namely preparing policing students for the six-month 'real-world', 'on-the-job' learning phase. It is also argued that the initial police learning model adopted in Sweden is more suited to a notion of police professionalism which is guided by a generalist policing style supported by a more lean, distributed approach to leadership and management, which tends more towards adhocracy, as in Finland, rather than the hierarchical, horizontally fragmented policing model which exists in Sweden and Scotland.

6.2 The Approach to initial police learning.

This section provides a comparative analysis of the extent to which aspects of the mechanism or the 'how' of initial learning, were perceived as being helpful or otherwise in the professional development of police recruits and policing students within the case study countries. In doing so it explores two notable themes developed from a comparative analysis of the data. Firstly, the sequencing and duration of the initial 'classroom-based' learning phase and the 'real world' practice phase. Secondly the extent to which two elements of the 'technocratic' model of professional development (Bines and Watson, 1992), namely the acquisition of knowledge and supervised 'on-the-job' practice, were perceived as helping the development of desirable professional attributes.

6.2.1 Sequencing and duration of the learning phases

Whilst the data from this study showed that each country's initial police learning models were broadly reflective of the 'technological' model with regards sequencing of the phases, they differed markedly in relation to the duration of each phase. For example, in Scotland the initial 'classroom-based' phase was an eleven-week long ITC which took place at the Scottish Police College, with the 'on-the-job' phase being twenty-one-months long. In Sweden the initial 'classroom-based' phase was a two-

year long, university-based programme followed by a six-month ‘on-the-job’ learning phase. In Finland, the initial ‘classroom-based’ phase was an eighteen-month initial learning programme which took place at POLAMK, followed by an eleven-months ‘on-the-job’ learning phase. Unlike Scotland, the Swedish and Finnish models comprised a final ‘classroom-based’ learning phase, although since data gathering in 2019, this phase has been dropped from the Swedish model. On completion of their eleven-month ‘on-the-job’ learning phase, policing students in Finland returned for a final twenty weeks back at POLAMK where they completed their Bachelor’s Degree dissertations.

Beginning with the data gathered from Sweden, analysis revealed mixed views between academics on the one hand, and policing students and police officers on the other, about the balance between the two-year, university-based phase and the six-month ‘on-the-job’ phase. For policing students and police officers, having one week per term during the two-year long initial learning phase sitting in the back of a police vehicle observing experienced officers undertaking their role, did not provide adequate integration between knowledge acquisition and on-the-job application, as highlighted in the previous section. Indeed, as this senior manager within the Swedish Police Authority who had oversight of the initial police learning programme explained, policing students did not experience any ‘real world’ policing during the ‘classroom-based’ phase:

“... it takes two years for many people to even see a police station.”
[Participant SWP 08 - Senior Police Staff, Sweden]

Generally, policing students were of the view that this element of the programme should be reduced to one year. As exemplified by these comments from a tutor constable in Sweden, it was also suggested that there should be a more equitable balance between the ‘classroom-based’ phase and the ‘on-the-job’ phase, and that they should be more interwoven:

“I think maybe two aspirant six-month periods, which are separated. Maybe have an aspirant session for six-months after two or three semesters, then going back to school, and then have a few more

semesters and then a finishing aspirant session for six months” [Participant SWP09 - Tutor Constable, Sweden].

The rationale, they explained, was:

“Because there is a lot of things that you can learn from the outside world, the real world...” [Participant SWP09 - Tutor Constable, Sweden]

The phraseology used here, “outside world” and “real world” is interesting, seeming to differentiate between the ‘real world’ of operational policing on ‘the street’, and what they suggest is the ‘unreal, inside’ world of a mainstream university. That said, similar observations were also made by police officers in Scotland and Finland, reflecting it will be argued elsewhere in this thesis, the enduring cultural capital attached to on-the-job, experiential learning.

The data also suggested that ‘aspirants’ in Sweden undertaking their six-months field training in an urban area, lacked the ability to apply the theoretical and technical knowledge they had developed during the two-year initial ‘classroom-based’ phase in the ‘real world’, as this tutor constable explained:

“The students, they are very good at the theoretical side. They know a lot about the Swedish society, immigration, everything like that, the historical part of the police. But they have not a clue of how they should act, what they should do, how they should work with the public in a practical way.” [Participant SWP10 - Tutor Constable, Sweden]

However, in a more remote part of Sweden, where students attended a different university, this soon-to-graduate ‘aspirant’ was of the view that the ‘classroom-based’ learning phase had prepared them well for the practice phase:

“I say that they are focusing on very good stuff to prepare you for the practical.” [Participant SW12 - Police ‘Aspirant’, Sweden]

It appears from this conflicting data that in the first example, the theoretical and practical parts of the programmes were not sufficiently integrated, whereas in the second example they were, which as Hough and Stanko (2019) suggested, is necessary for effective adult learning in policing. This was supported by the comments of this

senior academic involved in the development and delivery of initial police learning at the more remote Swedish university:

“I would say our lead word is integration, and it is integration between practice and theory and integration with different kinds of expert knowledge, academic knowledge, expert knowledge from the police field.” [Participant SWP14 - Senior Academic, Sweden]

The different experiences of the two policing students might also be explained by the differing approaches of universities in delivering the initial learning phase. This study found that the contracted universities were interpreting the curriculum requirements differently and developing a variety of approaches to delivery. This might be explained by two factors: the difficulties being experienced by the Swedish Police Authority in ensuring a degree of standardisation across the five universities; and the lack of a sufficiently detailed national curriculum by the Swedish Police Authority.

This study found that the Police Authority had neither the capacity nor the capability to provide a level of oversight and governance which supported standardisation in delivery, as this comment from a chief police officer demonstrates:

“It means that it’s pretty divided because they [the five universities delivering the initial police learning programme] are doing it in different ways, and that is problematic. We [the Swedish Police Authority] are not skilled enough to really follow it up.” [Participant SWP11 - Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

This data from a university-based policing educator, highlights the impact on universities of trying to interpret the Swedish Police Authority’s requirements from their high-level, broad-brush, national curriculum:

“When we started [delivering the initial police learning programme], everything was just so chaotic. So, we looked at old curricula from the police academy and from [names another university which had been delivery the programme for some time] and just mumbled something together. We do see a need for a stricter, more detailed curriculum [from the Swedish Police Authority].” [Participant SWP05 - Policing Educator, Sweden].

Given these findings, and the call for a more detailed national curriculum, it is recommended that the Swedish Police Authority, and indeed other police services when contracting out delivery of initial police learning to external providers, ensure that they have sufficiently detailed curricula and adequate quality assurance processes in place to ensure an appropriate degree of standardisation of delivery.

Turning now to the data gathered from Scotland, analysis revealed differing perceptions amongst participants regarding the duration of the eleven-week Initial Training Course. For example, some police recruits and senior operational commanders expressed the view that there was insufficient time to develop the theoretical and technical knowledge required in the field, as this senior operational police commander and this police recruit explained:

“I don’t think it’s fit for purpose because it doesn’t prepare officers. I don’t think it prepares officers for what they get out on the streets...”
[Participant SCP13 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

“...the eleven weeks that we have here, they are extremely crammed because they’re purely just battering through everything. They are trying their absolute best to get everything... to fit it in. Probably need double the time...” [Focus Group SCPFG01 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

Whilst it was argued by police officers at the Scottish Police College with responsibility for ITC, that the duration of the course had been largely determined by the curriculum which in turn had been based on a training needs analysis, there was a suggestion that it was also based on tradition, as this senior policing educator explained:

“Well, it still has its roots in traditionally how it used to be.” [Participant SCP06 - Senior Educator, Scotland]

Interestingly, there was a widely held perception amongst participants in Sweden and Finland, that the eleven-week Scottish Initial Training Course was only providing police recruits with the theoretical knowledge and technical skills required of private security officers in their countries, as this experienced senior police officer and police union official in Sweden exemplifies:

“... eleven weeks, that’s basically... we have private security here... they can take drunk people off the tracks or the subway...there is a lot of hands-on work that we need to learn, especially when and how to question people in the right way... it’s an art you need to be able to do. If you do the first responder’s job really good, it will help the whole crime be solved in a better way.” [Participant SWP06 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

This last quotation from a senior police officer in Sweden, reinforces the argument made in chapter 5 of this thesis, that when dealing with more complex, multi-problem scenarios, a combination of epistemic knowledge, ‘craft’ knowledge, and practical wisdom is beneficial for decision making, and can result in dealing with things in what the officer above described as “a better way”. However, it is also argued that this combination of the ‘art’, ‘craft’, and ‘science’ of policing could also be helpful to those operating with greater adhocracy within senior and specialist roles within rational-efficient organisational cultures such as those within Police Scotland.

The findings developed from the data gathered from Finland on the other hand, revealed a widely held perception that the eighteen-month initial ‘classroom-based’ learning period provided was sufficiently long enough to develop the requisite level of theoretical knowledge and technical skills for not only the practice phase, but also well beyond graduation and employment as senior constables. Not only did policing students acquire a comprehensive knowledge and understanding of the law, but they also achieved competency in the use of their sidearm, driving police vehicles, the use of ICT systems, and even in how to recover forensic evidence from all but the most complex scenes of crime. It also provided enough space and time through learning and reflection to develop and reinforce desirable cultural norms and critical thinking.

Having considered the sequencing and duration of the three phases comprising the technological model, the following sub-section will unpack participant perceptions relating to knowledge acquisition and its application through specific cognitive processes.

6.2.2 Knowledge acquisition during the initial, 'classroom-based' learning phase

Theoretical and 'craft' knowledge which was perceived as being of direct use in police work was, unsurprisingly, foregrounded by police recruits and policing students from each of the case study countries as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital. For example, this study found that "knowledge of the law, rights and procedures" were perceived "to be closely related to their ability to make correct practical decisions" (Inzunza and Wikström, 2020, p. 1246), as this operational Police Sergeant who had responsibility for tutor constables demonstrated in the following remark:

"... if they know the laws and things, if somebody asks, they know the laws, why they are doing something like that, because basically they have to know from day one when they start working... they should be able to answer questions why they do something, why they are not doing anything, or something like that." [Participant FP14 - Police Sergeant, Finland]

However, analysis of the data also revealed different perceptions between police officers in Scotland, and between police officers in Sweden and Finland, about the depth and breadth of legal knowledge required. For example, the prevailing view in Scotland was that as the role of a front-line response constable was largely providing an initial response to an incident or complaint. Therefore, it was argued, police recruits did not require the breadth and depth of legal knowledge which was then (2019) being taught on the eleven-week ITC, as this senior police officer explained:

"... we done a lot of research in terms of what police officers actually deal with... it's been really useful because it's informing what we do in terms of what the future content's gonna be like. It's still heavily... it's almost overweight in terms of legislation, specific legislation that a cop on the street won't deal with... If you go into a classroom now, they'll show you a book with all the sexual offences and they'll not have to deal with these. They're first responders these days..." [Participant SCP03 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

Some participants, such as this senior educator within the Scottish Police College, were of the view that ITC's curriculum was already largely devoted to the

development of technical skills and professional behaviours rather than theoretical knowledge:

“I would maybe say there is now greater emphasis on behaviours and skills as opposed to knowledge...” [Participant SCP06 - Senior Policing Educator, Scotland]

A police sergeant concerned with revising the ITC curriculum following the review of a front-line first response constable’s role, explained that the new curriculum would focus on:

“... initial contact [with the public], for example initial evidence gathering and then passing it on to specialists.” [Participant SCP09 - Police Sergeant, Scotland]

This refocusing of the intended outcomes from the ITC can therefore be understood, in part, by the re-configured notion of organisational professionalism within Police Scotland which encapsulates a more vertically and horizontally fragmented Scottish policing model (Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019). This re-configured notion of professionalism was, as argued in chapter 4, leading to a de-skilling and de-professionalisation of front-line response constables. It might also be understood by a risk-averse organisational culture, also discussed in chapter 4, which does not tend towards adhocery. As this experienced police officer explained, senior leaders do not trust junior officers and do not want to give them responsibility to deal with more complex tasks in their entirety:

“It’s a risk averse culture, they [senior leaders] don’t trust cops. They don’t want to give them responsibility to deal with more complex tasks from cradle to grave. It’s become increasingly centralised and hierarchical. There is very little decision-making responsibility given to front-line cops.” [Participant SCP09 - Police Sergeant, Scotland]

In Sweden and Finland on the other hand, there was a widely held belief amongst participants that policing students required a comprehensive knowledge and understanding of the law, as this chief police officer in Finland explained:

“The approach to policing... requires sophisticated legal thinking competence” [Participant FP18 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

This finding might be understood in light of the widely held perception amongst police officers and policing students in Finland, that decision-making and subsequent action by police officers must be strictly in accordance with the law, as these quotations firstly from a senior police officer, and secondly from a police sergeant, both of whom were on the staff of the Finnish Police University College demonstrate:

“I would say that working as a professional is meaning that of course you are doing everything by the law and the rules, and so on.”
[Participant FP07 - Senior Police Officer, Finland]

“Everything we do is based on law, that’s really important.” [Participant FP04 - Police Sergeant, Finland]

However, this somewhat rigid perspective was contradicted, to a degree, by this observation from a ‘civilian’ educator at the Finnish Police University College:

“Everything he does, so he knows what is the basis, what is the law, why is he doing this or that, but also that you take in consideration the circumstances, so you understand that this is a person you are talking to, so it’s maybe not always strictly by the book, but you have to take under consideration what is happening here, and this is a tragedy for him or her. So, you have here something internal so that you understand what is going on.” [Participant FP16 - Policing Educator, Finland]

As this participant infers, decision-making can be nuanced and complex requiring officers to draw on and blend together, to different degrees depending on the unique situation they are facing, ‘episteme’, ‘techne’ and ‘phronesis’. The relationship between these different elements is not binary, it takes these different types of knowledge and blends them together with learning, through reflection, to provide a unique recipe for success when operating within the “swampy lowland, messy, confusing” (Schön, 1987, p.3) environment of operational policing.

Whilst it has been argued that ‘phronesis’ is a useful concept, ‘doing the right thing’ or ‘bending the rules’ rather than ‘doing it the right way’, may risk officers straying into ‘noble cause corruption’ (Cooper, 2012; Honey, 2014), whereby police officers believe that despite knowingly breaking the law or bending procedural rules, their actions bring about a ‘good’ outcome. For example, this study found that some police recruits and indeed senior officers in Scotland, were more accepting of non-legalistic

action than their counterparts in Finland. As this sixteen-month service recruit stated, they preferred to base their decisions and actions in the field on what they euphemistically referred to as ‘the Ways and Means Act’:

“I prefer ways and means everyday [laughter from the other recruits].”
[Focus Group SCPFG01 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

From the researcher’s own experience as a police officer in Scotland, the phrase “ways and means” does not mean using discretion: ‘doing the right thing’ over ‘doing it the right way’ to achieve an ethically sound outcome. Rather, it is a euphemism for what Skolnick, (1966) called ‘extra-legal variables’, whereby “legal rules and departmental regulations are marginal to an account of how policework operates” (Wilson, 1968 cited in Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki, 2019, p.170). The recruit’s claimed preference for this approach might be indicative of the ‘underlying assumptions’ (Schein, 2017) within a culture which foregrounds “quick and tangible results” (Fekjaer and Petersson, 2019, p.940). It might also be that this police recruits’ legal and epistemic knowledge was inadequate. If they do not have a sufficient knowledge of the law, nor of the policing environment within which they were operating, they may be inclined to rely on experiential knowledge of what has worked for them before. However, as has been discussed previously, decision-making founded primarily on experiential knowledge, which is not supported by sufficient theoretical knowledge, be that legal, procedural, or epistemic, is associated with an artisan occupation rather than a profession.

These findings concerning the extent to which policing students in Scotland on the one hand, and policing students in Finland on the other, were accepting of non-legalistic action, might be understood in light of similar findings which emerged from the recently published RECPOL longitudinal comparative study of initial police learning in seven European countries which included Scotland and Sweden, but not Finland (Bjorgo and Damen, 2020). It found, as did this study with regards policing students in Finland, that policing students in Sweden displayed less acceptance of non-legalistic measures than recruits in Scotland, although the differences were slight, and the Scottish data was partial. However, it is argued that the findings from this study show that the difference in this regard between police recruits and students in Scotland

and policing students in Finland was marked. As the police sergeant from Finland (participant FP04) quoted earlier stated, “[e]verything we do is based on law, that’s really important.” This was a view which was consistently expressed by policing students and by police officers at all levels in Finland who took part in this study. Compliance with the law on all occasions was regarded as paramount and a cornerstone of policing in Finland.

However, such strict adherence to ‘legal variables’ (Skolnick, 1966) does raise some interesting questions concerning the ability of police officers in Finland to utilise ‘practical wisdom’ with a view to ‘doing the right thing’ in the varied situations facing them, particularly those which are complex, multi-problem issues. If officers must comply strictly with what the law says they must or must not do, a broader knowledge and understanding of their operating environment seems at first sight to be unnecessary. However, as this study and others have found (for example, Charman, 2017), public service work, including policing, is gradually being reconfigured and relocated (Noordegraaf, 2015, 2016; Martin, 2021). This, it is argued, requires a ‘re-professionalisation’ (Holdaway, 2017) of policing to include not only integration of the ‘art’, ‘craft’ and ‘science’ of policing (Willis and Mastrofski, 2018, p.28), but also the application of ‘practical wisdom’ which, as adult learners, necessitates police recruits and policing students understanding ‘*why*’.

This study found amongst participants in Sweden and Finland that understanding *why* legislation had been enacted was important, as this educator involved in initial police learning in Sweden explained:

“When we study law, we don’t just teach them this is what the law is saying, we try to get them to understand why it’s looking like this, and how can you understand and interpret the law, you need to read the motives for the law, and then it’s easier for them to be able to understand...” [Participant SWP14 - Senior Academic, Sweden]

Understanding ‘*why*’, supports critical thinking in adult learners (Knowles, 1970, 1973, 1980), thereby supporting the development of intelligent, intellectual police officers, which is a key policy outcome of the academisation of initial police learning in Sweden and Finland. The desire to understand *why* within Swedish and Finnish

initial police learning programmes is, it is argued, an important foundation for the development through experience of ‘practical wisdom’ or ‘phronesis’. Knowing when bending the rules is ethically acceptable and when it is not, is helpful with regards maintaining police legitimacy. As Fekjaer and Petersson (2019, p.947) argue, a “formal, legalistic approach may in some cases alienate the police from the public they are supposed to serve.” The approaches to initial police learning in Sweden and Finland appeared to enhance policing student’s understanding of the *why*, underpinning their learning. Understanding why enhances not only an officer’s critical thinking but also their ability to explain their actions.

It appears from the comparative analysis of the data discussed in this section, that the influence of situated cultural norms, both actual and intended, within the initial learning venues were to differing degrees perceived as both helping and hindering the socialisation process and the development of desirable professional attributes.

6.3 The outcome.

What is meant by ‘learning’ has been described as a “wily shapeshifter” which often leads to a “tendency to omit explicit definitions of learning” (Fenwick, 2010, p.80). The first two sections of this chapter have explored ‘learning’ as a verb: the process of learning. This section focuses on exploring ‘learning’ as a noun: the product or outcome of a change process (Fenwick, 2010, p.84), with a particular focus on the extent to which initial police learning aligns with, and supports, the situated notions of professionalism in each of the case study countries. It does so, using some of the different conceptual levels pursued within policing research: “the macro-environmental/institutional level, the meso-strategic and tactical organizational levels, and the micro-work group and individual police officer levels” (Greene, 2014, p.203).

6.3.1 Macro-level

At a macro-level of analysis, both the Swedish and Finish initial police learning programmes accord with the OECD definition of “expanding knowledge and

learning” as a means by which to maintain and develop individual and societal well-being (Casey, 2006, p.345). In other north-western European countries these socio-political drivers are being realised, in part through broader meso-level strategies such as the widening of access to HE, and comparability in the standards, quality, and standardisation of European-wide academic accreditation, such as the Bologna Process. They are also reflected in broader professionalisation strategies within public services which rely less on a classic notion of profession for legitimacy, and more on being knowledge-based. In this regard, policing within the case study countries is mirroring similar developments within public sector occupations in that increasingly complex, unpredictable, and rapidly changing operating environments require work to be undertaken by knowledge workers, rather than those working in an artisan trade where HE is “not a pre-requisite to employment” (McCanney, Taylor and Bates, 2022, p.315).

Notions of professionalism within public sector services, including policing, are being reorganised, re-stratified and relocated (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.783) within the case study countries, not only in response to these socio-political drivers, but also in response to the increasingly complex and rapidly changing social, cultural, political, and economic operating environments. These in turn have influenced organisational restructuring and managerial frameworks which in the views of some scholars have resulted in “reframe[ing] understandings of professional work” (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.789). Whilst in Scotland and Sweden this has led to a rational-efficient, vertically, and horizontally fragmented policing model in which expert knowledge is concentrated within managerial and specialist police officers and civilian staff, it has also served to ‘de-skill’ and ‘de-professionalise’ front-line response officers through the imposition of greater managerial control over occupational culture (Cockcroft, 2015, p.183), and a reshaping of their role into one which is comparatively less complex, more predictable, and unchanging.

However, whilst this is reflected in the artisan-based training approach (Stanislas, 2014) to initial police learning in Scotland, the Swedish approach, as in Finland, reflects the macro-level drivers to develop knowledge-based economies, including the

re-professionalisation of public services which increasingly rely for legitimacy on developing a knowledge-based expertise through greater engagement with HE. Whilst this will be explored in greater detail in chapter 7, it is sufficient to say at this point, that in Sweden and Finland, the aspirational policy outcomes to be derived from a closer alignment of initial police learning with HE, accord with the OECDs ideals of expanding knowledge and learning as a means by which to maintain and develop individual and societal well-being.

6.3.2 Meso-level

At a meso or organisational level, the extent to which the respective initial police learning models aligned with the prevailing notions of organisational professionalism were found to be different. Broadly, there was a greater degree of synergy between intended policy outcomes and their realisation in Scotland and Finland than in Sweden.

The Scottish model focused on what some scholars would define as artisan-level training (for example Stanislas, 2014, p.4) and was widely perceived as being closely aligned with the prevailing notion of organisational professionalism which had reduced the scope and complexity of front-line response constables, arguably de-skilling, and de-professionalising them and, thereby, requiring comparatively less theoretical knowledge, for example, of the law. This, coupled with an organisational and occupational cultural norm which foregrounded the passing of tacit knowledge from more experienced tutor constables to recruits as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital, was reflected in the comparatively lengthy, twenty-one month 'on-the-job' practice phase. There was also synergy between the environment at the Scottish Police College within which the initial, eleven-week 'classroom-based, ITC took place, and prevailing notions of hierarchical control.

However, whilst both the Swedish and Finnish models both overlaid artisan-level training with higher academic education, the extent to which the intended policy outcomes of re-configuring policing into an expert, knowledge-based occupation were

perceived as being realised, differed between both countries. In the case of Sweden, it is argued that the intended policy outcomes to be derived from greater engagement with HE were conflicting not only with the occupational cultural norms (for example, the isolating behaviours of policing students), but also with the prevailing notion of organisational culture guided by a rational-efficient policing style, where knowledge-based expertise is situated within increasingly vertically and horizontally fragmented organisational structures, rather than within generalist front-line response constables who have greater individual autonomy. That said, whilst the hierarchical approach to leadership, coupled with the organisational structures, might be somewhat prescriptive and limiting with regards the ability for newly qualified constables to fully utilise the knowledge and skills developed during the two-year initial ‘classroom-based’ learning phase, more transformative leaders were drawing on the epistemic knowledge-base of junior officers, as the data from an operational senior police officer (participant SWP07) replicated on page 110 showed.

It could be argued that the Swedish model provides a level of learning which is unnecessary for front-line response constables (an argument supported by the Conservative political parties within the Swedish Parliament). However, as in Finland, it is a foundational element of wider police professionalisation agendas in which the linear development of officers throughout their potentially forty-year long service is viewed as fundamental in enabling policing to develop a level of knowledge-based expertise necessary to facilitate “ongoing configurations and reconfigurations of practice” (Fenwick, 2010, p.84; Noordegraaf, 2016).

At a more granular, mechanistic level, the spaces within which the initial learning programmes were taking place were found to be helpful in some respects and unhelpful in others. For example, whilst the universities within which the initial ‘classroom-based’ phases took place provided an opportunity for espoused organisational norms to be re-enforced away from the more problematic aspects of ‘real world’ police occupational culture, this intended policy outcome was not being fully realised, as the findings concerning early student isolation in Sweden, and sexist attitudes in Finland exemplified. Whilst these might, in part, be due to the persistence

of more negative aspects of police culture, they might also be due, in part, to the pre-entry socialisation of recruits and policing students which had been influenced by broader societal norms, or the influence of public perceptions regarding police occupational culture. It might also be in part, as Aristotle argued, due to the development of less virtuous characteristics during childhood, a view supported by some scholars who contend that "...the personal qualities required to handle personal interactions competently can only be developed to a limited degree through experience and training, so innate qualities are crucial elements" (Inzunza and Wikström, 2020, p.1245). Whilst beyond the scope of this study, it is interesting to note that whilst in Sweden and Finland potential policing students are subjected to comprehensive psychological assessment, potential recruits in Scotland are not.

6.3.3 Micro-level

At a micro-level, the focus in each of the case study countries, was to develop police recruits and policing students to a point where on completion of their initial police learning programmes, they were competent to perform the generic role of police officer effectively. Whilst, as discussed previously, the generic role of recently 'graduated' police officers differed between countries, the development of ethical decision-making had been foregrounded by police officers as a particularly desirable professional attribute. This finding is "intimately linked with questions about the common good, and about the kinds of society that support human dignity, well-being and fairness for all" (Fenwick, 2010, p.92). Drawing on the discussion in chapter 5 in which it was argued that 'practical wisdom' or 'phronesis' was a particularly desirable professional attribute in this regard, it is worth considering whether initial police learning in the case study countries was providing police recruits and policing students with the requisite theoretical knowledge, and technical skills which, through experience, they could develop 'practical wisdom' or 'phronesis'.

It is argued, based on the findings analysed in this chapter, that the initial learning programmes in each of the case study countries were doing that, but to different extents. Returning to Aristotle's argument that experience alone is insufficient, the

Scottish model compared with the approaches in Sweden and Finland, did not provide the same extent of theoretical knowledge, particularly epistemic theoretical knowledge. Nor did it adequately enable a recruit's individual agency or character to facilitate sense-making through reflection, compared with the approaches in Sweden and Finland. However, it is also argued that whilst the Swedish approach provided both the requisite theoretical (including epistemic) knowledge and technical knowledge, it failed to provide adequate 'on-the-job' practice experience through which to begin developing 'phronesis'. The approach in Finland, by way of contrast, successfully brought together all the messy, interconnected elements of learning in a way which supported the subsequent development of 'phronesis'. 'Phronesis' is a particularly important professional attribute for the front-line, generalist police officer in Finland when operating in an organisation where the notion of organisational professionalism is guided by a lean, distributed approach to worker control, and a tendency towards greater adhocism.

With regards the spaces within which the initial, 'classroom-based' learning phases were taking place, it is argued, based on this study's findings, that the 'closed', semi-militaristic environment of the Scottish Police College was not as helpful for police recruits' acquisition of knowledge as that of the 'open' Swedish mainstream universities or POLAMK. The more 'open' learning environments in Sweden and Finland facilitated a focus on individual meaning-making by for example, providing time and space for self-directed learning, reflection, and explanation of the 'why', thereby it is argued, increasing the 'human capital' of individual officers. However, it is also argued that POLAMK was more helpful than the Swedish universities in combining learning with establishing cultural norms through the socialisation process.

Whilst the sequencing of the learning phases was generally perceived as being helpful to knowledge and skill development, variations in the duration of each phase raises some interesting questions which merit further consideration. The duration of the two main learning phases, the initial 'classroom-based' phase and the 'on-the-job' learning phase varied, in some instances considerably, between the case study countries. Whilst it was argued in Scotland that the comparatively limited theoretical knowledge

required for a recruit to undertake the practice phase did not require a lengthy 'classroom-based' phase, much of the deeper learning was taking place in recruits' own time due to the lack of space within the busy eleven-week timetable for self-directed learning and reflection. The twenty-one-month practice phase not only reflected the foregrounding of experiential learning as a source of cultural capital, but it also reflected police recruit's status in Scotland as sworn, salaried constables who were viewed by managers as deployable resources on the street. By way of contrast, whilst supporting the wider aspirational professionalisation agenda, the two-year 'classroom-based' phase in Sweden is questionable, particularly when it is followed by such a comparatively short six-month practice phase. As this, and other studies have found, learning 'on-the-job' was valued more highly than "any other form of training or education within the police service" (Charman, 2017, p.224). This is not unique to policing and is a fundamental principle of adult education. Consideration should, therefore, be given, to introducing policing students in Sweden earlier to 'on-the-job' learning and to extending the duration of this phase.

Whilst sense-checking this study's findings and interpretations regarding the imbalance between these two phases, senior academics involved in the development and delivery of the initial police learning programme in Sweden, were of the view that it would be helpful if the recommendation of the 2016 Governmental Working Party report on initial police education were enacted. The report recommended that the 'general exam' quality assurance criteria, which encapsulate a more academic theoretical set of assessment measures, be replaced with those for designated professional (vocational) university programmes, such as nursing.

Finally, with regards Finland, the duration of the learning phases (an initial eighteen-months learning at POLAMK, followed by an eleven-month 'on-the-job' practice phase) prepared policing students well for graduation and subsequent employment as senior constables. That said, the final twenty-week dissertation completion phase, which followed the practice phase, was widely perceived by policing students as foregrounding the needs of academia with regards degree accreditation, over their desire to graduate and seek employment. However, as this police sergeant with

responsibility for overseeing the tutoring of policing students in the field explained, the system is flexible, and students can still graduate after two-and-a-half years:

“There’s three years allowed for it, but that includes 20 weeks at the end to write their project. The reality is that a lot of the students are writing the projects during their field work, so that when they come back, they’ve finished, and they can graduate after two and a half years”
[Participant FP13 - Police Sergeant, Finland]

Whilst the wider intended policy outcomes were generally being realised, some interesting aspects are worthy of further research and debate. For example, it is argued that whilst the Scottish initial learning programme was adequately preparing recruits for their comparatively limited roles, it was not providing them with the ability to either continue their own professional development within what are likely to be increasingly complex and rapidly changing policing environments during careers which might span thirty to forty years. Nor is it enhancing their ability to “construct flexible and sustainable careers across the life course” (Tomlinson *et al.*, 2018, p.4) both within and outside of policing.

It also raises broader questions about the future role and initial professional development of front-line response constables in Scotland. Given the increasingly challenging internal and external policing environments within which Scottish policing is operating, particularly with regards public sector funding in the post-pandemic era, it is perhaps time for a broader public debate about the sustainability of the existing policing model, particularly given Finland’s ability to police the same size population with a third of the police officers whilst apparently maintaining higher levels of public trust and confidence. Given that organisational notions of professionalism, the role of a front-line response constable, and the knowledge, skills, and behaviours they require are inextricably linked, any such debate should encapsulate initial police learning.

6.4 Conclusion

This chapter highlighted that once again, variables of context were important in understanding the findings, particularly situated notions of professionalism and cultural norms. It argued that the two-year, 'craft' model in Scotland, which comprised an initial eleven-week, training-focused, 'classroom' based phase within a 'traditional', regimented, training school, followed by a twenty-one month practice phase, reflected an organisational notion of professionalism in which the role of a junior, front-line response constable was marginalised to 'routine' tasks, and tacit knowledge developed through 'real world' experience was foregrounded as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital. It was, therefore, generally perceived as a helpful approach.

This was contrasted with the approaches in Sweden and Finland which focused, through longer programmes (two-and-a-half years in Sweden, three-years in Finland) on both training *and* education. It was shown that the extent to which their longer, university-based, initial 'classroom-based' learning phases (two-years in Sweden, eighteen-months in Finland), and shorter 'real world' practice phases (six months in Sweden, eleven months in Finland) were perceived as helpful in the initial professional development of policing students differed. In Finland, the initial 'classroom-based' phase was generally perceived as helpful in developing the requisite level of theoretical knowledge and technical skills for their generalist role. However, in Sweden, perceptions were mixed. Whilst academics viewed the initial two-year 'classroom' based phase as helpful, policing students were of the view that it foregrounded the assessment criteria needs of academia over their vocational needs. Spending two-years at university before having the opportunity to apply their learning in the 'real world' was perceived by senior police officers and policing students as being unhelpful in bridging the theory-practice divide.

Finally, the chapter analysed participant perceptions regarding the extent to which the product, or outcome, of initial police learning aligned with, and supported, situated notions of professionalisation at a macro, meso, and micro level of analysis. Within

that analysis, it was argued that in not following the academisation trend, Police Scotland is at odds with the macro-level driver of achieving a knowledge-based economy as seen in other public services in Scotland, such as nursing, teaching, social work and more recently, paramedicine.

Chapter 7: Initial police learning, HE, and professionalisation

Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to outline and analyse the findings from this study concerning the research question: what factors explain the divergence between ‘policy network actors’ perceptions within the case study countries on the impact, or potential impact, of academic education on the professionalisation of police recruits and policing students?

Section 7.1 begins by revealing that academics, educators, and senior police officers in Sweden, and academics, police officers across ranks, and policing students in Finland, perceived undergraduate degree-level education as enhancing policing students’ professionalism in several ways. For example: deepening knowledge and understanding of their role within the wider social context within which they are operating, thereby constraining the ‘heroic’ police occupational culture; enhancing the capability for, and disposition towards, lifelong learning and policing’s capability to develop a unique corpus of knowledge; cultivating critical, analytical thinking and reflective practice; and enhancing receptivity to evidence-informed practice. Finally, this section reveals that whilst chief police officers, academics, and some policing students in Sweden and Finland perceived degree accreditation as a source of social, cultural, and economic capital, policing students more commonly did not.

Section 7.2 uncovers the contradictory perceptions in Scottish policing about the cultural capital of HE found in Scotland. The perception generally held by police officers was that HE had no relevance for front-line, initial response policing. This is contrasted, however, with the view of some, that graduates were well-suited to the complexity of contemporary policing. This section then progresses to highlight that whilst HE and qualifications were acknowledged as forms of self-legitimacy, they conflicted with what constituted cultural capital within the organisational culture (Cockcroft and Hallenberg, 2017; Williams, Norman, and Rowe, 2019). The argument regularly rendered, not only by police officers but also by those in oversight and

governance roles, was that graduates are not necessarily ‘better’ police officers. This perception was not only found amongst experienced officers, but also amongst police recruits in the first week of their ITC. This section also highlights the cultural resistance in Scotland (apart from within academia) to policing becoming a graduate-entry only occupation as part of a wider professionalisation strategy. This was founded, in part, on a concern that this would deter applicants from socially or economically disadvantaged backgrounds, and thereby adversely affect Police Scotland’s representativeness and acceptance from those communities (Martin, 2021).

Section 7.3 argues that a notion of professionalism founded in part, on epistemic knowledge together with critical, analytical thinking and reflective practice, could be achieved by aligning initial police learning more closely with HE. However, it is also argued that in doing so, emphasis needs to be placed on bridging the theory practice divide. This section argues that ‘practical wisdom’ (phronesis), could be an effective way to do that by blending the ‘art’, ‘craft’, and ‘science’ of policing (Wood, *et.al.*, 2018, p.176) to make deliberative, ethical decisions which aim to do the right thing in any given set of circumstances. It then moves on to highlight that the academisation of initial police learning may be better suited to a notion of professionalism that is guided by a generalist policing style, within a lean, distributed approach to the management of tasks and leadership. Finally, concerns about pre-entry and post-entry structural inequalities which might arise from academisation are discussed together with potential mitigations.

The chapter concludes with section 7.4, in which it is argued that a closer alignment of initial police learning with HE provides a foundation, in part, for a reconfigured, contemporary notion of professionalism (Noordegraaf, 2016), based not only on craft knowledge developed through training and experience, but also on science-based knowledge, critical and reflective practice, career-long learning, and the development of new knowledge through academic research and evidence-informed policing, for which degree accreditation is not necessarily the answer (Tong and Wood, 2011, p. 71). This not only moves beyond the traditional ‘craft’-based training courses, but also the trait-driven focus on degree-accreditation.

7.1 'It's good to know this stuff': the Swedish and Finnish perspectives

This section analyses findings developed from the Swedish and Finnish study data. Given the extent to which their initial police learning programmes had become closely aligned with HE, these findings will be considered together. Scotland, which had not aligned their programme with HE will be considered separately. Whilst there were differing perceptions in Sweden and Finland, mainly between senior police officers and academics on the one hand and policing students on the other, participants were generally of the view that a closer alignment of initial police learning with HE did enhance the professionalism of policing students.

7.1.1 A deeper understanding of policing's context in wider society

Academics, educators, and senior police officers in Sweden, and academics, police officers of all ranks, and policing students in Finland who participated in this study, perceived that undergraduate degree-level education was enhancing policing students' professionalism. For example, as this Swedish educator teaching on the Swedish initial learning programme explained, the programme included a module entitled 'Policing in Society' which gave students a deeper understanding of the historical and social context within which Swedish policing was operating:

“In the first semester we have this course called Policing in Society... the course talks about the police organisation historically within Sweden, the police organisation, what is policing as an idea in the world”
[Participant SWP05 - Policing Educator, Sweden]

Having a broader and deeper understanding of policing as a concept and of its historical, social, cultural, and political context was also perceived as being important within the initial police learning programme in Finland. For example, providing policing students there with a knowledge and understanding of the historical context of post-war police professionalisation was widely perceived as helping to instil a commitment to maintain the legacy of public trust and confidence which policing had been developing for seventy-years, as this quote from a policing student exemplifies:

“... one of the first things we go through is history of Finnish police... to know what we are aiming for, what has happened from the current police we have, and probably because also of knowing what mistakes have been made, or how things have changed. At some point police was feared and completely pretty much the opposite of what it is now, so it’s good to know all this stuff.” [FP17 - Policing Student, Finland]

Police officer participants in Finland, were acutely aware that since World War Two, policing in Finland had undergone a seventy-year period of transforming itself from being the hated state-arm of an oppressive right-wing Government, to an organisation with high levels of public trust and confidence. Aligning an organisation’s underlying assumptions and espoused values is thought by some scholars (for example, Schein, 2017) to increase the likelihood of cultural buy-in to realising intended policy outcomes across all levels of an organisation. Whilst educating policing students about the historical context of policing in Finland was helpful in this regard, it was also deepening policing student’s knowledge and understanding regarding the boundaries of their role within Finnish society, as this senior operational police commander explained:

“You know your role, okay. And you know where you fit into the picture of society and who else has got responsibility.” [Participant FP11 - Senior Police Officer, Finland]

The inference taken from this data is that an understanding of policing’s role within wider society in Finland could mitigate, in part, against the ‘heroic’ police occupational culture (Chan, 1997; Reiner, 2010; Sklansky, 2011; Westmarland, 2017; Southern, 2018), whereby police officers attempt to address all of society’s ills. Having a deeper knowledge and understanding regarding the boundaries of their roles could enhance police officer’s operational confidence within an increasingly collaborative public service sector, providing greater clarity as to where their responsibilities begin and end. This is particularly relevant within the context of multi-agency collaboration and challenging public sector funding arrangements (Martin and Graham, 2022).

Within the initial police learning programmes in Sweden and Finland, this broader and deeper understanding included epistemic theoretical knowledge such as criminology,

psychology, and sociology. Whilst no such learning was found within the Scottish initial police learning programme's curriculum, its benefits were acknowledged by this senior police officer in Scotland who had completed in-service⁵ undergraduate and Master's degrees:

“So, I guess it did open my mind a bit given the fact I joined so young, and I could almost have been institutionalised. So, I felt it broke me out of the mould of being institutionalised a bit, yeah? It was a lot to do with politics and wider theories and how we got to be where we are in terms of policing by consent and everything. And then going on to criminology and studying it and really looking at minds and behaviours and I really enjoyed that aspect of it.” [Participant SCP17 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland]

Whilst there was no evidence that this officer had subsequently utilised this learning in their professional practice, HE appears to have broadened and deepened their conceptual knowledge and understanding of the historical and social context of policing. The potential benefit of HE in changing insular, police-centric perspectives, echoes the work of Hallenberg (2017, p.14) and her study of those working within police training schools in England and Wales. She found that the insularity of these spaces was not always open to other ways of thinking. She argued that HE helped overcome that by introducing other conceptual theories such as criminology, psychology and sociology, an argument which the data from this study supports.

7.1.2 Lifelong learning

Stimulating intellectual curiosity and creating the capacity for lifelong, self-directed learning was perceived as another key benefit to be derived from a closer alignment of initial police learning with HE amongst senior police officers and academics in Sweden and Finland. They argued that constantly changing and increasingly complex operating environments, required policing students to have the capability and motivation to develop and maintain their own professional knowledge throughout

⁵ Higher education undertaken during their service, either with or without the support of their organisation, but separate from mandatory learning and development.

what for many was likely to be a forty-year plus career, as these quotations firstly from a chief police officer in Sweden, and secondly from a police educator in Finland exemplify:

“...the police profession and the phenomena steering the police mission is being more complex all the time. The police is working within a more complex society, laws are changing and the conditions under which people live under are more complex... The notion of the idea of lifelong learning that the police officers could not learn for working within one time-period and then stop learning. But rather they want people to be able to develop through their whole professional life.” [Participant SWP 11 - Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

“...there will be big changes, so this lifelong studying is a big issue that we should concentrate on.” [Participant FP16 - Policing Educator, Finland]

This chief police officer in Scotland appeared to agree with the significance of continual learning when they said:

“...the thing that I really value is learning. I think we should constantly encourage people to have learning mindsets and I think in a really fast changing world that’s the thing you should encourage, is learning...” [Participant SCP14 - Chief Police Officer, Scotland].

What is interesting here is that whilst “encouraging people to have learning mindsets” was espoused as a source of cultural capital, no evidence was found within the data concerning how Police Scotland stimulated learning mindsets amongst recruits or supported them to develop the capacity to undertake lifelong or career-long learning. An ongoing doctoral study exploring continuous professional development within Police Scotland (Engelmann, 2021), has found little evidence of a structured, organisational approach to continual lifelong or career-long learning.

The ambition of policing both in Sweden and Finland is to instil a disposition towards lifelong learning, which can also be understood within the context of the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) for lifelong learning, which was adopted by the European Union in 2008, and later revised in 2017. It aims to “contribute to better transparency and comparability of qualifications of different national systems” (2017/C 189/03(5)). However, some participants suggested that academic education

and qualifications were not necessary for policing students or recruits to develop a disposition for lifelong learning. For example, as this police recruit in Scotland argued, it was job satisfaction which principally drove lifelong learning:

“Coming back to the lifelong learning thing, like we were saying before, if you want to be in the police and this is your job, and you’re enjoying it, you will have it in you to want to keep learning to keep doing your job, it’ll be in you anyway... So, I definitely don’t think you need a degree necessarily...” [Focus Group SCPFG01 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

Whilst job satisfaction alone may well be sufficient to develop and sustain a disposition for lifelong learning and professional development, it is argued that these are enhanced by having the knowledge and skills in how to source reliable, credible academic research, how to critically analyse and interpret it, and how to reflect on its “potential to support professional practice” (Hallenberg 2017, p.8). This Neyroud (2011), argued is especially important within specialist areas of policing if the requisite level of expertise is to be developed.

7.1.3 Reflective practitioners

The fieldwork in Sweden and Finland found that several senior police officers, academics, and educators, were of the view that the closer alignment of HE with initial police learning had enhanced the professionalism of policing students by developing their capacity and capability to be reflective practitioners. For example, this police educator from POLAMK argued that there was a correlation between the gradual academisation of initial police learning since the year 2000, and policing students having become increasingly reflective in their practice:

“...when I think about my students from 2000 to now, 2019, I honestly think that they are more reflective and more tolerant and more wide-open, and they understand that this is just a process, this is a lifelong learning...” [FP16 - Policing Educator, Finland]

What appears to be happening here, insofar as this experienced educator perceives it, is that in being educated in the process of reflective practice, policing students are developing desirable professional attributes namely, tolerance and open-mindedness.

Interestingly, it appears from this data that policing students in Finland are not only developing the capacity, through being taught the ‘process’ of reflective practice, but also developing an awareness that enhancing their professionalism through reflective practice is a career-long undertaking.

Further support for the notion that developing reflective practice amongst policing students enhances their professionalism, was also found within the data from Sweden. For example, as this educator who teaches policing students during the two-year phase of the initial learning programme explained, it enhances their ability to confront ethical dilemmas:

“I was sceptical, and I was really afraid that the students would hate it, but they love it. Some of them still hate it, of course they do, but they talk about everything. And their essays have been what happens, the problems with ranks. You need ranks and you need someone to tell you what to do, it is needed, especially in an organisation like this, but what happens when that person is wrong, and you have this gut feeling that that decision is wrong, but you are lower in rank, and what can you actually do? I wonder how willing they would have been to write as honestly about some of these ethical dilemmas if they’d been based at the police school?” [Participant SWP05 - Policing Educator, Sweden]

According to scholars in the field of police education, a closer alignment of initial police learning with HE and the principles of reflective practice to provide the capability to “reconsider what they are doing and why, both before and after action” (Bergman, 2017, p.84), might be helpful “if deeper learning is to remain with recruits beyond the classroom and to survive the more corrosive elements of police occupational culture” (Hough *et al.*, 2018, p.7). Engelmann (2022, forthcoming), found that police officers in Scotland were reluctant to challenge higher ranking officers with whom they disagreed for fear of repercussions.

7.1.4 Examining their own practice: developing expertise

Another important finding is the perception amongst senior police officers, academics, and police educators in Finland, that developing a knowledge and understanding of academic research methods to successfully complete an undergraduate degree-level

research-based dissertation as part of their initial learning programme, provided policing students with the inspiration and capacity to critically engage in examination of their own practice, as this chief officer in Finland explained:

“I would say that it gives policemen a really good basis to go forward and to continue studying to do some research and so on, and I think that we will never have enough research on policing in a way. It’s a good thing that we have people who think critically, think how could they do this in another way, could they do it in a better way. That kind of education gives them a better starting point to develop their work in general, and maybe do some research for the police forces.” [Participant FP09 - Chief Police Officer, Finland]

As discussed in chapter 4, similar policy aspirations underpinned the partial academisation of initial police learning in Sweden. However, the data from this study also found that the intended policy outcomes in this regard had yet to be fully realised there, as firstly this senior academic with responsibility for delivering the initial two-year phase of the initial police learning at a Swedish university, and secondly this Swedish chief police officer, explained:

“The other next step that is not taken yet, is to sort of make police students part of the knowledge production.” [SWP02 - Senior Academic, Sweden]

“We don’t have any police science. It’s not a subject on the university, and with this kind of system, Bachelor system, that would be an opportunity for universities to build that up, so we can have police research more practical evidence-based police or whatever you call it, because right now, we don’t have that in Sweden.” [SWP11 - Chief Police Officer, Sweden]

Some scholars have argued that police officers being part of knowledge production allows policing to claim institutional jurisdiction and cognitive hegemony (Ericson and Haggerty, 1997, cited in Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2014, p.5), and that “the profession of policing will not emerge in the true sense until practitioners engage in examination of their own practice” (Green and Gates, 2014, p.79), thereby contributing to the development of a unique corpus of professional knowledge.

The development of a unique corpus of knowledge is often associated with differentiating between a 'blue collar job' and a profession within the sociology of professions literature (for example, Weisburd and Neyroud, 2011, p.10). The wider acceptance of science-based knowledge as being important to the development of a policing as a profession has been advanced by the evidence-based policing (Sherman, 1998; Weisburd and Neyroud, 2011) and evidence-informed policing (Fyfe and Wilson, 2012) movements. This was reflected in the comments of these senior police officers from Sweden and Finland, the first a police union official, and the second an operational commander:

“A major thing for us to become a proper university education is the research. The possibility of researching on your own profession... The things that we do, the methods that we use, we don't really know if they are good or bad... and the positive thing about being at the universities now is that there's a mindset there that actually could bring this forward. We have very few people that do any research on the actual police methods because we don't have a police research, police officers can't research at the moment... So, we have a little bit of research. But the police force in general, they're not very research friendly.” [Participant SWP06 - Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

“...now police itself can produce some scientific material... and have this proof maybe.” [Participant FP04 - Senior Police Officer, Finland]

The development of science-based expertise within policing was linked by academics and senior police officers in Sweden, to policing's positionality on the continuum of professions (Eraut, 1994), as this data from a senior police officer there demonstrates when asked if policing was regarded as having the same social status as doctors and lawyers:

“No, I think it's level under that really... it is the time they spend at university and the research base... they are seen as more of an expert, their profession, than we are. We know a little bit of a lot of things, but we're not really experts in anything really.” [Participant SWP07 – Senior Police Officer, Sweden]

Whilst the development of the requisite research knowledge and skills was necessary for completion of a final research-based dissertation (a requirement for the award of a Bachelor's degree), one policing student in Finland nearing graduation argued that

getting the opportunity to utilise academic research skills was more challenging during the early stages of an officer's career:

“I know that they can be utilised, but they are kind of hard to utilise in the beginning of your law enforcement career.” [Participant FFG02 - Policing Student, Finland]

This argument was reflected in the views of a police recruit in Scotland, who argued that whilst critical thinking and analytical skills were not necessary for front-line response officers (a view held by numerous other police officers in Scotland of all ranks), they might be more appropriate for officers working within specialist roles:

“I don't think it's necessary... it's not an analytical job, unless you go into a unit that requires that.” [Focus Group SCPFG01 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

However, within the police professionalisation literature, some scholars argue that there are many benefits to be derived from HE, such as “increased self-esteem”, which are beneficial not only to the individual, but also to policing more widely (Hallenberg, 2017, p.13). For example, it has been argued that it increases “job motivation” and “the potential for personal development...” (Hallenberg, 2017, p.13). Lee and Punch (2004, p.245-246) found in their interviews with graduates from the 1960s Essex scheme, that “they had gained a considerable measure of personal and professional self-confidence” from being seconded from policing to university to undertake their first undergraduate degree. They also found that the experience enabled them to be “more self-reflexive and questioning, gave them more confidence to challenge commonly accepted stances and shaped them to be more eager to look for evidence in arguments”. In their study of police officers in England who had undertaken in-service HE learning, Cockcroft and Hallenberg (2021, p.10) found that many “perceived developments in cognitive ability, strategic focus and confidence”.

On the other hand, some scholars have also argued (for example, Williams, Norman and Rowe, 2019) that HE not only pulls against limitations to individual adhocacy, but also, in respect of officers undertaking in-service HE learning, poses a ‘double threat’ to the organisation as these officers possess “both the practical, insider

experience of the profession (the ‘credibility’) and skills and willingness to challenge the status quo” (Cockcroft and Hallenberg, 2021, p.11). HE, therefore, might be seen as a threat to long-established hierarchical power within policing. Indeed, in Norway and Finland, the closer alignment of HE with initial police learning was found to have “challenged traditional police hierarchy” (Schaap and Terpstra, 2020, p.5). This might, therefore, partly explain the resistance amongst senior police officers in Scotland and indeed, those within Scottish policing’s oversight and governance structures, to the academisation of initial police learning. Some police officers argued that the hierarchical, mistrustful approach to leadership within Police Scotland which was reinforced by increasingly restrictive policies and procedures (for example, in responding to allegations of domestic abuse), limited their ability to utilise individual discretion. These limitations were compounded by the exponential increase in specialist departments within the force which, some senior officers argued, had resulted in the role of junior, front-line, first response officers becoming less generalist in nature. Instead, it was argued, their role had become less complex: they were expected to deal with a narrower range of less complex, more routine tasks. Their main role was to provide a speedy initial response to calls, secure evidence and pass on any cases which were not ‘routine’ to specialist units. Whilst not as restricting as managerial control, the remaining space within which first responders had the capacity to apply individual professional judgement was relatively narrow. This operating environment it is argued, was not conducive to challenging Police Scotland’s commonly accepted espoused values and underlying assumptions (Schein, 2017, pp. 19-25). The resistance to a closer alignment of initial police learning amongst police recruits on the other hand, might be understood in part, from pre-socialisation which may have informed perceptions of how “police work ideally should be performed” (Moberg, 2020, p. 72), but also who should be performing it, namely officers from ‘blue-collar’ backgrounds.

7.1.5 Degree accreditation

It was expected, and indeed found, that chief police officers and academics in Sweden and Finland would perceive degree accreditation of initial police learning as a source

of social, cultural, and economic capital. This view was supported by some policing students, as this example from Finland demonstrates:

“There’s so many benefits of getting a degree... if I wanna be a police officer the rest of my life, then it doesn’t really matter if I do have a degree... but if in the future I decide that it’s not my thing and I want to do something else I do have a degree.” [Focus Group FFG1 - Policing Student, Finland]

Degree accreditation then, was perceived by this policing student as providing them with “increased career flexibility, allowing people to move on to other jobs more easily, whether after retirement or earlier if a police career is no longer the right one for them” (Hallenberg, 2017, p.12). Whilst this was generally perceived amongst senior police officers in Sweden and Finland as a positive outcome of degree accreditation, including the Swedish police union, this was not the case for this senior police officer and union official in Scotland:

“...what other profession trains its people so that they’re skilled to leave?” (Participant SCP04 - Senior Police Officer, Scotland)

Interestingly, this chief police officer in Finland perceived the retention of highly educated and degree qualified officers as a leadership challenge, one which could be met by ensuring that the role of a front line, operational response constable was sufficiently interesting and rewarding for them to remain within policing:

“...you have to realise that your young constables are not lorry drivers anymore, er, they are people... many of them are people with two academic degrees... they are really well educated, they have a broad range of competencies... you have to listen to these bright young people, you have to be ready to provide them with new challenges.” (Participant FP02 - Chief Police Officer, Finland)

The participant’s perspective reflects a change in the long-term career choices of the ‘new breed’ (Charman, 2017) of people entering policing who, as in many other public service occupations, “no longer view it as a job for life” (Martin, 2021, p. 9). The COP in England and Wales has recognised that the contemporary workforce needs to be flexible, “with various...lengths of service, as well as the possibility of re-joining at a later stage” (Martin, 2021, p.9). Being a graduate, within societies where academic

attainment levels are rising and access to HE is widening, will, it is argued, enhance not only 'external' career flexibility, but also 'internal' career trajectories.

It was also expected that the main motivation for policing students in Finland to undertake the initial learning programme was to become police officers rather than to obtain a degree, and indeed this was found to be the case, as this policing educator at POLAMK explained:

“...it’s not the main point... they want to do this work because they are very interested, and they are very motivated.” (Participant FP16 - Policing Educator, Finland]

This finding echoes that of a recent study involving early student cohorts undertaking the Police Constable Degree Apprenticeship Scheme, which has recently been implemented in England and Wales. It also found that gaining a degree through the scheme “was not a driving force for 12 (40%) [of the] participants to join policing” (Watkinson-Miley, Cox and Deshpande, 2022, p.5).

However, in drawing on the trait-based approach to defining profession, the participants from academia in this study, together with senior police officers in Sweden, generally considered the presence or absence of compulsory, undergraduate degree accredited, initial police learning programmes as a determining factor in whether policing was to be defined as either a profession, or a semi-profession (Etzioni, 1969). This response from a senior academic in Sweden when asked whether they considered policing to be a profession, exemplifies this:

“Semi-profession I would say. Since we don’t have this degree, it’s not really a profession.” [Participant SWP14 - Senior Academic, Sweden]

Police officers on the other hand from each of the case study countries, apart from senior officers in Sweden, generally regarded policing as a profession. In doing so, they did not draw on the trait-based presence or absence of graduate-entry only, but rather drew on notions that policing was a 'vocation', a 'calling', as this data firstly from a soon to graduate policing student in Sweden, and secondly from a sixteen-month service police recruit in Scotland, show:

“It’s a calling.” [Participant SWP09 - Policing Student, Sweden]

‘It’s a vocation.’ [Focus Group SCPFG1 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

This “optimistic view” of professionalism (Evetts, 2014, p.36) reflects the principle that professional work is that which is considered important to wider society. It also reflects the “motivational force – the belief system” (Wynia *et al.*, 2014, p.712) or essence of what it means to be a professional, which transcends lists of desirable professional attributes, including the requirement for new entrants to be graduates.

These differing perspectives between academics and police officers reflect the complex debates within the academy about whether policing is a profession, a ‘semi-profession’ (Etzioni, 1969), or an artisan trade (Jones, 2016, p.233). Whilst police officer’s in this study generally considered themselves to be professionals, echoing Lumsden’s (2017) study of police officers in England, for some academics, policing remains at best, as this study has shown, a ‘semi-profession’ (Etzioni, 1969). On that basis, it might be argued by some academics, that policing in Scotland remains “a public service bureaucracy with the ethos of “blue-collar factory workers” pre-occupied “with discipline, their quasi-military management practices” in their “rule-bound world which discourages initiative” (Bayley, 2008, p.14). However, this would fail to take account of Noordegraaf’s (2016) argument that professional work, especially public service work, is being ‘reorganised’ (for example, through strategies such as New Public Management); ‘restratified’ (for example, through increased specialisation); and relocated (for example, community policing and multi-agency working), in response to increasingly complex and challenging social, cultural, political, and financial environments. This ‘reconfiguration” of professional work it is argued, challenges these “dualistic and oppositional understandings” (Noordegraaf, 2015, p.188) of profession and professionalism.

7.2 ‘It’s got nothing to do with policing’: the Scottish perspective

This section analyses findings developed from the Scottish data which showed mixed and contradictory perceptions about the cultural capital of HE within initial police

learning. For example, on the one hand the perception held by police officers that HE had nothing to do with policing, whilst on the other, the perception of some that graduates were welcome given the complexity of contemporary policing. It also explores the concerns held by Scottish police officers of all levels, that the Swedish and Finnish models would deter applicants who can't afford to undertake a university degree, thereby adversely affecting Police Scotland's representativeness, a concern which was also raised, albeit to a lesser extent in Sweden and Finland.

7.2.1 Does a degree make you a better police officer?

Analysis found a perception amongst police officers in Scotland that, whilst undertaking higher academic education was beneficial for the individual, it does not enhance their professionalism. This evidence, firstly from a chief police officer, and secondly from a police recruit in their first week of the ITC, demonstrate this point:

“I don't think it's a bad thing to have a degree and to have the opportunity to study as an individual, as a person, is hugely healthy, but does it make you a better police officer? No.” [Participant SCP07 - Chief Police Officer, Scotland]

“I think if you took one of these police officers from Finland, who went through the whole process and he has five years' service and you stood him with a cop from Scotland who has five years' service, would they be a better cop?” [Focus Group SCPFG02 - Police Recruit, Scotland]

This is an argument “regularly rendered in opposition to academic police education” (Hallenberg, 2017, p.22), not only by some police practitioners, as this study has shown, but also by some scholars such as Paterson (2011), Wimshurst and Ransley (2007), and Brown (2020). That said, whilst the views of the chief officer quoted above might have been based on a combination of professional judgement and experience, the same cannot be said of the recruit in their very first week of employment in Police Scotland. It is likely therefore, that the recruit's perceptions had, in part, been influenced by pre-entry acculturation “constituted by the narrative of the police profession – a narrative that the individual encounters in daily life, especially from the media (Moberg, 2020, p.63). The narrative which some scholars argue

attaches immense” “symbolic and legitimising value” of academising policing (Hallenberg, 2017, p.22), did not resonate within the cultural and political context of Scottish policing.

Building on the work of Martin and Wooff (2020) who found ‘little political appetite’ for a degree pathway as one of several possible pathways into Scottish policing, this study found that opposition to graduate-entry only was vehemently opposed, not only within Police Scotland, but also by those participants within oversight and governance roles. The pejorative language often used highlighted the level of cultural resistance, as this comment from a chief officer about the English and Welsh PEQF demonstrates:

“...you know this thing about giving people three-year undergraduate degrees... [I am] not in favour... I think it’s just a conceit quite frankly ... there is something about policing in England and Wales having a massive inferiority complex and wanting to be seen as a profession, wanting to be seen as equivalent to doctors and lawyers and teachers (slapping hand down on the desk repeatedly with each point). And the way to achieve that seems to be that everybody has some sort of academic qualification.” [Participant SCP14 - Chief Police Officer, Scotland]

The language used here reflects the strength of feeling which police officer participants in Scotland expressed in opposition to the notion of Scottish policing becoming graduate-entry only. It also highlights the cultural differences between policymakers within Scottish policing and those in Sweden and Finland, with regards graduate-entry only. The culture in Scotland may, on the one hand, be understood within the context of an ‘anti-academia’ or ‘anti-intellectual’ culture, which some scholars have argued exists within policing (for example, Lee and Punch, 2004). However, on the other hand, it might be argued that the data requires a more nuanced interpretation, one in which there is a culture within Scottish policing which regards the “self-fulfilment” (Paoline and Gau, 2020, p.58) or ‘self-satisfaction’ (Cockcroft and Hallenberg, 2021, p.10) of HE positively, whilst also perceiving it as having little relevance to policing (Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2017), or to the professional development of individual officers (Cockcroft and Hallenberg, 2021). Fieldwork data, firstly from a previous member of the SPCF, and secondly from a chief police officer, illustrate this dichotomy:

“What does academic learning have to do with policing?” [Participant SCP20 - former SPCF Member]

“Now don’t get me wrong, I’m all in favour of academia...we really, really welcome graduates into the organisation because you know this is a complex job, there’s a lot of challenges...” [Participant SCP14 - Chief Police Officer, Scotland]

An inference which could be taken from the latter comment is that graduates are better suited than non-graduates to the dynamic complexities of contemporary policing, which is one of the factors underpinning the move towards graduate entry only in Sweden and Finland. That said, the subtle difference between this participant’s rationale and that of their peers in Sweden and Finland, is that they reject the notion that the complexity of front-line, operational, first response policing “increasingly dictates that an academic underpinning and perspective is required” (Christopher, 2015, p.388). This accords with the finding from this study that graduate-level learning was probably more appropriate for those undertaking more complex roles in senior promoted posts and specialist roles. They go on to argue that the blend of police officers with different skill sets, different abilities, and different strengths ‘makes’ Police Scotland:

“I think that blend of people with different skills, different abilities, different strengths is actually what makes policing in Scotland. I don’t want a homogenous workforce.” [Participant SCP14 - Chief Police Officer, Scotland]

Whilst what was meant by ‘makes’ was not explained, one inference which might be drawn from this comment is that an ‘homogenous workforce’ comprised entirely of graduate officers, may be unrepresentative of wider society. This may in turn, adversely impact on its operational effectiveness as well as public levels of trust and confidence. Concerns about the impact of a graduate-entry only policy on Scottish policing with regards representativeness were also reflected in the comments of the former Scottish Cabinet Secretary for Justice, Kenny MacAskill, who argued that it could “potentially reduce the diversity of the force and narrow the types of recruits entering the service” (Martin and Wooff, 2020, p.332).

The importance of workforce ‘blend’ can be understood by drawing on the notion of representative bureaucracies. The prevailing point of view within the literature is that a representative bureaucracy within public service organisations more broadly, including the police, enhances public trust, confidence, and cooperation (see for example, (Jackson *et al.*, 2012; Riccucci and Van Ryzin, 2017), and supports the policing by consent model operating within democratic societies (Martin, 2021). It is also argued that a representative bureaucracy provides greater insight into different societal groups, enhancing problem solving and thereby enhancing “better goal achievement to the benefit of all” (Moberg, 2020, p.58) and greater effectiveness within increasingly diverse societies (Hallenberg, 2017). The suggestion, therefore, that limiting entry to graduates might adversely affect the diversity of applicants merits further analysis and discussion, particularly given the increasing diversity (Moberg, 2020, p.58) and social inequalities within many western societies.

7.2.2 Diversity and representativeness

Whilst the issues of social and economic disadvantage, class, and representativeness were not a focus for this study, they emerged as an important theme within the data. For example, with regards the issue of social and economic disadvantage, police officers and police staff at all levels in Scotland were concerned that the introduction of graduate-entry only, might exclude potential recruits from such backgrounds, as this senior Human Resources Manager from Police Scotland exemplifies:

“...so, my initial instinct around making it a prerequisite to be a graduate is that we potentially exclude a huge range of people, particularly from our target audiences. So, we exclude people from socially disadvantaged backgrounds who can’t afford to send their kids to university.”
[Participant SCP16 - Senior Police Staff, Scotland]

Concerns about the adoption of a compulsory, pre-entry, undergraduate degree accredited, initial learning programme deterring applicants, were also found within the data gathered for this study from Sweden. Here, however, they were founded not on socio-economic status and cost, but rather on social class and an associated lack of confidence in undertaking a HE programme. For example, as this senior Human

Resources manager with oversight of the initial police learning programme within the Swedish Police Authority explained, it had deterred some people from what they called ‘working-class’ applicants who viewed HE as ‘scary’:

“...we lose some of them, the working-class, because it’s oh, higher education, scary.” [Participant SWP08 - Senior Police Staff, Sweden]

This echoes the findings of Hallenberg (2017, p.20), who found concerns amongst those involved in initial police learning in England, that requiring all police recruits to complete a pre-entry vocational undergraduate degree, might exclude applicants who were not academically inclined, or who had not had the opportunity to engage with HE. It is widely recognised within the sociology of education literature, that “people from lower social classes tend to have weaker academic achievements” on completion of their secondary school education, than those from ‘higher’ social classes, and are therefore, less likely to engage with HE (Iannelli, Gamoran and Paterson, 2018, p.9). However, it is also widely recognised that decisions whether to enter HE are “more the result of inherited family advantages and disadvantages than the result of true choices”, such as parental or carer educational attainment levels (Iannelli, Gamoran and Paterson, 2018, p.9). Where people from such backgrounds do enter HE, their social background, and weaker academic achievements, “constrain their choice of field of study and institution” (Iannelli, Gamoran and Paterson, 2018, p.9). They do, however, tend to select fields of study and HE institutions which hold a lower risk of failure, whilst at the same time enhancing their prospects within the labour market (Iannelli, Gamoran and Paterson, 2018, p.10).

Post-graduation career choices are a key factor in what subjects students select for higher educational study and this “is especially true for disadvantaged applicants” with 52% of POLAR4 Q1 students (those young people from the twenty percent of geographical areas within the UK with the lowest rates of participation in HE) “choosing their degree subject to pursue a specific career” (UCAS, 2021, p.10). This is contrary to the argument of some scholars that “[i]t defeats the purpose if officers take a degree together in a tailor-made programme, or if the content is shaped to be overly functional for policing” (Lee and Punch, 2004, p.247). Whilst Lee and Punch’s view reflects the traditionally Scottish liberal approach to HE, it is at odds with the

contemporary vocational approach reflected in other public service occupations such as medicine, teaching, and social work. These occupations or professions require those entering to first obtain pre-entry, undergraduate (and in some cases post-graduate) degree qualifications which are vocationally functional. There appears to be broad agreement within the sociology of education literature, that HE programmes with direct pathways to employment are more likely to attract those from less advantaged backgrounds than a more liberal higher education (Scott, 1999, p.3).

However, broader concerns about “exclusionary social closure” (McCann and Granter, 2019, p.226), may not be entirely without foundation as far as social class is concerned. For example, based on the data from the longitudinal RECPOOL study, Moberg (2020, pp.69-70) argued that recruits from working class backgrounds are “over-represented among policing students” in Scotland compared with Nordic countries, where graduate-entry only has increasingly become the norm. If the introduction of degree-entry only admission criteria are changing workforce demographics in this regard, “issues of diversity and academisation could be pulling in different directions” (Moberg, 2020, p.77). However, despite Moberg’s argument that “admission criteria will have implications for the composition of the educational backgrounds of students” (Moberg, 2020, p.71), it is not clear whether there is a correlational or causal relationship between the social background of recruits and the introduction of graduate-entry only policies.

7.2.3 Elitism

This study also found evidence within the data from Scotland and Finland, that degree-entry routes into policing were perceived as elitist, as firstly this ex-member of the Scottish Police Consultative Forum, and secondly this senior police officer in Finland explained:

“...(The) more elitist degree route didn’t sit comfortably with the SNP.”
[Participant SCP20 - Former SPCF Member]

“Since our aim is to have the police force as a picture of the people, it should reflect the people, the police force. Well, most of the people are

not so educated as our police force. How does it fit this?” [Participant FP08 - Senior Police Officer, Finland]

This finding might be interpreted as “a belief that educational qualifications are inextricably linked to social elitism” (Christopher, 2015, p.392). If so, this presentation of policing as an ‘elite’ might result in a “tension between legitimisation of police being drawn from the community” (Green and Gates, 2014, p.770). This might be understood, particularly within the Scottish context, from the “historical and symbolic marker of the police’s historical professional status” (Lumsden, 2017, p.20) derived in part from the so-called Peelian principles. These include a focus on the importance of maintaining public respect and support by maintaining “at all times a relationship with the public that gives reality to the historic tradition that the police are the public and that the public are the police” (Bowling, Reiner, and Sheptycki, 2019, p.103).

Concerns about a closer alignment with HE, particularly the introduction of a compulsory pre-entry degree programme, being perceived as elitist, might also be explained by the existence of the notion amongst policing practitioners that policing is a ‘blue-collar’ occupation. The concept of ‘blue, pink, and white-collar’ occupations is variously utilised within the literature to distinguish different occupations from one another. For example, it has been used to denote different types of work, with ‘white-collar’ workers being defined as those in “clerical and higher non-clerical occupations, including salespersons” (Hanushek *et al.*, 2017, p.31) and ‘blue-collar’ workers as those who are “typically manual workers” (Hanushek *et al.*, 2017, p.31). It has also been used to define occupations based on socio-economic class (Vandecasteele, 2015, p.62), with ‘blue-collar’ often being associated with the background and positive values of working class communities, such as a “strong work ethic, provider orientation, the dignity of all... workers” (Lucas, 2011, p.3), the importance workers place on the dignity of meaningful work (Lips-Wiersma, Wright and Dik, 2016), and levels of academic education (Hanushek *et al.*, 2017, p.31). It has often been argued within the literature that the “manual, technical” nature of street-level police work (McCann and Granter, 2019, p.213), coupled with “the failure of science to establish itself in policing [and] the limited progress to create accredited standards for education

prior to joining the force and throughout the careers of police officers” (Weisburd and Neyroud, 2011, p.10), means that policing still bears many of the hallmarks of ‘blue-collar’ work (McCann and Granter, 2019, p.213). This ‘blue-collar’ notion of police work has been reflected in policing’s tradition of recruiting people predominantly from the “respectable working or lower middle-class backgrounds” (Lee and Punch, 2004, p.242; see also Bowling, Reiner and Sheptycki, 2019, p.176), which has been “a key strategy to ensure a greater likelihood of acceptance from these communities” (Martin, 2021, p.3).

These concerns in Scotland might also be partly explained in the Scottish context by the cultural and political narrative of ‘free’ HE, which contrasts with that in England, for example, where “young people ... have grown up in an era of tuition fees and have clearly internalised the message that HE delivers private benefits, and as a result, individuals are expected to contribute to its costs” (Minty, 2015, p.67). However, concerns that a compulsory, pre-entry undergraduate degree may adversely impact on Police Scotland’s representativeness, or that it may be perceived as elitist, belie the expansion of university access to “a kaleidoscope of students from a gamut of social class, ethnicity, academic and disability backgrounds (Christopher, 2015, p.392). They are at odds with claims that “participation among disadvantaged students has continued to rise” (UCAS, 2021, p.10) and that the introduction of degree apprenticeships like the PCDA in England and Wales “will allow aspiring police officers to join the organisation without a degree but accredit learning to degree level during the training and operational practice” (Tong and Hallenberg, 2018, p.28). Some scholars have argued that rather than the academisation of initial police learning being elitist, “academic education and its recognizable qualifications (cultural capital) improve the police’s status with the public... (social capital), in turn strengthening the claim for pay and resources (economic capital)” (Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2017, p. 276). Despite this, the concerns in Scotland that compulsory, pre-entry degree-models could contribute to pre-entry structural inequalities through “exclusionary social closure” (McCann and Granter, 2019, p.226), should not be ignored. To that end, some mitigating options are briefly discussed.

7.2.4 Addressing Scotland's concerns

It is acknowledged within the sociology of education literature that when selecting HE programmes, individuals from less socio-economically advantaged backgrounds tend to choose those which are integral to specific occupational pathways which have a low risk of unemployment, foreground financial reward over status, and which thereby “compensate for the “risk” of enrolling in higher education” (Iannelli, Gamoran and Paterson, 2018, p.3). Within the UK context this tends to be vocational rather than liberal courses, delivered by post-1992 universities (Iannelli, Gamoran and Paterson, 2018), like Universities of Applied Science found in Finland. Potential pre-entry structural inequalities in policing might, therefore, be mitigated in several ways. For example, for those who were not academically inclined, or who had not had the opportunity to engage with HE (Hallenberg, 2017, p.20) and who, as a result, may not have the requisite qualifications and/or confidence to undertake HE, the introduction of externally accredited qualifications like the Higher National Certificate (HNC) in Policing Studies being offered to secondary school students by Further Education Colleges in Scotland. Access programmes such as the Access to Social Work Diploma in Higher Education (Dip HE) in England and Wales, could also help to redress “social and educational disadvantage” (Jones, 2006, p.495). In England, students on the Access to Social Work Diploma in Higher Education were found to have “a real excitement in the discovery of their ability to become learners... a strong determination” to succeed (Jones, 2006, p.495), and thereby to gain entry to university and to their chosen career (Iannelli, Gamoran and Paterson, 2018, p.10).

For those who might be deterred from undertaking a full-time further or HE programme due to the financial costs, alternatives which enable students to earn and learn could be helpful. For example, nursing in England has a few such access routes including the Nursing Associate route. Nursing Associates are registered but non-graduate members of nursing teams. Whilst providing support with undertaking less complex and challenging roles, this model can also provide a progression route into graduate level nursing. Nursing Associates who wish to train as a registered nurse can have their qualifications accredited against a nursing degree, or a nurse degree

apprenticeship, which will shorten both. Building Programmes are also available which are designed to upskill those who do not have the requisite learning skills and qualifications needed to progress and succeed in higher level learning programmes, including degree level apprenticeships.

Having secured the requisite educational qualifications for entry to compulsory, pre-entry undergraduate degree programmes, there are alternative delivery models which again may be more suited to those who are financially less advantaged. For example, the English Nursing Degree Apprenticeship provides an alternative route to becoming a graduate registered nurse which does not require full-time university study. The programme typically takes four years to complete, but this may be shortened if the apprentice already has prior learning and experience which is accepted under the Accreditation of Prior Experiential Learning (Lester, 2007). The UK apprenticeship levy scheme (Fuller, 2016) can be used by the employer to pay for the cost of training and assessment, up to £27,000, with employers meeting the salary cost of each apprentice and any additional training required. The nurse degree apprenticeship could be an attractive route into nursing for people aspiring to enter nursing who do not have the necessary financial means, or time, to attend a full-time university course. There are parallels between the Nursing Degree Apprenticeship and the PCDA recently introduced in England and Wales (Hough *et al.*, 2018; Belur *et al.*, 2020; Heslop, 2019; Wood, 2020; Watkinson-Miley, Cox and Deshpande, 2022). As with the Nursing Degree Apprenticeship, PCDA student officers are salaried throughout their initial learning period, and do not have to pay tuition fees.

7.3 HE and re-configured professionalism

As this study found, the reorganisation of initial police learning from the traditional training model to one more closely aligned with HE, was perceived by policy makers in Sweden and Finland as providing policing students with the “basis of professional knowledge and skills” (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.783), required to support a reconfiguration of police professionalism based on “knowledge and expertise” (Noordegraaf, 2015, p.191), as well as ‘craft’ knowledge. In particular, it was

perceived as developing epistemic or explicit science-based knowledge; developing critical and reflective practice; developing the capability and inclination to draw on academic research as part of their career-long professional development, and to develop and utilise new knowledge through academic research regarding their professional practice.

7.3.1 Initial learning and professionalism reconfigured

Concepts of how knowledge, skills, and behaviours are learned by entry-level police officers are rapidly changing. The traditional approach to initial police learning tends to comprise traditional short, ‘craft’ skills focused training courses, practice experience, and the passing on of knowledge from experienced officers to less experienced recruits. It also tends to focus on “how to do policing” over “the social context surrounding policing activities” (Charman 2017, p.236), and on compliance with behavioural standards which, it has been argued, result in two different sites of learning: the classroom and ‘real’ police work on the streets (Charman, 2017, p.235; HMIC, 2002). “[L]earning from doing, learning from watching, learning from mistakes, learning from common sense, learning from experience, and learning from adapting” (Charman, 2017, p. 319) whilst undertaking ‘real’ police work, will always be “a crucial component of the learning process for police officers” (Tong and Wood, 2011, p.71), especially for entry-level officers. However, this approach is increasingly being translated into HE across the world (Cordner and Shain, 2011), as policy makers acknowledge that contemporary police professionalism requires knowledge developed not only through a model of learning which develops the ‘art’ and ‘craft’ of policing, but also the ‘science’ (Innes, 2010; Tong and Wood, 2011, p.71).

Whilst the terms ‘art’ and ‘craft’ help to characterise traditional notions of police professionalism, it is argued that the inclusion of ‘science’ helps to characterise a contemporary, reconfigured, expert notion of police professionalism which combines all three (Tong and Bowling, 2006, p.3). The ‘art’ of policing “concerns intuition, instinctive feelings and hunches towards problem solving” which “appears from some perspectives to be a quality that only experience can provide” (Tong and Bowling,

2006, p.3). However, “efforts have been directed for some time at developing police ‘professionalism’ based on a more scientific approach to policing practice” (Tong and Bowling, 2006, pp. 2-3), which in part are being realised through a closer alignment of initial police learning with HE and, in part, through evidence-based (Sherman, 1998) or evidence-informed (Fyfe and Wilson, 2012) practice. However, some scholars have argued that framing the debate about police knowledge “almost exclusively with a police science discourse... is unnecessarily restrictive and exclusionary” (Wood *et al.*, 2018, p.184). A “greater emphasis needs to be placed on the role that officers can play in developing, embedding and applying police knowledge in practice” (Wood *et al.*, 2018, p.184). The academised initial police learning programmes in Sweden and Finland, as this study has shown, aspire to realise these outcomes by developing the knowledge and skills of policing students with regards critical and reflective practice, and basic academic research skills, coupled with encouragement to research their own professional practice and that of their organisations.

However, whilst a closer alignment between initial police learning and HE may help to develop knowledgeable police officers, contemporary police professionalism requires officers to have “an acute sense of context” (Wood *et al.*, 2018, p.184) and to apply a blend of ‘art’, ‘craft’ and ‘science’ when formulating decisions and taking action. For example, “embedding understandings of social sciences and the police role in society is useful knowledge beyond a focus simply on rational, technical, and narrowly defined what works agendas” (Martin, 2021, p.5). As argued in chapter 5, the concept of practical wisdom or ‘phronesis’ encapsulates the application of intellectually, practically, and ethically motivated deliberations in the application of expert decision-making and actions (Breier and Ralphs, 2009, p.485) with the aim of doing the right thing by clients and society (see also Evetts, 2006; Noordegraaf 2020, p.207). They need to know not only what to do and how to do it, but why (Hough and Stanko, 2019). This requires, it is argued, not only a deeper knowledge and understanding of the ‘science’ of policing, but also officers who have the capacity and capability to think beyond hierarchical and procedural constraints to ‘do the right thing’ in any given set of circumstances. Some scholars have argued that to avoid a

“uniformity and conformity” of thought within policing, “policing needs to be enriched with critical, enquiring and challenging minds” for which a “sound university education still provides the best basis” (Lee and Punch, 2004, p. 248). The findings from this study show that in Sweden and Finland, these aspirations underpin the closer alignment of initial police learning with HE which, in the case of Finland, recently culminated in the introduction of a compulsory, pre-entry undergraduate degree programme.

The policy aspirations of a closer alignment with HE were generally perceived within these two countries, albeit more so amongst academics than police officers and policing students in Sweden, to be providing policing students not only with a foundation upon which to meet immediate post-graduation practice needs, but also the capacity and capability to source, critically analyse and utilise academic theoretical knowledge to support self-motivated career-long learning and professional development. Indeed, some trait-based scholars have argued that a commitment to ongoing professional development and life-long learning is a defining characteristic of profession (Green and Gates, 2014). Others have argued that career-long learning and development “are critical to ensure the police are equipped to deal with the changing dynamics of complex societies” (Martin, 2021, p.5; see also Blakemore and Simpson, 2010). In making the European education area a reality, the European Commission is focused on a “lifelong learning perspective” (Chirop, 2021, p.2).

7.3.2 Evidence-based practice

One way to develop ‘knowing police officers’ who embed and apply abstract, theoretical knowledge within their professional practice, is through evidence-based policing (Sherman, 1998; Weisburd and Neyroud, 2011). Police practitioners either utilise scientific knowledge to inform practice or generate new knowledge themselves through an examination of their own practice (Green and Gates, 2014), thereby becoming “architects of police knowledge” (Wood *et. al.*, 2018, p.176). As discussed in chapter 5, senior police officers and academics in Sweden and Finland believed there to be a positive correlation between the development of policing student’s

knowledge and understanding of academic research, and their willingness to not only incorporate it into their practice, but also to develop new research concerning their practice, thereby strengthening the evidence base for policing. This, it is argued, is one of the pillars upon which police professionalism can adapt from the “traditional custom and practice associated with bureaucratic, command-based... discipline and servitude” (McCann and Granter, 2019, p.241), to a reconfigured, knowledge-based, hybrid concept of police professionalism (Noordegraaf, 2015).

However, policing needs to guard against replacing bureaucratic notions of professionalism with a technocratic, science-based notion of professionalism, thereby once again becoming distant from the priorities of the public and elected politicians, as it did in the USA during the 1980s. This, coupled with centralisation, rationalisation, and bureaucratisation was “blamed for making police departments... insular, arrogant, resistant to outside criticism, and – perhaps most disastrous of all – feckless in responding to the social ferment of the 1960s and 1970s” (Sklansky, 2011, p.5). Hence, it is argued, the importance of a reconfigured notion of professionalism which encapsulates ethical, values-based, ‘evidence-informed’ decision-making (Fyfe and Wilson, 2012; Aston, Murray and O’Neill, 2021; Hunter, May and Hough, 2019; Hunter and May, 2020), which foregrounds ‘doing the right thing’ within the situated social and cultural context, both for the individual and for wider society, over ‘doing it the right way’, strictly in accordance with “evidence-based protocols developed out of scientific research” (McCann and Granter, 2019, p.214).

Whilst undergraduate degree-level education in Sweden and Finland requires policing students to develop a basic knowledge and understanding of academic research to complete a research-based dissertation, the extent to which this enhanced the receptivity of police officers to academic research and the extent to which it was utilised within practice, was beyond the scope of this study. Despite evidence-based policing being an area of on-going debate and research (see for example, Lum *et.al.*, 2012; Goode and Lumsden, 2018; Hunter, May and Hough, 2019; Hunter and May, 2020; Martin, 2021), it has been argued that “the level of officer education can be instrumental in ensuring openness to new ideas such as EBP [Evidence Based

Policing]” (Kalyal, 2020, p.620). If so, this would support the belief expressed by senior police officers and academics in Sweden and Finland that a pre-entry, undergraduate degree-level initial learning programme which encapsulates the development of academic research skills, will enhance not only career-long learning and critical thinking, but also contribute to the development of a unique corpus of policing knowledge. As Martin (2021, p.2) highlighted, within the context of policing in England and Wales, the trait-based model of profession which has been adopted places “a strong emphasis on the need to adopt evidence-based policing”, and also appears to have been, in part, a driver of academisation in Sweden and Finland.

However, the appropriateness of developing academic research knowledge amongst entry-level officers, particularly those who are ‘generalists’, requires, some scholars argue, “more thought” (Bryant *et al.*, 2014, p.390), suggesting that this learning might be more appropriate for officers in specialist or promoted roles. Apart from developing the requisite knowledge and skills to utilise epistemic knowledge to undertake research on policing practice, “other factors such as leadership support as well as organizational culture and climate also affect openness to EBP” (Kalyal, 2020, p.620). Whilst the EBP orthodoxy “underestimates the challenges of applying knowledge within culturally mediated police practice” (Wood *et al.*, 2018, p.173), there was an enthusiasm amongst the senior police leaders from Sweden and Finland who took part in this study, for early-career officers to develop a professionalism founded in part, on science-based expertise as a means by which to develop a unique corpus of policing knowledge, the extent to which these intended policy outcomes are actually being realised may be worthy of future study.

7.4 Conclusion

The aim of this chapter was to outline and analyse the findings from this study concerning the research question: what factors explain the divergence between ‘policy network actors’ perceptions within the case study countries on the impact, or potential impact, of academic education on the professionalisation of police recruits and policing students? It has shown that perceptions regarding the role of HE within initial

police learning broadly differed between Scotland on the one hand, and Sweden and Finland on the other. It revealed that whilst those within Police Scotland and those in oversight and governance roles, generally acknowledged HE and tertiary qualifications as forms of self-fulfilment, they were also perceived as having little organisational legitimacy (Cockcroft and Hallenberg 2017; Williams, Norman, and Rowe, 2019). However, some police officers did acknowledge that graduates were well suited to the complexity of contemporary policing, and that tertiary education could be relevant for those in senior and/or specialist roles. It was also highlighted that police officers in Scotland, at all levels, were culturally opposed to policing becoming graduate-entry only. This was founded, in part, on a concern that this would deter applicants from less socially or economically advantaged backgrounds, and thereby adversely affect Police Scotland's representativeness and acceptance from those communities (Martin, 2021). Alternative approaches such as the Nursing Degree Apprenticeship and the Police Degree Apprenticeship in England and Wales which could help to mitigate these concerns were also briefly explored.

Participants in Sweden and Finland on the other hand, generally perceived undergraduate degree-level education as enhancing policing students' professionalism in several ways: deepening knowledge and understanding of their role; enhancing the capability for, and disposition towards, lifelong learning; enhancing policing's capability to develop a unique corpus of knowledge; cultivating critical, analytical thinking and reflective practice; enhancing receptivity to evidence-informed practice; developing the capability to contribute towards the development of a unique corpus of knowledge; and lifelong career flexibility. However, it also shown that whilst chief police officers, academics, and some policing students in Sweden and Finland perceived degree accreditation as a source of social, cultural, and economic capital, on the whole policing students did not. This finding challenges the notion that degree accreditation of initial police learning programmes is a motivating factor for people who wish to join policing.

Finally, this chapter argued that whilst the academisation of initial police learning programmes could help to move policing beyond the traditional notions of police

professionalism which tend to rely on the ‘art’ and ‘craft’ of policing, to one which includes a more scientific approach to policing, it should not be constrained by the unnecessarily restrictive and exclusionary framing of Evidence Based Policing. Rather it is argued that socially and culturally mediated police practice requires an acknowledgement that “what counts as effective policing is more “art” or “craft” than “science” (Innes, 2010, p.32), particularly given the rapidly changing and increasingly complex, multi-problem realities of contemporary policing and the increasing demand for ethical policing. Hence, it is argued, the importance of a reconfigured notion of professionalism which encapsulates ethical, values-based, ‘evidence-informed’ decision-making (Fyfe and Wilson, 2012; Bristow, Carter and Martin, 2015; Aston, Murray and O’Neill, 2021), which foregrounds ‘doing the right thing’ within the situated social and cultural context, both for the individual and for wider society, over ‘doing it the right way’, strictly in accordance with “evidence-based protocols developed out of scientific research” (McCann and Granter, p.214).

Chapter 8: Discussion

Introduction

This chapter explores the key themes developed within the findings chapters through the lenses of meaning, context, and process (Maxwell, 2020). Comprising five sections, the first (section 8.1) briefly presents Maxwell's (2020) typology of meaning, context, and process which is used in this chapter to unpack and explain the findings from this thesis within the broader context of police professionalisation through Higher Education. Section 8.2 then draws on this typology to discuss the tendency of academics, and some senior police officers, to draw on the trait-based paradigm, particularly the presence or absence of graduate-entry only for new entrants, which is contrasted with the tendency of police officers to draw on a sense of vocation. It then moves on to discuss the significance of meaning with regards notions of police professionalism, highlighting ethical decision-making and action which is "right or good" (DeMartino, 2019, p.9) which was foregrounded as a key indicator of professionalism. It explores how what was considered 'right or good' by police differed between the case study countries, with greater importance being attached to a deontological or rules-based approach in Finland, compared with Scotland and Sweden. The argument is made that within an increasingly complex policing environment, a deontological approach may not always be the right or good thing to do. Therefore, a reconfigured, hybrid notion of professionalism (Noordegraaf, 2016), could benefit from the utilisation of 'practical wisdom' (phronesis) which blends the 'art', 'craft', and 'science' of policing (Innes, 2010; Wood, *et.al.*, 2018).

Section 8.3 discusses the multi-directional influence of context on agenda setting, policy formulation, and the extent to which intended policy outcomes were being realised. It begins in section 8.3.1 by discussing the dichotomy in Scotland between the raising of societal academic attainment levels, including within public service occupations, but not in respect of policing. It then moves on in section 8.3.2 to discuss the extent to which political context influenced not only ownership and control of policy formulation and its implementation, but also the extent to which 'hot' or 'cold'

political climates foregrounded political ideology over the vocational needs of policing. In the next sub-section (8.3.3) the interplay between organisational structures, leadership cultures, the complexity of junior first response constables' roles, and the extent to which a lengthy period of HE was perceived as being required is discussed. Sub-section 8.3.4 discusses the extent to which cultural and epistemological alignments and schisms within and between the 'three worlds thinking' of politics, academia, and policing influenced change. Namely, whether initial police learning models remained 'frozen' (Cummings, Bridgman and Brown, 2016) in a 'closed-circuit' (Felts and Dinca, 2012), 'traditional' model as in Scotland, or became 'unfrozen' (Cummings, Bridgman and Brown, 2016) and moved towards an open, university-based model as in Sweden and Finland.

Section 8.4 discusses how fundamental relational power and the extent of interaction between the 'three worlds' of politics, academia, and policing were to the process of shaping initial police learning, particularly the extent to which it was aligned with HE. In doing so, it focuses on the extent to which these spaces were "sites of struggle between individuals or institutions competing for capital" (Heslop and White, 2011, p.4), some more so than others. It is argued that in Sweden an attempt should be made to rebalance the power relationship to help ensure that professional policing practitioners have an appropriate degree of influence in shaping the needs of their profession. It is further argued that initial police learning in Scotland would benefit from developing a closer relationship with HE, whilst being mindful of the unintended consequences which might arise from empowering academia too much.

Finally, section 8.5 reflects on the broader implications concerning the cultural and structural challenges of police professionalisation through HE, by exploring how the findings from this study might be drawn upon to develop an alternative approach to the ongoing professionalisation of policing in Scotland. It is argued, that in those political, social, cultural, and structural contexts where ongoing police professionalisation through the academisation of initial police learning is precluded or hindered, the targeted use of micro-credentials involving senior leaders and those in specialist roles, is more likely to lead to epistemic knowledge being acknowledged

internally and externally as a source of cultural capital, than the academisation of initial police learning.

8.1 The importance of meaning, context, and process

Maxwell (2020) presents a typology of meaning, context, and process, which is used in this chapter to unpack and explain the findings from this thesis within the broader context of police professionalisation through HE. Understanding how people make sense of and react to policies, understanding the interplay between differing contexts and their influence on policy formulation and implementation, and understanding “the processes through which policies achieve their results... are critical for developing policies that actually achieve their goals, and avoid unintended and damaging consequences” (Maxwell, 2020, p.177). This can be summarised “in three statements about what matters in planning and evaluating such policies and programs: that meaning matters, context matters, and process matters” (Maxwell, 2020, p.181).

8.2 Meaning

A primary goal of this interpretative study has been to understand “the meaning that a particular policy or program has, both for those creating it or implementing [policy], and for those affected by it... people’s beliefs, values, theories, understandings, and other “mental phenomena” (Maxwell, 2020, p.181). In providing the kind of rich, ‘thick’ data often lacking within quantitative approaches, it has provided an understanding of the “complexity and diversity of people’s views” (Maxwell, 2020, p.181) which influence how they make sense of, and react to, the approaches to initial police learning programmes in their respective countries. Given that associated policies and their implementation were found by this study to have been based largely on professional judgement, it has been important to understand the socially and culturally constructed meaning which participants attached to notions of policing as a profession, police professionalism, and police professionalisation.

8.2.1 Policing as a profession

The data gathered for this study showed that in each of the case study countries it was important to participants that policing be regarded as a profession, or that it should aspire to be regarded as a profession. However, when it came to explaining why policing could or could not be regarded as a profession, perceptual differences emerged. Academics tended to draw on the trait-based paradigm, arguing that, in the absence of graduate-entry only, policing might at best be defined as a semi-profession or an emerging profession. Police officers on the other hand, generally regarded policing as a profession, irrespective of academic entry requirements. For them policing as a profession generally meant a sense of vocation, commitment to a way of life, more than ‘just a job’. That said, policing’s social status also had meaning for them. In positioning policing below that of the medical profession (medical doctors) and lawyers, police officers drew on the notion that there is a continuum of professions, a concept often associated with the trait-based paradigm. In explaining why, they attached meaning to educational attainment levels and expertise.

Based on the findings from this study, and (mis)appropriating Noordegraaf’s (2016) concept of hybrid-professionalism, it is argued that the concept of policing as a profession was hybrid, drawing on a combination of trait-based and philosophical paradigms.

8.2.2 Police professionalism

Meaning was also found to be important with regards police professionalism. Participants from each of the case study countries, frequently foregrounded ethical decision-making and action which is “right or good” (DeMartino, 2019, p.9) as a key indicator of professionalism. That said, doing the right thing, even if that meant not doing it the right way, was more prevalent amongst police officers in Scotland than those in Finland, where compliance with the law was foregrounded.

‘Sound’ decision-making frequently meant “the ability to perceive a situation, to have the appropriate feelings or desires about it, to deliberate about what was appropriate in these circumstances, and to act” (Schwartz and Sharpe, 2010, p.5). In each of the case study countries, perceiving a situation appropriately, frequently meant using ‘craft’ knowledge and experiential knowledge developed both from life in general, and from being a police officer. ‘Craft’ based knowledge developed through experience still prevailed as a source of cultural capital, but there were indications in Sweden and Finland that epistemic or ‘science’ based knowledge was viewed as an important part of developing professional expertise, and for developing a unique corpus of knowledge, so that policing was based on more than experience. However, in Scotland, policing participants rarely mentioned epistemic knowledge as being helpful.

Adopting a deontological, or “duty or rules approach” (Hurteau and Gagnon, 2022, p.182) might “not offer an acceptable solution to a complex problem” (Hurteau and Gagnon, 2022, p.186). This thesis argues that sound, ethical decision making within the increasingly complex and rapidly changing environments within which policing is operating, could be enhanced by the application of ‘practical wisdom’ (phronesis). Whilst it is a “slippery concept” (Kinsella and Pitman, 2012, p.2), the Aristotelian concept of ‘phronesis’, encapsulates conscious, ethical decision making which is most likely to produce ‘good’ outcomes. Interpretations consistently suggest that conscious decision making which is most likely to produce ‘good’ outcomes, is based in part, on reasoned or scientific knowledge (episteme) which can be “validated by offering standardized methods to guarantee predictable and reliable results” (Hurteau and Gagnon, 2022, p.183). Interpretations of phronesis, also consistently comprise “some kind of moral knowledge or conscience... which allows us to do and act good in a given situation, based on our understanding of how to live well overall” (Weiss, 2018, p.13).

Whilst this study found that ethical decision making was important to participants within each of the case study countries, the role of epistemic knowledge was perceived differently by police officers in Scotland compared with those in Sweden and Finland.

In Scotland it was generally perceived as having no vocational relevance to junior, front-line, response constables. Therefore, it was not included in the initial police learning programme, which instead foregrounded ‘craft’ knowledge developed through experiential learning. In Sweden and Finland on the other hand, this study found that the closer alignment of initial police learning with HE, supported the development of a notion of professionalism which blended the ‘art’, ‘craft’ and ‘science’ of policing (Wood, *et.al.*, 2018, p.176). This notion of professionalism is appropriate within contemporary policing, not only considering the increasing complexity of the operational environment, but also the necessity of ensuring that societal norms and values are upheld, and that professional work is trusted and legitimated” (Noordegraaf, 2016, p.784).

8.2.3 Police professionalisation through higher education

The meaning attached to police professionalisation through HE, specifically the academisation of initial police learning, was of significance for some, but not for others. The academisation of initial police learning was perceived by policy makers in Sweden and Finland as a cornerstone of police professionalisation. However, this was not the case in Scotland, where professionalisation through HE was generally viewed as being of little to no relevance to professional practice. Policing participants in Scotland frequently questioned the validity of claims that HE enhanced individual professionalism, a view echoed by scholars such as Paterson (2011) and Brown (2020). Several police officers in Scotland, and those in oversight and governance roles, differentiated between an individual’s academic achievements and their professional identity; they were perceived as mutually exclusive. The suggestion that policing should be graduate-entry only ran counter to police officers being ordinary citizens in uniform, with ‘ordinary’ citizens frequently being equated to the respectable ‘blue-collar’ working classes. Attempts to raise the status of policing in England and Wales to that of a profession, based on the trait-based notion of graduate-entry only, were derided. As one chief officer put it, it was a “conceit” and indicative of English and Welsh policing’s “inferiority complex”. The cultural and epistemological schism in this regard between Police Scotland, other emerging

professions, and policing in other north-western European countries, was considerable. Despite this, the same senior officer who described the PEQF as a ‘conceit’ also welcomed graduate entrants for the different worldviews they brought into Police Scotland, and their ability to deal with complexity. These apparent contradictions of meaning may be indicative of deeply held cultural myths concerning police professionalism and professionalisation through the academisation of initial police learning, particularly graduate-entry only.

The academisation of initial police learning was also viewed as a risk to the representativeness of policing, more so in Scotland than in Sweden and Finland. There were concerns in Scotland that, due to financial constraints, applicants from disadvantaged and ‘blue-collar’ working-class backgrounds would be less likely than those from more affluent, ‘white-collar’ middle-class backgrounds to undertake lengthy, pre-entry, degree accredited, learning. Indeed, Moberg (2020, pp.69-70) argued that the “classical understanding of the police force as primarily recruiting from the working class is no longer valid in Nordic countries”, whereas in Scotland “the working class is still overrepresented among police students”. However, Fekjær (2014) previously found that the class background of policing students in Sweden and Norway had little influence on their choice of career, despite the academisation of initial police learning. This might, in part, be explained by the different funding arrangements in Nordic countries. For example, in Sweden and Finland, policing students regardless of background or financial means, are supported by a combination of free HE, state grants, and loans which are increased if students are older and/or have worked previously. This is regardless of whether they are already graduates. Concerns were also expressed by some senior police officers in each of the case study countries that were all police officers to be graduates, policing might be viewed by the public as elitist. Whilst beyond the scope of this study, policing’s ability to build and maintain effective, trusting relationships within the increasingly diverse communities they serve, is fundamental to policing by consent. Policing in democratic countries cannot be “too much of a special institution” (Banton, 1964, p.262) separated from society. Given the lacuna within the extant literature with regards the relationship between police professionalisation through HE, pre-entry structural inequalities,

representativeness, and public trust and confidence, it is argued that addressing this important knowledge gap should be a focus for future research.

In contrast to Scotland, for senior police officers and the police unions in Sweden, and to a lesser degree in Finland, academisation not only meant improved officer competence, but also enhanced social, political, and economic capital for policing. However, for policing students in Sweden and Finland, academisation, including degree accreditation, generally had little meaning as respects attracting them into policing or policing's social status. However, there was evidence that policing students in Finland, and some senior officers, welcomed the enhanced career flexibility degree accreditation provided new entrants, who viewed the ability for graduates to move from policing to other roles within the security sector positively.

Whilst some of the findings from this study contradict some of the theoretical benefits espoused by policing scholars which might be derived from degree entry only, they should not be misunderstood as dismissing the benefits of relevant epistemic knowledge, particularly that which enhances 'practical wisdom'. As some scholars have argued, professional practice "needs to be recognized as a blend of art, science, craft, and humanity" (Kinsella and Pitman, 2012, p.78) including within contemporary policing (Tong and Bowling, 2006; Willis and Mastrofski, 2018). This thesis argues that whilst it is "difficult to reconcile HE as the platform through which initial training is delivered" (Cockcroft and Hallenberg, 2021, p.15) in all social, cultural, and political contexts, initial police learning should encapsulate vocationally relevant epistemic knowledge which enhances the application of 'practical wisdom' in those situations which do not lend themselves to a deontological, or "duty or rules approach" (Hurteau and Gagnon, 2022, p.182).

Finally, as well as a developing trend towards the academisation of initial police learning, including graduate-entry only within many north-western European countries, there is also an increasing expectation that senior officers should be qualified at Master's degree level. This is being echoed in England and Wales, which may have future implications for those in Scotland applying for senior roles in either

country, or for the UK-wide chief police officer selection process. Whilst, according to senior police officers at the Scottish Police College, about 40% of Police Scotland's recruits in recent years have been graduates, thereby providing them with an articulation route into Master's degree level learning, this might not be the case for non-graduate officers. In effect, it is argued, post-structural inequalities might arise both within Police Scotland and within UK policing more widely, which results in non-graduate officers being disadvantaged as regards progression into senior leadership or specialist roles.

8.3 Context

This study has also shown that context is influential. It has revealed several social, political, and organisational features within each of the case study countries which influenced, in a multi-directional way, agenda setting, policy formulation and the extent to which intended policy outcomes were being realised.

8.3.1 Society

In each of the case study countries, strategic Governmental responses to increasing social, economic, and cultural complexity has included the raising of societal academic attainment levels, with HE's role to "enable society to make progress through an understanding of itself and its world: in short, to sustain a learning society" (Dearing, 1997, p.72). This raising of academic attainment levels more generally within society, has also been reflected within public service occupations in each of the case study countries. Over the last few decades, nursing, teaching, social work, and paramedicine for example, have become graduate-entry only occupations or professions, requiring new entrants to complete compulsory, pre-entry, vocationally focused, undergraduate degrees. With regards policing, this development has been mirrored in both Sweden (albeit partly) and in Finland. With general levels of education rising across Scottish society, maintaining, or improving policing's future social, economic, and political capital, may require Scottish policing to move in the same direction. However, as this study revealed, degree accreditation was not a factor

that attracted students to policing in Finland, nor would it have in Sweden. Indeed, the argument that degree-accreditation helps to attract high-quality, well-educated entrants is further weakened by the number of graduates joining Police Scotland. This is an important finding and potentially has significant implications for police professionalisation, particularly those approaches which foreground degree entry only.

8.3.2 Politics

Political context influenced not only the positionality of ownership and control over initial police learning within and between the ‘three worlds’ of national Governments, academia, and policing, but also whether the political climate was ‘hot’ or ‘cold’. Based on the findings from this study, it is argued that the greater the political control over policy formulation and its operationalisation, particularly within a ‘hot’ political climate (Murray and Harkin, 2017), the greater the chance that political ideological needs will be foregrounded over the vocational needs of policing. This was evident in Sweden, where opposing political ideologies had resulted in the academisation of initial police learning becoming something of a political ‘football’. When in power, the Social Democratic Party pushed policy towards academisation, whilst the Conservative parties, when in power, hindered further progress along the academisation pathway. Similarly, the greater academia’s ownership and control, the greater the likelihood that the accreditation needs of academia will be foregrounded over the vocational needs of policing, as in Sweden. Finally, it is also argued that the greater the ownership and control by policing, the more likely the vocational needs of policing will be foregrounded over those of national Governments and academia. For example, in Scotland the eleven-week initial police learning programme was revised in 2019 by Police Scotland, without any consultation with academia, and became increasingly focused on its traditional ‘craft’ based approach, reducing theoretical knowledge to that required to undertake the twenty-one-month practice-based phase.

In Finland, whilst national Governments played a more benign role within a much cooler political climate, political support from the national Government and the

Finnish Parliament was critical. Whilst initial political resistance by one ruling party delayed support for degree accreditation by a few years, and might therefore, be said to have been subjected to the influence of political ideology, as in Sweden, policy was driven by the police with the support of academia, and not the other way around as in Sweden.

8.3.3 Organisational structure and leadership culture

This study found that structural and leadership responses to the rapidly changing and increasingly complex operating environments influenced the extent to which initial police learning was aligned with HE. Several senior police officers in Scotland expressed the view that the ‘routine’ role of junior first responders did not require epistemic knowledge, although it was perceived by both senior officers and recruits as having greater relevance for specialist and senior officers. This was reflected in the approach to initial police learning in Scotland, where the focus of the eleven-week ITC was on providing recruits with sufficient knowledge and skills to either deal with ‘routine’ tasks, or in more complex non-routine cases, to preserve and gather initial evidence before handing over subsequent investigations to specialist officers and staff.

The two and a half year, university-based, undergraduate degree level initial police learning programme in Sweden seemed at odds with the organisational structures which, as in Scotland, were more horizontally and vertically fragmented than in Finland. However, this study did find that transformational senior police officers embraced the epistemic knowledge and critical thinking skills of junior officers who had graduated from the initial police learning programme, particularly during slower-time, collective team planning. There was also a recognition that in fast paced, high risk situations, a transactional, hierarchical leadership approach was still required, which was acknowledged by policing students who participated in this study. Generalist first responders in Finland on the other hand, working within an organisation with few specialist departments and a leaner, more distributed leadership culture, are expected to fully utilise the learning from their three-year, Bachelor’s degree accredited initial learning programme. This is especially so for those officers

working in remote rural areas where the nearest police officers are hundreds of kilometres away.

8.3.4 Cultural alignments and schisms

This study has revealed that cultural alignments and schisms influenced initial police learning within the case study countries and associated processes of change. In Scotland, there was a high degree of cultural alignment or congruence between the two worlds thinking of policing and politics, although not with academia. When there is congruence between various aspects of an organisation's culture, "the dominant characteristics all tend to emphasize the same set of cultural values" (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p.84), thereby acting as a "glue that holds the organization together... and reinforces continuity and consistency" (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p.166), making change challenging. As revealed by this study, the espoused values, and underlying assumptions within Police Scotland (Schein, 2017) which emphasised an organisational climate of rational efficiency and specialisation were strongly aligned. This, it is argued, helps to understand why the initial police learning has remained fundamentally unchanged for decades, retaining its 'craft' based approach, and why the lack of 'appetite' (Martin and Wooff, 2020) for a degree entry pathway into policing, let alone graduate-entry only, is likely to be resisted unless there is a "realization and acceptance that the old ways need to change, and new ones learned" (Schein, 2017, pp.325-326).

The organisational culture within Police Scotland also emphasised stability and risk aversity, through a hierarchical system of control and direction, over a high degree of flexibility and individuality (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p.76), which manifested itself in a risk averse culture which had marginalised and de-professionalised the role of a junior, front-line, operational response officer. As the Chief Constable explained at the SIPR International Conference in May 2022, allowing these officers greater adhocacy would be "an abdication of leadership". Such congruent cultures

although not a prerequisite for success, are more typical of high-performing organizations than incongruent cultures...sharing some of

the same assumptions simply eliminates many of the complications, disconnects, and obstacles that can get in the way of effective performance (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p.85).

Police Scotland is, by the many different measures in which it is evaluated, a high-performing organisation, and until recently there have been no indications of a recognition that the old ways concerning initial police learning need to change. However, in March 2022, the Chair of the Scottish Police Federation publicly stated at a conference, that the eleven-week initial training course should be lengthened and broadened. Whilst he did not go into any detail as to what he meant by lengthened and broadened, he did express the view that on completion of ITC, police recruits should be ‘the complete package’. The findings from this study present an opportunity to inform and influence policy formulation not only within the Scottish Police Federation, but also more widely within Police Scotland (at the time of writing in 2022, the service is undertaking a strategic review of training delivery, which this study has helped to inform), the SPA, and HMICS. The latter will be undertaking a review of initial police learning within the next few years and has requested that the findings from this study be shared with them at that time.

In Finland, the unfreezing, change, and re-freezing (Cummings, Bridgman and Brown, 2016) of initial police learning which has resulted in the current three-year, degree-accredited programme, can be traced back to the post-World War Two era, when policing did not have the general population’s support. There was a realisation and acceptance then, that the old ways of policing and how it recruited and developed new entrants needed to change. In the intervening years initial police learning has undergone gradual unfreezing, change, and re-freezing in response to changes in the social, cultural, and political contexts (Jansson *et al.*, 2018). The most recent, following a realisation that the rapidly changing and increasingly complex policing environment required the development of new knowledge and skills amongst junior, front line response officers. It was argued that the programme needed to be lengthened to three-years to accommodate the additional, undergraduate degree *level* learning which policing students required. A degree was not seen as the answer to the ongoing professionalisation of new entrants, but rather a ‘nice-to-have’ consequence of the

reform. Despite being a ‘top-down’ change process, the practical focus of the programme (Terpstra and Schaap, 2021) which had been developed largely by policing with the support of academia, had, it is argued, played a significant role in a greater degree of cultural congruence within the police service in Finland, than was the case in Sweden.

In Sweden, cultural incongruence has, as it often does, led “to differences in perspectives, differences in goals, and differences in strategies within the organization” (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p.85). As this study has revealed, whilst there was an acceptance amongst some politicians, those in academia, and some senior police officers that changes in the external political, social, and cultural contexts within Sweden, required policing to move towards becoming a profession through becoming graduate-entry only, there was also cultural incongruence as respects other politicians and particularly from policing recruits, which was inhibiting the academisation process. Whilst proponents of the academisation pathway in Sweden might argue that one of the drivers for academisation is to address policing’s shortcomings, research has consistently demonstrated that:

...[m]ost changes attempted in organizations... do not succeed because of cultural incompatibility (Cameron and Quinn, 2011, p.163)

Given this, the suggestion by many proponents of academisation is that policing:

...will have to make changes to both management practices and policies if they are to create a decision-making milieu that facilitates graduate officers in the use of their critical thinking skills and discretion in 21st century policing (McCanney, Taylor and Bates, 2022, p.327).

However, this belies the complexities involved in such change. Police occupational cultures can undermine reform efforts if they are not modified sufficiently to view reform as legitimate (Aston, Murray and O’Neill, 2021, p.41). Therefore, unless political and cultural schisms in Sweden are resolved, it is argued that the partly unfrozen change process will remain in its current unfrozen, incomplete state. Having the level of disaffection with the initial police learning programme amongst policing students, as revealed by this study, is clearly unhelpful and could adversely affect the

attraction and retention of new entrants. At the heart of their disaffection is a perception that the programme foregrounds the needs of academia over those of policing which, it is argued, should be acknowledged, and addressed. This disaffection may in large part be attributable to the ‘general exam’ quality assurance criteria which encapsulate a more academic, theoretical set of assessment measures, than those for the designated professional University programmes for the likes of teaching and nursing, which are assessed as vocational qualifications. Changing these assessment criteria would require legislative change. This was recommended in the 2016 Governmental Working Party report on police basic education but was not realised. This recommendation it is argued, should be reconsidered and enacted.

Consequently, as this chapter has shown, context matters, particularly the extent to which there are cultural alignments and schisms within and between the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of politics, academia, and policing, and is important in the dynamics of change. The extent to which academisation of initial police learning is accepted as being legitimate and necessary requires cultural congruence, not only between the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing, but crucially between policy makers and those subjected to top-down reform. Without it change will either be unlikely, as in the case of Scotland, or messy as in the case of Sweden. Socially, culturally, and politically constructed understandings concerning policing as a profession, the knowledge required, and how that should be acquired and developed, all influenced the extent to which there was congruence or incongruence. These are important factors which those advocating for police professionalisation through the academisation of initial police learning would do well to consider. As the management consultant Peter Drucker has been credited with arguing, ‘culture eats strategy for breakfast’ when explaining “how plans on paper matter less than ‘how things get done’ in actual practice” (Whitzman, 2016). This has important implications not only for understanding the findings from this study, but also for cross-national transferability. These variable context-dependencies are also important in so far as they “support or impede the goals of the policy, and how these interact with each other and with the policy to shape its outcomes” (Maxwell, 2020, p.182).

8.4 Process

In unpacking the interactions between the three-worlds thinking of politics, academia, and policing, this study has revealed that relational power and the extent of interaction, were fundamental in shaping initial police learning, particularly the extent to which it was aligned with HE.

8.4.1 Relational power and policy formulation

In Scotland and Finland, national Governments were comparatively passive, largely approving, or rejecting policy reforms driven primarily by the police. That said, progress along the policy pathway in Finland, had initially been hindered by an epistemological misalignment between the police and academia on the one hand, and the national Government on the other. Only once there was a change of Government which led to alignment of ‘three-worlds thinking’, was the degree accreditation realised. In Sweden on the other hand, national Governments dominated policy formulation, which was pushed and pulled in contradictory directions by diametrically opposed political ideologies. If on-going police professionalisation is to reflect other professions, such as medicine and the legal profession, Swedish Governments should facilitate greater professional independence, including the setting of entry criteria and the professional development of its members. This argument should not be viewed as an attempt to undermine the role of elected representatives with regards policing, but rather an attempt to rebalance the power relationship to help ensure that professional policing practitioners have an appropriate degree of influence in shaping the needs of their profession.

Academia’s relational power within the policy formulation process is also important. Too little influence, as in Scotland, had contributed to an initial learning programme which had no academic theoretical content. It was focused primarily on developing a comparatively basic level of ‘craft’ knowledge primarily through experiential, on-the-job learning. Whilst initial police learning in Scotland could, subject to the existing cultural and structural barriers being removed, benefit from developing a closer

relationship with HE to facilitate the inclusion of vocationally relevant epistemic knowledge, together with critical and reflective thinking, the findings from Sweden highlight the unintended consequences which might arise from empowering academia too much.

The extent to which policing had too much or too little power within the policy formulation process was also influential. The passive role of the Scottish Government, policing oversight and governance bodies, and the exclusion of academia, had resulted in a monolithic process in which Police Scotland effectively had a monopoly over agenda setting, policy formulation and its implementation. Policing's world view remained largely unchallenged, with the result that the artisan, 'craft' based approach to initial police learning had remained fundamentally unchanged since the 1960s. Consequently, this inertia has resulted in the early career development of new entrants becoming increasingly divergent from that in other north-western European countries, and indeed within the UK, not only with regards policing, but also other emerging professions such as nursing, teaching, and paramedicine. Conversely, the consequences of policing having too little power within the policy formulation process may, as in Sweden, result in the vocational needs of policing being subsumed by the political ideological needs of national Governments and/or the academic assessment needs of academia. This may result in a cultural and epistemological schism which hinders realisation of the intended policy outcomes.

8.4.2 Extent of interaction

The monolithic approach to policy formulation in Scotland, meant that Police Scotland whilst answerable to the Scottish Police Authority, effectively had a monopoly over agenda setting and policy formulation. Despite an increasing interaction between policing and academia over the past decade, it did not extend to initial police learning. There remains a 'dialogue of the deaf' (Bradley and Nixon, 2009) between the 'two worlds thinking' (Hallenberg, 2012) of policing and academia, in so far as initial police learning is concerned. This study revealed that this may, in part, be attributable to concerns within Police Scotland regarding ownership and control. As one senior

police manager put it, the ‘tail’ should not be allowed to ‘wag the dog’. Whilst this study has revealed, in the case of Sweden, that allowing academia too much control can result in the needs of academia being foregrounded over the vocational needs of policing, the relationship in Finland between policing and academia might be one which Police Scotland and the Swedish Police Authority consider emulating. The needs of policing have been foregrounded in the Finnish context, whilst at the same time drawing on academia’s knowledge and expertise with regards curriculum design and delivery. Whilst it is a University of Applied Science within the wider HE sector, its focus as the exclusive provider of vocational police learning, is first and foremost to meet the needs of policing.

This thesis argues therefore, that whilst policy formulation might be enhanced by the adoption of an heterogenous process which encapsulates the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of policing, academia, and politics, relational power should rest primarily, but not exclusively, with policing. This would help to ensure that the needs of policing are foregrounded over those of national Governments and academia whilst maximising the benefits to be derived from a closer association with HE.

8.4.3 Policy Implementation

This study revealed that the learning environments within which initial police learning took place mattered. The cultural “climate” (Schein, 2017, p.3) of the Scottish Police College contrasted markedly with the mainstream Swedish universities and POLAMK. The former was focused on enculturation of police recruits into the dominant, deferential, unquestioning, hierarchical culture of Police Scotland which some police staff educators and policing students viewed as an unhelpful learning environment. By way of contrast, the mainstream Swedish universities and POLAMK had moved away from the traditional police training school environment towards those more consistent with HE and a focus on learning. However, as this study and others (for example, Cox and Kirby, 2018, p.560) have shown, simply moving the ‘classroom’ based phases of initial police learning programmes to mainstream universities is not, in and of itself, a panacea for addressing policing’s shortcomings,

as was evident in Sweden. Despite policing students in Sweden attending mainstream universities for the first two years of their initial police learning programme, the “cultural barriers between cops and ‘others’” were quickly erected within these subliminal spaces, with policing students identifying more with being police officers than university students, thereby “reinforcing the internal solidarity” within policing (Atkinson, 2013, p.84). Regardless of the setting for the initial classroom-based phase, identity, and self-image (Schein, 2017, p.4) as police officers formed very quickly which, whilst not helpful in some respects, can also be helpful in forming bonds with fellow recruits and students.

Some scholars (for example, Brown, 2020), argue that police learning which is overly controlled by policing (what Feltes and Dinca, 2012, p.193 called a 'closed circuit' learning system), can reinforce rather than transform the more problematic aspects of police culture. It might, therefore, undermine the benefits to be derived by attending university “if officers take a degree together in a tailor-made programme or if the content is shaped to be overly functional for policing” (Brown, 2020, pp.19-20). Whilst initial police learning programmes which foreground the operational needs of policing may improve operational effectiveness in the short-term, it is argued that academia’s expertise as respects epistemic knowledge, reflective practice, critical and analytical thinking, might enhance both individual and organisational professionalism in the longer term. However, based on the findings from this study, it is also argued that the mainstream university settings in Sweden were overly focused on academia’s assessment criteria, with the result that policing students had difficulty making connections between some aspects of the curriculum and their professional practice. Spending two years at university before having the opportunity to apply their theoretical and practical skills knowledge operationally, and then only for six months, was resulting in ‘aspirants’ experiencing difficulties in applying their ‘classroom’ based learning on the street. Within POLAMK on the other hand, there was a real sense amongst policing students that the programme was practically focused (Terpstra and Schaap, 2021) and less colonised by academic thinking which was not vocationally relevant. Policing students expressed satisfaction that the programme was equipping them with an appropriate balance of vocationally relevant epistemic, ‘craft’,

and experiential knowledge. They, their tutor constables, and operational leaders were of the view that graduates were well equipped to undertake their generalist role within the lean management, distributed leadership culture of policing in Finland, in which they were expected to deal with a wider range of more complex tasks from beginning to end, than their peers in Scotland and Sweden. They appeared to be more the ‘complete package’ being sought by the Scottish Police Federation, than their peers in Scotland and Sweden, which was reflected in their appointment as senior constables on graduation.

8.4.4 Ownership and control

In Scotland, ownership, control, and delivery effectively sat entirely within Police Scotland’s purview. There was no interaction with academia. The SPA was invited to approve a re-focusing of the eleven-week Initial Training Course in 2019. The outcome was a programme which had remained fundamentally unchanged for several decades, and which the Chair of the Scottish Police Federation recently acknowledged needed to be lengthened and broadened, with a view to developing recruits who, as highlighted in sub-section 8.4.3, were ‘the complete package’.

In Finland, ‘ownership’ and ‘control’ of initial police learning was negotiated between the National Police Board (the client), POLAMK (the provider) and the HE sector, of which POLAMK was a statutorily independent part. The latter bestowed on POLAMK the status of University of Applied Science and the authority to award degrees. Its client/provider status helped to ensure that the vocational needs of policing were foregrounded whilst at the same time, quality assurance and accreditation was provided through its positionality as a University of Applied Science within the HE sector. Its governance arrangements comprised several layers incorporating College managers, policing, academia, the police union, teaching staff and policing students. This collegiate, heterogenous structure echoed that which had existed within the Scottish Police College prior to the establishment of Police Scotland in 2013. Ownership, control and the co-production and delivery of an “integrated theory and

practice curriculum” (Brown, 2020, p.20) was more apparent in Finland, than in either Scotland or Sweden.

In Sweden, the ‘gap’ between the Swedish Police Authority’s high level, national curriculum and their capacity and capability to quality assure its delivery had, in effect, handed control over the development of detailed curricula to the universities. Each university developed their own detailed version of the national curriculum, which resulted in a lack of standardisation across the five universities contracted by the Police Authority to deliver the initial learning programme. It is argued that universities had too much control over curriculum development and delivery, as they foregrounded their academic assessment needs over the vocational needs of policing. The focus on academic assessment and accreditation criteria, rather than vocational assessment criteria, had resulted in a number of unintended consequences: policing students, their tutor constables and some of their senior leaders were of the view that they were not being fully and adequately prepared to undertake operational policing; they were spending the first two years of the programme almost entirely in university without practice experience; and the six-month practice phase at the end of the initial university-based phase was generally perceived by police practitioners at all levels to be too short and inadequately integrated with theory.

8.4.5 Workforce planning

Beyond the meso, macro, and micro level benefits and challenges which are invariably the focus of scholarly discourse concerning police professionalisation through HE, there are also more practical considerations which are less frequently discussed. For example, the importance of workforce planning (Hallenberg 2012, p.191). How many recruits are needed, where will their learning take place, is there a sufficiency of suitably qualified trainers, educators, and tutor constables, will there be vacancies once recruits and policing students have completed their initial learning programme, to highlight but a few.

Whilst not a focus of this study, these practical considerations became apparent during the data gathering phase and highlighted some of the advantages and disadvantages of the pre and post entry models. For example, there have been challenges in Finland in recent years concerning the availability of permanent posts for policing students following their graduation. For a couple of years, there had been a surplus of graduates, resulting in some having to find alternative employment until vacancies arose. Planning three years in advance to match demand with supply is challenging, particularly when budget agreements are negotiated annually, are subject to the vagaries of political and economic instability and unexpected operational demands, and attrition rates which can be difficult to predict that far in advance. For example, in Sweden, during the data gathering phase in 2019, the Government there announced a significant increase in police establishment from 20,000 to 30,000 staff. Universities delivering the initial police learning programmes were concerned about their capacity to meet this level of demand. Senior participants from policing and academia also expressed the view that the resultant focus on increasing establishment levels would consign any further progress along the academization pathway to, as one participant described it, ‘the bottom drawer’.

The post-entry model in Scotland on the other hand, provides greater flexibility, enabling Police Scotland to respond more quickly to changing political, economic, and workforce factors. However, this also places considerable demand on the learning providers, namely the Scottish Police College and operational policing divisions. During the data gathering phase for this study, Police Scotland had been recruiting heavily resulting in significant pressure being placed on the Scottish Police College to accommodate them. Operational Divisions struggled to provide tutor constables, who were often being instructed to undertake the role against their will. Despite featuring infrequently in the literature, these practical considerations matter, and should, it is argued, be acknowledged within the theoretical discourse.

8.5 Conclusion: The way forward for Scotland and Sweden

As this and other studies have shown (Hallenberg and Cockcroft, 2017; Watkinson-Miley, Cox and Deshpande, 2022; McCanney, Taylor and Bates, 2022), there are both structural and cultural factors within different countries which can preclude or hinder the academisation of initial police learning, and indeed the role of HE in wider professionalisation strategies (Cockcroft and Hallenberg, 2021, p.12). These factors can include organisational structures, policing styles, organisational cultures (Pepper, Brown and Stubbs, 2022, p.42), and politics, which collectively create path dependencies which preclude (in the case of Scotland), and inhibit (in the case of Sweden), change. This section briefly discusses how the on-going professionalisation of policing through HE might be advanced in both countries, which could also have wider implications beyond those geographical boundaries.

As this study has argued, there is strong cultural congruence within and between policing and politics in Scotland concerning organisational structures, policing styles, and the guiding notions of professionalism. As discussed previously, the strong emphasis on hierarchical control through structures, processes, and procedures coupled with an increasing specialisation of the workforce, marginalised, and narrowed the remit and complexity of junior-ranking, front-line response officers. The role, it was argued, had become “less dependent on human skills, abilities and knowledge...contributing to de-humanising [and] deskilling” (Terpstra, Fyfe and Salet, 2019, pp.353-354). This in turn, helped to explain the perception amongst policy makers in Scottish policing, that a lengthy period of undergraduate degree level learning for new entrants was not required. However, given the continuing challenges as regards public sector funding, it is argued that consideration should be given as to whether a more generalist policing model should be adopted, together with a more distributed, lean approach to leadership and management. It is argued, that by broadening the marginalised, de-professionalised role of junior-ranking front-line response officers, and enabling greater individual adhocacy, workforce capacity and capability could be enhanced. If such a reconfigured notion of organisational professionalism were to be implemented, it is also argued that the initial police

learning programme would require to be more closely aligned with HE, so that police recruits might be more adequately prepared for their expanded, more complex role. However, given the cultural congruence which currently exists between Police Scotland and those in governance and oversight roles, and the still quite ‘hot’ political climate within which it is operating (Murray and Harkin, 2017), it is unlikely that this debate would take place anytime soon, if indeed at all. This means that the academisation of initial police learning is likely to continue to be perceived as unnecessary for some time to come.

Proponents of academisation might argue that Police Scotland simply needs to change, to remove these cultural and structural barriers, and align itself with the worldview of HE institutions and actors. However, given the lack of a “decisive body of work that can clearly articulate the full range of benefits higher education can bring to policing” (Green and Tong, 2020, p. 296), doubts concerning the validity of the body of work which does exist (Brown, 2020), and the challenges of implementing change in Sweden, and indeed in England and Wales with regards the PCDA, provide perhaps good reason for policy makers in Scotland to be cautious.

Reflecting on the current situation with regards the PCDA, early studies have revealed that whilst PCDA apprentices “shared an appreciation of gaining a degree, this was not the motivating factor to join the PCDA... it was viewed by participants as the access route into the career” (Watkinson-Miley, Cox and Deshpande, 2022, p.132), echoing the findings from this study discussed in chapter 7. It is reasonable to assume therefore, that the introduction of a degree accredited initial learning programme in Scotland would be unlikely to be a motivating factor for people applying to join the service. Indeed, with 40% of recruits in recent years being graduates, broadly representative of that societal demographic, policing in Scotland appears to be attractive to a representative proportion of both graduates and non-graduates. Watkinson-Miley, Cox and Deshpande (2022) also found that those who had undertaken ‘on-the-job’ practice, questioned the relevance of the academic theoretical knowledge, often disregarding the academic teaching in favour of ‘on-the-job’ practice learning. Whilst they argued that this “may be suggestive of traditional

[cultural] patterns repeating themselves”, they also found evidence of a disconnect between the “two-worlds” of academia and policing (Hallenberg, 2012) and of tensions between an “‘us and them’ culture between police and academic staff” (Wilkinson Miley, Cox and Deshpande, 2022, p.131). Indeed, there are indications that a broader cultural, epistemological, and possibly political disconnect between politics, academia, and policing in England and Wales, is leading to some police forces offering alternative pathways into policing which do not require completion of the PCDA.

It should be noted, once again, that the more practice-focused epistemic knowledge delivered on the initial learning programme in Finland (Terpstra and Schaap, 2021) was generally accepted by policing students there as being vocationally relevant. There was cultural congruence between the policy makers, those who designed and delivered the programme, and policing students. In essence, then, it is argued that situated meanings, context, and processes within each country should influence “what is taught, to whom it is taught, and how it is taught” (Wheelahan and Moodie, 2021, p.212). It is argued, therefore, that simply ignoring situated meanings, context, and processes, and instead ‘sheep-dipping’ all new entrants through a compulsory pre-entry degree programme is not necessarily the answer.

In those contexts which preclude the academisation of initial police learning, as in Scotland, a refocusing of ongoing professionalisation through HE, onto areas where the potential benefits are more readily apparent should be considered. For example, as this study found, police officers in Scotland were generally of the view that HE was more likely to be useful in the workplace for more senior-ranked (Norman and Fleming, 2022, p.162) and specialist officers. This could present an opportunity to make some comparatively ‘quick wins’, which might bring about a “realization and acceptance that the old ways need to change, and new ones learned” (Schein, 2017, pp.325-326). This could be realised through, for example, the targeted use of micro-credentials.

Some scholars, Governments, and employers have suggested that HE needs to acknowledge and respond to the wider 21st century employability discourse which

attempts to align HE policy and universities' curricula more closely with labour market requirements. It is argued, that the knowledge and skill needs of policing in Scotland and Sweden concerning its police recruits and policing students, are colliding with the "traditional education paradigms" (Lemoine and Richardson, 2015, p.1) with regards HE. The challenge, it is argued, is for HE to acknowledge and accept that in the cultural and structural contexts of Scotland and Sweden, and indeed other jurisdictions with similar policing models, initial police learning requires a narrow focus on preparation for work, which will require HE to not only reframe its classification of knowledge, but also reconsider how it might support policing to increase HE participation through a lens of reform and innovation (Whelehan and Moodie, 2021).

One way in which this might be achieved is using micro-credentials which are specific to the person, rank, and role. Whilst they have been largely associated with vocational learning, they are increasingly becoming associated with HE policy. Some countries such as New Zealand and Australia now include micro-credentials within their HE curricula, with the latter offering a six-month undergraduate higher education certificate (Whelehan and Moodie 2021, p.214). Within the EU, a Common Micro-credential Framework has been launched to create portable credentials for lifelong learners (Ubachs, 2019). Whilst defining what they are and what they are not is difficult, there is "a generally shared assumption... that a micro-credential can 'count' towards a 'parent' qualification such as a diploma, bachelor's degree, or higher-level qualification" (Whelehan and Moodie, 2021, p.214). Micro-credentials can be completed quickly and provide "the ability to pursue career, professional and personal development...through...a thematic set of competencies in an abbreviated time frame and receive some form of digital authentication and documentation of what they achieve", which is accredited by Higher Education (Greenberg, 2020, p.1).

Police Scotland could develop a suite of micro-credentials aimed initially at the those in senior promoted posts and those in specialist roles. This could help police professionalism in these fields to move past reliance on the 'art' and 'craft' of policing, to also include the 'science of policing: epistemic knowledge together with critical and

reflective practice. Given the recommendation of the Christie Report (2011), the initial focus could be on developing the inter and connective professionalism (Meurs and Noordegraaf, 2022) of senior officers and those in specialist posts who work in collaboration with other public services to provide person-centred responses to endemic, multiple-problem issues underpinning social and health inequalities. Given the report's emphasis on cross-sector professional working, these micro-credentials could be developed and delivered collaboratively by relevant organisations. Given the concerns of some scholars (Greenberg, 2020) as regards the external recognition and acceptance of micro-credentials, it is suggested that they be developed in collaboration with the HE community in Scotland, possibly through the auspices of SIPR. Given that the Scottish Police College is an SCQF credit rating body, they could be credit-rated. External recognition could be further enhanced through the SQA, and/or accreditation by collaborating HE institutions. However, as the findings from Sweden have demonstrated, the development of micro-credential learning programmes should focus on the regulative principle which foreground the dispositions required by the employer (Wheelahan and Moodie, 2021, p.220), rather than those of academia. These regulative principles should shape the instructional discourse (the curriculum), as they do in Finland as regards the initial police learning programme.

This approach to the enhancing the professionalisation of policing in Scotland through targeted micro-credentials, recognises the cultural and structural realities which preclude the academisation of initial police learning. Instead, it provides a realistic opportunity for the 'three-worlds thinking' of policing, academia, and politics, to collaborate through a heterogenous approach to policy formulation and implementation, to enhance the service's capability to achieve its main policing purpose: "to improve the safety and wellbeing of persons, localities, and communities in Scotland and... working in collaboration with others where appropriate" (Police and Fire Reform (Scotland) Act, 2012, s.32). It is argued, based on the findings from this study, that in those political, social, cultural, and structural contexts where ongoing police professionalisation through the academisation of initial police learning is precluded or hindered, the targeted use of micro-credentials involving senior leaders and those in specialist roles, is more likely to lead to epistemic knowledge being

acknowledged internally and externally as a source of cultural capital, than the academisation of initial police learning. If so, it could provide a 'quick' win which could begin to slowly unfreeze the cultural preference for 'craft' knowledge developed primarily through experiential, 'on-the-job' learning. It could, over time, lead to a realisation and acceptance that epistemic knowledge, when combined with practical wisdom (phronesis), supports a reconfigured notion of professionalism which more accurately reflects the rapidly changing and increasingly complex realities of 21st century policing. It could also demonstrate that in the on-going professionalisation of policing through HE, the compulsory completion of a degree-accredited initial learning programme is not necessarily the answer.

Chapter 9: Methodological coda

Introduction

Research in the field of policing has a long tradition of reflecting on methods (see for example Van Maanen, 2011). Taking inspiration from these methods in reflecting on and discussing the experience of implementing this study's methodological design, this section will focus on two main themes. Firstly, the experience of conducting a cross-national, multiple case study and the importance of networks of trusting relationships. Secondly, the researcher's positionality as a retired senior police officer and fledgling academic: what Brown (1996) defined as an outsider/insider perspective and how this may have coloured the social, cultural, and political 'reality' I have tried to convey.

9.1 The importance of established networks of trusting relationships

Gaining access and my subsequent fieldwork journey, has involved a complex process of building up of layered permissions through both pre-existing relationships of trust, and through negotiating and creating confidence within new relationships. These were crucial in successfully navigating power relations within and between the various organisations and across geographical and cultural boundaries (Merriam *et al.* 2001, p.406; Robinson *et al.*, 2021, p.9). For example, after several months of unsuccessfully attempting to negotiate the formal approval process agreed between SIPR and Police Scotland in a Memorandum of Understanding through the appointed single point of contact within Police Scotland, I eventually drew on personal contacts with ex-colleagues to secure the requisite gatekeeper approvals. The horizontally and vertically fragmented structures within the force required several different gatekeeper approvals from senior managers within different business areas. This proved time-consuming, confusing, frustrating, and disappointing. A personal connection with a recently retired elite practitioner from within Scottish policing's oversight and governance structures also facilitated access to others who were then still working in that world. Unfortunately, requests to interview politicians and civil servants within

the Scottish Government were declined, and in the case of Sweden and Finland, ignored. This was regrettable and has resulted in a data gap which future studies, in addition to that of Terpstra and Schaap (2021) should aim to address. However, this gap was partially addressed by gathering data from elite actors in each of the case study countries who interacted directly with key political actors during policy formulation processes.

Similarly, established personal and professional relationships between SIPR, myself, and senior leaders at the Finnish Police University College (POLAMK) were pivotal in securing access there. I was invited to present my initial thoughts about the aim and research design to senior educational and research staff from POLAMK, during a SIPR hosted knowledge exchange event in early 2018. During this event and the subsequent social gathering, a strong personal rapport was quickly built with these and other members of the POLAMK delegation, which resulted in a request from the Head of Education to be included as one of the case studies. Being actively invited and encouraged in this way by the senior leadership team at POLAMK, including the Director who was a serving chief police officer with an extensive background in academia and forensic science, was highly motivating. It also had practical implications which helped facilitate data gathering. Access requests to policing practitioners at all levels, and to documents, were readily acceded to, and introductions were made to elite actors within academia. The Head of Research at POLAMK was nominated as a single point of contact which was also very helpful, both in terms of having one person to liaise with, as opposed to several as in Scotland, and their positionality as a senior leader.

Conversely, it was recognised from the outset that gaining access approval in Sweden would be more challenging. I was unable to leverage any pre-existing personal and professional relationships either within policing, or academia, to gain access. After a year of sending numerous introductory e-mails to various people and departments within the Swedish Police Authority and receiving no replies, it was a speculative e-mail to a policing researcher who also taught on the initial police programme at one of the universities in Sweden, which unlocked access. They provided personal

introductions to a police officer within the Human Resources Department of the Police Authority, and to a senior academic and Deputy Director of the initial police learning programme being delivered at one of the universities. Both were colleagues of the policing researcher and proved to be pivotal in helping to secure the requisite gatekeeper approvals, identify potential participants, and make personal introductions within their respective ‘worlds’ of policing and academia.

As these different experiences demonstrate, pre-existing, trusting personal and professional relationships were pivotal to the successful completion of data gathering in this study. Not only my positionality with regards Police Scotland helped, eventually, so too did the relationships developed by SIPR. Through their established memorandum of understanding with the Finnish Police University College, I was able to quickly develop my own personal and professional relationships in Finland, secure access approval, and crucially be actively encouraged and supported with my research.

9.2 Benefits and challenges of being an ‘outsider insider’ researcher

Whilst Brown’s (1996) typology of policing researcher categorises me as an ‘outsider outsider’ (a ‘civilian’ working for a ‘civilian’ organisation), this fails to capture my thirty-year affiliation with policing, largely within the Scottish context, including as Head of the Probationer (police recruit) Training Division at the Scottish Police College. Despite having retired from Police Scotland in 2014, it is argued ‘outsider insider’ more accurately reflects the shared meanings and cultural homogeneity (Merriam *et al.* 2001, pp.406-407) of being an ex-police officer. That said, the time which had elapsed since my retirement, coupled with the monumental organisational changes which had taken place following the establishment of Police Scotland in 2013, and the rapidly decreasing number of ex-colleagues still serving within the force, provided a necessary degree of critical distance (Tatnell, 2019). Despite this, I still felt a strong sense of loyalty towards the Scottish Police College and towards the Probationer Training Division which I had been appointed to lead in 2008. I prefer to think that my awareness of this bias helped to mitigate the associated risks. As a fledgling academic, I also felt somewhat marginal as I grappled with an unfamiliar

culture, a limited network of established, trusting personal and professional networks, and the challenge of quickly developing competence as a doctoral researcher, all of which contributed to my sense of being an imposter within the world of academia. As well as my positionality as an ‘outsider insider’ researcher, I was also conscious of my positionality with regards my age (in 2019 I was in my mid-fifties), my gender, my social class, my ethnicity, my nationality, my level of education, and that English was my only language. Whilst these different aspects of my positionality and the impact which they may have had on this study should be acknowledged and considered by the reader, their interaction it is argued, are helpful within a social constructivist and interpretivist approach, to providing a balanced, considered, and credible analysis of the data.

My data gathering phase largely comprising of one-to-one, semi-structured interviews, and focus groups, required the development of a relationship between myself as the interviewer and the interviewees as part of the research process. The nature of my interactions with participants were inevitably influenced and nuanced by our respective positionalities and personal characteristics, which in turn framed the nature of the interaction. For example, whilst I rarely began each new ‘relationship’ by introducing myself as a retired senior police officer, it often quickly became apparent that participants already knew. Despite this, I was sometimes perceived as an ‘outsider/outsider’ (Brown, 1996), particularly by senior officers in Scotland, who treated me with suspicion, resulting in them being somewhat defensive of Police Scotland’s policies and practices concerning initial police learning and the contentious issue of graduate-entry only. On one occasion, I requested access to unrestricted documents relating to Police Scotland’s Pathways Project which had been considering the introduction of a combination of different entry routes into Police Scotland, including a degree entry route. Whilst I was granted access, it was on the proviso that I was only permitted to read the documents on police premises, under the supervision of a police officer, that I was not to photocopy or photograph the documents, and that any handwritten notes I made were to be inspected by the police officer supervising me. The level of suspicion and distrust which I experienced from several senior police officers was disappointing, but not entirely surprising. Police officers had expressed

the view that a ‘blame culture’ had developed within Scottish policing following reform in 2013, which had created what was frequently described as a ‘climate of fear’ amongst some within leadership and management roles. Whilst not apparent from the data, this might in part be attributable to the ‘hot’ post-reform policing climate (Murray and Harkin, 2017). Conversely police recruits and ‘civilian’ staff in Scotland, policing students, senior officers, and ‘civilian’ staff in Sweden and Finland tended to treat me as an ‘insider/outsider’ (Brown, 2016), appearing to speak openly and honestly about their perspectives.

However, despite my default approach of not revealing my alliances with policing, there were occasions when revealing them helped. For example, whilst gathering data at one of the Swedish universities, a member of staff contacted a senior police officer at a nearby police station and requested that I be granted permission to interview a group of officers who had recently completed their initial learning programme. On initially being told that I was a PhD student, access was refused. However, upon being informed that I was also a recently retired senior police officer, access was immediately granted. In Finland, the first interview I conducted with an experienced police sergeant on the instructing staff at POLAMK got off to a difficult start. From his body language and curt replies to my initial questions, I realised that he regarded me as an ‘outsider outsider’ researcher and was suspicious and distrustful of me as an academic. To overcome this, I informed him that I was a retired, thirty-year service police officer. He immediately relaxed and spoke fluidly and openly, so much so that he candidly shared his views concerning the physical unsuitability of some women to be police officers. Apart from these extreme examples, I was not conscious of my age, gender, or positionality as an ‘outsider insider’ researcher adversely impacting this study.

Indeed, I do think that possessing the knowledge, skills, and thirty years’ experience of structured interviewing, helped me to gather a very rich data set comprising the deeply held perceptions of participants. Participants often commented on how thought-provoking the discussions had been, as it had given them a rare opportunity to think about and articulate what influenced their underlying assumptions concerning

policing as a profession, police professionalism, and police professionalisation through HE.

Overall, it is hoped that the research process did not just benefit the researcher, but had a wider, broader contribution to make to research participants by opening space for them to reflect on their history, identity, and future in the context of an increasingly professionalising police service.

Chapter 10: Conclusion

Introduction

The central contribution to this thesis is that the extent to which initial police learning programmes in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland were aligned with HE, were influenced largely by the social, cultural, organisational, and political contexts, the situated notions of profession, professionalism, and professionalisation, and the extent of interaction and relational power between the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing.

10.1 Returning to the research questions

10.1.1 Principal research question

The principal research question for this study, as stated in chapter 3, was as follows:

To what extent do the different social, cultural, and political contexts in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland influence the perception of the role of higher education in police recruit learning?

This question was broken down into four supplementary research questions to explore, and the following four sections address these.

10.1.2 Supplementary research questions

Research Question 1: How has initial police learning evolved in the case study countries?

As discussed in chapter 4, the answer to this question is that initial police learning has evolved differently in each of the three case study countries, influenced in part by the extent of interaction and relational power between the ‘three-worlds’ of politics,

policing, and academia, and in part by the meaning ascribed by each to social, culturally, and politically contextualised meanings of profession, professionalism, and professionalisation, rather than empirical research.

In the case of Scotland, policy formulation with regards initial police learning, has been largely a homogenous, non-negotiated approach, which involves not looking outwith Police Scotland. Driven almost entirely by the ‘one-world thinking’ of policing, with little interaction with politics or academia, the initial police learning model has remained fundamentally unchanged since its inception in the 1960s. In addition, there has been long-standing political and practitioner resistance to the academisation of initial police learning.

In the case of Sweden, whilst initial police learning has evolved, progress along the academisation policy pathway has ebbed and flowed. This is characteristic of policy development in general, as argued by Greene (2012), in that it is influenced by external forces which are often beyond the control of policy makers. This was found to be the case in Sweden, in terms of opposing political ideologies within the Swedish parliament. Whilst policy formulation was heterogenous and negotiated, involving the ‘three-worlds thinking’ of politics, academia, and policing, relational power was located largely within the ‘two-worlds’ of politics and academia, with policing having a less powerful voice. These findings concerning Sweden’s complex, stop-start policy pathway provide rich data and colour to Furuhausen’s (2015) review of published Swedish Government papers which charted the policy formulation process.

Whilst policy formulation in Finland was also heterogenous and negotiated, relational power between the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia and policing differed. Being located principally with the police and supported by academia, the resultant three-year, Bachelor’s degree accredited programme foregrounds the vocational needs of policing whilst also meeting the accreditation needs of academia. However, progression along the policy pathway was delayed for a few years by a misalignment between academia and policing on the one hand, and politics on the other. Further progression was dependent on a subsequent change of national Government and the

appointment of a Minister for Education whose views aligned with those of academia and policing. The symbolism of degree accreditation and the Police College becoming a University of Applied Science was secondary to the vocational needs of policing.

Research Question 2: What knowledge, skills, and behaviours do ‘policy network actors’ (Savage, Charman and Cope, 2000) within the case study countries perceive as desirable in a professional police officer?

As discussed in chapter 5, the answer to this question is that whilst police officers generally foregrounded ‘craft’ knowledge developed through practice experience as a privileged form of knowledge and source of cultural capital over academic, theoretical knowledge, this study found mixed perceptions within and between the case study countries. Police officers in Scotland generally subscribed to a view that privileged ‘craft’ knowledge and practical experience. Police officers in Sweden and Finland generally subscribed to a view that foregrounded both vocationally relevant academic knowledge and ‘craft’ knowledge as privileged forms of knowledge, and sources of cultural capital. Both were perceived as foundational to the development of professional expertise through practice experience. However, whilst some academic theory was initially perceived as less vocationally relevant by policing students in Sweden, there was some evidence that its vocational relevance became more apparent with experience and seniority in rank. A similar finding was revealed in Scotland with regards specialist roles and senior ranks.

It was also found within each of the case study countries that values-driven, ethical decision-making which aimed to ‘do-the-right-thing’ and achieve a ‘good’ outcome in a variety of circumstances, particularly with regards to societies’ vulnerable, was foregrounded as a desirable professional skill.

Research Question 3: To what extent are the current approaches to initial police learning perceived by ‘policy network actors’ within the case study countries as helping in the development of desirable professional attributes?

As discussed in chapter 6, the answer to this question is that despite being at opposing ends of the academisation spectrum (a traditional ‘craft’ based approach in Scotland

and a degree-accredited approach in Finland), each country generally considered their respective approaches to be helpful. The data from Sweden revealed a complexity of cultural synergies and dissonances within and between the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing: between political parties; between ‘management cops’ and policing students; between policing students and academia; and between policing and some political parties. The outcome, it is argued, has been an initial police learning model which police officers generally perceived as foregrounding political ideology and the accreditation needs of academia, over the vocational needs of policing

Finally, the fieldwork data highlighted mixed views amongst participants in Scotland regarding the extent to which the initial learning environments of the semi-militaristic, more traditional environment of the Scottish Police College, and in Sweden the mainstream universities, were helping the development of desirable professional attributes. However, participants in Finland generally perceived the hybrid environment of the Finnish Police University College as helpful, providing a learning environment which was particularly well-suited to adult, policing students and for blending the ‘art’, ‘craft’, and ‘science’ of policing.

Research Question 4: What factors explain the divergence between ‘policy network actors’ perceptions within the case study countries on the impact, or potential impact, of academic education on the professionalisation of police recruits and policing students?

As discussed in chapter 7, the answer to this question is that the divergence between ‘policy network actors’ perceptions within the case study countries on the impact, or potential impact, of academic education on the professionalisation of police recruits and policing students, can be explained largely by the influence of three factors. Firstly, the social, cultural, organisational, and political contexts. Secondly, the situated notions of profession, professionalism, and professionalisation. Thirdly, the extent of interaction and relational power between the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing.

This chapter highlighted the generally held view amongst police officers and those in oversight and governance roles in Scotland, that HE has little vocational relevance to

policing. It also highlighted their embedded opposition to policing becoming a graduate-entry only occupation amid concerns that the financial cost, and academic rigour of HE, could deter applicants from less socioeconomically advantaged backgrounds, thereby adversely affecting policing's representativeness. The chapter also explained that the closer alignment of initial police learning with HE in Sweden and Finland, was generally perceived as providing a foundation for a reconfigured, expert, knowledge-based notion of professionalism: an expertise encapsulating a blend of 'art', 'craft' and 'science'. However, it was hypothesised that the correlation between the introduction of compulsory, pre-entry, undergraduate-level initial learning programmes and Nordic countries recruiting predominantly from middle-class backgrounds rather than working class backgrounds, may result in pre-entry structural class inequalities.

10.2 Thesis contribution and future research

10.2.1 Key contributions to knowledge

This thesis set out to explore why policy makers in Scotland, Sweden and Finland adopted different strategies with regards the role of academic education in initial police learning. Through this exploration, and in answering the guiding research questions, it not only adds to the limited number of cross-national comparative policing studies field, but also makes several original contributions to knowledge.

Firstly, this thesis makes an original contribution to knowledge by providing new and empirically based understandings of police professionalisation and how they relate to concepts of initial learning. This study discloses that police professionalisation has different meanings in different social, cultural, and political contexts, and helps to fill the gap in comparative, cross-national, empirical analysis. This original contribution also helps to understand why there is no consensus about how policing should be professionalised, and that doing so through the academisation of initial police learning is not necessarily the answer. It demonstrates that different approaches are appropriate,

and those that are deployed must be attuned to the different social, cultural, and political contexts in which they are situated.

Secondly, this thesis makes an original contribution to knowledge by providing new empirically based evidence that supports, through a synthesis of data refracted through Noordegraaf's (2015) analytical framework, claims that policing is not a 'pure' profession as shown in trait-based definitions, but is at best 'hybrid' combining "professional and managerial principles such as autonomy and control, or quality and efficiency" (Noordegraaf, 2015, pp.187-188). In doing so this thesis also demonstrates that different levels of hybridity might exist within different social, cultural, and political contexts.

Thirdly, this thesis also makes an original contribution to knowledge by providing evidence that demonstrates, through a synthesis of the different elements of Kingdon's (1995) multiple streams approach, and through the development of Hallenberg's (2012) concept of 'two-worlds thinking' into one of 'three-worlds thinking', that within policy formulation processes variables of social, cultural, and political context are important. It builds on the work of other scholars by demonstrating: that the extent to which there are cultural alignments and schisms within and between the 'three-worlds thinking' of politics, academia, and policing are important in the dynamics of change; that the political context and relational power within the policy formulation process are of particular significance; that decision making during the policy formulation process is not entirely rational nor linear; and finally, that 'policy' streams need to coalesce to provide 'windows of opportunity' for change. As this and other studies have shown these factors collectively create path dependencies which can preclude, hinder, or facilitate professionalisation strategies.

Finally, this thesis makes an original contribution to knowledge by providing new understandings of the theory-practice dichotomy which is often portrayed within the literature as an 'anti-theoretical' or 'anti-academia' police culture. It demonstrates that the extent to which academic theoretical knowledge, 'craft' knowledge, and experiential knowledge are foregrounded as privileged forms of knowledge and

sources of cultural capital within policing vary within different social, cultural, and political contexts.

10.2.2 Recommendations for policy and practice

This study is of interest to policymakers from the ‘three-worlds’ of politics, academia, and policing, together with those with responsibility for realising intended policy outcomes. The findings can be applied to generate recommendations for policy and practice. Whilst acknowledging that policy and practice are context-specific, making direct importation from one to another challenging, it is hoped that countries can learn from one another and include these lessons in discussion, decisions, and practice reviews.

Recommendation 1

As suggested in chapter 4, section 4.3, it is recommended that countries which have adopted a homogenous ‘one-world thinking’ policy formulation and implementation process as respects initial police learning, should move towards a more heterogenous approach which encapsulates relevant stakeholders. This could, for example, include those in oversight and governance roles (such as the SPA, HMICS, and SPCF in the Scottish context), police unions, academia, police educators and trainers, police recruits or policing students, partner agencies, and members of the public. However, as suggested in chapter 8, section 8.2.1, such a heterogenous policy formulation and implementation process should be guided by the reality of policing’s on-going reconfiguration and hybridity rather than a list of traits. Policing practitioners should have sufficient influence within the process to ensure that the learning needs of their organisations are foregrounded over the accreditation needs of academia and over political ideology.

Recommendation 2

Building on recommendation 1, and as discussed in Chapter 6, section 6.3.3, and in Chapter 8, section 8.3.4, the recommendation of the 2016 Governmental Working Party report on police education in Sweden, that the ‘general exam’ quality assurance

criteria which encapsulate a more academic, theoretical set of assessment measures, be replaced with those for designated professional (vocational) university programmes, should be enacted.

Recommendation 3

As highlighted in section 6.2.1, the Swedish Police Authority were experiencing difficulties in ensuring a degree of standardisation across the five universities contracted by them to deliver the initial ‘classroom’ based learning phase. Their high-level, broad-brush national curriculum had resulted in the contracted universities interpreting the curriculum requirements differently and developing a variety of approaches to delivery. This was compounded by the Authority’s lack of capacity and capability with regards quality assurance. It is therefore recommended that police services, when contracting out delivery of initial police learning to external providers, such as universities, ensure that they have sufficiently detailed curricula and adequate quality assurance processes in place, to ensure an appropriate degree of standardisation of curriculum content and delivery.

Recommendation 4

Given, as discussed in Chapter 5, section 5.6.2 and in Chapter 6, section 6.3.3, the rapidly changing and increasingly complex operating environments within which policing operates, it is recommended that an emphasis be placed within initial police learning programmes on the development of ‘practical wisdom’ (phronesis), with a view to blending the ‘art’, ‘craft’ and ‘science’ of policing (Wood, *et.al.*, 2018, p.176) with ethical decision-making which focuses on doing the right thing and achieving a ‘good’ outcome in any given set of circumstances.

Recommendation 5

With regards the spaces within which the initial, ‘classroom-based’ learning phases were taking place, as discussed in section 6.3.3, it is recommended that initial police learning programmes should move away from traditional learning environments which focus on acculturation of recruits and policing students into unquestioning hierarchical cultural norms, and towards those which focus on the acquisition of

knowledge. Learning environments should provide time and space for self-directed learning, critical thinking, and reflection. The Police University College in Finland provides an exemplar which other countries may wish to draw lessons from.

Recommendation 6

As discussed in Chapter 6, section 6.3.3, the duration of the ‘classroom’ based ITC in Scotland should be increased to provide sufficient time and space for self-directed learning, critical thinking, and reflection.

Recommendation 7

As suggested in Chapter 6, section 6.3.3, and Chapter 8, section 8.4.3, spending two-years without any ‘on-the-job’ practice learning in Sweden is not conducive to minimising policing student’s practice-theory gap during the six-month ‘aspirant’ phase. Consideration should, therefore, be given, to introducing policing students earlier to ‘on-the-job’ learning.

Recommendation 8

As highlighted in Chapter 6, section 6.3.3, ‘on-the-job’ learning is valued more highly than “any other form of training or education within the police service” (Charman, 2017, p.224). This is not unique to policing and is a fundamental principle of adult education. However, in Sweden, policing students and police officers perceived the six months ‘on-the-job’ aspirant phase as being too short. It is therefore recommended that policy makers in Sweden consider extending this phase.

Recommendation 9

As discussed in section 8.5, it is recommended that consideration should be given as to whether a more generalist policing model should be adopted in Scotland, together with a more distributed, lean approach to leadership and management. If such a reconfigured notion of organisational professionalism were to be implemented, it is also recommended that the initial police learning programme be more closely aligned with HE to draw on its expertise in developing the epistemic knowledge, critical

thinking, and reflective practice which police recruits will require for their expanded, more complex role.

Recommendation 10

As suggested in section 7.2.4, for those countries where a closer alignment of initial police learning with HE already exists, or is being considered, and there are concerns that people from less advantaged socio-economic backgrounds might be deterred from undertaking HE programmes, it is recommended that alternative progression routes into graduate-level policing which enable students to earn and learn should be considered. For example, a Policing Associate route where, as in nursing in England, Associates would be non-graduate members of policing teams, providing support by undertaking less complex and challenging roles, whilst also undertaking academic learning which would provide an articulation route into undergraduate degree programmes.

10.3 Limitations of the study

All studies and methods have their limitations. A single, short-term study such as this is limited in the extent to which it can explore the complexity of police professionalisation, even through the relatively narrow lens of initial police learning. This section considers limitations of the study, how these limitations constrain interpretations and conclusions drawn from the fieldwork data, and what mitigating actions were taken.

I would like to have gathered data from politicians involved in policy formulation or oversight in each of the case study countries. Understanding perceptions from the political ‘world’ of politics was therefore limited to police officers and academics who had interacted directly with politicians during policy formulation processes, and to the peer-reviewed work of other scholars. I would also like to have gathered data from police officers working in remote geographical areas, to gather alternative views from those in urban areas. However, time and financial constraints prevented this.

Despite these limitations, the study findings were generated from the perceptions and experiences of police officers, including recruits, policing students, tutor constables, operational commanders, chief officers, and police union officials; academics, educators, and police officer instructors involved in the development and delivery of initial police learning; and those in oversight and governance roles. These perceptions were gathered from the contexts within which the participants lived and practiced. Therefore, the “findings produced by research conducted in a particular country are not necessarily applicable to other countries” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.297): the reliance on data is subject to the limitation of transferability (Guba, 1985, cited in Clark *et al.*, 2021, pp.363-364). That said, providing an in-depth or ‘thick description’ (Geertz, 1973, cited in Hupe, 2014, p.170) of the contextual uniqueness of an aspect of the social world being studied, may provide others with a “‘database’ for making judgements about the possible transferability of findings to other settings” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.366). As such, readers may identify aspects of the political, social, and cultural contexts of the case study countries which may make some of the findings from this study transferable and therefore helpful to them.

Data gathered in one-to-one, semi-structured interviews and focus groups is subject to bias which may result in interviewees not giving an accurate response. Interviewees may provide responses which attempt to enhance their credibility, or that of their organisation with the researcher, or undermine the credibility of other people, their organisation, or other organisations. Their responses and subsequent interpretation may also have been influenced, to differing degrees, by the characteristics of the interviewer/interviewee relationship (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.206). Age, gender, nationality, and the researcher’s positionality as an ‘outsider insider’ (Brown, 1996), particularly as a retired senior police officer, may all have influenced participant bias and responses. The “researchers’ own accounts of the social world are constructions” which mean that the researcher has presented “a specific version of social reality, rather than one that can be regarded as definitive” (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.28).

Conducting interviews and focus groups in Sweden and Finland in English was another limitation. Whilst participants in both countries all spoke English, it was not

their first language and there were variations in ability. The researcher spoke neither Swedish nor Finnish. It is possible that there may have misunderstandings of meaning which neither the participant nor the researcher were aware of. To overcome this limitation, probing, clarifying questioning was utilised and interpretations of the data subsequently validated with key participants (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.364).

Interviews conducted by a single researcher could also be considered a limitation, resulting in personal bias, which is unavoidable. However, detailed, and on-going engagement with the data, coupled with subsequent respondent validation (Clark *et al.*, 2021, p.364) of the findings with key participants from each of the case study countries, together with frequent and regular discussions with supervisors and other policing academics, presentations of emerging findings at academic conferences and publications provided some mitigation. As Clark *et al.*, (2021, p.472) note, focus groups “have considerable potential for investigating research questions that are concerned with the processes through which meaning is collectively constructed” by participants which, it is argued, help to validate interpretation of the data gathered during individual interviews. Collectively, these mitigations helped to enhance the study’s credibility and confirmability.

Time was also a limitation, with regards both the duration of interviews and focus groups and when the fieldwork data was gathered. With regards the former, individual interviews and focus groups ranged from about an hour to an hour and a half, which provided limited opportunity to fully explore participant perceptions. With regards the latter, data was gathered three years ago within social, cultural, and political contexts which may have evolved considerably in the interim, along with participant perceptions.

In conclusion, future studies, or extension of this study to other contexts or settings should take all possible limitations highlighted into consideration.

10.4 Recommendations for future research

Following what has been considered above, one of the questions which arises is how to further develop the research considering this study's findings.

Future studies might consider adopting an alternative design to the one employed here, to gain alternative insights. For example, a longitudinal strategy following police recruits from Scotland together with policing students from Sweden and Finland, might provide useful insights, as might replicating the methods employed by the ongoing RECPOL study (Moberg, 2020) to provide greater comparative value.

They might also consider a longitudinal study involving those secondary students undertaking the Higher National Certificate (HNC) in Policing, and those post-secondary school students undertaking policing-related, undergraduate degree programmes within Scottish universities who intend to join Police Scotland as police recruits. The study could follow these students through their HNC and/or undergraduate degree programmes, through their two-year initial police learning programme, and through the following few years of their career. This approach could provide a better understanding of the influence of the different environments on learning, the influence of both university and police culture on learning, and the extent to which the knowledge and skills developed are utilised in day-to-day police work. Similar studies in Sweden and Finland might also be considered, with an additional objective to explore in greater detail whether perceptions concerning the vocational relevance of epistemic knowledge change over time and between different operational contexts, for example urban -v- rural, generalist -v- specialist, junior-ranking-v-senior-ranking officers.

Finally, given the apparent lacuna within the literature with regards what, if any, influence the academisation of initial police learning has on policing's representativeness and ability to build and maintain effective, trusting relationships with the communities they serve, addressing this important knowledge gap should be a focus for future research.

10.5 Final thoughts

The value of this thesis will, for doctoral examination purposes, be measured by the extent to which it has generated new knowledge. Whilst this is clearly fundamental, and has remained my focus throughout this ambitious study, as a retired senior police officer and previous Head of Probationer Training at the Scottish Police College, I also harbour ambitions that my findings might have a positive impact on policy and practice, particularly in Scotland.

When I first began this study, people often asked what I was researching. My ‘elevator pitch’ was “should all Scottish cops be graduates?”. It always provoked interest and often lengthy discussion. Everyone it seemed had a view, but they tended to be somewhat polarised. The following comments exemplify this. One academic observed “if I had my way, every police officer would have a degree”. My ex-police officer colleagues invariably replied “naw” (no), which was usually accompanied by several expletives. The ‘dialogue of the deaf’ (Bradley and Nixon, 2009) it appeared, was alive and kicking at least as far as policing in Scotland becoming a graduate-entry only occupation was concerned. Now, as I reach the end of what has been a fascinating, challenging, and enriching journey, I am often asked “so, what do you think? Should they all be graduates?”. In truth, I’m not sure. Whilst there was much to admire about the approach in Finland, a key finding from this study, namely that the situated social, political, and cultural contexts were important as regards both policy formulation and its operationalisation, means that simply replicating it in Scotland or Sweden may not necessarily lead to the same outcomes. For example, the de-professionalisation of junior, front-line, response officers in Scotland make it unlikely that the benefits which could be derived from a lengthy period of degree level training *and* education would be fully realised. That said, I am also of the view that the ‘traditional’, ‘craft’ based approach in Scotland, which foregrounds tacit knowledge developed through experiential learning, will not sustain the necessary on-going professionalisation of policing in Scotland as it responds to the rapidly changing and increasingly complex

environment within which it operates, whilst also delivering an ethical, evidence-based service.

I have therefore, reached a view that initial police learning in Scotland should develop a closer alignment with HE and draw on their expertise in developing the epistemic knowledge, critical thinking, and reflective practice of police recruits. However, there are some caveats. The first is that an emphasis needs to be placed on bridging the theory practice divide by foregrounding ‘practical wisdom’ (phronesis), thereby not only blending the ‘art’, ‘craft’ and ‘science’ of policing (Wood, *et.al.*, 2018, p.176), but also foregrounding ethical decision-making which focus on doing the right thing in any given set of circumstances. The second caveat is that in developing policy and practice, the vocational needs of policing should be foregrounded over the accreditation needs of academia, and the undue influence of prevailing political ideologies emanating from the Scottish Government. The third caveat is that whilst the ongoing professionalisation of policing in Scotland could benefit from a university-level of education *and* training, a requirement to have completed an academic degree to gain entry to policing is not necessarily the answer. However, if a university level of education *and* training merits degree accreditation, foregrounds the vocational needs of policing, and does not deter people from socially and economically disadvantaged backgrounds from applying, then I would be supportive. Finally, the hazards of sublimating the vocational needs of policing into the accreditation needs of academia and the often diametrically opposed ideological needs of political parties, as demonstrated in Sweden, would need to be avoided. To have policing students spend two years at university before having the opportunity to experience and learn from the ‘real world’ of front-line, operational policing and even then, only for six months, is in my view, unhelpful in bridging the theory-practice divide.

Until recently, I had little hope of any of this happening in Scotland. However, HMICS’ recently published 2022-2025 Scrutiny Plan, includes an intention to undertake an audit and assurance review towards the end of the inspection cycle. HMICS have been made aware of this study and have indicated their interest in the

findings being used to inform their work. Police Scotland has also recently initiated a strategic review of training delivery, which includes initial police learning. The findings from this study have also been used to inform their work. The Chair of the Scottish Police Federation also stated publicly recently that the eleven-week initial learning phase (ITC) needed to be lengthened and broadened. The powerful cultural synergies which have existed within Scottish policing, and which have sustained the current model over several decades, may be about to become disrupted. The submission of this thesis and the subsequent publication of peer-reviewed academic journal articles, now seem fortuitously timely and could help to inform and influence the forthcoming debates.

Appendix A: Ethics Committee Approval

From: [REDACTED]
Subject: Ethics Application Approved
Date: 11 April 2018 at 11:16
To: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Dear Andrew Tatnell,

Your application 4345: The role of academic education in police professionalisation: A comparative analysis, submission reference 3374, has been **approved, with conditions**, by the Media Culture and Society SEC. The conditions can be found in the attached approval letter.

Dr Christopher O'Donnell

11/04/2018

Dear Andrew Tatnell,

Your application 4345: The role of academic education in police professionalisation: A comparative analysis, submission reference 3374, has been approved, with conditions, by the Media Culture and Society SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Approval from data collection site gatekeepers (i.e. NGO Police Scotland etc) has to be forwarded to the committee at [REDACTED] and when they are gained.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Christopher O'Donnell

Personal details withheld.

Appendix B: Example of Participant Information Letter

The Scottish Institute
for Policing Research

Dear,

The University of the West of Scotland, the Scottish Institute for Policing Research (SIPR), Police Scotland, the Finnish Police University College, the Swedish Police and Sodertorn University, Stockholm are all kindly supporting my PhD research which has now reached the data gathering phase.

Research Purpose/Aim

The purpose of my doctoral research is to explore and understand the extent to which the social, cultural, and political contexts within Scotland, Sweden and Finland have influenced the use, or otherwise, of tertiary level academic education in police recruit learning.

During the data gathering phase, I am exploring the beliefs and opinions of key 'central actors' who shape, implement, or are affected by policy in this area. In particular, I would like to understand the beliefs of policy makers and shapers such as yourself, around the drivers for police professionalisation in Scotland and the extent to which post-secondary academic education might help or hinder that process.

Potential Impact

I hope that this study will not only add to the current academic discussion around the role of academic education in police professionalisation, but that it may also help to inform police practitioners as they develop future policies and practices in relation to recruit learning. I would welcome the opportunity to share my detailed knowledge and understanding of recruit learning in Finland and Sweden with Police Scotland.

How you can help me

Given your role, I am very keen to seek your views. They are vital to my research, especially as I will also be interviewing your counterparts in Finland and Sweden over the coming months. I would be very grateful if you would kindly give your written consent to help me by agreeing to be interviewed for about an hour, at a time, date, and place convenient for you over the next few months.

If you agree to see me, I will be asking for your personal opinions as part of a one-to-one, semi-structured interview. Whilst I do have some pre-prepared questions, the discussion may take a different course depending on how the discussion develops.

Data Security

Any data gathered by me from the interview will be kept securely at all times and in accordance with Data Security legislation and in accordance with University of the West of Scotland's guidelines. Anonymised data collected may be retained for publication and further research purposes by the University of the West of Scotland. While being retained it will be kept securely and electronic materials will be password protected and stored on an encrypted computer.

I am also seeking your approval to audio record the discussion. This recording will be used to fully transcribe the interview and will be erased once the final thesis has been completed and assessed as being acceptable for a PhD to be awarded. During the study the digital recorder and any accompanying notes, will be kept securely at all times.

Ethical Issues

I want to reassure you that individual comments and data will not be made available to anyone which would make the source identifiable. In the first instance, my findings will be incorporated into my doctoral thesis. Subject to being assessed as of an acceptable standard, my findings will be used to form the basis of academic papers and presentations. They may also be used to provide a reliable evidence base in relation to police practices, policies, or procedures.

All aspects of the study will be conducted in full accordance with the ethical principles set forth by the British Educational Research Association and the University of the West of Scotland, observing procedures for ensuring informed consent, data security, confidentiality and right to withdraw.

Complaints

Any concerns about the conduct of this study can be discussed with Dr Christopher O'Donnell, University of the West of Scotland. E-mail: [REDACTED]. Alternatively, you can contact him by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Media, Culture and Society, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Questions?

If you would like any further clarification, please don't hesitate to contact me. My e-mail address is [REDACTED]

Your sincerely, Personal details withheld.

Andrew Tatnell,
PhD Student,
School of Media, Culture & Society,
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
Scotland,
PA1 2BE

Appendix C: Example of Participant Consent Form

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

The Scottish Institute
for Policing Research

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: *Police Professionalisation through Academic Education: A Comparative Analysis.*

Investigator(s): Andrew Tatnell

Researcher Email: [REDACTED] Personal details withheld.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

STATEMENT	INITIALS
I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and if asked, have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.	
I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.	
I agree to the interview being digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education & Social Sciences, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix D: Example of Interview Schedule

Introduction – Rapport building

- Thank participant for agreeing to see me. Build RAPPORt reminding them who I am, what I am studying and what I hope to achieve from the interview
- Negotiate boundaries – time (1-2 hours – check their time constraints)
- If they agree, the interview will be digitally recorded - notes will also be taken if that's ok with them.
- Any anticipated interruptions?
- Provide reassurance re ethical standards of confidentiality, anonymity, and secure storage of data. Alpha numeric descriptors will be used on all data relating to participants.
- Explain that the study is being fully supported by their organisation.
- Read over consent form, remind participant that they can stop or withdraw at any time, including once the interview has concluded. Once satisfied that they have given their fully informed and free consent ask them to sign and date form
- Any questions or concerns?

Overall aim of the study

“To understand the extent to which the different social, cultural and political contexts within Scotland, Sweden and Finland influence the use, or otherwise, of tertiary level academic education in initial police learning.”

Interview structure

This is a semi-structured interview in which several broad themes will be explored. They will act as focal points for what I hope will be a conversation as opposed to a rigid set of questions and answers.

I am primarily looking for personal *opinions, perceptions, and beliefs* in relation to: Police professionalism and professionalisation.

The relationship between ‘on-the-job’ learning, ‘craft’ knowledge and the role of higher academic education in police learning.

Icebreaker/Rapport Building

Q: Please tell me about your personal background and your career to date.

Q: Please tell me about your role and what it entails.

Probe: How long have you been in your current position?

Probe: What previous roles have you had?

RQ/Theme 1: Evolution of police learning

RQ is: How has initial police learning evolved in the case study countries (think I should add “why has it evolved the way that it has”)?

Q: Please tell me about the current arrangements for the delivery of recruit learning in your country.

Probe: What are your thoughts on the balance between theoretical learning and experiential, ‘on-the-job’ learning?

Probe: Why do you think that?

Q: In your experience, how has police recruit learning evolved in your country over the past few decades?

Probe: In your opinion, why has this evolution taken place?

Probe: What do you think have been the more positive aspects of this evolution?

Probe: What do you think should have been done differently? Why?

Probe: How is it viewed within the wider Scottish/Finnish/Swedish police service?

Q: In relation to police recruit learning, who (people and/or organisations) do you think are the most influential people in relation to policymaking and its implementation?

Probe: Why do you think this?

Probe: How do you think these arrangements are working?

Probe: In your opinion, what are the main benefits?

Probe: What do you think are the main challenges?

Q: What do you consider to be the main opportunities and challenges facing recruit learning in the immediate future?

Probe: Why do you think this?

Probe: How likely do you think this is to happen?

Probe: Why do you think that?

RQ/Theme 2: Police Professionalism

RQ is: What knowledge, skills and behaviours do ‘central actors’ within different social, cultural, and political contexts view as both desirable and undesirable in a professional police officer?

I would now like to explore your thoughts on policing as a profession.

Q: In your opinion, is policing a profession?

Probe: Why do you think this?

Probe: (If they think it is or should be.....) Do you think it can or should be regarded as being on a par with medicine or the law?

Probe: If not, what other professions in Scotland/Finland/Sweden would you equate it to?

Probe: Why do you think this?

Probe: How do you measure or reward police ‘professionalism’ in your organisation?

Q: Please describe what professionalism means to you, within the context of policing?

Probe: What do you think should be the qualities, values, attitudes, and behaviours of a good police officer?

Probe: Why are the things you have described important to you?

Probe: What do you think has shaped your views about this?

Probe: What are your views about the role of lifelong learning/continuous professional development in maintaining professionalism?

Probe: How do you measure or reward police ‘professionalism’ in your organisation?

Q: What does the professionalisation of policing mean to you?

Probe: In your opinion, what are the benefits for policing?

Probe: In your opinion, what are the risks for policing?

Probe: Why do you think there has been such a focus on professionalising policing in Scotland over the past few decades?

Probe: How effective do you believe Police Scotland/the Finnish Police Service/the Swedish Police Service has been in becoming more professional?

Theme 3: The extent to which current approaches to police learning are helping or hindering the development of police professionalisation

RQ is: To what extent are the current approaches to police learning within different social, cultural, and political contexts perceived as helping or hindering the development of desirable professional attributes?

I would now like to move on to explore your thoughts about the extent to which the current approach to police learning in your country is helping or hindering the professionalism of police recruits

Q: In your opinion, how effective in developing recruits into professional police officers, is the current approach to recruit learning in your country?

Prompt: (If they struggle....ask for 3 strengths and 3 weaknesses)

Probe: Why do you think that?

Q: What are your views on the current balance between classroom-based learning and experiential, on-the-job learning?

Probe: In your opinion, is the balance right? Why do you think this?

Q: I have heard it said...in Scotland, Finland, and Sweden, that when recruits (or potential recruits in the case of Sweden) leave the police college or university to begin the practical element of their learning, that their tutors/supervisors/instructors will say “forget what you have learned at police college/university, now we will show you how it’s really done. Why do you think they say that?

Q: What research evidence are you aware of, from your country or elsewhere, which has examined the effectiveness of your approach to police recruit learning?

Theme 4: The impact, or potential impact, of academic education on the professionalisation of new/potential recruits

RQ is: How do ‘policy network actors’ within Scotland, Sweden and Finland view the impact, or potential impact, of academic education on the professionalisation of new/potential police recruits?

For Sweden and Finland:

Q: In your opinion, how does having all police recruits (or potential recruits) undertake higher academic education benefit policing in your country?

Probe: Why do you think that?

For Scotland:

Q: In your opinion, how might it help or hinder policing in your country if all police recruits were to undertake some form of higher academic education either before joining or immediately upon joining?

Probe: Why do you think that?

Conclusion

Q: Is there anything else you would like to add about anything we have discussed?

- Thank you
- Business card
- Any other thoughts following interview please contact me.
- Any concerns, please contact me.
- Happy to be contacted if I have any follow up questions?

Appendix E: Example of Focus Group Schedule

Time	Cumm	
5	5	<p><u>Room Set Up</u></p> <p>Room should be comfortable, allow people to sit in a circular format, and permit the hanging of many sheets of flip chart paper on which responses will be written. In addition, there should be plenty of flip chart paper, marker pens, water.</p> <p>PUT SIGN ON DOOR TO STOP UNWANTED INTRUSIONS</p> <p><u>Introduction to the session – explaining the purpose of the focus group</u></p> <p>Explain who I am and my PhD research – this is a vital part of my work, getting their perceptions, beliefs and opinions and is fully supported by their organisation. Encourage openness and reassure participants that what they say during the session will remain confidential.</p> <p>Should be taking part only if they are doing so of their own free will and that if anyone doesn't wish to take part, they are free to leave at the start or indeed at any time during the session.</p> <p>Sign individual consent forms.</p> <p>Aim of my study:</p> <p>To understand why there are differences in policy around the role of higher education in police recruit learning in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland.</p> <p>I am going to achieve this by means of interviews and focus groups, gathering breadth and depth of opinion involving those in policing and those who have governance and oversight roles.</p> <p>Next two hours will be a casual discussion, want all opinions and all shades of opinion, to see where there is consensus and where there isn't. Explain audio recording, why I want to record and how I will use the recordings – seek permission to record. If anyone objects, I will just use flip charts.</p>

5	10	<p>Personal introduction – all to introduce themselves, first name only, educational background, length of service, length of time in current post, current job role.</p>
5	15	<p>Ground rules for the session</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Everything said in confidence and shouldn't go outside focus group. • Please everyone contribute – will be asking people's views if they are not contributing much. • Please respect other people's views. • Please speak one at a time so that I can hear everything that's said. • Please explain any acronyms you might use. • There is limited time, so apologies in advance if I have to move on from one question area to the next before the discussion has run its course. • Reiterate nothing that is said in the groups will be attributed to individuals. Comments will be treated confidentially and anonymously. • This is not a forum for you to raise personal grievances – comments need to focus on the issues being discussed. • Format not a series of questions and answers, but a conversation, one that everyone needs to participate in. Each group will cover the same areas but if there are matters that are more important to any group there is scope to spend more time exploring experiences, feelings etc. • Any immediate questions?
10	25	<p><u>Icebreaker</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please tell me about your personal backgrounds and careers to date.

20	45	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please tell me about your role and what it entails. • Why did you want to join the police? <p><u>Theme 1: Evolution of police training</u></p> <p>(For immediate supervisors of police recruits). I would like to start by exploring how recruit training has changed during your time in the police.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How has recruit training changed during your time in the police? • Why do think it has changed?
30	1.15	<p><u>Theme 2: Professionalism</u></p> <p>I would now like to explore what police professionalism means to you.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In your opinion, is policing a profession? Why do you think that? • What does professionalism in policing look like to you? • What does the professionalisation of policing mean to you? • In your opinion, what are the benefits and risks of the professionalisation of policing?
30	1.45	<p><u>Theme 3: Current approaches to recruit learning and impact on professionalisation</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In your opinion, how effective is the current approach to recruit learning in your country?

5	1.50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why do you think that? • What are your views on the current balance between theoretical learning and on-the-job learning? • Why do you think that? <p><u>Theme 4: The impact or potential impact of academic education</u></p> <p><u>For Sweden and Finland:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In your opinion, how does having all police recruits (or all potential recruits) undertake higher academic education benefit policing in your country? <p><u>For Scotland:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In your opinion, how might it benefit policing in your country if all police recruits were to undertake some form of higher education? <p>Conclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is there anything else you would like to add about anything we have discussed? • Please contact me at a later date (hand everyone my business card). • Thank you - please encourage their colleagues to get involved if asked.
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Appendix F: Participant Nomenclature

Nomenclature - Suffix	Participants Role
Police Officer	A participant employed by the police as a sworn, fully attested police officer. In Scotland, police officers hold the ‘office’ of constable. Technically, all police officers regardless of rank, hold the officer of constable.
Police Staff	A participant employed by the police who is not a police officer – sometimes referred to as ‘civilian’ staff.
Senior Police Staff	A participant employed by the police who is not a police officer – sometimes referred to as ‘civilian’ staff – in a senior management role.
Police Sergeant	A participant who is a police officer and whose positionality, in terms of rank, is between the more junior-ranking constable rank and the more senior Inspecting ranks.
Chief Police Officer	A participant who is a police officer and who has attained the rank of Chief Officer. Within the Scottish context this means either an Assistant Chief Constable, a Deputy Chief Constable, or a Chief Constable.
Senior Police Officer	A senior police officer, usually at a Superintending rank in Scotland, or equivalent in Sweden and Finland. These officers sit, in term of rank, between the more junior-ranking Inspecting ranks and the more senior-ranking Chief Officer ranks.
Senior Academic	A participant qualified to PhD level or equivalent and employed as a Head or Deputy Head of Department within the Higher Education sector, be that directly in the development of the initial police learning programme (in Sweden and Finland) or not.
SPA Member	A Board member of the Scottish Police Authority
SPCF Member	A member of the Scottish Police Consultative Forum
Tutor Constable	A police officer, usually an experienced constable, with responsibility for coaching police recruits (Scotland) and policing students (Sweden and Finland)

	during their 'on-the-job' practice, or field learning phase.
Police 'Aspirant'	A policing student in Sweden undertaking their six-month 'on-the-job' practice, or field learning.
Police Recruit	A sworn police constable on Scotland who is undertaking the two-year initial police learning programme.
Policing Student	A participant in Sweden and Finland who is undertaking their country's initial police learning programme. Whilst undertaking the 'classroom' based learning phases within university, they are not employed by the police. When they undertake their 'on-the-job' learning phase they are employed temporarily.
Policing Educator	A participant who is a member of police staff and employed either by the Scottish Police College, a university in Sweden, or the Finnish Police University College to develop and deliver learning to police recruits or policing students during the 'classroom' based phases of their respective initial police learning programmes.
Senior Policing Educator	A participant who is a member of police staff and employed as a department Head either by the Scottish Police College, a university in Sweden, or the Finnish Police University College to develop and deliver learning to police recruits or policing students during the 'classroom' based phases of their respective initial police learning programmes.
Police Trainer	A participant who is a police officer and employed either by the Scottish Police College, a university in Sweden, or the Finnish Police University College to develop and deliver learning to police recruits or policing students during the 'classroom' based phases of their respective initial police learning programmes.

Appendix G: Participant Unique Identifiers

Unique Identifier	Explanatory Remarks
SCP	A participant from Scotland.
SWP	A participant from Sweden.
FP	A participant from Finland.
SFG	Police recruits from Scotland participating in a focus group
SWFG	Policing students from Sweden participating in a focus group
FFG	Policing students from Finland participating in a focus group

Appendix H: Publications associated with this research

- Tatnell, A. (2021). The role of Higher Education in initial police learning: A comparative analysis of Scotland, Sweden, and Finland. Available at www.sipr.ac.uk
- Tatnell, A. (2019). Reforming Police Recruit Education and Professionalising the Police: What to expect in the Case of Finland? In Vuorensyrjä, M., Poliiskoulutuksen vaikuttavuusarviointi 2019: vuosina 2016-2017 valmistuneiden poliisien työllisyys ja arviot koulutuksen työelämävastaavuudesta [Evaluation of the effectiveness of police education 2019. Employment and occupational validity of the education as assessed by police officers who graduated during 2016-2017] (pp.127-140). Police University College of Finland, Tampere.

Appendix I: Conference presentations associated with this research

- “The role of higher education in police professionalisation: A comparative analysis of recruit learning in Scotland, Sweden, and Finland. Policing Conference Canterbury Christ Church University, June 2019
- “All Police Officers should be graduates, right?” OU/MOPAC Symposium, London, October 2019 (youtube.com)
- Higher (Initial) Police Education: Does it work in Sweden and Finland and why is it not welcomed in Scotland? The Nordic Policing Conference, June 2021

Appendix J: Sample of thematic coding examples

HE – Benefits to individuals
HE – Benefits for policing
HE – Disbenefits for policing
HE – Transferable skills
HE – Value of qualifications
HE – Rationale re extent of HE in IPLPs
HE – Reflective practice
HE – Critical thinking
HE – Instilling a sense of lifelong learning

IPLP – Balance btn theoretical and practical
IPLP – Contextualising theory through practice
IPLP – Duration
IPLP – Field training
IPLP – History of development
IPLP – Impact on diversity of recruits/students
IPLP – Practice shock/gap
IPLP – Socialisation
IPLP – Standardisation
IPLP – Venue

Occ Culture – Anti academia
Occ Culture – Bending the rules
Occ Culture – Craft knowledge (value of)
Occ Culture – Crime fighting
Occ Culture – Cynicism
Occ Culture – Discretion
Occ Culture – Diversity
Occ Culture – Experiential learning (value of)
Occ Culture – Making a difference

Occ Culture – Resistance to change
Occ Culture – Sense of vocation
Occ Culture – Theoretical knowledge (value)

Org Change – Drivers of
Org Change – Policy outcomes: expected
Org Change – Policy outcomes: actual
Org Change – Process of strategy formation
Org Change – Process of strategy implementation

Org Culture – Hierarchy
Org Culture – Sense of adhocracy
Org Culture – Policing philosophy
Org Culture – Specialisation -v omnicompetence
Org Culture – Complexity of role and requisite knowledge

Politics – (External) influence
Politics – (Internal) influence
Politics – Ideology

Profession – Defining: policing a profession
Profession – Defining: values based
Profession – Defining: trait based
Profession – Value of being regarded as a profession

Professionalisation – Other professions
Professionalisation through HE – Criticisms
Professionalisation through HE – Positives
Professionalisation through HE – Evidence or judgement?

Professionalism – Attitudes and behaviour
Professionalism – Lifelong learning

Professionalism – Craft skills
Professionalism – Critical thinking
Professionalism – Decision making
Professionalism – Ethical standards
Professionalism – Knowledge base
Professionalism – Phronesis
Professionalism – Problem solving
Professionalism – Theoretical knowledge
Professionalism – Reflective practice

Code Groups:

Policy formulation
Desirable knowledge, skills and behaviours
IPLP: influence on professional development
HE in IPLP: factors influencing role of HE

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